

Late Antique Basilicas on Cyprus

sources, contexts, histories

1: Text

Richard Maguire 2012

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For my Dad

6.12.13-1.1.93

It is commonly accepted that Late Antiquity Cyprus emerged from relative isolation to greater engagement with Constantinople. This thesis reverses the paradigm and offers a contextual account of the island's basilicas in support of the proposition.

Located between New Rome and New Jerusalem, fourth-century Cyprus occupied a nodal position in the Eastern Mediterranean. Under Epiphanius, bishop of Salamis (r.367-403) it was at the forefront of Nicene-Constantinopolitan faith-forging. In the late fourth and fifth centuries it was also the site of an ambitious building programme which instantiated its affiliations and produced buildings which, in scale and treatment, represented an engagement with Christendom's major monuments. This, arguably, was the period of greatest affiliation between Cyprus and Constantinople, not as centre and satellite, but in a shared recognition that Jerusalem was their new Christian capital.

By the late-fifth century post-Cyrilline Jerusalem had lost some of its hold on the Cypriot imagination and other issues - *autocephaly*, liturgical changes and the rise to prominence of its bishops - coalesced in a greater engagement with the wider Eastern Mediterranean. At about the same time healing the Orthodox-Monophysite schism became an imperial obsession. Monophysites were sponsored by the Sassanids intent on dividing the Empire before invading it. Reacting to threats from north as well as the east, Justinian reorganised the Empire relegating Cyprus to the eastern outpost of five provinces and transferring its administration from Constantinople to the Black Sea. The schism unresolved, in the seventh century Heraclius developed doctrinal 'innovations' designed to heal the breach with the Monophysites, insisting that Cyprus serve as his laboratory. For Orthodox believers doctrinal innovation was anathema to the extent that, on the eve of the Arab invasion, Cyprus found Old rather than New Rome a more congenial ally, a reorientation that the archaeology too, might support.

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In 1985 W.H.C.Frend wrote 'Working in the field is an essential counterpart to working in a library.' I would, therefore, like to thank Eleni Procopiou, Senior Archaeological Officer of the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus, for allowing me to participate in the dig at Katalymmata ton Plakaton during the 2008 and 2009 seasons. For library facilities on Cyprus, my thanks to Maria Economidou (Cyprus Museum Library) and Tom Davis, Andrew McCarthy, Evi Karyda and Vathoulla Moustoukki (Cyprus American Archaeological Research Institute).

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i. Cyprus and Late Antiquity: a review

...nothing was simply one thing.¹

There is no finality, and my interpretation is only a moment in a moving dialectic, but is nevertheless grounded in the patterned material remains.²

The introduction is in four sections. The first begins in Cyprus with the argument and its immediate context. The second sets the argument against wider issues and debates. The third discusses the framework of the thesis, its terminology and methodology. The fourth returns to a more specifically Cypriot context and discusses firstly, the early literature and secondly, the development of archaeology on the island. A coda provides an overview of the chapter layout.

i.1 Thesis: argument

i.1.1 Prevailing views

For the last forty years some of the most distinguished scholars of Cypriot archaeology have repeated the view that, from the end of the fifth century to the mid-seventh, a hitherto-isolated Cyprus was drawn more closely into the orbit of Constantinople. Megaw argued that ‘insular traditions were increasingly exposed to outside influences, which as time went on came more and more from the capital.’³ For Papageorghiou ‘...the Early Christian architecture of Cyprus was greatly influenced by...Constantinople...,’ a situation confirmed by Bakirtzis, who described how Constantinople ‘permeate[d] more or less all the Early Christian monuments of Cyprus’.⁴ Michaelides, referring to Peyia, a multi-church settlement on the island’s west coast, wrote that ‘what is sure is that this city has many ties with Constantinople which...reflects the general political and artistic re-orientation towards the metropolis at

¹ Woolf (1964) 211

² Hodder (1992) 160

³ Megaw (1974) 68

⁴ Papageorghiou (1986) 497; Bakirtzis (1995) 251

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the end of the fifth and especially in the sixth century.⁵ Finally, Metcalf outlined how '[u]ntil the early seventh century, Cyprus was relatively self-contained,' proposing '...certain periods of greater imperial outreach...namely the mid-sixth/early seventh century...'⁶

i.1.2 Proposition

Such uniformity of view from some of the most distinguished scholars of Cypriot archaeology and history might call for caution from those inclined to question their conclusions. However, I believe the evidence allows an alternative hypothesis. The argument presented in the following six chapters offers an inversion of the paradigm of increasing Constantinopolitanisation. It argues that Cyprus was a major force in eastern Christendom, especially under Epiphanius, bishop of Salamis, (367-403), and that from Justinian onwards, when Constantinople sought to remodel the Church after its own centralising administration of the Empire, Cyprus questioned both the capital's authority and its theology to the extent that, in the period immediately preceding the first Arab invasion in 649, Cyprus found Rome a more congenial ally.

i.1.3 Survey and synthesis

A radical re-reading was no part of my original project, the intention of which was to provide a survey and synthesis of the existing archaeological evidence for Late Antique Cyprus. The authors of two important recent studies of Middle Byzantine architecture on the island both regretted the lack of a survey for the period preceding their own.⁷ For Papacostas an 'overall synthesis from any point of view is still lacking.'⁸ Stewart, too, regretted there was no scholarly survey of the 6th century churches of Cyprus.⁹ For Lavan, Cyprus offered a particularly charged example of a wider malaise.

The main bulk of literature on late-antique urban topics relates neither to syntheses by region or topic, but to individual sites. In the absence of wider research agendas, this is disappointing.

⁵ Michaelides (2001a) 223

⁶ Metcalf (2009) 571, 254. For a recent exposition of Constantinopolitan centrality under Justinian see Shepard (2010) 372-385

⁷ Papacostas (1999); Stewart (2008)

⁸ Pers comm. 1811.07. Also Papacostas (1999) I.19. For site publications see *inter alia* des Gagniers and Tinh on Soloi (1985), Fejfer on Ayios Kononas (1989 and 1991-5), Flourentzos on Alassa (1996), Roux on Campanopetra (1998); Rautman and McClellan on Kalavastos-Kopetra (1988-2006), Manning and Manning on Maroni-Petrera (2002), Megaw on Kourion (2007)

⁹ Stewart (2008) 237 n. 34

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Whilst vast sums of money are spent on elucidating local topographical problems by excavation, comparatively little comparative research is undertaken to draw together wider themes.¹⁰

The most contextually complete survey, Megaw's 'Byzantine Architecture and Decoration in Cyprus, Metropolitan or Provincial?' was published in 1974.¹¹ Its predecessors and successors - Delvoye, Pallas, Papageorghiou and Michaelides – were all relatively brief and largely descriptive. Later surveys provided updates, but the kind of survey satisfying more recent demands remains to be written.¹²

The present text, too, leaves that demand unsatisfied. Before outlining why another course seemed more urgent, the problems involved in a survey demand enumeration both as justification for the alternative project and as a means establishing its context. They may be identified as follows: (1) a more than usually wide range of variation in the evidential base, (2) the appropriation of archaeology for overtly political purposes, (3) the privatisation of knowledge and non-publication, (4) differences of approach between field survey and 'big dig' archaeology, (5) present estimates of the value of typological accounts, and (6) the extent to which Cyprus might be understood as an entity. I will deal with each in turn.

i.1.4 Evidential base

In 1974, the same year that Megaw published his whole island study, the Turkish army invaded and continues to occupy the northern half of the island. Some sites – Lambousa/Lapethos, Tremetousia and Kirkklar Tekkesi amongst them – were included in military bases and repeated requests for admission have been consistently refused. The most far-reaching effect of the invasion was the division of the island into two archaeological time-zones. In 1974 four groups of archaeologists, including those working at Soli under Tinh and at Campanopetra under Roux, abandoned their excavations 'leaving the [north]...in a sort of archaeological limbo.'¹³ Because the Turkish Republic of North Cyprus (TRNC) lacked political recognition, excavation in the north was declared illegal under the provisions of Article 9 of the Second Protocol of the Hague

¹⁰ Lavan (2001) 9-26 at 12

¹¹ Megaw (1974) 57-88

¹² Delvoye (1972) 17-21; (1976) 2-60; (1980) 313-27; Pallas (1977) 289-293; Megaw (1976c) 3-29; Michaelides (2001a) 179-239; Papageorghiou (1985) 299-324

¹³ Rautman (2004) 191

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Convention of 1954. While excavation in the north came to a standstill, the pace of archaeology in the south increased rapidly.¹⁴

i.1.5 Appropriating archaeology

Casting the north as a vandalised no-man's-land, the south asserted its rights over the cultural heritage of the entire island.¹⁵ According to Papacostas,

...the Department of Antiquities...seems to have been particularly keen on preserving and investigating the material remains of periods that were considered particularly relevant to the formation of the 'national identity' of modern (Greek) Cypriots.¹⁶

History, religion and politics combined to make the excavation of churches particularly pertinent in reinforcing a specifically Greek-Cypriot, and hence Orthodox agenda. Cypriot archaeology post-1960 was largely undertaken by, or under the aegis of, institutions, which, because they were government departments, reinforced the prevailing view. Indeed, the rise in the number of churches identified and excavated may be directly related to government policy. In 1950, Megaw regretted that the number of early Christian basilicas on the island was 'unduly small,' but by 1966 Papageorghiou noted some 60 basilicas and, barely twenty years later, more than 80 - although the gazetteer appended to this thesis identifies barely more than seventy.¹⁷

i.1.6 Privatisation and non-publication

An archaeologically abundant south and an impoverished north has not necessarily been a bad thing for the north, nor has it been unproblematic for the south. Concerns were raised by Karageorghis, Director of the Department of the Antiquities between 1963-1989 who, in 1996 identified two related problems:

When I was writing my doctoral dissertation, a large number of objects that I wanted to include in my research...could not even be mentioned because the excavator had not published them...Talking to graduate students and young colleagues today, I realize the situation has not changed...

¹⁴ Herscher (1998) 331

¹⁵ For an overview see Kohl and Fawcett (1995) 3-18; Knapp and Antoniadou (1998) 13-43.

¹⁶ Papacostas (1999) I.17

¹⁷ Megaw (1950) 15; Papageorghiou (1966) 155; (1985) 300

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Turning his attention to an embarrassment of archaeological riches, he wrote:

Year after year this information increases, the volume of diaries and notebooks becomes larger...We are not immortals and unfortunately, many scholars die taking with them the secrets of many decades of excavation. For many excavations there is no published final report...Nevertheless we have not slowed the pace of digging...¹⁸

At a conference at the Cyprus American Archaeological Research Institute (CAARI), in Nicosia in 1998, Merrillees was excoriatingly succinct: 'If excavation is destruction, then non-publication is annihilation.'¹⁹

i.1.7 Field survey and 'big digs'

In field survey, data collection and analysis so overrides intervention that its methodology makes little sense without publication. Characteristic of field survey is a concern with settlement patterns (horizontal) rather than individual buildings (vertical), in ordinary lives rather than those of elites and in long-term trend-lines rather than *histoire événementielle*. What Brown has called the 'new archaeology of the late antique world' reflects, in part, the research methodologies of the field survey.

The new archaeology...is different from its predecessors...it looks out on new landscapes of which we had previously known nothing. It claims to tell us about long term trends of population, about patterns of settlement, about networks of exchange, about living standards and forms of social stratification that can be seen on the ground while they were never seen in texts.²⁰

The Cyprus Survey Branch of the Department of Antiquities was set up under Megaw in 1955, producing some of the earliest survey work anywhere in the Mediterranean.²¹ The Survey Department was closed by the Department of Antiquities in 1976, and there is now a considerable difference between low-impact and contextual field survey undertaken by multidisciplinary and overwhelmingly foreign teams, and Cypriot 'big-dig'

¹⁸ Karageorghis (1996) 28-30; Hadjisavas (2000) 5-9

¹⁹ Merrillees (2000) 53

²⁰ Brown (2011) 16

²¹ For example, the survey work undertaken in the southwest Peloponnese by McDonald and Hope Simpson and published in *AJA* 65 (1961) 221-260

archaeology undertaken in a markedly hierarchical milieu and largely confined to individual structures where the wider setting may not be a major concern.²²

Field survey does not exclude the excavation of individual buildings, but that is not its primary purpose. In her study *Ancient Akamas*, Fejfer devoted barely a tenth of her text to the basilica at Ayios Kononas.²³ Rautman established his excavation of three basilicas at Kalavassos in a wider setting in an important series of publications on the Cypriot countryside in the late sixth and early seventh-centuries.²⁴ Similarly, the on-going survey work of Pettegrew, Caraher and Scott-Moore at Pyla-Koutsopetria provides a context for the earlier excavation of a basilica by Hadjicosti.²⁵ In each case, the privileged status of churches was set aside in favour of a multidisciplinary re-contextualising.

i.1.8 Typological surveys

Churches were the principal concern of all the Constantinopolitanists, apart from Metcalf. To the problems of evidence must be added doubts about the contextual flexibility of the typological approach, particularly applied to the study of churches. For Wharton, Grabar's *Martyrium* embodied 'traditions of research in which abstract thinking and the urge to categorize are combined...'²⁶ Grabar divided fourth-century buildings into longitudinal congregational basilicas and centralized martyria. Krautheimer showed that Grabar's preference for classification over development produced too rigid a division.²⁷ But 'developmentalists,' too, tended towards linear explanations of what remained essentially exclusive typologies. Tafuri emphasised a more conflicted than continuous architectural history and buildings as subject to multiple constraints.²⁸ Three years after Tafuri's publication Mathews explored the liturgical 'constraint' in *The Early Churches of Constantinople*, introducing a bi-disciplinary, if not a multidisciplinary approach.²⁹ More recently, Balderstone emphasised theology rather than liturgy in her *Early Church Architectural Forms*, in which she sought to establish that certain kinds of architecture 'became accepted

²² For overviews see Cadogan (2004) 17-22; Cherry (2004) 23-35 and Hadjisavvas (2004) 37-41

²³ Fejfer (1995)

²⁴ Rautman (2000) 317-331; (2001) 241-262; (2003); (2004) 189-218; (2008) 90-4

²⁵ Pettegrew, Caraher and Scott Moore (2010)

²⁶ Wharton (1990) 3; Grabar (1943-6)

²⁷ Krautheimer (1969) 152, 157

²⁸ Tafuri (1968, 1980 trans.)

²⁹ Mathews (1971)

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through association with particular doctrinal positions.’³⁰ However, her subtitle - ‘a theologically contextual typology’ - is an explicit statement in favour of churches as a discreet subject of study. For example, Grossman writing in the same year, 2007, promoted churches as ‘enjoy[ing] a special status in the built environment, as structures where builders were likely to be most attentive and for which donors were most generous.’³¹

However, more than twenty years earlier Mango argued that an ‘exclusive...preoccupation with ecclesiastical architecture needs to be corrected.’³² For Bowden in 2008,

...the study of Christian buildings has become largely self-referencing. Buildings [are] interpreted by comparing them with other buildings...In this way a typology of Christian buildings has been developed in which architectural...features are ascribed origins in particular geographical areas or chronological periods...³³

The typological approach also had repercussions beyond the geographical and chronological. According to Mango,

... where a resemblance is found a connection is assumed even across a wide gulf in space and time.³⁴

While Mango demonstrates that inter-regional resemblance, lacking corroborative evidence, risks a spurious affinity, Bowden implies that a church typology confined by time and place risks an equally spurious regionalism.

i.1.9 ‘Place in whatever guise is...a social construct’³⁵

Islands generate an exaggerated specificity and homogeneity of place. Identified with a single name, so the argument goes, they must, *de facto*, be a single entity. Metcalf argued that in order to construct the history of Cyprus it was only possible to use ‘evidence relating specifically to Cyprus’ because ‘[t]rends within the Empire as a whole

³⁰ Balderstone (2007) iii

³¹ Grossmann (2007) 103

³² Mango (1991) 41

³³ Bowden (2008) 301-332

³⁴ Mango (1991) 40-44; Brubaker and Haldon (2001) 6

³⁵ Harvey (1993) 5

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were not necessarily matched in Cyprus.’ He went on to affirm that ‘Each province had its own distinctive economic life and social fabric’ identifying how ‘modern Byzantinists have sometimes offered comments on the history of Cyprus using evidence from the Empire as a whole’.³⁶ The present thesis diverges from his position, seeing its subject as less a place than a relationship – Cyprus and the eastern Mediterranean. How, then, could ‘economic life,’ understood in terms of trade and exchange, be conceived as distinctively Cypriot? If exchange involves interaction, conceptual space might well be understood in more flexible terms than those defined by either physical distinctiveness or administrative control.

i.2. Thesis: context

As a preamble to the methodology underpinning this thesis the following section examines two strategies, in one of which dominance is emphasised - the paradigm implicit in the approach taken by Megaw, Papageorghiou, Bakirtzis, Michaelides and Metcalf – while in the other the diverse, the micro and the local predominates.

i.2.1 The monocentric, monocausal and logocentric

It would be tempting to imagine with Matthews that the promotion of the imperial centre by some 20th century art historians was generated by a post-imperial nostalgia for the decline of empire, compounded, in the case of Constantinople, by the loss of much of the evidence that might have served as testament to that city’s magnificence.³⁷ Nevertheless, an absence of evidence has not inhibited attempts at reconstructing the ‘centre’ from material assembled at the ‘margins.’ Piccirillo for example, conjures a Constantinople *imaginaire* from mosaics in Jordan:

Because a similar change is evident in other regions of the Byzantine Empire at the time of the Emperor Justinian...we can only conclude that the impetus for change came from Constantinople, the capital city, and that this was part of a general tendency rather than a spontaneous evolution by local mosaicists.³⁸

³⁶ Metcalf (2009) 17-19

³⁷ Matthews (1995) 14-22

³⁸ Piccirillo (1992) 22; Dagron (1984)

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With much the same intent, Ward-Perkins sought to demonstrate that the mosaics at S.Vitale in Ravenna were part of a Justinianic masterplan conceived in Constantinople:

A fifth-century visitor to Ravenna who had previously seen Constantinople would have been in no doubt as to which imperial partner was the most powerful and wealthy ruler within the Roman world; and, similarly, an observer of both cities in the early sixth century would have rapidly formed the correct impression that Ravenna was an impressive but scaled-down version of the imperial capital ...[which] was by then the great city of the Mediterranean....³⁹

Maas, too, identifies an Empire 'whose focal point...[was] the city of Constantinople and the Emperor who dominated its life'.⁴⁰ And still more recently Grossmann has argued that

Constantinople is without doubt the leading cultural centre of the late Roman empire, the acknowledged origin of the most important cultural and artistic developments.⁴¹

Justinian's spin-doctors, several of them very recent indeed, extended the mystique of Constantinople and its Emperor from the physical limits of the empire to the temporal expansiveness of a whole era, prolonged beyond an 'Age of Justinian' and 'the long sixth-century' to the rise of Islam.⁴²

Models in which hierarchies predominate informed other approaches. For example, self-styled counter-revisionist Ward-Perkins describes the fall of Rome as a monocausal and catastrophic collapse by which 'the ancient world ended,' adding that 'this was essentially a bad thing.'⁴³ Logocentrism too, in so far as it insists on the primacy of text over other forms of evidence, is informed by a similar mind-set. Metcalf, for example, implied just such a primacy in his assessment of 'mere stones,' when he wrote that, '[m]uch scholarly effort has been devoted to the architectural details [of Cypriot churches] and the liturgical implications of their ground-plans; but these are mere stones,' warning of 'relying too much on the archaeological remains of basilicas'.⁴⁴

³⁹ Ward-Perkins (2000) 73, 75

⁴⁰ Maas (2004) 21

⁴¹ Grossmann (2007) 103-136

⁴² Evans (1996); Bell (2007) 1

⁴³ Ward-Perkins (2001) 240

⁴⁴ Metcalf (2009) 344, 253, 307

Finley felt it was self-evident 'that the potential contribution of archaeology to history is, in a rough way, inversely proportional to the quantity and quality of the available written sources.'⁴⁵ His approach may owe something to Hawkes, who allowed that archaeology might contribute to low-order conclusions (techniques of manufacture, subsistence economies etc.) while maintaining that, in high-order assumptions (social/political groups, religious institutions and the life of faith) textual evidence was paramount.⁴⁶

Monocentricisms, however, did not have things all their way. Other strategies emphasised the diverse, the polycasual and a more heterogeneous approach to the nature of evidence.

i.2.2 Bury's *Later Roman Empire* and 'Brown's big bang'

Counterparts to those mourning the loss of empire were those theorists who challenged the notion of a stable centre and periphery. Macleod, for example proposed the 'moving metropolis' as a challenge to the dominant model.⁴⁷ Indeed, a post-colonial (and post-Soviet) milieu engendered innovative ways of thinking about empire and the imperial stereotypes it generated, to which those who studied earlier empires could hardly remain immune.⁴⁸ Indeed, the 2003 edition of Brown's *The Rise of Western Christendom* emphasised micro-Christendoms as a kind of Christian 'moving metropolis' in response to the dominance of the same monocentric model challenged by Macleod.⁴⁹

The obverse of land-based monocentricity was a Mediterranean conceived as a diverse 'liquid continent'. A concept long understood by prehistorians, it was Braudel's *La Méditerranée* which first constructed the 'unique intelligibility' of the Mediterranean.⁵⁰ Horden and Purcell fragmented Braudel's holism in favour of a more particulate sea of semi-autonomous micro-regions:

⁴⁵ Finley (1975) 93

⁴⁶ Hawkes (1957)161-162

⁴⁷ Mcleod (1987) 217-49

⁴⁸ Cameron (2002) 175-176

⁴⁹ Brown (2003a)

⁵⁰ Braudel (1949)

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The zones and localities that jostle in the Mediterranean can be differentiated in intensity of their fragmentation...The Nature of the diversity is itself diverse.⁵¹

McCormick and Abulafia counter the third part of Braudel's thesis that famously downplayed the role of individuals, by emphasising the Mediterranean as a site of communication and human interaction.⁵² In their compendious specificity, the 'new thalassologists' shared a research trajectory with Late Antique studies, which also de-emphasised dominance in favour of more patinated accounts.⁵³

In a milieu in which centres gave way to micro-Christendoms and micro-regions, monocausalists were unlikely to escape interrogation. From the same city (Oxford) and in the same year (2005) that Ward-Perkins argued for Rome's catastrophic collapse, Heather identified the 'decline' of the Empire as polycasual: the ripple effect from vulnerable borders and a military too thinly spread protecting an empire with too limited a tax-raising capacity. However, as early as 1889, Bury in his *Later Roman Empire* argued that 'no general causes can be assigned which made...[decline and fall] inevitable.'⁵⁴ Furthermore, Bury questioned the decline *topos*, arguing that '[t]he change of masters was not the result of anything that could be called a cataclysm,' citing the relative 'success' of the East.⁵⁵

Where the monocentric and the monocausal were challenged, logocentrism was hardly likely to survive unscathed. In 1978, Mango offered an implicit caution against too great a reliance on texts.

Buildings provide the most tangible and concrete legacy of a past civilisation. They are historical documents: in some cases they even speak with a clearer voice than the written word...[T]he written records of Byzantine civilisation... tell us a great deal about the nature of Christ, but very little about the facts of everyday life.⁵⁶

⁵¹ Horden and Purcell (2000) 78

⁵² Horden and Purcell (2000); McCormick (2001); Hoffmann (2007) 3; Abulafia (2011). A counter argument might identify a fetishized Mediterranean as the new monocentrism.

⁵³ Stelzer (2010) 1

⁵⁴ Bury (1923) 1.311

⁵⁵ Bury (1923) I.viii

⁵⁶ Mango (1978) 8

Strzygowski had earlier insisted on the material over the textual, particularly in marginalised areas where texts were lacking.⁵⁷ Those margins were in part geographical, in part material. Riegl's *Spätromische Kunstindustrie* not only prioritized material evidence, it treated the otherwise-overlooked (belt buckles) and major monuments (the Arch of Constantine) as equally worthy of study, challenging connoisseurship as the dominating mode of art-history writing.⁵⁸ The inheritance from an approach which equated the quotidian and the formerly elite was a research methodology that conceived 'entirety' as 'an accumulation of vivid detail.'⁵⁹

i.2.3. Micro-history and multidisciplinary

Bury in his *History* and Jones in *The Later Roman Empire* defined their periods with reference to events – respectively, the deaths of Theodosius and Justinian, and the accession of Diocletian and the death of Maurice. Nevertheless, both reveal their proto-Late Antique credentials.⁶⁰ Jones' subtitle is *A Social, Economic and Administrative Survey* and Bury's introduction includes a description of his fifth-century sources strikingly close to the approach taken by students of Late Antiquity:

At that time hundreds of people were writing abundantly on all kinds of subjects: but amongst these there is no history of contemporary events and the story has to be pieced together from fragments, jejune chronicles, incidental references in poets, rhetoricians and theologians.⁶¹

Bury's concern that fragments do not easily coalesce into a history remains pertinent. In 2002, Elsner argued that '[t]he problem with plentiful data is that it is never easy to weld it into an overarching theory.'⁶² However, the value, even the possibility of *longue durée* accounts and overarching theories has been questioned by, amongst others, Lyotard and Deleuze and Guattari.⁶³ The virtual fragmentation of linear narratives into a 'thousand plateaus' of dense research undertaken by scholars whose practice was as distinct as it was un-hierarchical constituted an implicit recognition that full, let alone complete accounts, were no longer achievable through the agency of any one discipline

⁵⁷ Elsner (2002) 361; Marchand (1994) 106

⁵⁸ Riegl (1927 ed.) eg. 293 fig 80, 85 fig.41

⁵⁹ Bowersock, Brown and Grabar (1999) xii

⁶⁰ Jones (1964) 2 vols

⁶¹ Bury (1923) 1.vii

⁶² Elsner (2002) 375; Finley (1975) 93

⁶³ Lyotard (1984); Deleuze and Guattari (2004)

or dominant paradigm. How, then, might a history be assembled from an ‘abundance on all kinds of subjects’? One approach is the polyvocal, multi-authored volume of complementary essays assembled under light-touch editorship: *inter alia* Cameron and Garnsey; Brown, Bowersock and Grabar; Swain and Edwards; Jeffreys; Harvey and Hunter, and James.⁶⁴ These ‘new histories,’ the dominant model of the first decade of the twenty-first century, may be understood as a counterpart to the compendious single-authored juggernauts, which dominated histories of Byzantium in the latter half of the twentieth – *inter alia* Ostrogorsky, Vasiliev, Stratos, and Kazhdan and Treadgold.⁶⁵ However, much of Brown’s own writing appeared in slim volumes and these, in turn, may be seen in the context of those Italian historians of the 70s and 80s who argued that historical change could only be understood as micro-history. Principal amongst these was Ginzburg, for whom all historical knowledge was indirect and all means of approaching that indirectness were equivalent.⁶⁶

i.2.4 Unequal couples and equivalent partners

Multiplicity and the micro are central to the approach taken by Burrus and Lyman who emphasise ‘*diversity* rather than sameness...the *local* rather than the universal, and...*practice* rather than doctrine’.⁶⁷ ‘All kinds of subjects’ also accords with Bowes’ preference for the multidisciplinary: she proposes, for example, ‘a healthy divorce between texts and material culture [which] empowers both forms of evidence, and produces far richer histories, than an un-problematized marriage’.⁶⁸ It might be argued that her ‘richer histories’ depend on multiple partners, given the problems with interdisciplinarity conceived as a relationship of pairs, two cases of which are particularly relevant to this thesis.

Theology and liturgiology have been somewhat hesitant in their engagement with other disciplines, preferring to occupy a kind of parallel universe. Seeking to include theology in a more flexible relationship with other disciplines, Clark made a plea for ‘less theology, more history,’ which Harvey and Hunter in a recent volume of essays

⁶⁴ Cameron and Garnsey (1998), Brown, Bowersock and Grabar (1999) Swain and Edwards (2004), Jeffreys (2008), Harvey and Hunter (2008) and James (2010)

⁶⁵ Ostrogorski (1969); Vasiliev (1954); Stratos (1986); Kazhdan (1991); Treadgold (1977)

⁶⁶ Ginzburg (1989)

⁶⁷ Burrus and Lyman (2005) 2

⁶⁸ Bowes (2008b) 609

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(including one by Clark herself) understood in terms of interrogating theology through a wider range of disciplines, an approach also adopted by Kieckhefer who set his study of architecture and theology in the context of multiple histories.⁶⁹

Liturgy, too, proved somewhat intractable, while at the same time hovering tantalizingly over buildings whose functions it seemed on the verge of elucidating. In 1971 Mathews wrote discouragingly that 'Liturgical planning is a concept...still poorly developed in the study of architectural history; in the study of Byzantine architecture, it is a shabby patchwork of vague suspicions and ill-considered generalizations.'⁷⁰ De Blaauw was barely more encouraging, regretting that 'liturgiological scholarship has traditionally focussed upon texts and much less on the spatial implications of worship'.⁷¹ For Poulter, the courtship of liturgy and architecture had reached an impasse: 'the relevance of architectural development to changes in the liturgy, once a hopeful line of enquiry, can now be shown in particular cases to be patently untrue,' given 'the variety of plans common to a given region.'⁷² A formal relationship between liturgy and architecture foundering on local variation is strikingly similar to developments in liturgiology itself: Dix argued that the liturgy was fixed at an early date, a view challenged by White as presenting too seamless a narrative.⁷³ Bradshaw took the challenge further, showing that the evolution of the liturgy was gradual, disjunctive and varied in practice.⁷⁴

Interdisciplinarity, which I understand as a relationship between two disciplines, has been undermined as much by the attempt of its advocates to construct a stable relationship as by the success of its detractors in questioning that stability. Furthermore, an inherent weakness in the bipartite relationship has been the tendency of one partner to attain dominance over the other. A multi-disciplinary approach, on the other hand, implies a community in which scholars are less inclined to see other specialisms as functionally ancillary to their own and for whom a more inclusive approach provides access to the formerly overlooked. Two such topics have received particular attention, the countryside and the private sphere, and in both cases the local is stressed. Holum has emphasised the rise of local bishops to economic and political prominence in the

⁶⁹ Clark (1986); Harvey and Hunter (2009); Kieckhefer (2004)

⁷⁰ Mathews (1971) 3, 5

⁷¹ De Blaauw (1991) 2

⁷² Poulter (1994) 249

⁷³ Dix (1945); White (1990) 15-17

⁷⁴ Bradshaw (2004)

sixth-century, a point argued in separate volumes by Rapp and Brogiolo.⁷⁵ Recent economic histories including Liebeschuetz, Laiou, Banaji, reflect a similar tendency.⁷⁶ Sarris identifies the independence of local landowners from imperial authority and the rise of a magistracy, which, while it represented imperial authority, nevertheless controlled access to local sources of wealth.⁷⁷

i.3 Thesis: parameters

i.3.1 Basilicas: privileged status or artefactual outcome?

The present study draws on a number of disciplines - archaeology, architecture, iconography, liturgy, theology, economics and ecclesiastical and military history – as its principal tools, without offering special pleading for any one. Nevertheless, it might be argued that while the study claims to be heterogeneous in its approach, its emphasis on basilicas serves to reinforce their privileged status. However, any such privilege is tempered by a recognition that churches constitute the material outcome of wider issues – the sense, perhaps, in which Papacostas refers to churches as testamentary.⁷⁸ Furthermore, their relationship to those issues is by no means consistent. The three-aisled, triapsidal basilica may have been a Cypriot vernacular in the later fifth and sixth centuries, but at the end of the fourth and the beginning of the fifth century, when the nature of the Trinity was a live issue, church forms may well have been integral to the debate. On the other hand, an early-seventh-century building on the Akrotiri Peninsular, which appears to turn its back on the vernacular, might nevertheless be understood as Orthodox in reaction to theological innovations from the capital. Accepting an *a priori* status for churches, therefore, not only obscures the extent to which the same form may play different roles over time, it also obscures the extent to which different forms may affirm the same doctrinal position - or none at all. Basilicas, then, allow access to wider issues and debates and may, indeed, be their artefactual outcome but they lack the contextual stability on which pre-eminence depends and from which a typological account might be forged.

⁷⁵ Holum (2004) 87-112; Brogiolo (2011) 79-80; Rapp (2005) 293

⁷⁶ Liebeschuetz (2003); Laiou (2002); Banaji (2007)

⁷⁷ Sarris (2006)

⁷⁸ Papacostas (1999) has as its subtitle 'The Testimony of its Churches.'

Questioning the status of churches might be extended to a more speculative approach to power structures in the eastern Mediterranean. It would be rash to assume, for example, that Cyprus's relationship with Constantinople was unicursal and consistent or that the island's status was throughout subaltern and peripheral - a deference implicit in Megaw's question 'Metropolitan or Provincial?' The working hypothesis of this thesis is the proposition that Cyprus occupied a nodal position in the eastern Mediterranean between the later fourth, fifth and the first half of the sixth centuries after which it was marginalised administratively but nevertheless remained fierce in its avowal of conciliar Orthodoxy, opposing detractors in the wider empire regardless of their status. Hence, *contra* Metcalf, evidence from the wider Empire is crucial; indeed, in order to argue the proposition, extended excursions from the principal material evidence may be necessary. Some excursions will be geographical, for example into the wider Mediterranean (Chapter 1), Egypt and Palestine (Chapter 2) or they may involve a change in orientation (Chapter 3). Others will extend beyond a tight periodization and the formal structural properties of basilicas (Chapter 4) and still others will cross disciplines. The part played by architecture in the controversies of the late sixth, and early seventh centuries would be meaningless without an understanding of the complexities of contemporary theological debate (Monophysitism. Monoergism and Monotheletism in Chapter 5). 'Excursions,' however, make little sense without some conception of place and period as their starting points.

i.3.2 Place

In his review of Metcalf's *Byzantine Cyprus*, Kaldellis wrote that '...fundamental problems should be kept alive in a deficient state of knowledge.'⁷⁹ In section 1 I identified deficiencies of data, the different methodologies involved in its collection and variations in its dissemination and availability. These are, perhaps, no more than the usual discrepancies with which scholars have to work.

In the case of Cyprus one discrepancy, however, is exceptional. An island with a hinterland dominated in the southwest by the Troodos Mountains (1952m), closed off in the north by the Kyrenia range (up to 1024m high and 160km long), with, 'between the mountains', the rain-deprived plain of the Mesaoria, is likely to be largely coastal in its

⁷⁹ Kaldellis (2011) 86

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settlement patterns. Different parts of the island not only had connections with different parts of the eastern Mediterranean, those connections, I argue in Chapter 1, may well have been stronger than connections with other parts of the same island. For example, however abundant the archaeological data from the south, it cannot be used to draw conclusions about the island as a whole precisely because that wholeness cannot be assumed. We might be cautious, therefore, in speaking of ‘Cypriot basilicas’, which implies a Cypriot *genus*, when it might be more appropriate to speak of basilicas *on* Cyprus, an approach which allows for affinities overseas while admitting diversity at home. Promoting a distinctively ‘Cypriot’ taxonomy, as we have seen, risks appropriation by a particularly *retardataire* sort of nationalism, a spurious analogy dismissed by Jones for whom ‘evidence for nationalism of any kind in the later Roman Empire is tenuous in the extreme,’ a view recently forcefully restated by Geary.⁸⁰

i.3.3 Period

If space is malleable are ‘periods’ any more secure? The position adopted by Deleuze and Guattari may lack serviceable definition, but it licences an altogether more flexible approach to both. Their preference for a ‘coming and going rather than starting and finishing’ not only raises questions about periodization, it permits an alternative to chronological dominance.⁸¹ The shape of later trend lines, for example, can nuance a trajectory the full meaning of which is not apparent where evidence is wholly confined to a rigidly, period-specific reading. Abandoning the vertical, linear and hierarchical, Deleuze and Guattari opt for a model that is ‘...open and connectable in all its dimensions’, spreading horizontally and heterogeneously.⁸² A model that eludes boundaries, and ‘... is always in the middle, between things...’ resonates with Late Antiquity understood as a period of transition.⁸³

i.3.4 Terminology

Late Antiquity is a very flexible period, nowadays generally defined in cultural terms.⁸⁴

⁸⁰ Jones (1959) 295; Geary (2003) 41-62

⁸¹ Deleuze and Guattari (1987) 28

⁸² Deleuze and Guattari (1987) 13, 23, 24

⁸³ Deleuze and Guattari (1987) 27

⁸⁴ Ward-Perkins (2001) 240

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...surely the effect of the discovery of this later period and the richness of the material...is...to liberate historians from their old classical focus and to open up new possibilities, rather than to bind them still more strongly to a comparison with the classical past.⁸⁵

Although I have used the term 'Late Antiquity' I have yet to justify its use. It may seem paradoxical that a period conceived in terms of 'vibrant renewal' continues to be served by a prefix suggesting a main event elsewhere-than-here, the point made by Wharton, who argued that Late Antiquity implies an inferior appendix to a more perfect classicism. The field is further confused by a plethora of terms - late and later Roman, early Byzantine, early Christian - all referring to approximately the same period and dominated by a single centre or faith. Rautman's work at Kalavassos, for example, is published under three descriptors, Late Roman, Byzantine and Late Antique.⁸⁶

'Early Byzantine,' the term preferred by Megaw, is also unhelpfully flexible.⁸⁷ Engelzakis begins the period in 330, but rather than terminating with the Arab raids of 649, as is usually the case, he extends the period to 699.⁸⁸ Moreover, Mango pointed out that '[t]here never was a state that called itself the Byzantine Empire.'⁸⁹

The 'Roman' issue is barely less conflicted. To Horden and Purcell's proposition that there was 'a strong sense in which the Roman Empire was not Roman,' Bowersock counter-claimed on behalf of 'Late Roman' that the citizens of the Eastern Empire called themselves *Romaioi*. Furthermore, he argued, Constantinople *was* Rome - the Italian city of the same name being largely unknown on the streets of Eastern Mediterranean cities.⁹⁰ Bowersock's Rome may have changed its address but it remained a dominant centre nevertheless. However, more than a century earlier Riegl had offered a definition of Roman that was wholly un-Romanocentric:

⁸⁵ Cameron (2001) 238-239

⁸⁶ Rautman: Late Roman (1992, 1998, 2000, 2001, 2004), Byzantine (2005) and Late Antique (2003)

⁸⁷ Megaw (1958), (1974). C.f. Catling (1982) 234 '...the Early Christian period (or, perhaps better – the Early Byzantine Period)'

⁸⁸ Engelzakis (1995) at 42 writes, 'early Byzantine is the only one [term] which properly belongs to the history of the Roman Empire in the East, the term 'later Empire', which is still used by some Cypriot archaeologists, being justifiable only in the West.'

⁸⁹ Mango (1978) 7

⁹⁰ Bowersock (2009) 47

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In selecting the word 'Roman' instead of 'antique' I had in mind the entire Roman empire but not – as I wish to emphasise strongly...the city of Rome or the italic people or the nations of the western half of the empire.⁹¹

'Early Christian' is similarly problematic. There is a discrepancy, for example, between Early Christians (post the death of Christ) and Early Christian architecture as defined, for example, by Krautheimer.⁹² Generally assumed to have ended with the Arab incursions, 'Early Christian' lacks terms comparable with Early and Middle Byzantine (how might 'Middle Christian' be construed?).

Furthermore, terms redolent of Byzantine, Roman or Christian dominance discourage co-habitation. It is, for example, quite likely that the community which inhabited the Late Roman city and rendered unto Caesar was the same community which, reconfigured as a congregation, inhabited an Early Christian world and rendered unto God. The principal basis, however, for rejecting 'Early Christian' is its dominance in accounts written by overwhelmingly Christian authors, to the exclusion of Hellenic, Judaic and Mithraic elements that, according to Mango, continued to be 'a live issue' to c.600.⁹³ Moreover, Christians have traditionally defined 'pagans' as those-who-are-not-Christian.⁹⁴ Rather, 'Hellēnes' was the term 'pagans' used to describe themselves and by which they were described.⁹⁵ Recent scholarly interest in what the two groups shared has shown that the Christian-Pagan binary was by no means clear-cut.⁹⁶ Because many cults had multiple deities, Philo called their followers 'polytheists,' but pagan monotheism too has begun to receive scholarly attention.⁹⁷ Conversely, it might be argued that polytheism was the prevailing habit of cultic observance and that the cult of saints and devotion to the Virgin were poly-cultic in practice if not strictly polytheist.⁹⁸

The descriptor 'Late Antiquity', therefore, avoids the default dominance of place or faith and offers a broadly-defined period extending from 250 to around 800, which, in the

⁹¹ Riegl (1927 ed.) 17

⁹² Krautheimer (1986)

⁹³ Mango (1963) 53-75, 55; (1980) 89-90

⁹⁴ Wharton (1996) xii

⁹⁵ Salzman (2008) 186-202; Rousselle (1999) 625; Kahlos (2007) 22, 25

⁹⁶ The early-seventh century *Vita* of Theodore of Sykeon, ch.118 uses the term 'Greek' when referring to pagans. See Dawes and Baynes (1996) 146; also Athanassiadi and Frede (1999) and Mitchell and van Nuffelen (2010). Liebeschuetz (2000) 984-1013 points to an early and shared monotheism.

⁹⁷ Daube (1994-5) 317

⁹⁸ Brown (1981) 15

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generosity of its length, with *termini* un-bracketed by events, is as nearly a non-period as a period might be.⁹⁹

i.4 Thesis: material

i.4.1 Earlier material

Although Section 2 was largely devoted to opposing methodologies and the literature that underpinned them, identifying the relevant literature has been an integral part of the introduction as a whole. This final section begins with a brief survey of some of the earliest texts for Cyprus under the headings of hagiography, history, the description of buildings and the proceedings of Ecumenical Councils – although, given that Ginzburg challenged the primacy of texts, arguing that ‘There are no neutral texts,’ we might be cautious in describing these as primary, if ‘primary’ means in some way privileged.¹⁰⁰

i.4.2 Hagiography

For Mango hagiography was ‘the literary equivalent of a religious painting; when we gaze at an icon...we do not regard it as a real portrait’, hence, as a vehicle for the promotion of a saint’s reputation, veracity was not an issue.¹⁰¹

The model hagiographical account was written c.356-62 by Epiphanius’ sometime correspondent, Athanasius, on the life of *Life of Anthony*, the founder of ascetic monasticism.¹⁰² Pachomius (293?-346), the founder of coenobitic monasticism, is celebrated in Coptic and Greek *Vitae*.¹⁰³ It is possible that Epiphanius had contacts with both Anthony and Pachomius when he was studying in Egypt as a young man, but even if he was not in direct contact with them he would surely have been familiar with the milieu of both.¹⁰⁴ Epiphanius’ own *Vita* (c.439-478) establishes its subject as a major figure amongst fourth-century clerics. As so often for the modern reader, it is evocations from the margins of early texts that prove most authentic, hence Rapp, whose text of

⁹⁹ Marcone (2008) 4-19; Cameron (2002) 165-6

¹⁰⁰ Ginzburg (1989) 161

¹⁰¹ Mango (1984) 41

¹⁰² Bartelink (1994); Meyer (1978)

¹⁰³ Veilleux, (1980) for the Coptic life and Halkin (1931), Festugière (1965) and Athanassakis (1975) for the *Vita Prima Graeca*.

¹⁰⁴ Sozomen *HE* 6.32.3 (2010 reprint) 266

the *Vita Epiphanii* is used throughout the thesis, argues convincingly that its text evokes 'Palestine and Cyprus in the 4th century.'¹⁰⁵ On the other hand, the *Vita* relocates Epiphanius' formative education from monastic Egypt to Palestine which the *Vita's* compiler was clearly intent on promoting as the crucible of monasticism.

Vitae were intimately related to place, both as readings on saints' days and as part of establishing the reputation of pilgrimage sites. As a pilgrim hub, Cyprus had *loca sancta* of its own: Hilarion at Paphos (Toumballos?), Barnabas at Salamis (either Ayios Barnabas or Campanopetra), Auxibios at Soloi, Tychon at Amathus, and inland, Spyridon at Tremetousia and Herakleidios at Tamassos. Amongst later saints, John the Almsgiver is usually associated with the basilica of Ayios Tykhon, in his home city of Amathus. Most Cypriot saints were the subject of a *Vita* or a panegyric.¹⁰⁶ Jerome's (340/2-420) *Vita Hilarionis* was written in 391, probably in Palestine; however, the greater number of lives were local products.¹⁰⁷ *Sancti Barnabae Laudatio*, for example, was written by Alexander, a monk at Ayios Varnavas.¹⁰⁸ The life of Auxibios was substantially 'borrowed' from the *Vita Epiphanii*¹⁰⁹. Spyridon was celebrated in two Cypriot *Vitae*: one by Leontius, the bishop of Neapolis (Limassol) (590-668) and the other by Theodore of Paphos which was famously given a public reading at Tremetousia in 655.¹¹⁰ Leontius also wrote the *Vita Iohannis Eleemosynarii* (c.641), a life of John the Almsgiver, whose background is a period of early-seventh-century crisis with which its author would have been hardly less familiar than his subject.¹¹¹ Finally, John, himself, wrote a panegyric on his fellow Amathusian, Tychon.¹¹² If Maximus the Confessor (c.580-662) whose life is celebrated in two *Vitae*, one Greek and the other Syriac, lacks immediate links with Cyprus – he may have visited the island as a young man and he certainly corresponded with a Cypriot monk – he is nevertheless a crucial figure in the Monothelite debates in which the island was unwillingly implicated.¹¹³

¹⁰⁵ Rapp (1991) 1.2

¹⁰⁶ Delehaye (1907) 161-297: for Herakleidios see 236-37. Also Maraval (1985) 358-60

¹⁰⁷ *PL* 23, 29-54; Jerome 'Life of Hilarion' in White (1998) 85-115; Delehaye (1907) 241-2, 252-67; Hackett (1901) 407-11; Sozomen *HE* 5.10.3 (2010 reprint) 192

¹⁰⁸ *PG* 87, c.4087-4106; van Deun (1993) 15-122; Delehaye (1907) 235-6; Cosby (forthcoming)

¹⁰⁹ *BHG* 204; Delehaye (1907) 237, 259; Noret (1993) 139-202

¹¹⁰ Delehaye (1907) 239-41; van den Ven (1953)

¹¹¹ *PG* 93, c.1617-1660; Dawes and Baynes (1948) 195; Delehaye (1907) 244-6; Festugière (1984) 329

¹¹² Dawes and Baynes (1948) 195; Delehaye (1907) 244-5, 229-32, 273-74

¹¹³ *PG* 90, 68A1-109B9; Brock (1973); Allen and Neil (2003)

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Epiphanius himself provides some of the earliest texts for Cyprus. The principal antagonists of his *Ancoratus* (*The well-anchored man*) (374) are Arians and the teachings of Origen, a theologian for whom Epiphanius espoused a particular loathing.¹¹⁴ A substantial part of the text was devoted to heresies, his most exhaustive treatment of which was the *Panarion* (374-377) - probably the model for all subsequent heresy lists - which identified 80 'errors' and served as the 'medicine chest' for the afflicted.¹¹⁵ Epiphanius' letter to John of Jerusalem, which attacks John's perceived Origenism, is an important document for the meeting between the two bishops in the Holy City in 393-4, the repercussions of which are explored in Chapter 2.¹¹⁶

i.4.2 History

Few texts survive from the first part of the fifth century but the mid-century saw two major contributions. Socrates Scholasticus' (380-447/8) grandfather had been converted by Epiphanius' mentor, Hilarion. Nevertheless, his first name suggests a continuing regard for Hellenic culture. Socrates' *Ecclesiastical History* covers the eastern Mediterranean from 306 to 439 and Book I.12.8 implies he visited Cyprus.¹¹⁷ He is scathing about John Chrysostom and Cyril of Jerusalem, with both of whom Epiphanius was in contact, and attacks Origen's detractors, although Epiphanius is not amongst them. The second major *Ecclesiastical History*, by Sozomen (c.400-c.450), covers the period 312-425.¹¹⁸ Book VII 19 mentions that, in fifth-century Cyprus, villages too had bishops.¹¹⁹ The most relevant of the later *Ecclesiastical Histories* is by John, the Monophysite bishop of Ephesus (c.507-c.586), only the third part of which survives, covering the period 571-586, and includes the conflict between Stephan, a Monophysite bishop from Cyprus and John Scholasticus, the patriarch of Constantinople referred to in my conclusion.¹²⁰

¹¹⁴ PG 43,c.12-236; Holl (1915)

¹¹⁵ PG 42,c.156-774; Williams (1994-2009); Amidon (1990). This exemplary number refers to the Song of Songs, the 80 concubines and the one true bride and is possibly related to *Panarion* II. 26.17.4-8 in which attempts are made to seduce the young Epiphanius: Williams (2009) I.106-7

¹¹⁶ PG 43, c.379-392

¹¹⁷ PG 67:28-842; Maraval 2004-7; Socrates I.12.8 (2009 reprint) 41-2

¹¹⁸ PG 67:843-1630; Sozomen *HE* (2010 reprint); Festugière and Sabbah (1983); Walford (1846).

¹¹⁹ Sozomen *HE* (2010 reprint) 305

¹²⁰ Payne-Smith (1860); van Ginkel (1995)

i.4.3 Buildings

The most extended text dedicated to sixth-century buildings is Procopius' *De aedificiis*: of Cyprus he mentions the construction of 'the poor-house of St Konon. His water-channel he [Justinian] renewed on Cyprus.'¹²¹ Neither has been satisfactorily identified and *De aedificiis* has limited value as an index of imperial outreach on the island under Justinian.¹²²

i.4.4 Councils

Tanner provides an invaluable background to Cypriot representation at Ecumenical Councils.¹²³ As an index of the island's involvement in wider ecclesiastical issues, their proceedings are referred to throughout the thesis. The construction of Orthodoxy is principally identified through the councils held at Nicaea (325), which defined the Father and the Son as consubstantial, and Constantinople (381), which initiated the debate which would, probably at a synod in Constantinople the following year, define the place of the Holy Spirit (Chapter 2).¹²⁴ The Council at Ephesus (431) recognised (a) Cypriot demands for autocephalous status independent of jurisdiction from Antioch and (b) the *Theotokos* as the Mother of God (Chapter 4). The Council of Chalcedon (451), which adopted the hypostatic union of Christ's human and divine natures, widened the schism with Monophysitism which recognised Christ's divine nature alone.¹²⁵ Finally, the Lateran Council (649) rejected Imperial compromise with the Monophysites (Chapter 5). A letter from the Cypriot archbishop Sergius, thoroughly Roman in tone, was appended to that Council's proceedings.¹²⁶

i.4.5 The later material

¹²¹ Procopius in Dewing (1954) V.ix.32

¹²² Fejfer (1995) 29; Procopius in Dewing V.ix 36-8 (1954) 361. For Cyprus/Kypros as a copyist's error for Cyrrhus/Kyrros in Syria see Christodoulou (2003) 149-55

¹²³ Tanner (1990) 2 vols

¹²⁴ For Nicaea see Luibhéid (1982)

¹²⁵ Price and Gaddis (2005)

¹²⁶ Cubitt (2009) 133-147. The Second Council of Constantinople (553) is not included in this overview, however the Lateran Council (649) is included although it is not usually listed amongst the seven Ecumenical Councils convened in the East between the first and second councils held at Nicaea (325 and 787)

Introduction

The first descriptions of Late Antique Cyprus emerge in texts chiefly devoted to Lusignan architecture (1192-1489) by writers for whom the gothic revival was closely identified with national identity. Camille Enlart (1862-1927) visited Cyprus between 1895 and 1897 under the aegis of the French Ministère de l'Instruction Publique et des Beaux-Arts. While earlier structures are identified in his *L'Art Gothique et la Renaissance en Chypre*, he admits to little interest in them.¹²⁷ The architect George Jeffery (1855-1939) visited Cyprus from his base in Jerusalem in 1897 and shared Enlart's interests and prejudices, including the opinion that, apart from Lusignan Gothic, 'there [was] certainly nothing else in Cyprus to attract the attention of the visitor.'¹²⁸ He became Curator of Ancient Monuments shortly after settling on the island in 1904/5 and began publishing a series of articles, culminating in *A Description of the Historic Monuments of Cyprus*, in which he recorded many important buildings for the first time, making them known to wider scholarship and thereby contributing to their survival.¹²⁹ The third, but earliest, of the pioneering scholars was the Russian Jakov Smirnov (1869-1918), who visited the island in 1895. The Studio of Decorative Mosaics in St Petersburg provides a context for his place as the first scholar to recognise the importance of the mosaics at Lythrankomi and Kiti.¹³⁰

Interest in 'Byzantine' monuments was, nevertheless, slow to develop. Although founded in 1893, the Cyprus Museum had no Byzantine section before the intervention of the governor, Sir Robert Storrs (r.1926-1932).¹³¹ At broadly the same time, Soteriou (1880-1965) published preliminary findings for a projected corpus of the island's Byzantine buildings, as 'The Early Christian and Byzantine Remains of Cyprus', in 1931.¹³² Based on this material, he planned a two-volume catalogue; the first, of plates and plans, was published, but the text volume never appeared.¹³³

For the next quarter of a century English-speaking scholarship again predominated. In 1936, four years after becoming the inspector of antiquities for the Cyprus Museum, Rupert Gunnis (1899-1965) published his archaeological guide, *Historic Cyprus*.¹³⁴ In the

¹²⁷ Enlart (1987 ed.)

¹²⁸ Jeffery (1897) 42

¹²⁹ Pilides (2009)

¹³⁰ Smirnov (1897) 65-91

¹³¹ Storrs (1937) 492

¹³² Soteriou (1931) 477-90

¹³³ Soteriou (1935)

¹³⁴ Gunnis (1936); Symons (1987) 3-10

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same year, another architect, 'Peter' Megaw (1910-2006), was appointed Director of the recently established Department of Antiquities, a post he held from 1936 to the end of colonial rule in 1960.¹³⁵ Neither a trained archaeologist nor a Byzantinist, Megaw's contribution to the archaeology of the island is unmatched. He continued Jeffery's and Soteriou's work, excavating, recording and restoring monuments with the help of the architects Pericleous and Mogabgab, whose plans for Soteriou remain a valuable resource. When the British left Cyprus in 1960, Megaw was appointed Director of the British School at Athens, from where he continued to make major contributions to Cypriot studies.

i.4.6 Coda: chapter layout

Evidence for the proposition that Cyprus did not emerge from isolation to 'greater imperial outreach,' but rather played a central role in the formation of Orthodoxy in the fourth century, and was fearless in its defence in the seventh, is presented in five broadly chronological chapters and a conclusion.

Chapter 1 argues that a surrounding sea, as an index of isolation, is a nesophile fallacy. Rather, the fourth-century Mediterranean was the medium through which networks of jurisdiction, allegiance and exchange challenged isolation and remoteness as the defining characteristic of islands. Chapter 2 sets the late fourth- and early-fifth century basilica of Agios Epiphanius at Salamis in the context of the Second Ecumenical Council and the Sion basilica in Jerusalem as the principal structural embodiment of the Council's deliberations. Chapter 3 develops the affinity with Jerusalem, arguing that the baptismal liturgy adopted in Cyprus was initially dependent on the rite developed in the Holy City in the 350s; later changes to Cypriot baptisteries attest both to a re-orientation towards wider Mediterranean practice, probably Syrian in origin, and to an enhanced status for Cypriot bishops. Chapter 4 changes register to examine the iconography of the three surviving apse mosaics of the Theotokos on Cyprus, firstly in the context of the bema and its furnishings, and secondly as a rural appropriation of a more widely attested *topos*. Chapter 5 surveys some plausible contexts for the early-seventh century transeptual building at Katalymmata-ton-Plakoton, a form otherwise unknown on the island or in the capital, but surviving in Rome and in the vicinity of Alexandria. The

¹³⁵ Karageorghis (1985) 1-10

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conclusion opens with a reassessment of the reputation of Epiphanius, arguing for his place in the vanguard of fourth-century faith-forging. Conversely, it cites two examples of sixth-century aggrandisement by Constantinople – its attempts, firstly, to usurp Jerusalem and, secondly, to appropriate the position of supreme patriarch. The thesis concludes by seeking an explanation for the continuing allure of the ‘Constantinople mystique.’

Notes

(1). The term orthodoxy was appropriated by disparate and diametrically opposed groups. Where Orthodoxy is capitalized it refers to adherents of *all* the Ecumenical Councils before the Arab invasions. Monophysites, for example, based their orthodoxy on Councils prior to Chalcedon.

(2) Greek toponyms have been retained as the currency of identification in scholarly citation.

(3) AD should be assumed unless otherwise stated.

(4) The material is presented in three volumes – text, figures and gazetteer. The plans which appear in volumes 2 and 3 are schematic re-workings primarily for purposes of comparison.

(5) Thanks to Professor Mike Cosby for the image on the front cover of v.1, to Jane Chick for the photographs of Ābū Mīnā and to Google Earth© for the satellite imagery. All other photographs are the author’s unless otherwise attributed.

1 Cyprus: a fluid zone of transition

Chapter 1

The factors which define the history of Cyprus are its immutable geographical position.¹

Islands 'are very often better conceived as fluid zones of transition...than as clear-cut lines on a landscape or a map.'²

Cyprus...an island far removed from the mainland, and abounding in harbours, besides having numerous towns, is made famous by two cities, Salamis and Paphos...This Cyprus is so fertile and so abounds in products of every kind, that without the need of any help from without, by its native resources alone, it builds cargo ships from the very keel to the topmost sails and equipping them completely, entrusts them to the deep.³

1.i Argument

The assumption that islands are isolated has been astonishingly persistent. Papacostas provides useful facts about Cyprus: at 9251sq.km the island is the third largest in the Mediterranean; it lies 69km south of Anemurium in Cilicia, 110km west of Antioch in Syria and 420km north of Alexandria in the Dioecesis Aegypti [1.1].⁴ However he prefaces his data with the comment that 'Cyprus stands alone...obstinately moored off the coast of the Levant.'⁵ Hill, too, described the island as 'remote from the centre of the Empire.'⁶ For Gunnis Cyprus was 'a little world in itself.'⁷ In 1993 Hadjisavvas argued that 'The insular character of Cyprus is the main factor which formulated its place in history from the very moment of its habitation up to the present day.'⁸ Descriptions of this kind have fostered the view that islands are categorically distinct – a distinctiveness reflected in their material culture.

¹ Englezakis (1995) 42

² Horden and Purcell (2000) 24

³ Ammianus Marcellinus XIV 8.14 in Rolfe (1935) v.173

⁴ Pliny *NH* V xxxv 129 in Rackham (1947) II.317-9. 'It contains 15 towns, New and Old Paphos, Curias, Citium, Corinaeum, Salamis, Amathus, Lapethos, Soloe, Tamasos, Epidaurus, Chyti, Arsinoe, Carpasium and Golgoe; and formerly there was also Cinyria, Mareum and Idalium.'

⁵ Papacostas (1999) 6

⁶ Hill (1940) I.258 n.1

⁷ Gunnis (1936) vii

⁸ Hadjisavvas (1995) 89

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This chapter is in five sections. The first discusses islands as coasts rather than landmasses, in which the relationship of land and sea, littoral and hinterland, is negotiable. The second proposes that the Late Antique Mediterranean constituted a remarkably changeable environment: tides, currents and winds, contemporary descriptions of earthquakes and tsunamis evoke the solid earth turning liquid and the sea revealing landscapes in its depth. In a related metaphor referring to trade, travel and the transmission of ideas, the sea is construed as a positive, inhabited, and 'solid' space, subverting the cartographical 'fix' and evoking a Mediterranean of concepts rather than things. The third section argues that Cyprus was not a single place simply because a single name served to identify it. Geographical proximity did not secure access for seafarers or exclude remoteness for ascetics. Such a fluid conception of space meant that the Mediterranean ended not at the shoreline but where the littoral met the hinterland, the space between the two constituting, in the case of Cyprus, a Christianised circuminsular ring. The fourth section identifies a Christian Mediterranean which, on the one hand, adjudicates against sinners and deviants from Ecumenical Orthodoxy and, on the other provisions Cyprus with its saints and bishops. As the context for the final chapter a coda asks to what extent the Akrotiri peninsula, in so far as it was serviced from the sea, continued to function as an island into the sixth and seventh centuries, even though it had physically ceased to be one.

A nesophile fallacy defines an island as land isolated by sea, attracting descriptors redolent of a discourse of dominance in which the more-or-less undeveloped is viewed from an assumed centre. But the island-as-concept is mutable, hence rich in variants and Cyprus, which constituted a nodal point of exchange, was elective and independent in its alliances, adaptive in its responses and, in many respects, an equal amongst equals.

1 Cyprus: a fluid zone of transition

1.1 Island approaches

There are no more deserts, there are no more islands. Yet the need for them makes itself felt.⁹

In the opening chapter of Golding's *Lord of the Flies*, Ralph makes a pertinent statement, '...we've got to decide if this is an island.'¹⁰ The necessity to decide allows the possibility that human agency might override geography. In 2004 Clark identified three criteria: 'size, distance to a continental mainland and intensity of contact and exchange with other places.'¹¹ Although he permits no absolute definition, two rubrics apply – a lexical one – as land surrounded by water - and a metaphorical one – as a more or less separated place. While peninsulas, deserts, mountains and forests were considered 'places apart' and hence suitable habitats for ascetics, hermits and Holy Men, they were often metaphorical and terrestrial 'islands' chosen for a remoteness more exemplary than real.¹² The *Vita S. Antoni*, for example, describes the paradox of an ascetic living in solitude 'near his own house.'¹³

Referring to Cyprus, Held claimed that one measure of insularity was visibility from a mainland.¹⁴ But visibility is no more an indicator of remoteness than distance. Close to the shore, the island of Geronisos off the Cypriot west coast rises sharply from the sea to a height of 21m [1.2]. Accessed with difficulty, two landing places were necessary to cope with changes in winds and currents.¹⁵ Archaeological evidence shows that in the sixth century a small group of monks inhabited the island, maintaining sheep and goats and cultivating a small garden and an olive grove. Although conceptually remote, their laura was nevertheless clearly visible from the thriving settlement at Peyia only 280m away on the mainland.¹⁶ Isolation was not only an imagined construction by ascetics; it has served

⁹ Camus (1968) 85

¹⁰ Golding (1954) 20

¹¹ Clark (2004) 288

¹² Brown (1971a) 91

¹³ Athanasius in Meyer (1950) 20. Halkin (1945) 57, describes the seventh-century Cypriot ascetic Kaïoumos was a 'reclus à Ammochostos' (Famagusta)

¹⁴ Held (1993) 26

¹⁵ Connelly (2000) 245, 255, fig.7

¹⁶ Connelly (2005) 152, 157; Connelly and Wilson (2002) 269-292

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as a model which authors, archaeologists and anthropologists have used as a controlling framework for particularly intense kinds of examination.

1.2 Island laboratories

If More's 'new island' *Utopia* was as much a no-place as an ideal one, Mann's lake-isle in the *Holy Sinner* was a no-man's land, 'a state for the stateless' and 'world-remote.'¹⁷ Crusoe's could be an 'Island of Despair.'¹⁸ For Durrell, Cyprus was somewhere 'other,' 'a strange mixture of flavours, the Bible, Anatolia and Greece.' Perhaps more pertinent for the present argument is the multifaceted island-commonwealth of Shakespeare's *Tempest* imagined as a continuous interplay of the terrestrial and aqueous.¹⁹

1.2 The Island of the Day Before²⁰

Prehistorians have emphasised the part played by restricted mobility and technological limitation in preserving insularity. In 'Islands as laboratories for the study of culture process' Evans argued that the

...special physical conditions of islands...made them particularly appropriate for archaeological study...[T]he fundamental limitation of island life is the restriction it imposes...on intercourse with groups living elsewhere...[I]t makes for closed communities and tends to eliminate some of the variables which afflict...mainland groups.'²¹

At a conference in 2002 to examine 'the many interpretations of the effect of insularity...and the impact these have on islands,' McKechnie was emphatic that islands made good case studies:

Islands are...set apart and self-contained: they are different...They have a clear inside and out...[they] offer the possibility of closure and manageable scale...Islands are perfect

¹⁷ More (1516); Mann (1992) 98, 139, 273

¹⁸ Defoe (2007) 60

¹⁹ Durrell (1959) 106; c.f. Durrell (2009) 20: '[t]he real island flavour' of Corfu, as 'remote from the responsibilities of an active life...[with] a sense of detachment from the real world.'

²⁰ Eco (1995)

²¹ Evans (1973) 517

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laboratories...for if processes of definition can't work there, if clarity, certainly can't be achieved there, where can it be achieved?²²

In 2004 Fitzpatrick confirmed islands as categorically distinct:

Different groups of people on islands, by virtue of their restricted territory and because they are surrounded by water, develop at least partial isolation, which influenced how they evolved culturally. Isolation is not solely geographical, but had psychological aspects as well. If we agree that islands have some inherent 'boundary,' whether mental or physical, then we can approach islands as methodologically and theoretically different than continental land masses.²³

This durability of difference as favourable to research has not always been understood so narrowly. Mead's 'Introduction to Polynesia as a Laboratory for the Development of Models of Cultural Evolution' (1957) takes as her subject 'very detailed comparative studies of particular societies in a given cultural area.'²⁴ According to Goldman 'A culture area' was not island-specific, but 'comprises historically related societies each showing significant variations from a common area pattern.'²⁵ Similarly MacArthur and Wilson's *The Theory of Island Biogeography* defines islands, not as land surrounded by water, but as eco-systems different from surrounding eco-systems.²⁶ Analogising laboratories and islands is ultimately unhelpful because laboratories establish control through isolation and not all islands are isolated.

1.3 Islands of disparagement

The problem with treating islands as terrestrial positives set in marine negatives is the pejorative epithets islands and islanders accrue. Islands are identified as passive, as 'clocks for seeing,' where time 'tick[s] at [a] different speed' or has stopped altogether.²⁷ Small is understood as less. Severed from mainlands, islands become the *îles prison* of the convict

²² McKechnie (2002) 127, 133

²³ Fitzpatrick (2004) 7

²⁴ Mead (1957) 145

²⁵ Goldman (1955) 680

²⁶ MacArthur and Wilson (1967) 182

²⁷ Held (1992) 1-2

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or leper.²⁸ They are like ‘so many cages in which their insulated occupants are shut in from external influences,’ and by whom mainlanders remain uncontaminated. For refugees and the stateless, islands serve as the mainland’s anterooms.²⁹ Where islands are inhabited, their populations are invariably uncivilised and underdeveloped - people from whom the future is withheld.³⁰ These conservative and introspective communities inhabit blank slates incapable of generating innovation. They endure ‘cultural retardation’ as civilisation’s dependent poor relations. However, as Stengers observed,

Isolation [in laboratories and other structures] is a dangerous game, and those who believe they can purify their objects in fact intervene actively in the significance of the object they observe.³¹

The inevitable result of ‘isolation’ as a defining characteristic is that the sea, as cause and conservator of insular deficits, is itself cast as pejorative. But the sea provides an exit-strategy to a more constructive and integrated approach which took island studies offshore.³²

1.4 The rehabilitation of the sea

It is the sea above all which shapes and defines the land, fashioning gulfs, oceans and straights, and likewise isthmuses, peninsulas and promontories...It is through such features that continents, nations, favourable sites of cities, and other refinements have been conceived.³³

For water is a great thing, and the noblest of the four visible elements of the world.³⁴

Strabo understands the sea as a defining positive. For Deleuze and Guattari land and sea are opposed equals. Sea is a space-expanding ‘smoothness,’ in contrast to the ‘striated’

²⁸ Febvre (1922) 265. Hill (1940), I.258 n.1, sees remoteness in terms of an island’s suitability as a place of banishment

²⁹ Hood (1970) 37-45

³⁰ Rainbird (2007) 18

³¹ Stengers (1997) 16

³² Gillis (2006) 20

³³ Strabo ii 5.17 in Jones (1917) I.463-65

³⁴ Cyril of Jerusalem CL.III.5 in Parker (1838) 27

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containment of terrestrial settlement.³⁵ Their emphasis is on its outward 'polyvocality of direction,' an expansive membrane connecting the different and disparate in opposition to the study of islands as a microscopic focus on the more or less quarantined. Deleuze posited 'a profound opposition between ocean and land' and that '[h]umans cannot live, nor live in security, unless they assume that the active struggle between earth and water is over.'³⁶

In 2000 Broodbank proposed an archaeology of unopposed equals in which an archaeology of the sea 'match[ed] that of the land...not simply...maritime archaeology...but an archaeology of maritime culture at a given period.'³⁷ The following year Parker argued that '[a]n appreciation of the maritime aspects of the historic landscape requires archaeologists to adopt a mariner's perspective...'³⁸ In 2006 Horden and Purcell went further to propose an all-embracing history of seas and oceans as 'the New Thalassology.'³⁹ In their 'Island Archaeology' of 2007 Boomert and Bright rejected the notion of islands as 'ideal units of analysis' with 'characteristics essentially different from those on mainlands' in favour of 'an archaeology of maritime identity.'⁴⁰ Rainbird offered the fullest exposition in his *Archaeology of Islands* in which he argued for '*an archaeology of the sea* that incorporate[d] the land' rather than merged with it.⁴¹

I wish to develop a thesis that links islands to the maritime environment...[S]uch an approach, one which decentres the land as the key defining geographical element, allows the development of an archaeology of islands that has at its heart a requirement to conceptualize coastal peoples, whether living on an island, boat or continent as members of maritime societies.⁴²

³⁵ Deleuze and Guattari (2004) 381

³⁶ Deleuze (2003) 9

³⁷ Broodbank (2000) 34

³⁸ Parker (2001) 39

³⁹ Horden and Purcell (2006) 723

⁴⁰ Boomert and Bright (2007) 4, 10

⁴¹ Rainbird (2007) 45

⁴² Rainbird (2007) 2

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1.2 Later Roman geographies

The nodal island and its surrounding sea was often so closely integrated with its surroundings as to appear embedded in single contextual matrix. Where this was the case, accepted distinctions and oppositions lost their precision, raising a number of questions: how might an island be distinguished from a continent, a river be distinguished from a sea, and why, in so many Later Roman accounts, is the terrestrial construed as fluid and the marine as solid?

1.2.1 Islands and continents

Seen from the sea, islands represent a particular concentration of multi-directional coastlines. But in what other ways might islands be distinguished from mainlands? Early maps identified their continents by convention rather than geography. Ancient Greek mariners originally used the names Europe and Asia, not to identify vast terrestrial tracts, but to distinguish between the shores of the Aegean, the Sea of Marmara and the Black Sea. According to Tozer,

[t]he names by which continents came to be designated seem to have been in use before the names of the continents themselves were known. This arose from their first being applied to coastlands...while afterwards their application was gradually extended, so as to include the whole of the country that lay behind.⁴³

If a littoral could claim to be a continent, size may not be the issue. Furthermore, approached from the sea, all land was coast. Whether it belonged to an island or a mainland was immaterial compared with its role in identifying location. Two Cypriot examples demonstrate the point, one between two different coasts and the second along a single coast. Akanthou-Arkosyko (Tatlisu-Ciftlikduzu) on the north coast of Cyprus was 'within sight of the Anatolian Taurus mountains ...[F]avourable currents [made] the journey between the mainland and the island both short and easy without going out of sight of

⁴³ Tozer (1935) 68-69

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land on clear days'.⁴⁴ [1.3] The second example comes from Leonard's investigations at Kioni on the west coast of the Akamas Peninsula which revealed year-through use [1.4]. Asking a local fisherman, 'What do you sight on for navigation?' he replied that, 'At night I look at the mountains, their shape.'⁴⁵ These line-of-sight readings made 'the coastal route scarcely different from a river.'⁴⁶ Such routes mimicked or supplemented coastal roads, taking their bearings from promontories, inlets and the shapes of hills and mountains - but also settlement profiles, the principal accents of which would have been churches and the occasional lighthouse [1.5].⁴⁷

1.2.2 *Okeanos* and river

Of the Rainless River born out of the world.⁴⁸

Unlike the *Okeanos*, the all-surrounding sea, the Mediterranean was bounded on the 'inside' by an all-but continuous littoral and, hence, was free from the myth of the precipitous perimeter.⁴⁹ Despite being contained, it was, in many respects, an image of the *Okeanos*, in that, as Braudel observed, the Mediterranean contained diminutive continents of its own, of which Cyprus was one.⁵⁰ Conversely, parts of the littoral might be construed as islands. Cyrenaica in Libya Superior was isolated by the sea from the north and by the desert on its remaining three sides. In Cyprus four peninsulas might be understood as islands-on-land: Akamas and Kormakitis in the north-west, Akrotiri in the

⁴⁴ Sevketoglu (2002) 99

⁴⁵ Leonard (1995b) 150

⁴⁶ Braudel (1972) I.105

⁴⁷ Cameron (1993) 58: '...in the post-Constantinian period churches...were simply more visible'. For lighthouses see Leyerle (2000) 458-474. Gunnis (1936) 381 noted that at the west end of the island of Geronisos, 'is the base of a Roman building, possibly a lighthouse.' Goodwin (1984) I.918, reported that at Lambousa there was a lighthouse the remains of which survive. For the lighthouse attached to the basilica of Limeniotissa at Paphos as belonging to the Arab garrisoning of the town see Stewart (2008) I 34, II 306 fig II.19

⁴⁸ 'JFR' in Luke and Jardine (1920) unpaginated

⁴⁹ The first use of *De mediterraneo mari* may be Isidore of Seville *Etymologies* 13.16.1. See Barney *et al* (2006) 277-8

⁵⁰ Braudel (1972) I.148. Eusebius: 'He (God) laid out the earth, and then encircled this with Ocean to embellish its outline with dark-blue colour:' cited in Graham (2006) 56

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south, Karpas in the north-east - if an island can be defined by boats as the principal means of communication. [1.6]⁵¹

If coasts are denominators common to islands and continents, islands are, arguably, no different from continents. The circular world maps of Anaximander (c.610-546 BC) and the *Orbis Terrarum* (20 AD) [1.7] imagined three continents, Europa, Asia and Africa - as entirely sea-girt.⁵² Rectangular world maps too - the Roman road map, the *Tabula Peutingeriana* (335-366) [1.8] and the world imagined by Cosmas Indicopleustes (c.547-549) show all land surrounded by the *Okeanos* [1.9].⁵³

Coasts and surrounding seas, then, constituted a denominator common to islands and mainlands. Although the Greeks had many words for the sea, their preference for 'pontos' suggests a contraction of the sea to riverine proportions. The *Tabula Peutingeriana*, for example, shows a remarkably fish-like Cyprus enclosed in a 'narrow channel of the Mediterranean widened to permit insertion of the island' [1.10].⁵⁴ But if the Mediterranean could be riverine, how might it be distinguished from the major rivers flowing into it? Could the Nile, for example, be understood as two particularly close coasts on which riverine traffic was indistinguishable from coastal traffic elsewhere in the Mediterranean?⁵⁵ We know that Egyptian monasteries operated river-craft, connecting their foundations to the capital. Pachomius went so far as to include the conduct required of monks aboard ship in his rule.⁵⁶ The monks of Antinoopolis inherited a boat and their church accounts include the expense of building a barque, boat repairs and caulking.⁵⁷ Taking the Nile as the model, could boats sailing between Akanthou/Tatlisu and Cilicia be understood as ferrying across a broad river whose banks were the coasts of Cyprus and Asia Minor? Could islands, indeed,

⁵¹ For the Akamas: Strabo VI 14.6.2 in Jones (1970) 375-7. For Cyrenaica see Shaw Brent (2003) 98

⁵² Strabo I.I.11 in Jones (1970) 23. For Anaximander's map as the model for the *periplus* of Hecataeus of Miletus (c.550-c.476) see Heidel (1921) 243-249

⁵³ For the dating of the archetype see Harley and Woodward (1987) 238; Anastos (1979) 76 suggests c.540-552

⁵⁴ Talbert (2010) 89-90. See also *Tertullian's Homily on Baptism* 1 (Evans (1964) 5): 'But we, being little fishes, as Jesus is our great Fish, begin our life in water, and only while we abide in water are we safe and sound'.

⁵⁵ Wace, Megaw and Skeat (1959) 78 imply a penetration of the Mediterranean as far as Ashumain.

⁵⁶ Monks (1953) 355-6 n.46

⁵⁷ Hardy (1931) 128

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be understood as moored coastlines with shipping as their ‘structural mediators?’⁵⁸
Braudel implies as much:

Large or small, [the] significance [of islands] lies in providing indispensable landfalls on the sea routes and affording stretches of comparatively calm water to which shipping [was] attracted, either between islands or between islands and mainland coasts.⁵⁹

1.2.3 A discourse of displacement

The Mediterranean did not always ‘afford...stretches of comparatively calm water.’ The battleground of the African and Eurasian tectonic plates lay in the Eastern Mediterranean; its position therefore rendered Cyprus particularly vulnerable [1.11]. At the centre of the account by Ammianus Marcellinus (325/330-post 391) of the great *tsunami* in 21st July 365 is an exchange of descriptors:

[T]he whole of the firm and solid earth was shaken and trembled, the sea with its rolling waves was driven back and withdrew from the land, so that in the abyss of the deep thus revealed men saw...vast mountains and deep valleys, which Nature...had hidden in the unplumbed depths....⁶⁰

The transposition of marine for terrestrial imagery and *vice-versa* is a recurring trope in the Later Roman period. It underlies Socrates Scholasticus’ account of the same catastrophe, written sometime before 439:

The sea also changed its accustomed boundaries, and overflowed to such an extent in some places, that vessels might sail where roads had previously existed; and it retired so much from other places, that the ground became dry.⁶¹

Ammianus and Socrates use a radical transposition of imagery to replay the catastrophe itself. A less apocalyptic discourse of displacement occurs in an observation that ‘so many ships were now sailing between Egypt and Constantinople that the sea looked more like

⁵⁸ Robb (2001) 191

⁵⁹ Braudel (1975) I.149

⁶⁰ Ammianus XXVI 10, 15 in Rolfe (1940) II 649

⁶¹ Socrates 6.3 (2009 reprint) 178

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dry land.⁶² For Arsenius, (350/354-445) too, the sea had become a highway.⁶³ Conversely, the imagery of the ship-on-land recurs in the fourth-century Syrian compilation, the *Apostolic Constitutions*:

2. When you gather together the church of God, like a helmsman of a great ship, command the congregation to behave with great discipline, instructing the deacons like sailors to assign the places to the brethren, like passengers...3. At first the church (*oikos*) should be oblong, facing the east with the sacristies on each side facing the east, resembling a ship. 4. Place the bishop's throne in the middle, seat the presbyters each side of him, and the deacons should stand nearby...for they are like sailors and those in charge of the rowers...9. And the presbyters should encourage the people, one after another, but not all of them, and last of all the bishop, who is like a helmsman...⁶⁴

Epiphanius deploys a similar *topos*,

God's ships takes any passengers except a bandit...But it takes a man on important business, the experienced seamen – the pilot and the helmsman, the bow lookout, the man in the stern (the one most used to command), the one who knows even a bit about cargo and lading – and someone who just wants to cross the ocean without drowning.⁶⁵

Epiphanius' *Ancoratus* (374) uses similar metaphors to explain that the 'barque' of the church of Syedra cannot enter harbour - the firm 'anchor' of faith - because of the adverse winds of heresy.⁶⁶ In the *Vita S Antoni* (356-362), Epiphanius' contemporary Athanasius (296/298-373) conceives the desert as a sea whose inhabitants – nomads and mariners - navigated by the stars, winds and seasons.⁶⁷ The analogy of sea and sand proved durable. In the late-fifth or early-sixth century, sand substituted for water in John Moschos' (c.550-619) tale of a young Jew crossing the desert who, near to death, begs his companions to baptize him; one amongst them fills his hands with sand and pours it three times over the

⁶² Theophylact Simocatta in McCormick (2001) 108-9

⁶³ Arsenius 28, 65.96 in Clark (2004) 74

⁶⁴ Lee (2000) 243

⁶⁵ Epiphanius 44.4.5-7 in Williams (1994) 2.117

⁶⁶ Rapp (1991) 22; Williams (1994) I xiii

⁶⁷ 'Therefore be off to the mountain as fish to the sea.' Athanasius ch.85 in Meyer, 90. See also Côte (2002) 108

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sick man's head. This was clearly more than an imitation of doubtful validity because the baptism subsequently received episcopal recognition.⁶⁸

So far, this section has identified a lack of a fixed distinction between the coastlines of islands and mainlands, between oceans, seas and rivers, even between the terrestrial and the marine. It has, however left the integrity of the Mediterranean and its islands largely untouched.

1.2.4 Micro-regionalising the Mediterranean

In 2005 Herzfeld expressed surprise that the 'Mediterranean' remained categorically intact when most categories have been exposed to fierce interrogation.⁶⁹ But has it survived? Before the era of the nation state there were few strategies for sequestering a sea which, while it may have connected the provinces of Late Antiquity, was itself stateless, even nameless. The Mediterranean, after all, was less a name than a location. Clearly, the Mediterranean was understood as a single entity as early as the *periplus* of Hecataeus of Miletus (c.550-c.476 BC), who describes the Mediterranean as 'The Great Sea,' a term which Isidore of Seville (c.560-636) also uses but then, perhaps for the first time, identifies the 'Great Sea' as 'the Mediterranean because it flows through the middle of the land (*media terrae*).'⁷⁰ Herzfeld's misgivings may be recent, but Isidore wrote that 'just as the land, though it is a single thing, may be referred to with various names in different places, so also this Great Sea is named with different names according to the region.'⁷¹ Braudel, too, evoked an inhabited, socialised Mediterranean of regional and localised seas.⁷² Earlier still Plato described Mediterraneans as 'dwelling around the sea like ants and frogs around a pond.'⁷³ In the *Deipnosophistae* of Athenaeus (early-third century), the Mediterranean became a cauldron for boiling a fish 'bigger in bulk than Crete.'⁷⁴ These texts evoke

⁶⁸ Moschos in Wortley (1992) 145

⁶⁹ Herzfeld (2005) 46

⁷⁰ Isidore in Barney (2006) 277

⁷¹ Isidore in Barney (2006) 277-8

⁷² Braudel (1972) I.23

⁷³ Plato *Phaedo*, 109b in Sedley and Long (2010) 106

⁷⁴ Athenaeus, *The Deipnosophists* in Gulick (1927-9) VIII.346-7 vol. IV 71-3

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communities orientated towards the Mediterranean as a domesticated *mare nostrum*.⁷⁵ Navigators, too, micro-managed the sea. The nearest they came to a bird's-eye-view map was its inversion in the night sky.⁷⁶ Otherwise it is doubtful that navigators understood the Mediterranean as more than an agglomeration of maritime regions and sub-regions. Navigation would have been dominated by local conditions – currents, winds and seasons – and the legibility of the land viewed from the sea.

...the relatively small distances involved in the Mediterranean meant that it was most unusual for a ship to be more than a week out of sight of land; indeed in separate Mediterranean basins the coast would be seen every day.⁷⁷

1.3 'Cyprus and the Sea'

1.3.1 Cyprus in the *Stadiasmus Periplus Maris Magni*

The fullest contemporary account of the harbours of Late Antique Cyprus is the anonymous, mid-fourth-century *Stadiasmus Periplus Maris Magni*. This begins with a description of the ports on the south coast, travelling from west to east. Paphos is described as 'a city in the south [which] has a triple harbour for every kind of wind.' Kargaiai, the south-eastern promontory of the Akrotiri Peninsula, has 'a harbour, an anchorage and water.' Ammochostos (Famagusta) has 'a harbour suitable for any kind of wind, but at its entrance there are three reefs.' Of the capital, Salamis, our geographer says no more than that it is 'a city with a harbour.' The final stop on the south coast is Palaia, possibly Knidos, 'a village which has a harbour and water.'⁷⁸

⁷⁵ Horden and Purcell (2000) 11

⁷⁶ Broodbank (2000) 23

⁷⁷ Harley and Woodward (1987) 441

⁷⁸ Marangou (2002) 54; Goodwin (1984) 483 reports that 'the ruins of the port are still to be seen.' After Citium Strabo identifies 'the city of Amathus, and, in the interval, to a small town called Palaea...Then to Curias;' Strabo 14.6.3 in Jones (1970) 379. Mitford (1980) 1339 n.242 suggests Palaea may be identified with Mazōtos.

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Travelling along the north coast from west to east, of the first two ports known to have been active in the export of copper ore in Late Antiquity, Arsinoe is described as ‘a city with a deserted harbour’ and ‘Soloï [as] a city without a harbour.’ Melabron is described as having a summer harbour but Lapethos, which certainly exported copper in the Roman period, is simply described as ‘a city with an inlet’ despite its fame for ship-building.⁷⁹ The final two stops on the north coast are Kyrenia with an anchorage and Karpasia which ‘has a harbour for small ships.’⁸⁰ [1.12-3]

1.3.2 Adjacent distance 1

The tendency has always been strong to believe that whatever received a name must be an entity...having an independent existence of its own.⁸¹

If the Mediterranean was both a single place *and* an agglomeration of micro-regions, is the integrity of islands anything more than a nesophile fallacy? Mainlanders may claim that islands resulting from continental drift are ex-continental and, hence, mainlands-set-adrift. Are Turkish claims on Cyprus an initiative to heal a severance or does the Turkish coast serve as the north bank of a unifying river? Here the larger lays claim to the smaller: in the south the case is reversed. The Greek-Cypriot campaign for union with Greece (*Ενωσις*) was based on the perception of a common heritage with an entirely invisible mainland to which the island never geologically belonged.⁸² The net effect is one place of two halves that are, simultaneously, adjacent and apart, each basing their legitimacy on the authority of sponsoring states independent of their proximity.

If the north of Cyprus was visible from Cilicia, and the south coast was entirely invisible from any mainland, the north might be less insular than the south. However, in Late

⁷⁹ Wallace and Orphanides (1990) 135. According to Ammianus Marcellinus and the *Expositio Totius Mundi et Gentium* Cyprus could provide all that was need for the construction of ships, see; Karageorghis and Michaelides (1996) 146. Lokin (1985) 43-4 identifies Cyprus as having had the biggest shipyards in the Eastern Mediterranean. Zosimus’ entry for 322 records that when Constantine was preparing for war against Licinius, Licinius sent out a call for warships throughout his realm to which Cyprus responded with thirty triremes: Zosimus 2:22 in Ridley (1982) 33-4.

⁸⁰ Marangou (2002) 54; Strabo XIV. 6 in Jones (1970) 379-381

⁸¹ Mill (1896) 5

⁸² Although the policy was officially abandoned in the 1970’s, the south, nevertheless celebrates Greek independence day on March 25th and Greek flags are a common sight in the south.

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Antiquity departing from the north coast for Anatolia and the Aegean involved considerable risk, particularly in winter. So sailings would have departed from the south, thence to Syria, hugging its coastline northwards and then striking westwards along the Anatolian coast to the Aegean [1.14].⁸³ In the case of Cyprus, then, two indicators of insularity were in opposition: the coast which could be seen from the mainland was, in winter months, a *mare clausum* largely excluded from participation in the wider networks of exchange in which the southern harbour-cities continued to participate.

In the late fourth century, differently configured space was compounded by differently configured time. The island was split between east and west, between Rome and a more generalised Egyptian orientation. In the *Panarion* 51.24.1, Epiphanius identifies different Cypriot computations of Christ's birthday: 'In the Cypriote or Salaminian it is the fifth day of the fifth month. In the Paphian it is the fourteenth of July.'⁸⁴ Mitford identified the Salaminian as an Egyptian calendar and the Paphian as a 'concoction' for the benefit of the Imperial capital as Paphos' principal Cypriot trading partner and the seat of the island's governor.⁸⁵

1.3.3 Adjacent distance 2

To divisions between north and south may be added divisions between coast and hinterland. The littoral was oriented toward the sea but hinterlands were remote, disconnected and alien – hence an ideal 'battleground for defeating the demons.'⁸⁶ Hilarion (291-371) arrived at Paphos in the 330s, and '...began to live in obscurity about two miles from the city' until fame caused him to seek 'a spot... higher up and more retired...twelve miles from the sea, far off among the recesses of rugged mountains, the

⁸³ Raban (1995) 140. Empereur and Picon (1989) 243, defined broad distribution trends showing that Rhodes provisioned the Cilician coast and North Syria with amphorae, while Cyprus, closer to both, supplied Egypt. Papacostas, pers comm, suggests a more complex pattern of distribution and manufacture including finds of Cypriot Red Slip Ware at Amenourion and Limyra in Asia Minor.

⁸⁴ Epiphanius IV 31(51) 24.1 in Williams II. 55

⁸⁵ For reservations see Mitford (1980) 1358; at 1322 he writes 'Salamis, unlike Paphos, appears to have been ill at ease with Rome'.

⁸⁶ Kyrris (1987) 93-108 at 98

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ascent to which could hardly be accomplished by creeping on hands and knees...'⁸⁷ Hilarion's first cell, far from being distant from a civilising littoral, constructed its 'obscurity' adjacent to it.⁸⁸

Hinterlands, the site of particular kinds of spiritual confrontation, also involved a material confrontation with the more or less intractable, namely the extraction of copper, gold, asbestos and gypsum [1.15].⁸⁹ In the busy coastal ports, or arteries dependent on them, these raw materials were processed and exported. According to Raber, copper smelting was an activity of the foothills or the coastal plain near villages and towns.⁹⁰ For example, Marion-Arsinoë, in the north-west, had a small harbour which served the mines at Limni and Tamassos, which was also linked by a Roman road to the harbour at Soloi, and the anchorage at Zygi on the south coast served the copper mines of Kalavastos-*Spilioi* in the Vasilikos Valley in the sixth and early seventh centuries.⁹¹

Agriculture attests to a more graduated relationship between littoral and hinterland in Late Antiquity. The Mesaoria ('between the mountains'), the vast alluvial plain dividing the Troodos in the south-west from the Kyrenia range in the north, received barely 200-400mm of rain annually.⁹² Furthermore, '[t]he rivers are all dried up in the summer months long before they reach the sea.'⁹³ While vini- and oleoculture penetrated the hinterland most deeply, the cultivation of barley, small amounts of vetch, flax, linseed, aniseed and hemp were confined to coastal plains irrigated by rivers and springs - notably the fertile *terra rossa* of the south and the land above Lambousa in the north.⁹⁴ That agriculture, too,

⁸⁷ Jerome *Life of Hilarion* 42-43 in White (London 1998) 112-113; Brock (2001) 22, describes Hilarion 'living in a cave on the outskirts of Paphos.'

⁸⁸ Obscure proximity may account for the late survival of so-called rural cults. Barely 10km north of Neapolis (Limassol) the Temple of Zeus Labranios on Kastro Hill at Phasoula saw late artefactual investment in the form of a limestone head of Zeus from the 5th or 6th century (Limassol Archaeological Museum), although Megaw (1958) 25-34 at 31-2 fig.10c proposes a date no later than the 4th century.

⁸⁹ Papacostas (2001), 107-128 at 111-2. Strabo VI 14.6.5 in Jones (1970) 383 for mining generally; Edwards (2010) 184-196 (copper), 166-8, 194-6 (gypsum); for timber see Meiggs (1982), 118, 136-7, 281, 353, 373, 379, 397-8

⁹⁰ Raber (1987) 305-6

⁹¹ Papacostas (2001) 111

⁹² Hill (1940) I 1-14; Malamut (1998) I.36-37

⁹³ Luke and Jardine (1920) 231

⁹⁴ Thirgood (1987) 60-1, 70-2; Karageorghis and Michaelides (1996) 148

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was dependent on coastal processing is attested by the number of wine/olive presses found in broadly ecclesiastical contexts, e.g. Peyia, Paphos, Kourion, Amathus and Salamis.⁹⁵

Evidence that, in the sixth century, the hinterland was understood as uncivilised is suggested by Procopius' description of 'rural people [who] have cast aside their ploughshares and live like city-dwellers, exchanging their rural lifestyle for civilisation.'⁹⁶ For Braudel, too, civilisation was 'an urban and lowland achievement.'⁹⁷ That being the case, it is arguable that the Mediterranean ended, not on the shoreline, but where the littoral and the hinterland met.

Trump identified the Mediterranean as a 'peninsular in reverse, a body of water almost entirely surrounded by land.'⁹⁸ The reflex from this 'liquid continent' was hinterlands which acquired many of the pejorative epithets reserved for islands. If a coast was distant from its adjacent hinterland was it closer to other coasts, however distant, particularly if they belonged to the same trading network? This seems to be the gist of Epiphanius' observation that,

the *medimnos* varies amongst the Cyprians, for the people of Salamis, that is to say, of Constantia, have a *medimnos* of 5 *modii*, while those of Paphos and the Sicilians measure it as 4½ *modii*.⁹⁹

The implication might be that Paphos and Salamis were less likely trading partners than Paphos and Sicily. The relative independence of the cities of the Cypriot littoral should

⁹⁵ At Agia Varvara, east of Amathus the buildings around the court, immediately to the west of the basilica, include 'a place where the olives were crushed at first...and the press-room where the oil was subsequently produced...In front of the press there is a shallow well for the collection of the olive oil.' *ARDA* (1976) 30. *ARDA* (1977) 36 says of the southwest basilica at Amathus that 'The water supply system for the church and the adjacent olive-press and flour mills installations has also been investigated.'

⁹⁶ Procopius VI. 6. 15 in Dewing (1954) 387

⁹⁷ Braudel (1972) I.34

⁹⁸ Trump (1980) 3

⁹⁹ Epiphanius in Dean (1935) 41, 137, 142

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come as no surprise. They were strung along a 650km-coastline.¹⁰⁰ No one city was the focus of a major road network, partly because the majority were accessed in linear sequence from a circuminsular highway established by the late Hellenistic period, a route largely confined on one side by the sea and on the other by mountains, a topography that hindered the development of a monocentric inland focus to which the cities of the littoral might have access.¹⁰¹

1.3.4 Cyprus and Constantinople 1: decentred cities

Lacking a major inland centre, Cypriot cities were, so to speak, on the outside looking out; conversely the cities of the mainland littoral were orientated inwards towards the Mediterranean. A multi-directional coastline meant that, of the thirteen Cypriot *poleis* listed in the *Synekdemos* (527-8) of Hierokles, all but Chytroi and Tamassos, were, like much of the Christian Mediterranean, circumferential – churches overlooked the sea and, viewed from it, they identified a particular coast and signified the perimeter of a Christian thalassocracy.¹⁰² Soloi was raised on an artificial *parterre* overlooking the sea, while Kourion occupied a natural eminence so close to the cliff edge that its atrium and entrance had to be displaced to the north. In Salamis, Campanopetra was approached by a monumental staircase directly from the port. Although the identification of basilicas at Paphos and Kourion with Panagia Limeniotissa (Our Lady of the Harbour) are much later attestations they may, nevertheless, refer to an earlier function. Furthermore, at least two episcopal basilicas, Ayios Philon and Amathus, were directly attached to harbours. Indeed the identity of Christian Cyprus was predominantly vested in a circuminsular ring which penetrated barely a few hundred metres inland.

Despite the dominance of Imperial Rome, a 46,000km-long Mediterranean coastline of embayments, peninsulas and regional seas was more conducive to a number of dispersed centres than a single central focus. Indeed, for the first 150 years of its existence,

¹⁰⁰ Only slightly less than the coasts of Syria, Lebanon and Palestine combined: 196+225+272= 693km. According to Strabo the 'circuit of Cyprus is three thousand four hundred and twenty stadia:' see Strabo VI 14.6.2 in Jones (1970) 375

¹⁰¹ For the Late Antique road network in Cyprus see Bekker-Nielsen (2004) 108-113 figs 15-16

¹⁰² Honigman (1939) 2, 38, map 1

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Constantine's new capital went out of its way not to destabilize a Mediterranean of distributed centres, to the extent that Dagron argued that Constantine's Christian capital was not Constantinople at all, but Jerusalem.¹⁰³ Rather than centralising his new empire, Constantine added two new centres to those already widely distributed. Furthermore, two essential signatures of a Christian capital were lacking in Constantinople - a major congregational church, for which there is no evidence before 360, and permanent residency by the emperor, which did not happen much before Arcadius (r.383-408).¹⁰⁴ Indeed, for most of the fourth century, according to Themistius (317-c390), writing in 384, Constantinople's topography was hardly more than sketched (σκιαγραφία), its buildings were hastily thrown up and its administration was elsewhere.¹⁰⁵ True, Constantinople started with a major disadvantage. It lacked the apostolic imprimatur which gave the 'older' centres their Christian legitimacy. This, together with the hiatus in 'activating' the capital, strengthened the distributed metropoleis, so that when the Pentarchy, the five patriarchal cities (Rome, Constantinople, Alexandria, Antioch and Jerusalem) became an accomplished fact, under Justinian, all five sees had, according to Anastos, 'equality and independence [1.16].'¹⁰⁶

III.5 Cyprus and Constantinople 2: nodal 'islands'

Fourth-century Cyprus might have felt a particular affinity with Constantine's new capital. Constantinople's population increased so that the city was 'an ocean of people...flowing from everywhere.'¹⁰⁷ A large proportion of the 500 ships of the *corpus naviculariorum* transporting the *annona civica*, which supplied this influx with grain from Egypt, were serviced in Cyprus.¹⁰⁸ Furthermore, Constantinople was, if not an island, at least peninsular and similarly characterised by its multidirectional shoreline. Indeed, its city *Tyche* was commonly represented standing on the prow of a ship as if Constantinople itself lay moored between the Sea of Marmara and the Bosphorus [1.17]. Like the thirteen of the Cypriot *poleis* [1.18], eleven of the city's twelve urban regions listed in the *Notitia urbis*

¹⁰³ Dagron (1974) 389

¹⁰⁴ Jones (1964) I.367 for the peripatetic *comitatus*.

¹⁰⁵ Themistius (Orat. 18, 222c-d) in Mango (2005) 320

¹⁰⁶ Anastos (2001) VIII 57. See Dvornik (1958) 3 for the hierarchising of the sees.

¹⁰⁷ Cited in van Dam (2010) 53

¹⁰⁸ Bakirtzis (1995) 247-53; Laiou and Morrison (2007) 34-5; Teall (1959) 91-2

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Constantinopolitanae (c.425) bordered the sea, which was visible from almost every part of the city [1.19].¹⁰⁹ By the mid-sixth century the capital had become a great mother-ship with two-and-half miles of docks able to accommodate the entire *corpus naviculariorum*.¹¹⁰ Seaside locations were clearly 'desirable for loading, unloading, storage, and marketing of seaborne merchandise.'¹¹¹ Furthermore, Julian of Ascalon's sixth-century treatise on urban planning suggests that a view of the sea was an embellishment to city living.¹¹²

If a man can see a harbour or the shore, or even just look at ships at anchor in the case of a town or village which does not have a proper harbour, his view of them should in no way be impaired or removed, for they are a source of recreation to those who behold them.¹¹³

1.4 Towards a Christian thalassocracy

1.4.1 The adjudicating sea

The tri-partite passage of the *annona civica*, via Cyprus and Rhodes, was rich in miracles.¹¹⁴ Sees were substantial shipowners: the *Vita* of John the Almsgiver, Cypriot and Patriarch of Alexandria (r.610-617), refers to a fleet of thirteen ships trading from the Egyptian capital including a ship sent to Sicily for corn.¹¹⁵ For the Church, divine protection was a given; for the lay shipowners of Alexandria divine blessings were sought. The Piacenza Pilgrim describes how at the Jordan,

¹⁰⁹ Croke (2005) 61; Seeck (1876) 229-241. On Cyprus only Tamassos and Chytroi were not coastal.

¹¹⁰ van Dam (2010) 55. According to Justinian's *Edicta* 13.8 Egypt shipped eight million *artabae* of grain to Constantinople, calculated as 36 million *modii* by Garnsey (1988) 231 and Haas (1997) 42, as 27 million *modii* by Jones II (1964) 698, and as 24 million by Durliat (1990) 257. For docks see Mango (1985) 38-40; for the granary at Tenedos 'large enough for the whole fleet to unload' see Procopius 5.1.7-16 in Dewing (1954) 319-21

¹¹¹ Magdalino (2000) 209

¹¹² Magdalino (2000) 210

¹¹³ Saliou (1996) 72-3

¹¹⁴ Bakirtzis (1995) 248, fig.1

¹¹⁵ Dawes and Baynes (1996) 199-262, ch.10 at 217; ch.13 at 223; ch.28 at 239

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[a]ll the ship-owners of Alexandria have men there that day with great jars of spices and balsam, and as soon as the river has been blessed...they pour them out into the water, and draw out holy water. This water they use for sprinkling their ships when they are about to set sail.¹¹⁶

The concerns of the Alexandrian agents were well founded: tales abound of adjudicating seas. John gave a certain captain money for a cargo. When the captain's ship foundered it was, according to John, because the Church's money had been mixed with the captain's own. John gave him new money with the proviso that it not be mixed with the old, but a second ship, too, sank having been acquired by dishonest means. Finally John gave the captain a ship belonging to the church, loaded with 'twenty thousand bushels of corn.' The captain reported, on his return, that

[caught in] a violent wind we were unable to tell in what direction we were going either by the stars or by the coast. But the only thing we knew was that the steersman saw the patriarch by his side holding the tiller and saying to him: 'Fear not! You are sailing quite right.'¹¹⁷

An emphasis on economic histories of the Mediterranean has tended to underplay the integration of trade and faith. For Basil of Caesarea Mazaca (r.370-379)

...the [Mediterranean] sea is good in the eyes of God, because it girdles the isles, of which it forms at the same time the rampart and the beauty, because it brings together the most distant parts of the earth, facilitates the intercommunication of mariners. By this means it gives us the boon of general information, supplies the merchant with his wealth, and easily provides the necessities of life, allowing the rich to export their superfluities, and blessing the poor with the supply of what they lack.¹¹⁸

Basil was appointed to Caesarea in 370, three years after his friend Epiphanius arrived in Salamis-Constantia. From his landlocked bishopric it is impossible to know the extent of Basil's direct experience of the Mediterranean; however, there is no reason to doubt that his views were representative. Epiphanius certainly had more direct experience of a sea 'good in the eyes of God,' given his embassies to Antioch (c.376), Constantinople (c.380

¹¹⁶ Wilkinson (2002b) 136

¹¹⁷ Leontios in Dawes and Baynes (1996) 216-218, 235-237

¹¹⁸ Basil of Caesarea 4.7 in Giet (1968) 274-275

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and 403), Rome (c.382), Jerusalem (393) and Bethlehem (394) [1.20]. The promotion of Nicene/Constantinopolitan Orthodoxy constituted his principal mission, facilitated by a sea construed as emphatically Orthodox and, therefore explicitly anti-Arian, the heresy that argued Christ was God's creature and, therefore, his subordinate.

Mark the Deacon's *Life of Porphyry*, describes how, *en route* from Constantinople to Gaza, Porphyry visited an anchorite on Rhodes, but two days after resuming his voyage a violent storm arose which failed to abate despite his prayers. In a dream the anchorite addressed Porphyry, 'Instruct the owner of the ship...(for he is of the abominable heresy of Arius) and prepare him to call Arius accursed and his evil faith, and straightway this so great tempest will cease...' Porphyry confronted the owner, 'Deny thine evil faith and believe on the true faith, and be saved, thou and they ship and all of us,' to which the owner replied, 'I believe as you believe and I deny the heresy of Arius and Arius himself' ...And in the meantime also the tempest ceased and toward evening the wind turned, and we sailed fairly.¹¹⁹

1.4.2 Four Cypriot saints

1.4.2.i Spyridon

Apart from evidence that Paul and Barnabas travelled to Seleucia-Pieria, the harbour-city of Antioch, 'and from thence they sailed to Cyprus,' the *Laudatio* of Barnabas offers no additional connection between the 'Cypriot' apostle and the sea.¹²⁰ However, by the beginning of the fourth century the sea was a recurring theme in the *vitae* of four fourth-century saints. Like Porphyry, Spyridon (c.270-348), one of three Cypriot bishops attending the Council of Nicaea, was favoured by a specifically Orthodox, Anti-Arian, sea:

When he was about to leave for the great conference at Nicaea, eleven Arian bishops, also bound for the same place, fearing the effect of Spyridon's powerful advocacy...persuaded the governor, who was of their party, to forbid any ship to receive him as a passenger. The order was duly issued, but it could not hinder the saint from appearing at the Council. Days after the departure of the

¹¹⁹ Mark the Deacon in Hill (1913) 65-68

¹²⁰ I am grateful to Professor Cosby of Messiah University, currently undertaking a new translation of the Barnabas *Laudatio*, for this information.

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eleven heretics, Spyridon went down to the sea-shore and taking off his hermit's cloak placed one half of it upon the water, and tying the other as a sail to his staff, which served as a mast, committed himself in this strange craft to the mercy of the winds and the waves. The weather being favourable, he reached his destination before his Arian rivals, who were greatly astonished at what he had done.¹²¹

1.4.2.ii Hilarion and Epiphanius

Abating storms were a staple of the adjudicating sea. According to Sozomen (c.400-c.450), Hilarion's (291-371) last miracle before arriving in Cyprus in 363 was to suppress 'an inundation of the sea' which he 'restored...to its proper bounds.'¹²² The *Vita* of Epiphanius gives a vivid account of its subject's death en route to Cyprus, on his return from Constantinople and his encounter with John Chrysostom in 403:

He sits down in the rear of the ship, holding the Gospels in his hands...Epiphanius then addresses his disciples and the crew on the ship. In the evening, a heavy storm comes up...After two days, he gives up the ghost and immediately the storm subsides.¹²³

This is almost immediately followed by Epiphanius' second post-mortem miracle. A sailor, curious to know whether the bishop had been circumcised, attempted to lift the bishop's garment and was given such a violent kick by the corpse that he lay prone for three days and was only revived by touching the saint's body.¹²⁴

A provident sea also provided the island with its bishops. After their meeting in Cyprus, Epiphanius told Hilarion of his intention to return to Palestine. Hilarion warned his pupil against departure because he would be in grave danger at sea. Hilarion's prophecy was

¹²¹ Hackett (1901) 382

¹²² Sozomen *HE* 5.10. (2010 reprint) 192. The description in Chapters 119-123 of the *Vita* of the death of Epiphanius and the gospel book on his chest may be the source for same image in the *Encomium* of Alexander the Monk (527-565) written between 550-553, describing the discovery, in 447, of the body of Barnabas with the Gospel of St Matthew on his chest. Downey (1958) 224-228.

¹²³ *Vita* 119,121 in Rapp (1991) I.86; II.198, 202. Sozomen *HE* 8.15 (2010 reprint) 340-1 records the acrimonious parting of the pair, John, expressing the wish that Epiphanius might not live to see Cyprus – presumably a wish that the sea might adjudicate their quarrel. Rapp (1993) 182 makes no mention of this exchange and furthermore suggests that Epiphanius was in Constantinople in support of Chrysostom.

¹²⁴ *Vita* 124 in Rapp (1991) I, 107, 168; II 205

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realised and Epiphanius' ship foundered - but at Salamis-Constantia, on the day the island's bishops assembled to choose their new leader.¹²⁵ After his resurrection in Bethany, Lazarus, too, was 'committed to the mercy of the winds and the waves' and was 'wafted to the shores near Kition (Larnaca) and consecrated its first bishop.'¹²⁶

1.4.2.iii Mamas

Saints also arrived by sea: the stone coffin of St Mamas floated across from Asia Minor where it came to rest near Morphou.¹²⁷

The saint, appearing...in a dream to a pious Christian of that place, ordered him to proceed with his yoke of oxen and his four sons to the coast and drag the coffin to land. The man, incredulous at first, finally obeyed. Walking dry shod over the sea with his sons and his oxen, as though it had been on dry ground, he attached a rope to the sarcophagus and drew it to land.¹²⁸

In its new setting, the coffin served a similar apotropaic purpose to the balsam-infused waters of the Jordan, exuding a fluid efficacious as 'a special preservative against shipwreck' [1.21].¹²⁹

1.4.3 The congregational shore

The *Vitae* of Epiphanius and Porphyry provide evidence for the shore as a congregational space.

During the drought of 393-396 Faustianus, a member of a powerful pagan family in Salamis-Constantia, used his authority as the city's sole supplier of grain to charge 'the

¹²⁵ *Vita* 54, 56, 57 in Rapp (1991), I, 140, II 120, 124. For the reef off Salamis and its danger particularly to winter shipping see Flemming (1974) 163-173

¹²⁶ Hackett (1901) 411; Rapp (1991) II 231 understands this as a later tradition which Papacostas, pers comm, identifies as Middle Byzantine.

¹²⁷ Kyrris (1970) 176 dates the cult of Mamas to the fifth century. Papacostas, pers comm, identifies the Mamas tradition as 14th c and the myrrh-exuding sarcophagus as 15th c. For the Cappodocian origins of Mamas, Barnabas and Hilarion see Kyrris (1991) 211-12. For Mamas see also Mouriki (1993) 249-51

¹²⁸ Hackett (1901) 416; Leontios Makhairas in Dawkins (1932) I.33

¹²⁹ Hackett (1901) 417

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exorbitant rate of three modia of grain per nomisma' despite Epiphanius' pleading on his flock's behalf.¹³⁰ Faustianus' granary held supplies sufficient for the whole city and following the discovery of gold in the Temple of Zeus Epiphanius bought the merchant's entire stock.¹³¹ His granaries empty, Faustianus used his own six ships and hired five more to import grain from Calabria.¹³² But as his ships approached Salamis-Constantia they foundered and grain was washed ashore where it was 'harvested' by the city's population.¹³³ Less than a decade later the populace again flocked to the harbour when their bishop's body was brought ashore.

Men and brethren, citizens of the populous metropolis of Constantia, come down to the sea at the place called Dianeuterion and receive the precious remains of our holy and most blessed father Epiphanius, for he has finished his human life.¹³⁴

Mark the Deacon's account of marble arriving for the embellishment of the cathedral at Gaza imagines the congregational shore as a site of spectacle.

As these columns arrived by sea...everyone, upon hearing the news, rushed to the shore...They brought carts and, after loading the columns one by one, pulled them along and deposited them in the open space of the church.¹³⁵

In the late fifth and sixth centuries substantial amounts of marble were imported from the quarries of Proconnesus in the Sea of Marmara, 100 nautical miles west of Constantinople [1.22]. It is chiefly attested in the shoreline churches of the west, south and east coasts of Cyprus – particularly at Polis-Arsinoë [1.23], Peyia [1.24], Limeniotissa at Kourion [1.25] and

¹³⁰ *Vita* 93 in Rapp (1991) I 162; II 166. Also van den Ven (1953) 49. Talbot Rice and Gunnis (1937) 170 report an icon taken in procession from Lythrankomi to the sea in times of drought and thrice dipped in the waves.

¹³¹ *Vita* 95 in Rapp (1991) I 162; II 169

¹³² The drought must have affected the whole of the Eastern Mediterranean for Faustianus to source his supplies at such a distance.

¹³³ *Vita* 6 in Rapp (1991) I 151, 157, 159; II 170; for a similar story in which rain caused the granary of a rich man to collapse so that the starving are able to help themselves. See also *Vita Spyridonis* 2. in van den Ven (1953) 49-50, 11-14

¹³⁴ *Vita* 125 in Rapp (1991) I 159; II 207. Hackett (1902) 13 suggests Epiphanius died 'when almost within sight of Constantia'.

¹³⁵ Mark the Deacon in Hill (1913) 94

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Campanopetra [1.26][1.27].¹³⁶ In the Central Basilica at Peyia, where the mosaic floor of the bema is inhabited by fish [1.28], the remains of a Proconnesian ambo bore the inscription ΥΠΕΡ ΕΥΧΗΣ ΝΑΥΤΩΝ (in fulfilment of the vow of sailors) which Michaelides has interpreted as an offering by mariners for the safe voyage of their ships [1.29].¹³⁷

IV.5 Cyprus at the centre I: a pilgrimage *île-carrefour*

According to Chapter 13 of his *Vita*, Epiphanius' body remained in his eponymous church for ten days, 'causing many miracles.' Indeed, the principal purpose of his *Vita* may have been the promotion of an Epiphanian cult at the crossroads of two major pilgrimage axes.¹³⁸ The east-west axis was predominantly associated with Holy Land pilgrimage, from Constantinople to Jerusalem. Evidence that Salamis-Constantia was also a station *en-route* to and from the Holy Land is provided by the Piacenza Pilgrim, writing c.570.

Leaving Constantinople we came to the island of Cyprus and the city of Constantia the resting-place of Saint Epiphanius. It is a beautiful and pleasant city with lovely date-palms.¹³⁹

To the north lay the shrine of St Thekla at Meriamlik in Cilicia and to the south the shrines of Menouthis and ʿĀbū Mīnā, east and west of Alexandria [1.30]. Connections between Cyprus and the Alexandrian shrines are attested by a Menas ampulla excavated at Peyia, by the probability that most of the LR1 amphora excavated there were of Cypriot origin and evidence from the *Vita* of the John the Almsgiver, that its author, Bishop Leontios of Neapolis (Limassol), worshipped at the shrines of Menouthis and ʿĀbū Mīnā.¹⁴⁰

IV.6 Cyprus at the Centre II: the centrifugal and the omphalic

¹³⁶ Sodini (1989) 163-86 figs 3-7, 11

¹³⁷ Michaelides (2001b) 51; Daszewski and Michaelides (1988) 97 and fig. 11; Michaelides (1987b) 49 and fig. 58

¹³⁸ Rapp (1991) I.215

¹³⁹ Wilkinson (2002b) 129; Elsner (2000) 189

¹⁴⁰ For Cypriot red slip 'in overwhelming quantities in groups of the late fifth and early sixth century...until the seventh century' at ʿĀbū Mīnā see Hayes (1972) 372-85. For Cypriot pilgrims at the Alexandrian shrines *PG* 87/3 col.3635, 3628, 3652-56; Dawes and Baynes (1996) 204, 208; Vryonis (1981) 200-201; Festugiere (1974) 345, 362, 408-9, Fernandez Marcos (1975) 370-72, 387-89; Van den Ven (1953) 81-2 and Miracle 15 'Un bateau chypriote sauvé de la tempête' and Miracle 37 'La même source guérit un Chypriote aveugle,' in Dagrón (1978) 330-2, 390.

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I have proposed a Late Antique Mediterranean of dispersed centres, in the conceptual midst of which Cyprus constituted an *île-carrefour*. There was, however, another sense in which the island occupied a central position – its proximity to the *omphalic* centres of the Eastern Christendom.

The *Orbis Terrarum* and the maps of Anaximander and Indicopleustes indicate that Cyprus, far from being isolated, would have been located close to the centre of world.¹⁴¹ The *omphalos* of Delphi took the form of a stone baetylus, and the baetylus at the sanctuary of Aphrodite at Palaipaphos may be understood as similarly operating.¹⁴² Furthermore the attacks made on the cult by Firmicius Maternus (c.345-50) suggests that its force extended into the Christian era.¹⁴³ In Jerusalem, the *omphalos* at the centre of the Holy of Holies in the Jewish Temple marked the position of the Ark.¹⁴⁴ However, according to Arnold, ‘the historic ark...was not a unique but a manifold object...and the theory of a single ark, corresponding to...a single legitimate sanctuary, is the last surviving Deuteronomistic conceit.’¹⁴⁵ A manifold Christian *omphalos*, then, might come as no surprise. Although, in the *Anacreonticon* 20:29, Sophronius (560-638) described Golgotha as ‘...the navel-point of the earth,’ it was not the only Christian *omphalos* in the Holy City.¹⁴⁶ According to the *Book of Jubilees*, a text referenced by Epiphanius,

...the Garden of Eden is the holy of holies...and Mount Sinai is the centre of the desert, and Mount Zion – the centre of the navel of the earth: these three were created as holy places facing each other.¹⁴⁷

¹⁴¹ Harley and Woodward (1987) 135 fig. 8.5; 263 fig.15.2

¹⁴² See the coin of Julia Domnia (193-217) in Maier (2004) 50 fig.35. The stone is exhibited in the on-site museum.

¹⁴³ Forbes (1970) 65-6

¹⁴⁴ According to Kedoshim 10 of the second century *Midrash Tanhuma* (Hertzberg (1963) 143) ‘Israel is the centre of the world, Jerusalem is the centre of the land of Israel, the Temple is at the centre of Jerusalem, the Holy of Holies is at the centre of the Temple, the Ark is at the centre of the Holy of Holies and the Foundation stone, is in front of the Ark, which spot is the foundation of the world.’

¹⁴⁵ Arnold (1917) 26-7;

¹⁴⁶ Sophronios *Anacreonticon* 20.19 in Wilkinson (2002b) 158

¹⁴⁷ *The Book of Jubilees* viii:19 in Charles (2010) 74. For the Garden of Eden’s mountain location see Summers (2003) 136

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Sinai, the Temple Mount, Golgotha and Zion were high places. Deleuze, and Braudel before him, drew a parallel between mountains and islands.¹⁴⁸ Deleuze, returned to the ‘... well-known ...the myth of the flood. The ark sets down on the one place on earth that remains uncovered by water...It is an island or a mountain, or both at once: the island is a mountain under water, and the mountain, an island that is still dry.’¹⁴⁹ Located at sea-level, Agios Epiphanius clearly cannot qualify as an elevated site but Cyprus as ‘a place on earth...uncovered by water’ qualifies as a Deleuzian mountain, at the foot of which, according to Ammianus, the sea conceals ‘deep valleys...’¹⁵⁰

1.4.6 ...the sea, believe me, is safer than the land.¹⁵¹

The early-seventh century *Vision of Kaioumos* tells of Philentolos of Salamis, whose income came ‘from land and sea,’ which might be understood as ‘an entrepreneur mediating between raw materials from the hinterland, processed at the coast, and traded overseas.’¹⁵² Indeed, it is a characteristic shared by entrepreneurs, traders and ecclesiastics that they seek to make permeable the more-or-less fixed geographies defined by cartographers. Mountains were barriers to be overcome for those in search of mineral deposits, and winds, currents and winter weather were barriers to be overcome by those whose lives depended upon networks of exchange. Against the oft-repeated claim for a closed season, Frost argues that

[p]eople go where they want to go for socio-economic reasons: winds and currents never completely dictate ports of call, instead seamanship and local knowledge compensate for navigational difficulties...Nevertheless academic dogma is produced to explain what could, or could not, be done at sea in antiquity. It is for instance, commonly assumed that ancient seafarers *never* crossed the open sea, *never* ventured forth out of season and *never* sailed by night...theories [which]...tend to clash with archaeological findings.¹⁵³

¹⁴⁸ Braudel (1972) I.39

¹⁴⁹ Deleuze (2003) 13

¹⁵⁰ Ammianus XXVI 10, 15 in Rolfe (1940) II 649. According to a local Cypriot tradition Noah’s Ark rested for while on the summit of Mount Olympus (1953m). In the pre-Pleistocene period the Mesaoria was a sea separating the predecessors of the Troodos Mountains and the Kyrenian range.

¹⁵¹ Claudius Claudianus (4th-5th c) in Roberts (2000) 49

¹⁵² Bowersock (2000) 15-16; Halkin (1945) 58

¹⁵³ Frost (1995) 1

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Demosthenes (384-322 BC) mentions that trade between Egypt and Rhodes continued throughout the winter months although this may have principally applied to the *annona* and military shipping.¹⁵⁴ Smaller vessels would have avoided the open sea in favour of longer, coastal routes involving a greater number of ports, harbours and anchorages.¹⁵⁵

Generally and '[d]espite the obvious dangers,' for Horden and Purcell, 'sea transport so far surpassed land communications...as to make the Mediterranean a milieu of interlocking routes on to which the coastlands and the harbours faced.'¹⁵⁶ In 1964 Jones famously argued for the superiority of marine networks. On the evidence of Diocletian's Price Edict of 301, he calculated that a wagon of wheat, travelling by road, would have doubled its price every 300 miles.¹⁵⁷ It would, therefore, have been quicker and cheaper to carry the wheat by ship from Egypt to Rome than to travel even seventy-five miles on land. Indeed road transport was often co-opted as an extension of *cabotage*, described by Horden and Purcell as the 'fluvialization' of the land.¹⁵⁸

The ships of the *annona* may have been serviced at the substantial anchorage at Kioni on the west coast of the Akamas from the fresh water springs close to the shore.¹⁵⁹ Leonard suggests that Kioni also served 'local coasters transporting goods and passengers to and from outlying settlements...which were often more difficult to reach by land.'¹⁶⁰ Morris and Peatfield, too, suggest that 'Communication via small boats up and down the coast [of Cyprus] may have been easier than overland methods.'¹⁶¹

¹⁵⁴ Demosthenes *Against Dionysodorus* in Murray (1939) 213; Bakirtzis (1995) 251

¹⁵⁵ Hadjisavvas (1995) 94

¹⁵⁶ Horden and Purcell (2000) 11

¹⁵⁷ Jones (1964) II. 841

¹⁵⁸ Horden and Purcell (2000) 140

¹⁵⁹ For Kioni see Gunnis (1936) 382 and Leonard (1995b) 133. When Koini was active seagoing ships were large; seventh-century Yassi Ada was about 21m long and the grain ships larger still.

¹⁶⁰ Leonard (1995b) 133. For later traffic which 'crept along the shore' see Cobham (1908) 54-55, 72

¹⁶¹ Morris and Peatfield (1987) 119-212 at 203

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1.4.7 Trade and the transmission of ideas

That the sea surrounds islands and cuts them off from the rest of the world more effectively than any other environment is certainly true whenever they are really situated outside the normal sea routes. But when they are integrated into shipping routes...[they] become one of the links in a chain...[and] actively involved in the dealings of the outside world.¹⁶²

Where the sea was a transactional space, islands were integrated or remote in proportion to their integration in networks of exchange. Ricardo's rule states that partners in international trade benefit equally by specialising in the production of commodities in which they hold a comparative advantage.¹⁶³ Thus trade overrode jurisdiction because the purpose of negotiation between parties was the diminution of difference and the consequent construction of equivalence at the point of exchange – hence, one quantity (one nomisma) might be exchanged for another (three modia of grain). Functioning independently of trade, gift exchange too implies equivalence - Anthemius gifted the gospel book found with the body of St Barnabas to Emperor Zeno (r.474-5/476-491) who, in response, gifted Agios Varnavas (or Campanopetra) as the centre for the Barnabas cult.¹⁶⁴

Roullet proposed that the presence of Egypt in the wider Mediterranean was disseminated via trade routes, but these two examples point to different registers of exchange in which trade was not the master template: trade co-existed with, but did not determine reception from a supposed centre.¹⁶⁵ For Sinclair '[t]he transmission of ideas can be achieved by single individuals, and in principle can occur over long distances even in environments with very low interaction capacity.'¹⁶⁶ Becker emphasises an unpredictability in the direction of flow even to the point of inverting the dominant model: '[The] movement of texts and ideas out from the...center created new paths for the transmission of knowledge, paths that could at times circuit back, allowing for the periphery to flow to the centre in richly

¹⁶² Braudel (1972) 1.150

¹⁶³ Bouare (2009) 99-103

¹⁶⁴ 'The body of the Holy apostle Barnabas was found in Cyprus and he had in his hand the gospel according to Matthew which he was himself revealing,' Victor Tununensis (444-567) in Roberts (2000) 52

¹⁶⁵ Roullet (1972) 4-5

¹⁶⁶ Buzan and Little (2000) 1291

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generative and new ways.¹⁶⁷ Traffic between metropolis and province, therefore, need not be determined by the dominant authority.

As I shall emphasise, particularly in Chapter 5 and the conclusion, Cypriot opposition to the capital not only demonstrated doctrinal independence but also a considerable degree of self-confidence. When the Monophysite bishop of Cyprus opposed John Scholasticus, patriarch of Constantinople in the late 560's or early 70s and Orthodox bishops on the island opposed Heraclian Monothelitism in 630s, they clearly regarded themselves as *equal* to the fight. After all, the Cypriot *Tyche* on the Vrap Cup, quite probably the product of a Cypriot workshop, is represented not as a dependency of Constantinople, nor even as an *imitatio Constantinopitanae urbis*, but as its equivalent [1.31-4].

1.5. Coda: was Akrotiri an island?

An isle beyond an isle she lay, the pale ship anchored in the bay.¹⁶⁸

The final section of this chapter provides a context for the final chapter of the whole thesis. In Late Antiquity to what extent might the Akrotiri Peninsular, the site of the excavations discussed in the concluding chapter, have been understood as an 'island' for which greater Cyprus functioned as a 'mainland'? The names of two sites on the west coast of the island suggest that a peninsular might indeed be understood as an island. Geronisos (*hiera* = holy; *nēsos* = island), the name of the island identified at the beginning of this chapter, is also the name of the peninsula, Cape Geronisos, 14km to its north.¹⁶⁹ Because the anchorages at Cape Geronisos, Kioni and Kasha tou Kouttouroumou on the west side of the Akamas and Fontana Amorosa and Ayios Nikolaos on the east were serviced by 'local coasters transporting goods and passengers to and from outlying settlements...which were often difficult to reach by land' they were serviced from the sea as though they were islands [1.35].¹⁷⁰

¹⁶⁷ Becker (2006) 29

¹⁶⁸ Flecker (1947) 109

¹⁶⁹ What cannot be ascertained is the extent to which the name of the peninsular predates the Kitchener map of 1885

¹⁷⁰ Leonard (1995b) 133

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There is evidence that the twelve-kilometre-long peninsular on the south of the island at Akrotiri was similarly served. Originally an island, Akrotiri was separated from 'mainland' Cyprus to the north by a wide navigable channel [1.36].¹⁷¹ By the Later Roman period this had been blocked by spits extending southwards from the Kouris and Garyllis rivers [1.37].¹⁷² Although the debris created a causeway between 'island' and 'mainland,' there is no evidence for a connecting roadway.¹⁷³ It appears, therefore, that Akrotiri continued to be serviced by sea, principally from the south because neither Episkopi Bay on the west nor Akrotiri Bay on the east provided suitable anchorages.¹⁷⁴ Furthermore, Akrotiri lay between two ports, Amathus in the east and Kourion in the west, and traffic between the two would have passed the southern end of the peninsular. In the winter months, when the water-level was sufficiently high, Akrotiri may also have been serviced on its landward side across the salt lake, thereby avoiding the dangers of navigating round the two capes at the southern end of the Peninsular - Kouriakon (Cape Zevgari) in the south-west and Kargaiai (Cape Gata) to the south-east.¹⁷⁵ It appears, then, that to the north, the land connection was neither well-developed nor reliable, while to the south, the Peninsular was probably integrated into a network of coastal shipping. Hence, treating Akrotiri as an island may be justified even though, strictly speaking, it had ceased to be one. However, there is one principal difference between the Akamas and Akrotiri; the Akamas was sparsely populated whereas from the Hellenistic period to the end of the seventh century Akrotiri was occupied by a thriving community.¹⁷⁶

In his *Geography* (Bk. XIV.6), written in AD 23, Strabo describes the sea-passage along the south coast of the island: 'Then to the city of Amathus (*Αμαθούς*)...Then to Curias, (*Κουριάς*) which is peninsula-like (*χερσονησώδης*)...then to a city Curium (*Κούριον*), which

¹⁷¹ Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 191

¹⁷² Heywood (1982) 163. For changes to the Cypriot coast- and shoreline see Flemming (1974) 164 and Colombier (1987) 159-72 (167-8 for Akrotiri)

¹⁷³ Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 191

¹⁷⁴ Episkopi Bay Marine Survey discovered high levels of Late Antique traffic: *ARDA 2003* (2005) 89-92; 2004 (2006) 91-93; 2005 (2007) 79-80; (2008) 78-79. For a survey of Akrotiri-Dreamer's Bay: *ARDA 2006* (2008) 96-99

¹⁷⁵ Talbert (2000) map 72

¹⁷⁶ Heywood (1982) 167

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has a mooring place.¹⁷⁷ The *Stadiasmus Maris Magni* records a place called *Καργία* with a promontory (*ἀκρωτήριο*) with a harbour (*λιμὴν*) and an anchorage (*ὑφορμος*).¹⁷⁸ Although intended for use by mariners, the *Stadiasmus*, in common with other *peripli*, was not accompanied by a map. However a fifteenth-century copy of a Ptolomaic map of AD 160 appears to support the identification of Akrotiri with Curias by showing the Akrotiri Peninsula as *Curie Extrema*.¹⁷⁹ Porcacchi, in 1567, muddies the waters by introducing (i) 'Curias, another royal capital...near the sea-coast where now stands Piscopia' [Episkopi], and (ii) 'Curias, an ancient city [which] lay in the middle of the C. delle Gatta, two leagues and a half from Piscopia' - clinching the identification by describing 'a lake to the north of it, full of salt water.'¹⁸⁰ There are, then, two places called Curias, one 'where now stands' Episkopi and another 'two leagues and a half' from Episkopi,' south of the salt lake. On the basis of Strabo, the *Stadiasmus*, the Ptolomaic map and Porcacchi, I think it is reasonable to accept that Curias is the name of the peninsula *and* the name of a settlement located on it. But do the scant remains on the peninsular provide evidence for its location? There are three contenders either alone or, more probably, in combination, - Dreamer's Bay (Vounari tou Kambiou), Lania and Katalymmata ton Plakoton [1.38].

A recent survey at Dreamer's Bay revealed evidence of Late Antique occupation on top of the cliffs, including the foundations of three warehouses (*horea*), a possible villa, rock-cut foundations for a road and an eastern and a western necropolis.¹⁸¹ Perhaps the most spectacular evidence is an ashlar breakwater projecting some 200m south-eastwards from the north end of the bay, 5m wide at its shore end, widening to 10m at its south-eastern tip [1.39].¹⁸² Haggerty, who surveyed the site between 1984 and 1989, identified at least two column drums, which suggests that, like the breakwater at Nea Paphos, the Akrotiri

¹⁷⁷ Strabo XIV.6 in Jones (1970) 379. For the Latinised *Curias* see Pliny V.xxxv, 129-131 in Rackham (1942) II 319

¹⁷⁸ *Stadiasmus* 303 in Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 190 n.7

¹⁷⁹ Heywood (1982) 174

¹⁸⁰ Porcacchi (1590) 144-153

¹⁸¹ In 2006, the area was surveyed by Leonard and Parks (2006) 96-99. See also *ARDA* (2004) 93.

¹⁸² Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 189-202, 192-4, fig.5, 6. The breakwater begins c.40m offshore with a preserved length of c.165m

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breakwater would have been embellished with colonnades and hence may have accommodated larger vessels than those normally associated with *cabotage*.¹⁸³

Ceramic evidence in the immediate vicinity attests to the Akrotiri's participation in wider networks of exchange. The earliest belongs to the fourth century and is possibly Thasian; later sources include Crete (AC4), Anemurium, the Levant (LR3 and 4/5) Cilicia, Egypt (LR6) and Seleucia (Kuzmanov Type IX).¹⁸⁴ On a ledge a few metres beneath the water at the south west-tip at Cape Zevgari, about four kilometres west of Dreamer's Bay, lies the scattered cargo of a fifth- or sixth-century wreck, including Late Roman amphora (LR1) of a type typically associated with the olive oil industry based around Antioch.¹⁸⁵ Leonard and Demesticha conclude that '...the port at Dreamer's Bay appears from its surface pottery to have economic ties with (at least) Cilicia and Crete in the Roman period, and with the whole of the eastern Mediterranean region in the Late Roman period.'¹⁸⁶ Indeed Dreamer's Bay may not simply have been a link in a chain, but following the earthquake of 365 which wrought so much destruction at Kourion, as elsewhere, it possibly took over Kourion's role as 'the beginning of the westerly voyage in the direction of Rhodes.'¹⁸⁷ Leonard and Demesticha suggest that '... most goods moving through Dreamer's Bay were imports intended either for local consumption or further exchange, via *cabotage*, with other ports on the Cypriot south coast,' which might have included Kioni in the Akamas, Paphos, Kourion, Amathous, Zygi-Petrini, Laterou Chiftlik and Kition [1.40].¹⁸⁸

Of the two possible remaining sites for Curias, Lania has two subterranean basilica-like structures carved into the bedrock. Both are orientated north-south with aisles divided by piers and entered through doorways with anterooms either side, giving access to the

¹⁸³ Haggerty, *The Akrotiri Wall Project*, unpublished report in Leonard and Demesticha (2004) at 192-194

¹⁸⁴ Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 198-199

¹⁸⁵ Leidwanger (2007) 308

¹⁸⁶ Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 202

¹⁸⁷ Strabo XIV. 6 in Jones (1970) 381; Cobham (1908) 2; Soren (1987) 26 fig 11; Bullard (1987) 54, fig.27. The large amounts of marble revetment excavated at Katalymmata may have been cargo carried by the ships of the *annona*, perhaps stopping at Akrotiri *en route* to Alexandria - suggesting shipping may have been serviced on the south coast of the island as well as the west.

¹⁸⁸ Leonard and Demesticha (2004) 201

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aisles.¹⁸⁹ There is no indication of a date, apart from fifth- to seventh-century ceramic inclusions in the floor of one of them.¹⁹⁰ The evidence for Dreamer's Bay, the option preferred by Leonard and Demesticha, is clearly much richer. But Dreamer's Bay may have been the port of Curias and the remains currently being excavated at Katalymmata ton Plakoton, may have constituted the centre of the main settlement. [1.41].

In conclusion, how might the lexical and metaphorical definitions of an island, with which this chapter began, apply to the question 'was Akrotiri an island?' Amongst the chain of harbours and anchorages linked to it, Akrotiri was something of an exception. Given its poor and seasonally-conditioned connections to mainland Cyprus, Akrotiri must have been an emporium largely orientated to marine networks of exchange. It epitomized the apparent paradox of land (to the north) which isolates, and sea (to east, west and south) which connects. It also characterises another theme of this chapter, the island as a 'zone of transition.' From a thriving settlement in the sixth and early seventh centuries, by a later period Akrotiri acquired a quite different sense of the insular as medieval visitors disparaged its mosquitoes and serpents and its 'tainted and poisonous air.'¹⁹¹

¹⁸⁹ Heywood (1982) 168-9

¹⁹⁰ *ARDA*, (1996) 48; *BCH* 121.2 (1997) 902-3 figs 47-9

¹⁹¹ Heywood (1982) 166

Chapter 2

2.1 Argument

Regretting the anonymity of Byzantine architects, Mango wrote that '[b]ut for one or two exceptional cases the identity of the architect eludes us altogether.¹ It is quite possible that Epiphanius is one of those exceptions. Appointed bishop of Cyprus in 367, he is widely assumed to have been instrumental in planning the basilica at Salamis-Constantia which, by the early fifth century, bore his name.² Hazardous as it may be to identify one building as the principal source for another, the basilica built on Mount Sion in Jerusalem of the 390s is close enough in time, size and proportions to Salamis to suggest a shared programme.³ In 394 Epiphanius may have attended the consecration of Sion, perhaps the most important church constructed in the wake of the Second Ecumenical Council held at Constantinople in 381. Although Epiphanius probably left Constantinople for Rome before the Council assembled, he was closely identified with its convenor, Theodosius I, and with the Nicæan-Constantinopolitan Creed of which Epiphanius may have been the author.

The major doctrinal achievement of the Council of Nicaea in 325 had been the establishment of the consubstantial relationship of God and Christ, in response to the Egyptian priest Arius (250-336), who argued that Christ was God's creature and therefore His subordinate. Arianism and the related question of the Holy Spirit's place in the Trinity was the unfinished business the second Ecumenical Council sought to address. For Epiphanius, the Council came to represent both the final riposte to Arianism and the resolution of the consubstantial Trinity.

This chapter is in two sections. The first, set against the background of Nicaea in 325, traces Epiphanius' early career in Egypt and Palestine and examines the monastic, theological and architectural developments with which he came into contact. It

¹ Mango (1991) 44

² Rapp (1991) I.139; Jeffery (1928) 344-49; Delvoye (1980) 313-17; Megaw (1974) 61-64; Papageorgiou (1985) 301-304; Hackett (1901) 34. The Bordeaux pilgrim defines *basilica* with reference to the Martyrium on Golgotha, 'By order of the Emperor Constantine there has now been built there a 'basilica' – ...a 'place for the Lord''; Wilkinson (2002a) 31.

³ Mount Sion has been identified with a site on the eastern of two hills to the south of Jerusalem and by Josephus as the western hill. See Pixner and Riesner (2010) 320-322. Pixner (1990) 19 identifies Sion I with the Temple Mount and Sion II is located between the Tyropoeon and Kidron Valleys and Sion III is the hill now known by that name.

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identifies two key elements in the layout of Agios Epiphanius: (1) the rectangular ambulatory, common in civic basilicas, but in ecclesiastical complexes, largely confined to Egypt, and (2) the multi-columnar, multi-aisled basilica as a signifier of Christian self-assertion.

The second section concentrates on the last twenty years of the century and takes the Council of 381 as its starting point, identifying the three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica as its signature building. It argues that Salamis references Sion as part of a wider identification with the politics, theology and liturgical practice of late-fourth-century Jerusalem.

2.1 Egypt, Palestine and the First Ecumenical Council

2.1.1 Epiphanius: biography

Epiphanius was born between 310 and 320, of Jewish or mixed parentage, at Besandūk near Eleutheropolis in Palestine, 53 kms southwest of Jerusalem [2.1].⁴ The second decade of the century gave Christianity an entirely new status. In 313 Constantine (272-337) and Licinius (c.263-325) issued the *Edictum Mediolanensium* which recognised Christianity as a legal religion, removing the restrictions placed on it under Diocletian (244-311).

In his late teens Epiphanius set out for Egypt. Not only was Alexandria the empire's theological centre *par excellence*, the Egyptian hinterland saw the rise of two forms of early Christian practice - coenobitic monasticism, where the faithful lived as a community, and asceticism, which eschewed society for a life of impoverishment and prayer. Returning to Besandūk in the mid-330s, Epiphanius established a monastery there which he led until appointed to Cyprus in 367.⁵ Thereafter he travelled widely, his final journey being to Constantinople in 403, to accuse its patriarch, John Chrysostom

⁴ Goranson (1990) 35; Dechow (1988) 37

⁵ In the *Vita* Ch.32 Epiphanius' monastery has 50 monks and is called Spanhydrion; for the case for and against Besandūk as its location see Rapp (1991) I.119. For a monastery founded in his 20s see Rapp (1993) 170

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(c.349-407), of sheltering Origenist monks.⁶ On the return voyage Epiphanius died. The *Vita Epiphani* records his age as 114 and his episcopacy as lasting 55 years, although in reality it probably lasted 37.

2.1.2 Agios Epiphanius at Salamis

Epiphanius' episcopal complex was probably incomplete at the time of his death. Chapter 72 of the *Vita* records that about sixty craftsmen were engaged in the construction of the church, which proved necessary when the Christian population of Salamis-Constantia outgrew an earlier building.⁷

The late-fourth-century Agios Epiphanius was a timber-roofed basilica consisting of a nave and six flanking aisles, the outermost of which were narrow passageways [2.2]. The basilica was preceded by a narthex with apsidal north and south ends and a large western atrium. Its overall dimensions were 58m x 42m.⁸ Thirteen columns separated the nave from the inner aisles, fourteen separated the inner from the first outer aisles, and the outermost aisle/corridors were demarcated by the fourteen piers with attached shafts toward the nave. The columns defining the nave were assembled from *spoliata* stone drums 0.90m in diameter [2.3], set on bases 1.30m square [2.4] and crowned by purpose-made Corinthian capitals [2.5].⁹

Outer corridors, two on the north side and two on the south, ran the entire length of the basilica. The northern corridor contained two sets of stairs, probably leading to a gallery above the aisles [2.6-8]. Beyond the inner corridors were wider outer ones, articulated by attached pilasters and similar to those at Kourion identified by Megaw as *katechumenia*.¹⁰

⁶ The Origenist Tall Brothers were given sanctuary by Chrysostom and Epiphanius was persuaded to move against what he perceived as the patriarch's heresy. See Gregory (1979) 51-53. For Epiphanius' anti-Origenism see Clark (1992) 86-104

⁷ Rapp (1991) I.159; II.141. Stewart (2008) 65 doubts this was a place of Christian worship before Constantius.

⁸ Megaw (2007) 157; Jeffery (1928) 344 has 184ft by 148ft, a nave width of 38ft, and each double aisle as 52ft, giving a total area of 27,000 sq.ft. Papageorghiou (1985), 229-324 at 301 gives a length of 57m and a width of 35

⁹ Jeffery (1928) 346

¹⁰ Megaw (2007) 158

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The central nave concluded with a semi-circular apse [2.9], the inner aisles closed with inscribed apsidioles [2.10] and the outer aisles with rectangular recesses [2.11]. On the north side the narrowest aisle and the corridors accessed largely-unexcavated ancillary spaces; on the south, the three southern aisles and the inner corridor communicated with a large court at the east end of which was a baptistery.

2.1.3 Basilical origins

The increased demand for large, covered, congregational spaces in the wake of 313 would have required multiple supports as a matter of simple engineering. The 82 columns and piers at Agios Epiphanius, all probably the same height and comparable in girth, is an extraordinary number not otherwise found in ecclesiastical contexts outside Rome and North Africa.¹¹ However, the multi-columnar *aula*, understood as a hypostyle hall, had been identified by a group of early twentieth century scholars as a precursor of the Christian basilica, and although their hypothesis has subsequently received little attention it may, nevertheless, be helpful in contextualising Cypriot preferences.¹²

Christian basilicas as dispersed as those of Rome, North Africa and Cyprus could be understood as ‘halls with columns.’ While the *basilica forensis* was rare in the east, hypostyle halls were widely acculturated.¹³ On Cyprus, fourth-century Soloi A was evoked by Neal as ‘spectacular’ with a ‘forest’ of some 60 posts [2.12].¹⁴ Homogeneity would have been emphasised by a relatively narrow nave at 6.75m, and an aisle-width, which, rather than diminishing towards the outer wall, increased from 4m to 4.5m.¹⁵ Megaw dates Chrysopolitissa to the 370s, given that the earthquakes that destroyed Kourion in the 360s also destroyed Paphos [2.13].¹⁶ Its c.80 columns followed a not-dissimilar layout to Soloi: a nave of less than 9m, an inner aisle of 2.5m, a middle aisle

¹¹ The Lateran in Rome (Brandenburg (2005) 262 fig.13) had 38 nave columns out of alignment with the 42 columns dividing the aisles: cf. my fig. 2.76. Old St Peter’s had 88 columns and S.Paolo fuori le Mura had 80. Extra-mural Carthage was particularly rich in multi-columnar basilicas: St.Monique (78), the Basilica Majorum (96) and Damos al Karita (120 columns in the basilica and 215 in the overall complex).

¹² Leroux (1913) 146-148, fig. 49, 253-255, fig 66; also (1909) pls IV, V; Borchardt (1938); Swift (1951) 22; Langlotz (1951) 30-36

¹³ Ward-Perkins (1981) 258. Only two civic basilicas have been identified in Egypt; for Syrene see Jaritz in Kraus and Schalen (1988) 155-169 fig.1 and for Aswan see Grossmann in Bagnall (2007) 112

¹⁴ Neal (2010) 24. Cf Westolm (1933) figs 7 and 9

¹⁵ des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) 10

¹⁶ Megaw (1988) 139

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of 1.5m and, again, a slightly wider outer aisle of 1.75m.¹⁷ Both recalled hypostyle halls insofar as their rectangular plans entirely lacked apsidal projections, their naves were comparatively narrow and their aisles comparatively wide.

Two grid-based hypostyle structures from Roman Cyprus survived into the fourth century. West of Kourion, the Northwest Building of the Sanctuary of Apollo Hylates, was a Trajanic hall, raised on sixty-five columns, which Wright described as having 'the semblance of a forest of columns' [2.14-5].¹⁸ Another example, 'The Loutron' (1st-2nd c. - 4th-7th c.) lay barely 100m south of the atrium of Agios Epiphanius; a cistern c.60m by 20m, it was supported on 39 piers arranged three-by-thirteen, for which Wright provides a similarly afforested description [2.16-7].¹⁹

Malalas (c.491-578), writing in Justinianic Constantinople, makes two references to cisterns as *basilike kinsterna*. Yerebatan was one [2.18] and Binbirdirek [2.19] was probably the other, the cistern raised on 224 columns, which Wright suggests 'The Loutron' may have been intended to evoke.²⁰ Although the use of *basilike* may refer to imperial patronage, Downey makes the point that the cisterns Malalas cites were originally colonnaded courts before being in-filled with columns.²¹ If so, it is possible that, as late as the sixth century, the multi-columnar *basilike* and the hypostyle *basilike kisterna* were understood as belonging to the same genus.

The more commonly cited model for the Christian basilica is the *basilica forensis*, usually constructed with longitudinal aisles and an apse at one or both ends. Krautheimer thought it 'very possible that the doubling of the aisles at the Lateran, at St.Peter's, and on Golgotha...reflects a desire to emulate the great secular basilicas...the Basilica Julia and the Ulpia' [2.20-21].²² Ward-Perkins suggests that 'Constantine must assuredly have had the Basilica Ulpia in mind when he selected the timber-roofed, clerestory-lit basilica to be the standard type of building for...the newly enfranchised Christian religion.'²³ Two of the most distinctive features of Basilicas Ulpia

¹⁷ BCH 102 (1978) 936; 105 (1981) 1007; 108 (1984) 959; 110 (1986) 862; Megaw (1988) 136-139

¹⁸ Wright (1992) I.169

¹⁹ Wright (1992) I.154

²⁰ Wright (1992) I.498

²¹ Downey (1937) 205

²² Krautheimer (1967) 135 figs 4,5,8,9

²³ Ward-Perkins (2003) 64

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and Julia were their multiple, rectangular and concentric ambulatories around an open court, perhaps comparable with the Constantinopolitan cisterns before their columnar in-fill.

The rectangular ambulatory which lines the interior walls of Agios Epiphanius is unique amongst early Christian basilicas outside early-fourth-century Egypt. Grossmann has identified churches of this type of building as *Umgangsbasiliken*.²⁴ Originally complete circuits, their east aisles were interrupted by the subsequent projection of the sanctuary westwards, probably during the fifth century. Despite the conversion of Egyptian temples into Christian basilicas, Arnold urges caution in making a connection between the ambulatories in the two types of building:

In some multi-aisled churches the outer colonnades surround the raised central part on all four sides, similar to the festival hall of Thutmose III at Karnak. Since hypostyle halls were no longer built in the Late Period, it is deceptive...to reflect on such a connection between New Kingdom-period and Christian-period architecture.²⁵

Nevertheless, ambulatories in New Kingdom temples (1570-1070 BC) not only survived into the Christian period, they were adopted in those temples, like Karnak and Madīnat Hābū subject to Christian conversion.²⁶

The presence of Egypt in Later-Roman Cyprus is attested by trade, architecture and cult. Isis is identified in a second-century papyrus from Oxyrhynchus referring to Isis in Salamis and at Soloi, temples C and D may have been dedicated to her.²⁷ Although

²⁴Grossmann (2002) 28-31. For screened aisles open west and east see reconstructions of the Church of the Acheiropoietos in Salonica (c.450-70) in Krautheimer (1986) 100 fig. 50; sixth-century Basilica A at Amphipolis in Pallas (1977) fig. 57 and Lemerle's reconstruction of the Basilica A at Philippi in Hodinott (1963) 170 fig. 81

²⁵ Arnold (1999) 273 and 312-314. Leroux identified the festival hall at Karnak as the archetypal hypostyle hall: see Leroux (1913) 146-148 for Karnak and 253-255 for Delos. Temple conversion in Cyprus was rare probably because mid-fourth century earthquakes left more *spolia* for the construction of new churches than temples ripe for conversion. The Acropolis temple at Amathus may have been converted into a church as late as the fifth century: see Aupert (1996a) 161-4 and Rautman, www.stoa.org/hopper 21.04.09. According to Yon (1997) 283 and Callot (1985) 366-7 fig.3, the Temple of Zeus at Salamis was converted into a church.

²⁶ For temple conversions see McKenzie (2007) 312-316 and Saradi-Mendelovici (1990) 52-55

²⁷ Westholm (1936) 151. Wild (1984) 1821-1823 describes the Soloi temples as 'the only temples outside Egypt known to have imitated traditional Egyptian temple architecture.' For an inscription at Soloi with the name Potamon, common in the prosopography of Christian Egypt see Tinh (1985) 51 n.13. Stephanus of Byzantium (active c.528-535) in Pohlsander (1999) 46,

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Epiphanius was clear that Isis was an 'evil invention,' attitudes towards Egypt were complex.²⁸ On the one hand Egypt was 'the second Holy Land.'²⁹ On the other 'old' Egypt beguiled even the Christian emperor with whom Epiphanius is most closely identified.³⁰ In 390 or 391, Theodosius I (347-395) brought the obelisk of Thuthmosis III from Karnak and erected it on the *spina* of the hippodrome at Constantinople, setting it on a base on which he was conspicuously present [2.22-3].³¹

For theologians the lure of Egypt was principally the Didascalia, the catechetical school founded in Alexandria in 190 and famous for its espousal of orthodox theology. According to McKenzie, Alexandria's reputation as a theological centre overshadowed its importance 'as a major centre of architectural innovation and artistic influence from the Ptolomaic to the Byzantine periods.'³² Furthermore, there has been considerable disagreement amongst scholars concerning the relationship between Alexandria and its hinterland. In 1954 Ward-Perkins proposed that, while elsewhere in the Mediterranean the five-aisled basilica was identified with Constantinian triumph, in Egypt it was an entirely provincial affair.³³ However, in 2007 McKenzie argued that 'recent scholarship on Church history has revealed that there is no evidence that the Church in the rest of Egypt in the fourth to sixth centuries functioned as a separate world from that in Alexandria. This means there is no longer any reason to think that the churches in Egypt would not reflect those in Alexandria.'³⁴ Clearly Epiphanius knew something of churches in Alexandria because he describes how,

...in Constantine's time, it was decided to rebuild...[the Caesarium] as a church...It was burned down in Julian's time, and rebuilt by the blessed bishop Athanasius himself. But...there are many others, one called the church of Dionysius and those of Theonas, Pierus, Sarapion, Perseaea, Dizya Mendidus, Ammianus, and the church of Baucalis and others.³⁵

described Amathus as 'A very ancient city of Cyprus. There Adonis Osiris whom the Cypriots and Phoenicians identify as Egyptian, was honoured'.

²⁸ Epiphanius 1.4 2,5 in Williams (2009) I.22

²⁹ Duchesne in Cross (1951) xvii

³⁰ Rapp (1991) I.12-13, 21, 154, 176

³¹ For Imperial Rome's fascination with Egypt see Roulet (1972)

³² McKenzie (2007) 1

³³ Ward-Perkins (1954) 69-90; Grossmann (2002) 32

³⁴ McKenzie (2007) 261. Wace, Megaw and Skeat (1959) 78 regarded the transept at Hermopolis as an example of the deep penetration of Alexandria into its hinterland. Grossmann (2007) 104 argued that Alexandria was relatively detached from Upper Egypt.

³⁵ Epiphanius V.49 (69) 2, 2-3 in Williams (1994) II 326

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Furthermore, he described the church of 'Pierios and his brother Isidore,' as 'very large' presumably meaning multi-aisled and multi-columnar.³⁶ However, it is not clear that Epiphanius' knowledge was first-hand because, tempting as it is to accept that no orthodox cleric visiting Egypt could avoid Alexandria, the textual evidence is inconclusive.

2.1.4 Epiphanius in Egypt

Epiphanius arrived in Egypt when Arianism was still a live issue. The heresy had its origins in Alexandria in 318 in a dispute between Patriarch Alexander (r.313-326) and the priest Arian (c.250-336), who argued against a Trinity of the 'same essence.' However, Epiphanius reserved his most vociferous criticism for the early third-century theologian Origen, who he identified as the 'the father of Arius.'³⁷ Origen argued that ...the Son, being less than the Father, is superior to rational creatures alone...the Holy Spirit is still less....³⁸ Epiphanius' principal ally contra Origen/Arius was Alexander's successor, Athanasius I (r.328-373). The Creed adopted at Nicaea in 325 was essentially Athanasian. Athanasius also provided the template for the concept of *homoousios* – the belief that the three parts of the Trinity were consubstantial – the theology which underpinned Epiphanius' heresy list, the *Panarion* (374-377).³⁹

Although Epiphanius 'is always in communion with Athanasius,' there is little evidence of direct contact with S.Antony (c.251-356).⁴⁰ The most famous ascetic of his day and the subject of Athanasius' *Vita*, Antony was fiercely opposed to 'Ario-maniacs.'⁴¹ Sozomen described how Epiphanius had 'been instructed from his youth by the most celebrated ascetics,' and few were more celebrated than Antony.⁴² Antony's pupil, and Epiphanius' mentor, Hilarion (291-371), provides a surer Antonine connection as does

³⁶ McKenzie (2008) 244

³⁷ Frend (1985) 79 suggests 'The Holy Spirit was logically superfluous to Origen's theology.' According to Bigham (2008) 17-20 the so-called *Letter to Theodosius* claiming that Epiphanius was brought up 'in the faith of the fathers of Nicaea,' was probably a later interpolation intended to reinforce his orthodox credentials.

³⁸ Origen III.5 in Butterworth, (1966) 34

³⁹ Beeley (2008), 219, n.102

⁴⁰ Dechow (1988) 84

⁴¹ Athanasius in Meyer (1978), 6, 78-9, 87-9, 94-7, 128, n.236

⁴² Sozomen 6.32 (2010 reprint) 266

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Chapter 48 of the *Vita Epiphanii* in which another Antonine pupil, Paphnutius, gives Epiphanius a first-hand account of the ascetic's life.⁴³

2.1.5 Fourth-century Egypt: five-aisled basilicas and four-sided ambulatories

The five-aisled basilica enjoyed a particularly extended life in Egypt, where its plan was augmented by transverse aisles constructing a complete circuit lining the interior walls.⁴⁴ Ambulatories may have their origins in, for example, the Festival Hall of Thutmose III at Karnak [2.24], but they appear, at the same time, in the *Umgangsbasilike* constructed *de novo* at Antinoopolis and Pbow [2.25-6].⁴⁵

2.1.5.i Antinoopolis and Pbow

Pachomius (290-347), probably the founder of coenobitic monasticism, established his first monastery at Tabenissi between 318 and 323 and then moved a few kilometres south to Pbow (Faw Qibli), some 700 kms south of Alexandria, which became the centre for a new efflorescence. The Pbow basilica developed in three phases between c.337/8 and c.459.⁴⁶ Phase I was the most hypostyle-like, with five aisles of approximately the same width, divided by c.5.3m-tall granite columns, surrounded by a three-sided ambulatory.⁴⁷ In Phase III the nave was wider and the ambulatory was reduced to a narrow 2.8m-wide corridor. The number of columns increased dramatically from a minimum of forty-four to approximately eighty. The late-fourth century south church at Antinoopolis, some 300 kms north of Pbow, boasted ninety-four columns. Its ambulatory was formed from lateral aisles comparable with those at Pbow at 2.5m and, like Pbow, its eastern transverse aisle was subsequently appropriated by the westwards extension of the sanctuary.

⁴³ *Vita* Ch 48 in Rapp (1999) I.135; White (1998) 90; Chitty (1999) 14 describes Epiphanius as 'in some measure' Hilarion's pupil.

⁴⁴ For plans of five-aisled churches in Egypt see Grossmann (2002): Narmuthis CHD87, fig.42; CHH88 fig 43; seven-aisled CHG88 fig.44; the East Church at Philae (?) fig 78; 'Ayn Maṣūra, fig 6; Gruftkirche III at ʿAbū Mīnā fig.19; Festival Hall of Thutmose III fig 166

⁴⁵ Grossmann (2002): Karnak 46 fig.166; fifth-century Madīnat Hābū, 455-457 fig.73; Hermonthis 458-459 fig.74 probably from the first half of the fifth century.

⁴⁶ Grossmann (2002) for Antinoopolis 434-6 fig 55, Pbow 546-552-fig 163; McKenzie (2007) 271; Grossmann (2000) 269-81, 275 for 'umgänge' and 277 for Pbow.

⁴⁷ Grossmann (1979) 233 describes the three aisles in the middle of the basilica as replacing the nave of a standard basilica.

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Some scholars have suggested that Epiphanius received his education at a Pachomian monastery.⁴⁸ While Dechow doubts this, he suggests that Epiphanius may have known Pachomius.⁴⁹ Although the *Vita Prima* dates the foundation of Pbow to 330, the first phase of the basilica cannot be dated before c.337-8.⁵⁰ Dechow dates Epiphanius' return to Palestine as c.335, Bigham to 340.⁵¹ The difference may be less crucial than it seems given the similarities between Pbow and Antinoopolis, suggesting the existence of similar structures with which Epiphanius may have been familiar. If Epiphanius' Egypt of the 330s was a significant presence at Salamis in the 390s, how might the sixty year gap have been bridged? There is evidence for an essentially Egyptian practice at Epiphanius' monastery at Besandūk, of which he was the hegumen until 367, and with which he maintained contacts thereafter. Furthermore, Egyptian connections may have predated Epiphanius' arrival on the island as an Egyptian calendar was used in late-fourth-century Salamis.⁵²

2.1.6 Circumambulation

The typology of Antinoopolis and Pbow, then, may provide the model for the ambulatory at Agios Epiphanius. However, at Salamis the lateral aisles were narrower, defined by piers rather than columns and were separated from the aisles probably by wooden screens, except at their western and eastern ends which were open, implying a kind of transverse aisle. [2.27]⁵³ However, because attached shafts framed the openings, the 'transverse aisles' were more separated from the longitudinal aisles than was the case in Egypt [2.28].

One means of articulating the turn from one ambulatory corridor to the next involved the kind of tri-columnar support [2.29] which articulates the western and lateral aisles at the early-fourth-century East Church at Kellis in Egypt [2.30]. Epiphanius may have been familiar with these 'heart-shaped' columnar supports in Egypt, from the fourth-century synagogue at Capernaum on the occasions of his meeting with Joseph the Comes in Galilee, c.355-360 or, more immediately, from the corners of the peristyle of

⁴⁸ Riggi (1963) 101; for an opposing view see Dechow (1988) 33

⁴⁹ Dechow (1988) 32, 34

⁵⁰ For the *Vita Prima Graeca* see Halkin (1932)

⁵¹ Grossmann (2000) 281; Dechow (1988) 32-36; Bigham, (2008) 2; Rousseau (1985) 73

⁵² Chitty (1999) 14, 72-3; Stern (2012) 271-73

⁵³ Each opening was c. 2.70-2.80m wide, i.e. the same as an intercolumniation; Megaw (1956) 30. The early use of piers seems to have been rare: Marathovouno and Ayios Tykhonas.

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the Palaestra in Salamis itself [2.31].⁵⁴ Their use inside a church (as against an atrium) outside Egypt is rare. Rarer still is the manner of their use at Agios Epiphanius – not to effect a transition, but to construct an ‘entrance’ from the lateral into the transverse aisles by turning through 90° what was effectively a pier with attached shafts on two adjacent sides [2.32-3]. Perhaps the circuit was already old-fashioned when Epiphanius built his church, but whatever the reason, an eastern transverse aisle must have created a ‘circumambulated’ bema west of the eastern transverse aisle.⁵⁵ Here too, there may be an echo of Kellis, where one-metre-high wooden screens separated a presumably liturgical nave from the longitudinal and western aisles and possibly the eastern aisle too, effectively creating an ambulatory.⁵⁶ Fourth-century Chrysopolitissa in Paphos also had a central bema defined by screens and surrounded by aisles on four sides.⁵⁷ Megaw suggests a similar arrangement at Soloi A, with the altar close to the middle of the building.⁵⁸ The ‘circumambulated’ bema probably extended into the early-sixth century given that the apses of Soloi B, Kourion and Agios Epiphanius remained ‘empty’ until then.

2.1.7 Multi-aisled basilicas in Cyprus

The five-aisled basilica was rare in the east and the north of Cyprus. The sole Syrian example, the late-fourth or early-fifth-century church of Dionysus at Soueida, may be contemporary with Agios Epiphanius [2.34]. Although its east end was remarkably similar - salient apse, inscribed apsidioles and straight walls – the apsidioles and straight walls were enclosed in *pastophoria*, which, with the probable exception of Kourion and Ayios Konon, were unknown on the island.⁵⁹

⁵⁴ Jeffery (1928) 348 suggests a reference to the synagogues of Tiberius at Agios Epiphanius; Shanks (1979) 58 on heart-shaped columns in Galilean and Golan synagogues; Goranson, (1990) 70-71 for Epiphanius and Joseph.

⁵⁵ Equally elusive of explanation are Cypriot inter-apsidal passageways. While single passageways are not uncommon symmetrical passageways occur on Cyprus with an unmatched frequency.

⁵⁶ McKenzie (2007) 270 fig. 449; Eusebius *HE* X.iv.39 and 44 in Lawlor (1957) 423 and 427 describes how Paulinus filled the intercolumniations of the atrium at Tyre ‘with wooden barriers of lattice-work,’ and also enclosed the ‘holy of holies...with a fence of wooden lattice-work’. Mango (1986) 6 identifies the sanctuary at Tyre as ‘in the centre’.

⁵⁷ Megaw (1976c) unpaginated, suggests a relationship with Syrian exedra.

⁵⁸ Megaw (2001) Vol.2 171-180, figs 1-6

⁵⁹ Donceel-Voûte (1988) 308, fig. 128 and (1987) 91, fig. 2; Sodini (1991) 85-87; Deichmann (1941) *Beiblatt* 1/11, 90-1 figs 9-10

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Two of the most notable five-aisled memorial structures were to be found in Palestine: the Martyrium on Golgotha (325-336) [2.35] and the Church of the Nativity in Bethlehem (327-333) [2.36], pendant monuments of the building campaign initiated by Constantine and his mother Helena in the wake of Nicaea. The Golgotha complex consisted of an eastern atrium directly attached to a single-apsed, five-aisled basilica (Martyrium).⁶⁰ To the west was a second atrium enclosing the site of the Crucifixion in its south-east corner, with the aedicule of the Holy Sepulchre as its axial focus. Golgotha and Bethlehem both included centralised structures; that these are absent from Cyprus, may suggest an aversion to buildings associated with Arian patronage.

Coüasnon's reconstruction of the western court on Golgotha shows the Sepulchre in a rectangular recess in the west wall of the quadriporticus constructed in 335 by the Orthodox bishop, Macarius (314-333) under the Orthodox Constantine [2.37]. Around 348 this rectangular layout was swept away by the construction of the circular Anastasis under the Arian patriarch Maximus II (r. 333-50), whose patron was the Arian emperor Constantius II (337-363). Only a year earlier, in 347, the same patriarch and emperor were responsible for a circular church on Mount Sion, which was, in turn, demolished and replaced, barely forty years later, by the Theodosian five-aisled basilica. That a building whose patrons represented one theological position was, in both cases, demolished by the proponents of another, in the same century and arguably in the same street, is striking. Furthermore, the Golden Dome (341), the principal church in Antioch, the see whose unwarranted writ ran in Cyprus *and* Jerusalem, was also circular or octagonal and built under Constantius by the Arian bishop Stephen (?-344). Despite a lack of textual corroboration, it is conceivable that buildings perceived as Arian provided less-than-attractive prototypes for Orthodox patrons. This might explain why late-fifth, early-sixth-century Campanopetra, the most overtly Golgothian structure on Cyprus, did not incorporate a reference to the circular Anastasis, preferring instead, something similar to its predecessor, the square court constructed under Macarius.

⁶⁰ For Constantine's letter to Macarius see Eusebius VC Ch.31 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 134. Finnegan (1969) 164 identifies the letter as the first use of the term basilica in a Christian context.

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2.1.7.i Campanopetra

Built under the patronage of Emperor Zeno (r.474-491), Campanopetra lies 450m to the east of Agios Epiphanius [2.38].⁶¹ It was excavated by Roux between 1965 and 1974 and published in 1998. Including the apses, it is 51.6m long by 28.2m, with a square area of 1638sq.m.⁶² Roux makes a convincing case for a Holy Sepulchre reference, arguing that the square court behind the three apses sheltered a cult focus, possibly centred on a fragment from the True Cross [2.39].⁶³ This hypothesis is given added resonance by Eusebius' description of the setting for the Holy Sepulchre in 339 or earlier as 'a very large space wide open to the fresh air...and enclosed on three sides by long surrounding colonnades,' a description that might also serve for Campanopetra.⁶⁴

Two broad corridors connecting the atria, east and west, and directly attached to the north and south walls of the basilica (but otherwise independent of it) may be a reference to the Holy Sepulchre of the kind Orlandos, Vincent and Davies envisioned from Eusebius' description.⁶⁵ It might, of course be argued that the Martyrium on Golgotha was five-aisled and that Campanopetra was three-aisled [2.40]. However, Roux identifies the marble revetment of the lateral walls at Campanopetra as a fictive representation of a row of piers, hence, a reference to a five-aisled basilica - namely the Martyrium on Golgotha.⁶⁶ The fictive revetment may additionally have referred to the outer corridors which were also revetted, possibly using the same articulation. The

⁶¹ Roux (1998) 235

⁶² Roux (1998) 75

⁶³ Megaw in Runciman and Jeffreys (2006) 394-404 argues for Campanopetra as honouring the relics of Barnabas. Megaw (1974) 68 n.36, proposed a similar liturgy at Campanopetra to the *proskynesis* liturgy recorded for Golgotha. Englezakis (1995), 59 recalls another tradition that a rock from Golgotha was the object of veneration at Campanopetra.

⁶⁴ Eusebius VC 35 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 135-6, 289-90

⁶⁵ Eusebius VC iii.33 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 135-137 describes the site sequentially from west to east without indicating lateral corridors. There are none in the Madaba map or Arculf. Crowfoot (1941) 17 suggests 'Vincent is...probably right in showing the passages either side of the basilica, leading from the first atrium to the second.' See Vincent and Abel (1914) fig.119. For comparative plans see Wistrand (1952) 50 and Coüasnon (1974) 2. For a critique see Wharton (1995) 94-7 who dates the decline of 'classicizing' plans to Corbo (1981) v.I 226, v.II Pl.1 and (1988) 391-422 figs 59-66. For a 'post-classical' plan based on the archaeology see Gibson and Taylor (1994) 75 fig 45

⁶⁶ Roux (1998) 241. Eusebius VC III.37 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 136 describes the Martyrium: 'Round each of the sides extended twin ranges of double colonnades....' Krautheimer (1986) 61 fig. 27A shows outer colonnades raised on tall square bases. Broadly contemporary with Campanopetra, Hagia Sophia in Constantinople (537) deploys a similar fiction revetting the jambs of the tribelon of the ground floor exedra in imitation of its columns.

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fictive revetment inside the basilica, therefore, represented an outside inside, elucidating and anticipating an adjacent but occluded space which there was good reason to advertise as accessing the site's principal *locus sanctus* [2.41-2].

Presenting three-aisled Campanopetra as five-aisled was not only an interior fiction. Roux's reconstruction of the exterior aggregates extra-mural corridors and intra-mural aisles without distinguishing the two [2.43].⁶⁷ Reconstructions of Agios Epiphanius (Stewart) [2.44], and Kourion (Megaw) [2.45] reflect a similar garnering.⁶⁸ In the case of Campanopetra the fictive revetment may also have given an impression of the five aisles in order to correspond with the articulation of the roofs and the façade. This would not merely accord with Eusebius's description of 'churches of spacious dimensions,' but probably constituted, even into the early-sixth century, a preference for scale beyond the requirements of the liturgy and congregational demography.⁶⁹

2.1.7.ii Soloi B

References to the Holy Sepulchre at Soloi B, dated to 'the beginning of the sixth century and certainly before 550,' are altogether more coded.⁷⁰ The site was excavated under des Gagniers and Tinh between 1964 and 1974 and published in 1985. The basilica was 39.95m x 22.88m, giving a floor area of 1444sq.m [2.46].⁷¹ The means of access between the western atrium and the unexcavated area to the east of the basilica was not via outer corridors, but through the aisles.⁷² The east ends of the aisles combine apsidioles against the central apse with straight outer shoulders containing doorways [2.47].⁷³ The implicit corridor suggested by the 'shoulders' recalls the outer corridors sometimes associated with the Martyrium on Golgotha. However, a reference to the vertex marking the site of St Paul's tomb at S.Paolo fuori le mura [2.48-9] is also possible given vestigial walls [2.50-1] projecting eastwards from the apsidioles, suggesting an east court surrounded on three sides by porticoes, with a splayed *locus*

⁶⁷ Roux (1998) 79

⁶⁸ Stewart (2008) III 3.a; Roux (1998) Plan VII

⁶⁹ Eusebius/Lawton *HE* (1957) at II 253; Dagrón (1977) 6

⁷⁰ des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) 1.78

⁷¹ Megaw (2007) 157

⁷² des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) I.52

⁷³ Lambousa had a similar layout with three eastern apses enclosed by a straight wall to the east: see Papageorghiou (1985) 304-5. For five-aisled Ayia Varvara at Amathus see *BCH* 100 (1976) 888-891 and 101 (1977) 763-765

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sanctus directly attached to the exterior of main apse, for which two angled sections of wall, projecting from the apse, together with the layout of the paving, provide the evidence. [2.52-3].⁷⁴

Campanopetra and Soloi appear to have referenced the Holy Sepulchre by providing means of circulation - quasi-corridors inside the lateral walls at Soloi [2.54] and exterior corridors at Campanopetra [2.55]. Both had east ends consisting of a projecting main apse and apsidioles with straight shoulders pierced by portals, evoking a five-aisled basilica despite being three-aisled.

2.1.7.iii Kourion

Fifth-century Kourion was excavated by Megaw between 1974 and 1979 and published in 2007 [2.56]. The basilica was 39.95m by 22.88m with floor area of 914sq.m.⁷⁵ Megaw references the Holy Sepulchre briefly. While there were outer corridors at Kourion there is no evidence that they constructed a system of circulation, despite the presence of an east court and an unidentified focus against its east wall [2.57-8].⁷⁶

2.1.7.iv Chrysopolitissa

Chrysopolitissa was excavated by Papageorghiou between 1971 and 1989 and remains unpublished.⁷⁷ The trapezoidal basilica consisted of seven aisles in a box plan devoid of apsidal projections [2.59]. The bema lay towards the middle of the church and concluded in the east with a free-standing apse [2.60] behind which was an approximately square court accessible from the aisles [2.61-2]. There is, however, no indication of a *locus sanctus*.

2.1.7 Inflation, polyvalence and economy

It would seem that, although some of the earliest Cypriot basilicas had eastern courts, there are no grounds for a substantive reference to the Holy Sepulchre until possibly

⁷⁴ Brandenburg (2004) 285.2; Pallas (1977) 271, fig.189

⁷⁵ Megaw (2007) 157

⁷⁶ For the east court at Kourion and the Holy Sepulchre see Megaw (2007) 30 and 159 n11.

⁷⁷ Papageorghiou (1985) 305-7 fig.2

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Soloi or, more probably, Campanopetra. We can conclude, however, that even when the triapsidal basilica became canonical, probably at the beginning of the fifth century, there remained a preference for varieties of inflationary self-representation in which extra-mural corridors were presented as integral to the core structure. Overdimensioning was certainly a charge levelled at Porphyry's church in Gaza. When he became bishop in 395, the city's Christian population was probably no more than 280 but he justified his enterprise saying that he was building for the future, in which the Lord would so multiply his flock that the church would not be able to hold it.⁷⁸

If Agios Epiphanius and Kourion accommodated 'multiplied flocks,' their flanking corridors, identified by Megaw as *katechumenaia*, may well have been necessary [2.63-4]].⁷⁹ Megaw bases his identification on Eusebius's description of Tyre, which identifies auxiliary rooms directly attached to the basilica as accommodating catechumens.⁸⁰ But even at the height of adult baptism the size of these broad corridors would surely have exceeded demand.⁸¹ At Agios Epiphanius the catechumens could only have reached the '*katechumenia*' through the narthex, there being no direct access from the basilica of the kind described by Eusebius. At Kourion there was no access between the basilica and the southern corridor and only two doorways on the north side which, at no more than 1.10m-wide, would have been inadequate for the swift departure of even a moderate number of retirees.

The weight of scholarly opinion, however, from Mathews in 1971 to Caraher in 2003, rejects the narthex as the location of the *katechumenaion*.⁸² But as well as site evidence, there is good textual evidence which stresses the importance of portals in the drama of exclusion. The earliest reference to the withdrawal of catechumens is Egyptian, probably before 340. According to Dix, '[t]he deacons... proclaim: '[I]et the catechumens depart....' and when these had gone, cried again: 'The doors! The doors!' as a signal to

⁷⁸ Crowfoot (1941) 89 and Chapters 19 and 93 in Mark the Deacon *The Life of Porphyry, Bishop of Gaza* in Hill (1913) 25 and 102

⁷⁹ Megaw (2007) 14-15, 24-27, 158

⁸⁰ Eusebius X.iv.45 in Lawlor (1957) II.427: '...outside the temple... [Paulinus] hath constructed chambers and buildings on either side, very large, the which he hath skilfully joined together to the sides of the royal house, and united with the openings into the central building. Based on the Syrian *Testamentum Domini* (1.19) (post-350), Megaw (2007) 158 n.8 argued for lateral corridors as *katechumenia*.

⁸¹ Trigger (1990) 127: 'There is some evidence that the need to express power through the medium of monumental architecture may be greater during the formative stages....' See Dagron (1977) 6 for the multiplication of city churches which 'excèdent les nécessités du culte.'

⁸² Mathews (1971) 145; Caraher (2003) 102 and n. 159; Mango (1986) 25 n.8, citing *Testamentum* I.19, identifies the 'house for the catechumens' as the narthex.

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those of their number...who guarded the doors, to close them and lock them against all intrusion.⁸³ Three hundred years later, Chapter 15 of the *Mystagogia* of Maximus the Confessor (628-30) describes the '[t]he closing of the doors which takes place after the sacred reading of the holy Gospel and the dismissal of the catechumens.'⁸⁴ The classicist and theologian Allatius (1586-1669), understood the narthex as 'the place for those [monks not in orders and women] not permitted...to enter the interior of the church while the Divine Liturgy is celebrated.'⁸⁵ Hence, despite current opinion, the five western doors at Agios Epiphanius and the three at Kourion reinforce the likelihood that the narthex did indeed constitute the primary 'house for the catechumens' identified by the *Testamentum domini*.⁸⁶ If the nartheces of Agios Epiphanius and Kourion served as *katechumenaia*, what purpose did their broad outer corridors serve? *Faute de mieux*, the possibility must remain that they were intended to promote size in excess of congregational demography.

Characteristic of this 'inflation' is the number of readings early Cypriot basilicas permit. It could be argued that Agios Epiphanius was an eleven-aisled complex. Exclude the '*katechumenaia*' and the inner corridors, and the basilica can be identified as seven-aisled. If the narrow aisles of the interior can be identified as intra-mural versions of the extra-mural corridors at Campanopetra and Kourion then the interior of Agios Epiphanius might be understood as the five-aisled basilica identified by Delvoye.⁸⁷ The combination of pier and demi-shaft defining these passages and the use of pilasters in the corridors at Kourion and Agios Epiphanius, suggest a change of register between columns as signifiers of a more or less sacred space and piers and pilasters as identifying something more utilitarian.

Identifying the function of aisles is hampered by lack of evidence for a sustained pattern of use. For Krautheimer,

⁸³ Dix (1945) 42

⁸⁴ Maximus the Confessor in Berthold (1985) 201, 205

⁸⁵ Allatius in Cutler (1969) V.7

⁸⁶ *Testamentum Domini* in Sperry-White (Nottingham 1991) 1.19 at 46, 'Let a church have a house for the catechumens...It should not be separate from the church, but such that as they enter and are in it they may hear the readings and spiritual hymns of praise.'

⁸⁷ Delvoye (1978) 313

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one of the major problems in religious architecture during the fourth-century was...the necessity of finding sufficient accommodation within a single area for at least two and, at times, three liturgical functions – the celebration of the Divine Office...the presentation of offerings...and...the veneration of ‘memoria’....⁸⁸

At Agios Epiphanius the ambulatory lining the interior walls may have served as access for the faithful venerating the saint’s tomb; and the wall passages linking the apse, apsidioles and the rectangular recesses of the east wall may have been allocated to the officiating clergy. The Eucharist, then, would have been reserved to an independent bema west of the eastern transverse aisle. Evidence for multiple use comes from the *Vita*, Chapter 38, in which Epiphanius ‘does not take part in the chanting, but sits or stands apart in prayer, in a place where he cannot be seen by the monks. At the end of the liturgy Epiphanius appears and the monks greet each other.’⁸⁹

Epiphanius’ tomb was almost certainly located in the south central aisle, while at Campanopetra the north aisle probably served for the circulation of pilgrims venerating a *locus sanctus* in its east end [2.65-66].⁹⁰ It is probable, then, that the nave in both cases would have been congregational. At Chrysopolitissa, on the other hand, the closure screens framing the nave suggest that it functioned liturgically, the aisles being reserved to the faithful. It seems that, in later fourth-century Cyprus, local diversity had yet to be circumscribed by the economies of Orthodoxy. Nicaea began the construction of just such an ‘economy,’ but it was Constantinople in 381 which proved decisive in constraining ‘diversity’ and generating a new wave of church building which was to have a profound effect in Cyprus.

⁸⁸ Krautheimer (1971) 64. The aisles of some larger basilicas may simply have served as symmetrical makeweights.

⁸⁹ *Vita* 38 in Rapp (1991) II.233

⁹⁰ In the north apsidiole at Campanopetra is a small sarcophagus with libation holes, set against a revetment in which red predominates in contrast to the Proconnesian revetment in the south apsidiole. Roux (1998) 149 notes fragments of Sangarios stone or Bithynian marble revetment attached to the socle supporting the sarcophagus in which red also predominates. The monk who authored the sixth-century *Laudatio* of Barnabas describes his tomb as ‘to the right of the altar,’ the position of the *mensa martyris* at Agios Barnabas if he was facing east and the sarcophagus at Campanopetra if he was officiating facing west. Jeffery (1928) 346 identifies a ‘tomb built against the [north wall of the north corridor at Agios Epiphanius], measuring 16 ft. 3 ins by 4 ft. 9 in. This tomb although very well preserved was found quite empty. At n.2 he adds, ‘Can this have been the tomb of the Archbishop...?’

2.2. Sion and Agios Epiphanius and Second Ecumenical Council

2.2.1 Theodosius and Epiphanius

This section covers the last twenty years of the fourth century. The discussion begins with two powerful allegiances, firstly the mutual bond between Epiphanius and Theodosius, which the *Vita* clearly promoted, and secondly, Cypriot commitment to the Jerusalem project.

Chapter 99 of the *Vita Epiphanii* describes Epiphanius' first mission to Constantinople in 380 to cure Theodosius of an illness of the feet.⁹¹ The Emperor treats Epiphanius as a friend and '...rejoices when he sees Epiphanius, but comports himself as Epiphanius' equal.'⁹² Chapter 100 of the *Vita* goes so far as to portray Epiphanius as the spiritual father of Theodosius.⁹³ Chapters 85-92 re-inforce the intimacy. Arriving in Rome in 382, Epiphanius is received with 'great honour.' He heals Theodosius' daughter, Prokliane, and baptizes his sons Arcadius and Honorius.⁹⁴ The departure for Rome may account for his absence from Constantinople in 381. Nevertheless, scholars have argued for his contributions to two of the Council's great achievements: a new impetus in the resolution of the status of the Holy Spirit and the re-formulation of the Creed. For Torrence, 'Epiphanius did more than any other to clear away problems that had arisen in the doctrine of the Holy Trinity and to prepare the ground for the ecumenical consensus that was registered in the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed.'⁹⁵ According to Kyrris, the Creed agreed by the Council was essentially the creed concluding Epiphanius' *Ancoratus* of 374 and was either laid before the Council by Epiphanius himself, or by one of the four Cypriot bishops attending.'⁹⁶ Furthermore there is the evidence of Basil's Letter CCLVIII to Epiphanius:

⁹¹ According to Philostorgios, *HE* XI.2 in Amidon (2007) 145 Theodosius suffered from dropsy.

⁹² Rapp (1991) I.176, 185; II.176

⁹³ Rapp (1991) 1.177

⁹⁴ Rapp (1991) I, 180; II 157-165

⁹⁵ Torrence (2001) 184-5. Smith and Wace (1880) II.149 say of Epiphanius that 'the confession of faith found at the end of his *Ancoratus*...agrees almost word for word with the Constantinopolitan formula.'

⁹⁶ Epiphanius *Ancoratus* 120 in Hörmann (1919) 180-2; Kyrris (1985) 165 and (1987) 101

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...we can add nothing to the Creed of Nicaea...except for the glorification of the Holy Spirit, and this only because our fathers mentioned this topic incidentally, since the question regarding Him had not yet been raised at the time.⁹⁷

The principal evidence for a bond between bishop and Emperor is the *Vita* and the so-called *Letter to Theodosius*. Although the first may be a mid-fifth-century fiction and the second a forgery of 754-787, they may nevertheless represent residual evidence for a real alliance.⁹⁸ The *Panarion* identified only one heresy on Cyprus, the *Vita* increased the number to six, almost certainly to emphasise Theodosius' intervention as a demonstration of their intimacy.

There were...in the land of Cyprus many...heresies...Concerning these Epiphanius wrote a letter to Theodosius asking him to drive them from the island by imperial decree...When the emperor had received Epiphanius' letter he issued the following rescript: 'If anyone does not obey Father Epiphanius, the bishop of the land of Cyprus...let him leave the island...But those who are willing to repent and to recognize the common father...shall remain on the island and shall be taught by the common father.'⁹⁹

One canon of the Theodosian Council may have been particularly welcome in Cyprus. Canon III christened and even Christianised New Rome, according it 'the prerogative of honour after the Bishop of Rome,' thus relegating Antioch (and Alexandria) which had formerly occupied that position.¹⁰⁰ Despite Constantinople's new status, it was not the buildings of the capital which were influential in Cyprus but the monuments of Jerusalem, the city identified by Dagron as Constantine's Christian capital.¹⁰¹ For Epiphanius the Jerusalemite *locus* was quite specific - the Cenacle on Sion [2.67]. The affirmation of the Trinity in Canon V (possibly a later interpolation in or after 382) together with the Nicene-Constantinopolitan creed revalidated the site which bore witness to the descent of the Holy Spirit at Pentecost on an eminence which epitomized 381 as Golgotha epitomized 325.

⁹⁷ Basil of Caesarea IV 35-47 in Deferrari (1961-2) at 41

⁹⁸ Rapp (1991) I.186

⁹⁹ *Vita* 17.59 in Pohlsander (1999) 17

¹⁰⁰ Tanner (1990) I. 32

¹⁰¹ Dagron (1974) 389. For evidence that the title 'New Rome' may have predated 381 see Sozomen 7.9 (2010 reprint) 288 and Socrates 1.16 (2009 reprint) 46

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2.2.2 Bi-partite Salamis and bi-partite Jerusalem

Agios Epiphanius was exceptional amongst early Cypriot basilicas in having no eastern court. Hence, its extra-mural corridors, whatever their function, appear not to have been identified with a system of circulation. This alone removes Agios Epiphanius from identification with the Holy Sepulchre complex. Furthermore, the strength of allusion to the Holy Sepulchre at Campanopetra suggests that it may have served as a complement to whatever may have been the context of Agios Epiphanius, given that it is difficult to see why two buildings only 450m apart should duplicate the same reference.¹⁰²

2.2.3 Jerusalem: a bipartite and tripartite capital

In the *Panarion* Epiphanius makes reference to the *Book of Jubilees*.¹⁰³ This second-century BC Hebraic-Pharisaic text identified Mount Sion as 'the centre of the navel of the earth.'¹⁰⁴ It also identified Jerusalem and Sion as distinct, despite their proximity.¹⁰⁵

And Sion and Jerusalem will be holy.¹⁰⁶

Hebrews 12:22 also recognised a bipartite Jerusalem, 'But ye are come unto Mount Sion, *and* the city of the living God, the heavenly Jerusalem.'¹⁰⁷ In Finkelstein's reconstruction of the early Jewish grace, the *Birkat ha-mazon*, Sion is construed as a pendant to the temple.

Have mercy, O Lord, our God...on Thy city Jerusalem, on Thy Temple and Thy dwelling-place and on Zion Thy resting place...¹⁰⁸

¹⁰² For *basilicae geminatae* see Davies (1957) 173

¹⁰³ Epiphanius III 39.6.1 in Williams (2009) I.xxv and 280

¹⁰⁴ Charles (2010) VIII: v.19 74

¹⁰⁵ C.f. Theodosius in Wilkinson (2002b) 107

¹⁰⁶ *The Book of Jubilees* I: 27-8 in Charles (1917) 40. For Sion as omphalos see Alexander (1997) 147-149 and (1999) 104-8. For Sion or Jerusalem as a 'centrifugal force' and 'a visible sign of Jewish nationality' see Askowith (1947) 225

¹⁰⁷ My italics.

¹⁰⁸ Finkelstein (1928/9) 216

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Although Eusebius rejected the concept of Jerusalem as the Holy City - doubtless to preserve the pre-eminence of his own see which had jurisdiction over Jerusalem - he nevertheless distinguished between two of the city's high points 'Jerusalem that is above...and the mount Sion the heavenly mount.'¹⁰⁹ Cyril of Jerusalem's sixteenth *Catechetical Lecture* (348) on the subject of the Holy Spirit, also distinguishes the two but in terms of the second and third persons of the Trinity.

[I]t were most fitting, that as we discourse concerning Christ and Golgotha, upon this Golgotha, so also we should speak concerning the Holy Ghost in the Upper Church [the cenacle]: yet he who descended there jointly partakes of Him who was crucified here, we here speak concerning him who descended there.¹¹⁰

Post-381 the differences would have been more explicit, but so too would their equivalence and interdependence.

The city was a problematic concept for the followers of the *paysan* Jesus, and Jerusalem, the site of his crucifixion, was more problematic than most. For Chrysostom 'If you are a Christian, no earthly city is yours...'¹¹¹ Little wonder that he insisted that the survival of the church *in* the city depended on separation *from* it. The Holy Sepulchre complex was the real and idealized city which superseded Aelia Capitolina. For Eusebius it 'was the New Jerusalem built...facing the famous Jerusalem of old, which after the bloody murder of the Lord had been overthrown in utter devastation...'¹¹²

2.2.4 Mount Sion

The alternative to the Christian city-in-and-against-the-city was the Christian city on a site of erasure. Eusebius describes the preparations for the construction of the New Jerusalem:

the Emperor gave...orders that all the rubble of stones and timbers from the demolitions should be taken and dumped a long way from the site...that the site should be excavated to a great

¹⁰⁹ Eusebius *HE* X.iv.68-71 in Oulton (1957) II 443

¹¹⁰ Cyril of Jerusalem *CL* 16.4 in Parker (1838) 205. For an alternative translation see Finegan (1969) 148

¹¹¹ Chrysostom in Stephens (1889) 456

¹¹² Eusebius *VC* III 33 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 135

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depth and the pavement should be carried away with the rubble a long distance outside, because it was stained with demonic bloodshed.¹¹³

A less-manufactured sense of erasure pervades Epiphanius' description of Sion. In *De Mensuris et Ponderibus* (392) Epiphanius describes the sole synagogue which remained standing 'until the time of...Constantine [as] like a booth in a vineyard.'¹¹⁴ The Bordeaux Pilgrim arrived in Palestine in 333 and visited Sion before the Holy Sepulchre, describing it as 'ploughed and sown.'¹¹⁵ In his *Catechetical Lecture* 16:18, Cyril describes the Mount as '...left as a cottage in a vineyard, as a lodge in a garden of cucumbers, as a besieged city.'¹¹⁶ Sion, as desolate as the Temple Mount, was similarly invested with a Biblical past, having been raised by David as the principal city of the Kingdom.¹¹⁷

The basilica built on Sion in the final decade of the fourth century was rapidly embellished with a compendious topography of *loca sancta*. In the early fifth-century Hippolytus of Thebes identified Sion as the site of The Last Supper.¹¹⁸ The early-sixth century *Breviarium* of Eutropius described the crown of thorns '[i]n the centre of the basilica' and the seventh-century Latin version of Pseudo-Evodius (before 565) sets the *Koimesis* on Sion.¹¹⁹ The Piacenza Pilgrim (c.570) says the basilica 'contains many remarkable things, including the corner stone which the Bible tells us 'was rejected by the builders' [2.68].¹²⁰

Adomnan's account of 'This apostolic Church [which] is constructed of stone...[and] stands...on the summit of Mount Sion,' was written before 688.¹²¹ Based on the

¹¹³ Eusebius VC III 27 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 133

¹¹⁴ PG 43, 237-293; Dean (1935) 30

¹¹⁵ Wilkinson (2002a) 30-1; Kühnel (1987) 45

¹¹⁶ Taylor (1993) 21; Eusebius in Ferrar (1920) 2.141

¹¹⁷ 2 Sam 5:9, 1-10; 1 Chron 8.28. According the Zachariah's vision 'I God am coming back to Sion and will dwell in the middle of Jerusalem.'

¹¹⁸ For Sion see Hippolytus of Thebes IV 1-8 in Diekamp (1898) 18-25

¹¹⁹ Wilkinson (2002b) 209 for the description of Epiphanius the Monk, (before 692) who arrived via Cyprus; 219-20 for Bede (702-3); 241 for Hugelburc (724-5); 391 for an account in the anonymous *Life of Constantine*, also 350-355. Shoemaker (1999) 271 identifies only 'a single place' in which the Apostles assembled with Mary 'for the breaking of bread.' According to Diekamp (1898) 107 the first mention of Mary at Sion is Sophronios *Anacreonticon* XX 63-66 and the first mention of her death as the drawing accompanying *De locis sanctis*; Meehan (1958) 59 n.1 and 63 (18)

¹²⁰ Wilkinson (2002b) 140

¹²¹ Wilkinson, (2002b) 179

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descriptions of the Frankish bishop Arculf, who visited Jerusalem in 670, Adomnan's box-plan included the site of the Last Supper top left, Pentecost top right, the *Koimesis* bottom right and the pillar of the Flagellation bottom left. This is clearly schematic because Jerome, writing in 404, described the column of the flagellation 'holding up the porch of the church'¹²² The only 'architectural' features in Adomnan's drawing are a doorway in the south wall – hence, with its back to the city - and square projections west and south. The western projection is the stone on which Christ stood at the flagellation and the southern commemorates the stoning of Stephen. Beyond this conceptual Sion, what can be identified of the actual buildings?

2.2.5 The Sion Basilica

And the 15th of the same month [September] was the dedication of the holy and glorious Sion, which is the mother of all the churches that had been founded by the apostles, which the emperor, Theodosius the Great, has built, enlarged and glorified and in which the Holy Spirit had come down on the holy day of Pentecost.¹²³

Taylor dates the Sion basilica to c.336, but Balderstone argues for 390, when it replaced the circular church of 347.¹²⁴ Ovadiah's plan shows a five-aisled basilica raised on 32 columns with a central and fully projecting apse corresponding to the nave, two lightly projecting apsidioles corresponding to the inner aisles and straight walls corresponding to the outer aisles [2.69]. Germano's plan shows five-aisles divided by 68 columns with a single apse [2.70].¹²⁵

¹²² Jerome *Epistle* 108.9 in Hilberg (1961) 15-20

¹²³ van Esbroeck (1975) 314-315

¹²⁴ Taylor (1993) 211 suggests 333-348 and that the final synagogue disappeared from the Mount by 337. 'It is therefore logical to propose that this synagogue was flattened by the erection of the basilica of the Holy Sion about the year 336.' At 213 she argues against the construction of the basilica under John II and for construction under Maximus (r.333-c350); Balderstone (2007) 14, 55-6 dates the Sion basilica to 390 as the successor to a centralised structure of 347; Pixner (1990) 31 understands Theodosian Sion as Octagonal.

¹²⁵ Ovadiah (1970) 89-90 Pl. 38 fig. 77; Ovadiah confirmed *pers.comm* (17.10.2009) that despite the plan published by Germano 'The Ancient Church of the Apostles: Revisiting Jerusalem's Cenacle and David's Tomb,' 1-28 at 21, figs 11, 12, www.bibarch.com (27.10.2011), the plan published in his *Corpus* had not been superseded. Vincent and Abel (1914) I.421-481 fig.168 show Sion with a single apse and II.Pl.49 shows Sion with three apses; for Gethsemane see I.301-308, 1007-1013 and II.Pl.88

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The eye-witness account of an Armenian pilgrim, c.625, gives Sion's dimensions as 100 by 70 ells or 114m by 80m, giving an enormous 9120 sq.m.¹²⁶ He describes 'eighty columns joined by arches,' just short of an estimated eighty-two for Agios Epiphanius.¹²⁷ Renard, who excavated Sion in 1898-1899, gives a more probable estimate of its dimensions as 60m by 40 m (2400 square metres), almost exactly the dimensions of Agios Epiphanius at 58m by 42m (2436 square metres) [2.71].¹²⁸

There is every reason to suppose that the equivalence suggested by Cyril's description of Golgotha and Sion in 347-348 achieved a new resonance after 381, casting the Holy Sepulchre and Sion - two buildings now sharing a common size and proportion - as pendant structures. Dates for Sion coalesce around the early 390s and if, as van Esbroeck suggests, the consecration took place in 394, Epiphanius, a cleric of international standing already in Jerusalem on other business, may well have attended.¹²⁹

It seems likely that Epiphanius knew the Sion basilica and that he built a basilica on Cyprus of remarkably similar size, proportion and sub-division. Given the lack of consensus for the layout of Sion's east end, other Jerusalemite buildings post-381, notably Gethsemane and S.Mary Probatca, are so close in the layout of their east ends to the core arrangement at Agios Epiphanius that they may provide the template for Sion too.¹³⁰

2.2.6 Complementary structures

Megaw and Delvoye identified tri-apsidal basilicas as canonically Cypriot and Megaw asked, 'was it an importation by Epiphanius himself, and in that case from Palestine, his homeland?'¹³¹ What, then, is the evidence? The tri-apsidal east ends at Probatca and

¹²⁶ Wilkinson (2002b) 165

¹²⁷ The later *Commemoratorium* of c.808 gives a measurement of 39 dexteri long and 26 across, Wilkinson (2002b) 256

¹²⁸ Renard (1900) 17 refers to the form of the east end as 'mutmass' because the German excavators had no access to it. For competing theories on the structure, Taylor (1993) 211-220 and 218

¹²⁹ van Esbroeck (1984) 99-134, for Sion see 107-125

¹³⁰ Finnegan (1969) 144-5, 104-108

¹³¹ Megaw (1997) 348; Delvoye (1972) 20. Margalit (1990) 322 states that 'Our survey shows that the tri-apsidal churches are more frequent...in Palestine, than any other adjacent province,

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Gethsemane consisted of a main apse that sprang not from the east wall but from some way inside it, accompanied by inscribed apsidioles, exactly the tri-apsidal configuration at Agios Epiphanius [2.72-4]. It is probable that the form was specifically Jerusalemite despite Balderstone's recent identification of the Civic and East basilicas at Pella, both following the pattern identified at Probatika and Gethsemane, as Theodosian [2.75]. The excavation reports date the two Pella basilicas to the fifth- and sixth-centuries and they may, therefore, represent a reflex from the capital, perhaps commemorating the so-called flight to Pella when Christians sought refuge there on the eve of the Jewish War (66-70).¹³² Epiphanius refers to the flight twice in in the *Panarion* (374-5), but the fullest account is given in Chapter 15 of the *De Mensuris et Ponderibus* (392)

For when the city was about to be seized by the Romans, all the disciples were forewarned by an angel to migrate from the city...After they emigrated, they settled in Pella...across the Jordan...But after Jerusalem was destroyed, they returned...and performed great signs.¹³³

Pixner argued that one of the 'great signs' performed by the returning Christians was the reconstruction of the Cenacle to which the Sion basilica was subsequently attached.¹³⁴ Is it possible that fifth and sixth-century Pella referenced this 'great sign' by repeating the signature east end of the basilica attached to the Cenacle in the final decade of the fourth century?

2.2.7 Probatika and Gethsemane

Excavated between 1957 and 1962, S.Mary Probatika was three-aisled and 45m long by 18m wide.¹³⁵ The basilica at Gethsemane, excavated in 1920, was 26m long by 17.5m

an indication that Palestine was the focal point for the construction of tri-apsidal churches.' See Margalit (1989) 154-155; 157-159 for a list of Palestinian tri-apsidal churches.

¹³² Balderstone (2007) 14, 56, fig. 10. The Civic basilica at Pella is in three phases of which two and three show a projecting apse with inscribed apsidioles. R.H.Smith dates this to a 6thc remodelling; McNicoll dates the East Church to the fifth century; McNicoll (1992) 150 fig.22, at 151 (Civic); 154 fig.23, 160 (East Church). For the flight to Pella see Eusebius *HE* III.5.3-5 in Lake (1959) I.201

¹³³ Epiphanius 15 in Dean (1935), 30-31; Epiphanius II 29.7,7 and 30.2,7 in Williams (2009) at I.129 and 132. Koester (1989) 95 suggests that Epiphanius drew on a source independent of Eusebius

¹³⁴ Pixner (1990) 26 and (1997) 22-31, 64-67

¹³⁵ Probatika is generally assigned to Theodosius II although Theodosius I seems more probable: see Balderstone (2007) 17, 39, 57; Finegan (1969) 142-145; Duprez (1970) 54-56

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wide. It is first mentioned in Eusebius' *Onomasticon* (333) as a place 'in which even now the faithful are zealous in offering prayer', although the Bordeaux Pilgrim, writing in the same year, leaves no record of it.¹³⁶ Egeria, who was in Palestine between 381-384, mentions 'this graceful church,' which may have been under construction at the time, because Jerome, in his translation of Eusebius' *Onomasticon* (c 390), adds 'where now a church has been built,' suggesting recent construction.¹³⁷ Wilkinson argues for a tighter time-frame, between the accession of Theodosius in 379 and the departure of Egeria from Jerusalem 384.¹³⁸

Delvoye recognised the similarity between Gethsemane and Agios Epiphanius and suggested that Epiphanius knew the basilica from his stay in Jerusalem in 393-4.¹³⁹ However, Sion seems the more likely model. Egeria describes Sion as it would have been in 381-384, i.e. immediately post-381. Her account centres on two *loca sancta*, the Cenacle and 'the throne of James.'¹⁴⁰ In the *Panarion*, written only a few years before, Epiphanius makes exactly the same connection. He describes how 'the Spirit settled on each of them, and they spoke of God's wonders in tongues', and immediately follows it with a reference to 'the saints who shared James' throne,' in the specific context of a succession list in which he 'subjoin[s] their successive episcopates one by one, beginning with the episcopate of James.'¹⁴¹ James, according to Eusebius, 'was the first to receive from the Saviour and His apostles the episcopacy of the Jerusalem church.'¹⁴² Cyril's translation of James' remains to Sion in 351 would have underlined the apostolicity of his own see, in support of a claim against the jurisdiction of Caesarea and, hence, Antioch. Cyprus made the same claim against Antioch, also on

¹³⁶ Taylor and Freeman-Granville (2003) 45; Wilkinson (2002a) 38, 39 fig. 16 and (2002b) 305; Finegan (1969) 107-8 fig.133; Vincent and Abel (1914) I. Probatia, figs LXXV-VI; Gethsemane LXXXVIII; vol. II Probatia 669-677; Gethsemane 328-330 fig.143 301-308, 1007-1013; II Pl.88

¹³⁷ Jerome *Liber Locorum* in Taylor and Freeman-Granville (2003) 45.

¹³⁸ Wilkinson (2002b) 305

¹³⁹ Delvoye (1976) 12: 'Le chevet avec une abside médiane semi-circulaire saillante et une abside inscrite à l'extrémité des collatéraux intérieurs se retrouve, au cours de la seconde moitié du IVe s., peut-être sous le règne de Théodose I, en Palestine dans la basilique à 3 nefs de Gethsemane...' See also Ovadia (1970) Pl. 35, fig. 73, 84-5; Balderstone (2007) 14. Epiphanius may have had further reason to be in Palestine in 392/3 because, according to Theophanes (Mango and Scott (1997) 112), writing at the beginning of the ninth century but probably reflecting an earlier tradition, 'the relics of the prophets Habakkuk and Micah were found...in two villages in the district of Eleutheropolis.'

¹⁴⁰ Wilkinson (2002a) 88; Eusebius *HE* III.5.2 in Lake (1959) I.199. According to Ehrhardt (1953) 64-5 Hegessippus regarded James as *vicarius Christi*.

¹⁴¹ Epiphanius V 46 (60) 19.4. and 19.7-9 in Williams (1987) II 239

¹⁴² Eusebius *HE* II.23 in Lake (1959) I.168-9; Eusebius *HE* VII.19 in Oulton (1957) II.176-77

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the basis of apostolicity, Barnabas having been its first bishop.¹⁴³ The transfer of the Jerusalem bishopric from the Martyrion to Sion, presumably sometime after Cyril's death in 386, would have added further status to a site which, for Epiphanius, was already rich in significance.¹⁴⁴

2.2.8 The Theological position

In *Sacred Power and Sacred Space*, Kilde describes how with '[t]he development of the triple apse by the eighth century...builders incorporated the new influential symbol of the Trinity into the physical plan of the church.'¹⁴⁵ Megaw made the same identification in respect of fifth-century Cyprus, suggesting that three apses 'symbolize[d] the Christian trinity.'¹⁴⁶ The tri-apsidal east end was absent from Constantinian churches and its first appearance under Theodosius can be directly related to the reflex from the Second Ecumenical Council.

2.2.8.i Agios Epiphanius as evidence

If the tri-apsidal plan was imported by Epiphanius, we might expect it to be a significant feature of the only structure with which he can be specifically identified.¹⁴⁷ Clearly the inscribed apsidioles at Salamis formed a triad with the projecting main apse, but how might its multi-aisled interior be understood as tri-partite?¹⁴⁸

At Kourion the two rows of twelve columns dividing the nave from the aisles were aligned transversely with the pilasters in the extra-mural corridors and at Campanopetra two rows of eleven columns were aligned with the revetment décor of

¹⁴³ According to Erikson (1991) 93 the term autocephaly was not used until Theodore the Reader's *HE* (c.540).

¹⁴⁴ Diekamp (1898) 96 suggests that the earliest reference to the 'mother of all the churches' is Epiphanius' *De Mensuris* 14. 18-10. The pilgrim Theodosius writes of 'Holy Sion which is the Mother of All the Churches:' see Wilkinson (2002b) 107 and Cyril of Jerusalem XVI.4 in Finegan (1969) 148. For the transfer of the bishopric see Armstrong (1974) 8

¹⁴⁵ Kilde (2008) 57

¹⁴⁶ Megaw (1997) 348

¹⁴⁷ des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) 53 identify a projecting apse with inscribed apsidioles as fourth-century.

¹⁴⁸ Delvoye (1972) 18; (1976) 12; Megaw (1997) 348; Ovadiah (1970) 84-5, Pl.35, 73. Cypriot inscribed apsidioles continued into the sixth and seventh centuries: Peyia (Megaw (1995), fig. 7; (1974) fig. E); Synchrise (Chatzchristophe (1997) 277-383 fig 2) and Kalavassos-Kopetra, Sirmata and Area II; (Rautman (2003) fig. 3.8, 3.38)

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the lateral walls, identified by Roux as *trompe l'oeil* piers, with, as we have seen, a corresponding décor in the north and south corridors.¹⁴⁹ Hence, there would have been a transverse alignment at both sites embracing the central nave, inner aisles and outer corridors in a unifying quinquupartite grid. Transverse alignment is evident in the layouts of all the five-aisled basilicas so far referenced - Antinoopolis, Pbow, Soueida, Bethlehem, the Martyrium and Sion - as well as Old St Peter's in Rome [2.76].¹⁵⁰ There is no evidence that Epiphanius knew Soueida; the evidence that he knew Antinoopolis and Pbow is speculative, but he may well have known their predecessors and prototypes. The remaining examples, however, were the principal churches in cities that Epiphanius is known to have visited, and it is inconceivable that, in the years preceding the construction of his own church, he would have been unaware of their major characteristics, amongst which was the strict transversal alignment of structural supports. No such alignment exists at Agios Epiphanius, where thirteen columns divide the central nave from the aisles and fourteen columns divide the flanking aisles.¹⁵¹ Why then did Epiphanius abandon the simplest and strongest way of supporting a roof over a wide span evident in Christendom's most prestigious buildings?

2.2.8.ii Discrepant intervals

...in the earliest churches in Cyprus the use of spolia for their columns and their capitals was virtually universal. The disastrous earthquakes of the fourth century must have endowed the island with an inexhaustible supply of re-usable architecture of both limestone and marble.¹⁵²

Had Epiphanius used *spoliata* marble columns, the discrepancy between the number of columns in the nave and the aisles might be accounted for by availability. But he chose materials which were ostensibly more versatile - limestone *spoliata* drums acquired from the forum. These were rendered or, probably at the east end, revetted in *opus sectile*. [2.77]¹⁵³ Therefore, any mismatching or shortfall could have been concealed. However, the evidence suggests an elective discrepancy, possibly with the intention of

¹⁴⁹ Roux (1998) 241

¹⁵⁰ S. Paolo fuori le mura was not begun before 384, three years after Epiphanius left Rome.

¹⁵¹ For visits to Jerusalem see *Vita*, Ch.45, 55; Rapp (1991) II. 107, 122

¹⁵² Megaw (2001) 171-180 at 172

¹⁵³ Michaelides (1987b) No 48. 42-3. The imbricated motif was assembled from *crustae* in three colours framed by a light coloured listel and then a dark colour fascia. The treatment may belong to the original construction or the sixth century refurbishment that involved a re-flooring in *opus sectile*. Also Megaw (1974) 67 fig 6; (1976b) 20 fig 36; Asemakopoulou-Atzaka (1978) 73, c.f. pls VI c, XII c, d, VIIIc

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making a tripartite reading more explicit [2.78]. Stewart's reconstruction of the transverse section of the building supports this hypothesis [2.79].¹⁵⁴ Each pair of aisles was of equal height and width and accessed by twin portals also of equal height and width and covered by a single pent roof.¹⁵⁵ Hence, the aisles constituted twinned porticoes (*geminis porticibus*), comparable to, for example, the aisles of Old St Peter's in Rome, the Martyrium [2.80-1] and Sion.¹⁵⁶ Furthermore, the width of narrow outer-aisles at Agios Epiphanius added to the width of the double aisles gives a measurement of 11m, exactly the width of the nave – a tripartite template not evident at the other major basilicas Epiphanius might have known, with the exception of Sion.

In the sixth-century, implicitly tri-partite Agios Epiphanius became an accomplished fact when the inter-aisle colonnades were demolished [2.82]. Accepting Tinh's dating of sometime before 550 for Soloi B, and given a similarity of plan, we might assume that the changes at Agios Epiphanius belong to the same period.¹⁵⁷ According to a sixth-century inscription at Chrysopolitissa, Bishop Sergius reduced the number of aisles there from seven to five, emphasising a tripartite core by concluding the nave and the two inner aisles with apses and the outer aisles with straight walls, repeating the arrangement at Soloi B and Salamis [2.83].

2.2.8.iii Tri-apsidal east ends and the Trinity

Did the emphasis on a core structure of three aisles each terminating in an apse, have a symbolic or allegorical intent? Given Epiphanius' vehement condemnation of Origen's allegorical method, it is surprising to find that the eighty heresies listed in his *Panarion* represented a numerical allegory on the Song of Songs 6:8-9: 'There are threescore queens, and fourscore concubines, and virgins without number. My dove, my undefiled, is but one.'¹⁵⁸ As Young commented 'Epiphanius had to produce the number eighty...' In order to do so '[s]ome distinct groups are conflated [and] some heresies

¹⁵⁴ Stewart (2008) II 342

¹⁵⁵ Stewart (2008) II.3a

¹⁵⁶ For Paulinus of Nola's use of the term see Kelly (2004) 452 n.34

¹⁵⁷ des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) 78. Megaw (1981) 250 argues that Philon was active c.400 and was probably the founder of Agios Philon. For Philon ordained by Epiphanius, see Delehay (1907) 243

¹⁵⁸ For Epiphanius' attack on Origen's allegorising see IV 43 (63) 44 (64) in Williams (1994) II.128-137

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appear to have been created out of minor allusions.¹⁵⁹ While *De Mensuris et Ponderibus* is often thoroughly matter-of-fact, in Chapter 30 Epiphanius writes of ‘measures...appropriate for the spiritual contemplation.’ He identifies three as ‘the sacred measure’ and how ‘three measures’ summed up in one ‘showed them the equality of essence in the Holy Trinity...For in the measure there is a Trinity.’¹⁶⁰ There was clearly a difference between his use of arithmetic for the matter-of-fact, and number as an extra-linguistic vocabulary of signs. It is interesting that in Letter 258 Basil cautions Epiphanius against arithmetic’s cultic taint:

When the Lord taught us the doctrine of Father, Son and Holy Spirit, he did not make arithmetic part of this gift! He did not say, ‘In the first, second or third’ or ‘In one two or three’...There is one God and Father, one Only-Begotten Son, and one Holy Spirit...we will not let ignorant arithmetic lead us to polytheism.¹⁶¹

Further in the same letter, Basil, who understands *ousia* as the Trinitarian entity and *hypostasis* as its numerical corollary, writes,

It has given great comfort to my soul that, in addition to your other right and accurate statements in theology, you should acknowledge the necessity of stating that the hypostases are three.

An earlier reference to the relationship of architecture and the Trinity appears in the *Testamentum Domini* l. 19 of c.450: ‘Let a church be thus: with three entries in type of the Trinity.’¹⁶² The *Testamentum* makes no mention of apses, perhaps because it was composed either in Syria or Asia Minor, where the norm was a single apse, corresponding to the nave, and rectangular *pastophoria* corresponding to the aisles. The central apses at Agios Epiphanius, Soloi and Kourion were ‘empty’ because the bema was an independent element at the eastern end of the nave. A main apse free of liturgical function would be available to function as sign, and, combined with two apsidioles, might well be understood as ‘in type of the Trinity’ and hence as a visual-spatial equivalent of a theological concept.

¹⁵⁹ Young (1983) 138; (1982) 201-2

¹⁶⁰ Dean (1935) 40, 49. According to the Syriac biographer of Daniel the Stylite his the column had three drums ‘in honour of the Trinity’ : see Dawes and Baynes (1996) 5

¹⁶¹ St.Basil in Pruche (1968) 403

¹⁶² *Testamentum Domini* in Mango (1986) 25. For a description of a five-aisled basilica with three portals see Eusebius VC 3.37 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 136

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Arithmetic may, however, have been more germane to the transference, presumably by number, of the principal dimensions of Sion to Salamis.¹⁶³ Krautheimer identifies how 'Measurements are several times referred to as having been brought from Jerusalem for the specific purpose of laying out a copy...'¹⁶⁴ He goes on to suggest that 'only one or two measurements were selected from a much greater number.'¹⁶⁵ Given that layouts could be paced, but assessing elevations was more problematic, similarity of ground-plan represents *prima facie* evidence for a correspondence between Sion and Agios Epiphanius.

2.3 Conclusion: reconfiguring geography?

Cypriot tri-apsidal east ends constituted a demonstrable emphasis on Trinitarian orthodoxy of a particularly Theodosian cast. Their appearance on Cyprus occurred so soon after their appearance in Jerusalem that they could be regarded as part of the same *topos*.¹⁶⁶

By the fifth century, three aisles, quite as much as three apses, had become *de rigueur*. One of the principal effects of the new structural orthodoxy was a decline in the multi-valence of interiors, arguably as major a change as Christian adaptation of the *basilica forensis*. The relative homogeneity of 'afforested' halls had given way, in the late fifth and sixth-centuries, to a new sense of hierarchy calibrated along a central axis. The demolition of the intermediate aisles at Agios Epiphanius and Chrysopolitissa made the Eucharist, and those who performed it, more visually explicit but also more remote.¹⁶⁷ The apse doubled as the honorific canopy for the Eucharist and for the hierarch enthroned on the upper level of the stepped synthronon which, by the sixth century, typically lined the apse of a major basilica. This affirmation of episcopal power - probably related to the more developed roles of metropolitans and patriarchs - finds a parallel in the changes made to baptisteries - the subject of the next chapter. But in the fourth century the patriarchal system was no more than embryonic, episcopal authority

¹⁶³ Krautheimer (1942) 8: 'The number of parts that make up a geometrical pattern is always strongly stressed...The geometrical form is, as it were, translated into arithmetical figures.' Krautheimer's evidence is, however, largely drawn from later examples.

¹⁶⁴ Krautheimer (1942) 12

¹⁶⁵ Krautheimer (1942) 13

¹⁶⁶ Balderstone (2007) 13-14

¹⁶⁷ Stewart (2008) 68 for the removal of the intervening aisles at Agios Epiphanius.

2. Basilicas: Salamis and Sion

being legitimized more by an apostolic past than a hierarchical present. The formation of a single orthodoxy, however, was vested in conciliar authority and adherence to the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed.

However, Nicaea left practical and theological loose ends. Many bishops simply returned to their old sees and their old ways, while others, ostensibly acknowledging the Nicene straight-way, 'invented' deviations from it. Moreover, the consubstantial Trinity lacked an explicit resolution of its third person. By the accession of Theodosius in 380, indiscipline and incompleteness combined with a post-Apostate desire for *ananeosis* which coalesced around the Council and Synod assembled at Constantinople in 381 and 382.

It might be argued that the relationship between the two Councils is exemplified in two extant mosaics at the temporal and geographic limits of our period. Identification of the monuments in the depiction of Jerusalem in the pavement in St George's Church in Madaba has reached a general level of agreement. Dated to between 542 and 570, the mosaic shows the Holy Sepulchre and Sion as comparably impressive [2.84-5].¹⁶⁸ If identification of the topography of Jerusalem in the apse mosaic at S.Pudenziana in Rome (410-17) is more tentative, Vincent, Conant, Gibson and Taylor, Pullen, Cameron and Hall all agree that the domed rotunda to the left of the Christological axis can be identified with the Holy Sepulchre complex.¹⁶⁹ If Finegan is one of the few to identify a crenellated Cenacle and the building behind it with Sion, his identification, nevertheless, marries with the figure of 'Synagogue' below.¹⁷⁰ This might fit with Hellemo's interpretation in which the subject of the composition at S.Pudenziana's is the old and the new covenant represented by Sion and the New Jerusalem [2.86].¹⁷¹

¹⁶⁸ Tsafir in Piccirillo and Alliata (1999) 155-163, 252-254 respectively; Thomsen (1929) 192-219, for Sion see No.17 at 212-13, for the Cenacle see No.19 at 213

¹⁶⁹ Wilpert (1917) Plates III 42-44; Schlatter (1992) 276-295. For early scholarship identifying the city and its structures see Montini (1959) 29-30. According to Yarnold (2000) 19, Vincent, Conant, and Gibson and Taylor identify the Holy Sepulchre at S.Pudenziana.

¹⁷⁰ Finegan (1981) 234. The building identified as the Cenacle in the Madaba Map is flat roofed and the only comparable building at S.Pudenziana is the castellated structure which shares the Madaba Cenacle's proportions. See also Pixner (1990) who identifies the lower floor of the Cenacle as a Judeo-Christian synagogue: www.centuryone.org 19.8.12.

¹⁷¹ Hellemo (1998) 51-2. For an identification of the mosaic at S.Pudenziana as representing Rome rather than Jerusalem see Andaloro (2006) 118-9 figs 8-9

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Arguably, both mosaics retrace the history of Jerusalem's two Christian cities, the New Jerusalem on Golgotha and Old Christian Aelia on Sion. The basilica that incorporated and commemorated the site of the descent of the Holy Spirit inevitably incorporated and commemorated the spirit of the Council and Synod that determined its place in the Trinity. Less than sixty years before, the historicity of Holy Sepulchre complex, in so far as it incorporated the sites of Christ's death and resurrection, exemplified Nicaea's recognition of God and Christ as consubstantial. The remarkable similarity in size and proportion between the Martyrium and Sion constructed a conspicuously Nicene-Constantinopolitan 'synonymity.' The description seems justified as the term used by Krautheimer to describe the relationship of Peter and Paul exemplified in Constantine's Old St Peter's, begun as early as 326 (the year after Nicaea) and Theodosius' S.Paolo fuori le Mura begun in 386 (five years after the Council of 381).¹⁷²

If '...nothing was simply one thing' it would be misleading to assume that Agios Epiphanius, begun in the same decade as Sion and following its dimensions almost exactly, was indebted to Sion alone. Certainly Epiphanius would have known a Sion he could 'see and touch' constructed by an Emperor with whom he was probably intimate and in the milieu of a credo of which he was possibly the author and to which he certainly ascribed.¹⁷³ However, as a widely travelled cleric he would also have understood Sion's broader theological and doctrinal associations. Furthermore, it would be a mistake to see Agios Epiphanius as Sion referenced on remote Cyprus. Rather, theology, faith and conciliar authority collapsed the geography of the late fourth-century Eastern Mediterranean to construe Cyprus and Jerusalem as belonging to the same landscape of faith.

¹⁷² Krautheimer (1941) 399. See my Chapter 5

¹⁷³ Cyril of Jerusalem in Doval (2001) 182

Chapter 3

3.i Argument

Chapter one demonstrated how the Christianised cities of the Mediterranean littoral were orientated toward the sea as the medium through which jurisdiction, faith, and allegiance generated a high degree of mobility. Inverting the trope of the subject status of islands, the second chapter argued for the elective allegiance of Cyprus with the Orthodoxy of 325 and 381/2, within a specifically Jerusalemite milieu. The present chapter continues that trajectory in the context of baptism.

Two baptismal paradigms predominated in the fourth-century Eastern Mediterranean - the Johannine rite which drew on Christ's baptism in the Jordan and the Pauline rite in which 'those chosen' (the phōtizomenoi) partook Christ's death and resurrection. The first predominated in Egypt and Syria and the second was closely identified with the topography of Golgotha. The Pauline rite usually involved two anointings: the first, post-disrobing, was exorcistic and pre-immersion; the second, post-immersion and before re-robing, was increasingly associated with the gift of the Holy Spirit.¹ During the course of the later sixth and seventh centuries changes were made to the layout of those parts of Cypriot baptisteries assigned to this second anointing. Architecturally these changes took the form of apsidal addition representing a radical de-centering of a liturgy formerly constructed around the symmetry of the font.

At Agios Epiphanius a large and probably open court, aligned with the southern aisles, extended eastwards from the basilica. It prefaced a number of ancillary spaces further east, a group of which have been identified as a baptistery.² The excavated part of this baptistery consisted of a sequence of rooms forming a unicursal route beginning in the west and terminating in the east. Three further baptisteries on the island provide evidence for similarly sequential spaces and it seems appropriate, therefore, to describe these baptisteries as processional.

¹Johnson (2007) 138; Botte (1973) 63, 64, 65, 70; Brock (1981) 223; Logan (1998) 92-108. For the conferring of the Holy Spirit by sealing see 2 Corinthians 1: 21-22; Ephesians 1:13-14 and 4:30

² Pallas (1977) 292-3

2. Introduction

3.3.1 Baptisteries and fonts

In a synodical letter of c.400, Theophilus of Alexandria addressed the fifteen bishops of Cyprus.³ Given the presence of an episcopal basilica in each city and the role of the bishop in baptism, it might be expected that a baptistery would constitute a major signifier of episcopal authority. However, so far, only seven baptisteries have been identified on the island: Ayios Philon and Ayia Trias, on the north-east coast, Agios Epiphanius on the east, Kourion and Mazōtos-*Petounta* on the south coast and Shyrvallos and Peyia on the west coast [3.1]. The font at Peyia is round and in the centre of an open peristyle. The remaining fonts are cruciform and, with the probable exception Mazōtos-*Petounta* [3.2] and Shyrvallos, the remaining baptisteries - Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion – were cross-in-square and largely autonomous structures [3.3-4].⁴

A common theme among the relatively few surveys of early Christian baptisteries has been an emphasis on diversity of form, even within quite distinct regions. Cypriot baptisteries represent the most distinctive concentration of processional baptisteries in the Late Antique world, yet they remain remarkably little studied.⁵

³ Rapp (1993) 171 n.11. The bishops were, according to Jerome's Letter 17, Epiphanius, Marcianus, Agapetus, Boethius, Helpidius, Entasius, Norbanus, Macedonius, Aristo, Zeno, Asiaticus, Heraclides, another Zeno, Cyriacus and Aphroditus.' Also Hilberg (1996) 147

⁴ 'Cross-in-square' has been appropriated to identify Byzantine domed churches. Its use here is intended to emphasise a centralising tendency in Cypriot baptisteries as against a longitudinal emphasis amongst the island's basilicas. Other sites and possible sites of baptism include Shyrvallos, on the cliffs, east of Paphos, which was a three-aisled basilica. A long annex attached to its north side terminated in the east with a small transept and a projecting apse. A cruciform depression fronted the apse. Pallas (1997) 274-275, fig. 190 dates the building to the second half of the fifth century, Michaelides (1992) 7, 108 no.61 to the second half of the sixth and Ristow, (1998) no. 934 at 306, to between the fifth and the seventh centuries. Other sites include the Hagiasma of Nicodemus at Salamis consisting of two linked, possibly, first-century cisterns, one of which has an inscription from 2 Kings 2:21: 'Thus saith the Lord, I have healed these waters,' and another from Psalm 29:3, 'The voice of the Lord is upon the waters...the Lord is upon many waters.' See du Plat Taylor (1933) 97-108; Bardswell and Soteriou (1939), 443-445; Whitehouse (2009) 252-260. See also a room off the north aisle at Moroni: Manning (2002) 26. For the possibility of a baptistery in annexes 9-11 in the Acropolis basilica at Amathus see Aupert (1998) 75. For Campanopetra see Roux (1998) 211-219.

⁵ General surveys: Khatchatrian (1962) and (1982); Ristow (1998); Jensen, Rutherford, and Caraher (multi-media project – forthcoming). The most recent account, Jensen (2011), omits Cyprus; see also Jensen (2005) 117-44. See Pockney (1971) 309 for the distinction between

3. Baptisteries: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

The plan underlying all four processional baptisteries consisted of a double shell forming a rectangular ambulatory around a court divided into a nave and aisles oriented north-south. The court was probably intended for sponsors because elaborate measures were taken to screen the font where, at immersion, candidates were naked.⁶ In each case, the southern corridor of the ambulatory was occupied by the baptismal suite divided into three principal rooms: in the west, an *apodyterion* where the *phōtizomenoi* disrobed and received a pre-baptismal anointing, then the font where they underwent a triple immersion, and, finally, a *chrismarion*, where the newly baptised (*neophōtistoi*) received a second anointing before re-robing. Outer lobbies acted as ‘air-locks’ shielding the mysteries of the rite from the quasi-public court. From renunciation in the west aisle of the baptistery to entry into the adjacent basilica for the first communion, the baptizand would have completed almost an entire circuit of the baptistery.

Exactly comparable layouts are lacking, but those closest fall into two basic types, (1) the four-sided corridored-ambulatory which at Qal’at Sim’ān in Syria surrounds a square core containing an octagonal court, and (2) the group represented by Jerusalem, Sidé in Turkey and Gerash in Jordan, where a narthex prefaces three parallel rooms [3.5]. With the exception of Sidé, which had a cruciform font, explicit martyrial references are otherwise lacking, even where, as was the case at Jerusalem, the rite itself was understood in terms of sacrifice.⁷ These baptisteries were orientated to the east and are, therefore, to be distinguished from the Cypriot group which faced south.

Cruciform fonts are widely distributed throughout the Eastern Mediterranean.

Cruciform fonts	Greece	North Africa	Egypt	Asia Minor	Palestine	Syria
Davies (1962)	6	15	0	1	2	1

submersion and immersion. For Palestine see Bagatti (1957) 213-227 and Ben Pechat (1989) 165-188; for Jordan see Piccirillo (1985) 345-355

⁶ That baptisteries contained areas of assembly is suggested by John Chrysostom’s farewell to a group of widows and virgins assembled in the ‘Olympas,’ the baptistery located on the north side and towards the east end of Hagia Sophia. Mathews (1971) 12-13

⁷ Khatchatrian (1962) dates the baptistery at the Holy Sepulchre to the beginning of the fourth century, Sidé to between the fourth and the sixth, Qal’at Sim’ān to 476-490 and Gerash to 494-496. See 129, fig.120 for Sidé; 119 figs.58, 98 for Qal’at Sim’ān; 90, fig. 59 a, b, 64 for Gerash; 96 figs 65, 66 for Jerusalem.

3. Baptisteries: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

Khatchatrian (1962) 409 entries	14	20	0	8	13	4
Ristow (1998) 1061 entries	28	26	3	22	15	7

Outside Cyprus a combination of some kind of processional sequence associated with cruciform fonts can only be securely identified at Sidé and possibly at Bou Ismail (Castiglione) and Djemila in Algeria, both 4th-5th century - that is, at sites too dispersed and inconclusively dated to provide an obvious context for Cyprus.⁸

3.1.2 Dates and Sequence

Ristow is the author of the most recent 'complete' catalogue. However, his dates for Cyprus are unconvincing. Ayios Philon is assigned to the fifth century, but unaccountably he pushes Salamis into the sixth; Ayia Trias he dates from the sixth to the eighth and Kourion to two phases, one in the fifth and the other in the sixth and seventh centuries.⁹ For Megaw, Salamis is the earliest of the group.¹⁰ Ayios Philon he dates to the early years of the fifth century and given his assertion that the buildings are 'sufficiently similar in their construction ...to be the conception is a single individual' we may assume that this applies to the baptistery too.¹¹ Papageorghiou dates Ayia Trias to c.425 and there is no reason to doubt the baptistery too is early fifth century.¹² Megaw does not say that Kourion is the last of the group, but he dates the basilica to the fifth century and states that the baptistery 'followed the completion of the basilica.'¹³ Hence, Cypriot processional baptisteries might reasonably be said to belong between the death of Epiphanius in 403 and before the completion of the processional baptisteries at Qal'at Sim'ān, between 476-490 and St Theodore in Gerash of 494-96. Neither of these had cruciform fonts which Ben Pechat identified as predominantly a fifth-century phenomenon with relatively few examples in the sixth.¹⁴

⁸ Khatchatrian has no cruciform fonts contemporary with Cyprus, with the possible exception of Sidé (1962) 129 fig. 120. For Bou Ismail and Djemila see Gui (1992) I. 44-6, 95 and Duval (1992) Pl 43 figs 1,2,5

⁹ Ristow (1998) 274 (Salamis), 272 (Philon and Trias), 271 (Kourion).

¹⁰ Megaw (2007) 172. If not a later interpolation, the baptismal creed used at Salamis was included at the end of Epiphanius' *Ancoratus* (374)

¹¹ Du Plat Taylor and Megaw (1981) 249-50

¹² Papageorghiou (1964) 372-74

¹³ Megaw (2007) 172

¹⁴ Megaw (2007) 158; Ben Pechat (1989) 173-4. Ben Pechat 186 n.74 dates Agios Epiphanius to the end of the fourth century and the remaining three baptisteries to the fifth.

3.1.3 Liturgy and layout

In the previous chapter we saw that correlating aisles and function resulted in too great a variation to justify even broad conclusions. The baptistery, on the other hand, was devoted to a single rite bringing architecture and liturgy into a particularly intimate juxtaposition. Paradoxically, the bema, the basilica's principal liturgical focus, only became structurally integrated into its architectural setting in the late fifth and sixth centuries. By contrast, the font, as the focus of the early baptismal rite, was, from the first, structurally integral to its surroundings.¹⁵ If the basilica was visual and spatial, the baptistery was essentially tactile and sensory. The rite began before dawn after a period of fasting and all-night prayer; hence the first sequence of spaces was negotiated in semi-darkness. Orthodox initiation was a once-only event in which the sleep-deprived and disorientated *phōtizomenoi* lacked all foreknowledge of the topography of the ritual they were about to undergo.¹⁶ At the Renunciation of Satan, with which the rite began, the *phōtizomenoi*, arms outstretched, were led by presbyters through the first rooms, along body-hugging passages towards the triple immersion. In this way, each *phōtizomenos* approached the font in a state of symbolic blindness in which the baptistery itself was 'under a veil.'¹⁷ When Cyril of Jerusalem implored his hearers, 'tell nothing to a stranger' he was preserving not merely the mystery of the rite but the enigma of its setting.¹⁸ A sense of 'feeling-one's-way' is implicit in Wharton's claim that 'nowhere is touch more fully encoded in architecture and in ritual than in baptism.'¹⁹ Encoded touch arguably reached its apogee in fonts structurally integral to their baptisteries, where water provided the means by which the *phōtizomenoi* were immersed in their material surroundings. 'Encoding' also had its symbolic analogue in sealing, as the sign of incorporation into an *ecclesia* exemplified in Eusebius's allegory in which *catechumens* constituted the atrium of the church because they were 'still advancing and progressing' but who, having passed through the ritual of baptism, became the columns supporting the church.²⁰ Hence the *chrismarion* was a space in which the senses were revived, the body re-orientated, and where the *neophōtistoi* put

¹⁵ For masonry fonts see Ben Pechat (1989) 173

¹⁶ Yarnold (2000) 39

¹⁷ *Testamentum Domini* in Kraeling (1938) 176

¹⁸ *Protocatechesis* 12 in Cross (1951) 47

¹⁹ Wharton (1995) 84

²⁰ Smith (1989) 229-30

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on 'dazzling garment[s] of pure white' worn as 'a sign of the world's shining splendour'.²¹

3.1.4 Contexts

Attempting to establish a liturgical context for Cyprus is problematic; the island is rich in archaeology but lacks texts; conversely the Eastern Mediterranean is rich in textual comparanda but relevant archaeological examples are less abundant and more dispersed. Might Eastern Mediterranean liturgies provide the basis for a reconstruction of Cypriot baptismal theology and practice? Metcalf has cautioned against offering 'comments on the history of Cyprus using evidence from the Empire as a whole'.²² However, if a case for Cyprus as an *île-carrefour* can be sustained, the wider Empire is precisely where contexts might be sought. Furthermore, there is widespread agreement that a common core underlay local variation in baptismal practice. Yarnold writes that, 'Despite the different languages in which they were written and the local variations of the rite, the initiation ceremonies described in them conform in essentials to a common pattern'.²³

3.2. Material Evidence

3.2.1 Agios Epiphanius²⁴

Megaw dates the baptistery of Agios Epiphanius to the early fifth century.²⁵ Although only the south-western part of the baptistery has been excavated, evidence suggests that Agios Epiphanius provided the prototype for near-contemporary Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion.

The baptistery at Agios Epiphanius was aligned with the south side of the basilica, but its axis was skewed 10° south of east, a difference probably accounted for by the layout of

²¹ Theodore of Mopsuestia in Finn (1992) 96

²² Metcalf (2009) 19

²³ Yarnold (1994) 1

²⁴ Megaw (1974) 62-3 fig. A; Pallas (1977) 289-293 fig. 196; Delvoye (1980), 315, 324, fig. 13; Papageorgiou (1985) 299-324, 302 fig.1 and 304; Ristow (1998) no.788 at 274; no listing in Khatchatrian (1962)

²⁵ Megaw (2007) 172

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the subterranean network of rooms beneath it, identified as a bath complex.²⁶ On the basis of the layout shared by Philon, Trias and Kourion, it is possible to adduce that, to the north of the baptismal suite at Salamis, there would have been a court, probably about eleven metres wide, east-west, with three metre-wide aisles running north-south. Incomplete excavation means that it is not possible to determine the court's north-south dimension. It is likely that the 'nave' would have been lit by a clerestory supporting a pyramidal roof [3.6-7]. In the south wall of the court two apsidal recesses remain. The one corresponding to the *apodyterion* is in poor repair but may have been as large as 1.40m across and 0.70m deep [3.8]. Paired recesses at Philon and Trias suggest there would have been a niche corresponding to the *chrismarion* where Megaw's plan shows a doorway. A central niche corresponds to the font recess. This was marble-revetted, 0.75m across, and its rear wall was cut back to less than 0.10m, presumably to allow the hierarch ease of access to the *phōtizomenoi* [3.9].

From the present state of excavation it is impossible to determine whether the north court had an eastern focus similar to those at Philon and Kourion. The baptismal suite consisted of – from west to east – a lobby, an *apodyterion*, the font recess and an unexcavated *chrismarion* which may have been followed by a further lobby. The *apodyterion* measured 3.55m west-east and 2.85m north-south. At the south end of its east wall was a semi-circular niche, 0.70m across and 0.44m deep, the most likely position for the hierarch at the pre-baptismal anointing [3.10] (cf Philon).

The apsidal font-recess, 2.70m deep and 2.90m across, followed the *apodyterion* to the east [3.11]. It was aligned with the centre of the court to the north, for which it provided the focus. The font, in Roman brick, consisted of a rectangular tank oriented north-south, 1.25m deep, 0.83m across and 2.15 long, made cruciform by sets of stairs to the west and east, c.1m by 0.75m: four steps on the west prefaced by a high lip, 0.55m across and 0.40m deep, and five steps in the east. In the north arm of the font were two subsidiary tanks 0.47m by 0.44m and 0.45m deep, which Ristow suggests might have been heated [3.12].²⁷ Contact between hierarch and *phōtizomenoi* would have been facilitated by a step 0.23m high and c.0.45m deep at the end of the north arm of the

²⁶ ARDA for 1959 (17). For baptisteries and bathhouses see Ristow (1998) 20-21

²⁷ Ristow (1998) 274 cat. No. 788. Cf subsidiary tanks at Kos and Palestine; also Pallas (1977) 292. Ben Pechat (1989) 165-188 at 178-9 notes three small fonts within the larger one at Gerash, suggesting that these were used for infants with the priest presiding in an empty font. For footwashing (*pedilavium*) see Jensen (2011) 78-81, 230

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font (cf Kourion) [3.13].²⁸ Immediately beneath the font recess are the remains of a hypocaust with a furnace probably located to the south, on the evidence of stairs leading down to it [3.14].²⁹ The unexcavated *chrismarion* and the *apodyterion* probably shared the same dimensions. On the evidence of Philon and Trias, on leaving the *chrismarion*, the *neophōtistoi* would probably have processed along an east aisle into an east-west corridor and from there to the basilica for their first communion [3.15].

A mosaic-paved corridor immediately to the south of the baptistery was probably part of an eastern entrance, suggesting that, far from being in some remote corner of the complex, the baptistery may have been a very public building visible from the street [3.16].

3.2.2 Ayios Philon³⁰

Megaw dates Ayios Philon to the early fifth century, only a little later than Agios Epiphanius.³¹ Its baptistery [3.17] may have been an autonomous structure, firstly because all its outer doorways had rebated thresholds, suggesting that their doors could be secured from within and secondly, because, like Agios Epiphanius, baptistery and basilica were not aligned, the baptistery being 15° north of east while the basilica was only 3° to the north of east, suggesting that here too orientation may have been determined by an earlier structure. The baptistery lay immediately to the south of the basilica from which it was separated by a marmara-paved corridor which turned through 90° at its east end. There is evidence for an extensive later décor, substantial amounts of which survive in the revetment of the lower walls and an almost complete *opus sectile* floor [3.18].

Here too the north court would probably have been lit by a clerestory supporting a pyramidal roof. The even-sidedness of the 7.15m-by-6.99m court allowed it to serve as the 'nave' for two quasi-basilical readings. One axis was at right-angles to the basilica and consisted of a square 'nave' with 'aisles' west and east, with slightly raised floors.

²⁸ There was a step in the font at Qal'at Sim'ān presumably for the same purpose.

²⁹ For Epiphanian objections to heating see *Against Adamians* see IV 32 (52) 2.1 in Williams (1994) II.68. Evidence for heating the baptismal waters at Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon and Kourion lacks a satisfactory explanation.

³⁰ Khatchatrian (1962) 77; Megaw (1974) 64-66 fig.C; Pallas (1977) 305 fig. 202; du Plat Taylor and Megaw (1981) 235-238 pls XXXVII-XLIV; Papageorgiou (1985) 319, 323 fig.10; Michaelides (1992) 53 figs 65a, 65b; Ristow (1998) cat. no 784, 272, fig. 16b

³¹ Megaw (1997) 343

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Each aisle was separated from the 'nave' by two columns that were almost certainly reused, because their bases were individually cut to ensure a uniform height. Aligned with these but close to the court's south wall, two more columns on Proconnesian bases probably marked the position of an enclosure screening the font and extending the full width of the 'nave' [3.19]. There were doorways at both ends of the east and west 'aisles;' those to the north led to the corridor separating the baptistery from the basilica and those to the south led to the *apodyterion* and the *chrismarion*.

Like Agios Epiphanius and Ayia Trias, the south wall of the court was articulated by recesses; a rectangular recess, 0.30m deep and 2.00m across, corresponding to the font, was articulated by corner columns [3.20], either side of which were two semi-circular recesses, 0.52m across and 0.32m deep [3.21].

The second axis ran west-east, from a doorway [3.22] in the west aisle to an apse in the east wall of the east aisle, 1.4m across and 0.80 deep [3.23-4]. The two columns which created the aisles of a north-south reading now served to divide the baptistery into three approximately equal 2m-wide aisles orientated west-east.

The *phōtizomenoi* would probably have assembled in a marmara-paved portico outside the west door. After the Renunciation rite, performed facing the east apse, they would turn southwards towards a lobby, 1.9m east-west by 3m north-south. An *apodyterion*, 2.7m east-west by 3m north-south, lay immediately to the east of the lobby. An apse in the south end of its east wall, 0.60m deep and 1m across, repeats the feature at Agios Epiphanius, probably marking the position of the hierarch at the pre-baptismal anointing [3.25].

The font consisted of a rectangular tank, 1.75m north-south by 0.60m east-west with a depth of 0.90m, made cruciform by flights of stairs, west and east, 0.65m across by 0.70m deep [3.26]. The 2.00m square font recess had a 0.90m deep apse on its south side [3.27]. The whole recess was probably divided from the court by a parapet about 0.55m high. The font was revetted in Proconnesian marble. The floor of the apse recess was paved in *opus sectile* - all set in hydraulic plaster. In the northern angles of the font were two tanks c.0.45cm square and 0.50m deep, similar to those at Agios Epiphanius [3.28]. These were rendered in hydraulic plaster, although there is no evidence of revetment. To the rear of the font a stone-lined pit was discovered together with a

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quantity of ash, which suggested to Megaw that it 'may have been the furnace for heating the water for the font...' [3.29].³²

During the sixth century the *chrismarion* was probably extended southwards by a recess, 3.66m by 0.92m creating an L-shaped room, in the east wall of which was a central apse, 1.16m across and 0.78m deep, with rectangular alcoves either side, 0.92m deep and 1m across [3.30]. The outer alcoves were rebated for doors [3.31] and there is evidence for shelving in all three, shallow in the back of the apse but occupying the full depth of the alcoves. At the conclusion of the rite, the *neophōtistoi* probably processed northwards along the east aisle, turning west into the corridor between the basilica and the baptistery, entering the basilica through the narthex [3.32]. This corridor could have served as a *katechumenion*, although Megaw hypothesises a *katechumenion* on the north side of the basilica (cf Agios Epiphanius and Kourion).³³

3.2.3 Ayia Trias³⁴

Dated by Papageorghiou to the early fifth century, Ayia Trias was possibly contemporary with Ayios Philon but later than Agios Epiphanius.³⁵ Its baptistery lay to the east of its parent basilica with which, unlike our two previous cases, it was aligned 10° north of east. It consisted of an ambulatory surrounding a 'nave' and two 'aisles' orientated north-south: again, the baptismal suite occupied the southern corridor [3.33-4].

The 'nave' at Ayia Trias measured 5.5m north-south and 5.58m west-east. It, too, would probably have been lit by a clerestory under a pyramidal roof. Two columns divided the 'nave' from 1.60m-wide 'aisles.' There is no surviving focus in the east wall to construct a counter-axis starting at the west doorway.

The north and south responds of the colonnades took the form of pilasters set on tall bases. In the south wall of the 'nave' and adjacent to the southern pair of pilasters were two mural niches, 0.70m across and 0.40m deep, leaving remarkably thin rear walls of c.0.20m [3.35]. The rectangular recess fronting the font was 0.65m across and also

³² Du Plat Taylor/Megaw (1981) 214 and fig. 36 at 212

³³ Megaw (1974) 64 n.26; (2007) 3, 11, 14-15, 24-27, 158, 347-8

³⁴ Megaw (1974) 67, 70 fig D; Pallas (1977) 302 fig. 201; Papageorghiou (1985) 319, 320 fig.8; Ristow (1998) no 782, 272

³⁵ Papageorghiou (1964) 372-74 on the evidence of the style of the mosaics and a coin of Honorius (395-425).

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0.40m deep [3.36]. The enclosure screening the font must have occupied the entire southernmost bay of the 'nave,' given that the south faces of the bases of the southern pair of columns were routed to receive a screen [3.37]. The southwest respond was also routed but the southeast respond was not, perhaps indicating the entrance to the enclosure.³⁶

The south end of the western corridor accessed a lobby 2.75m square with a doorway in its east wall leading to an *apodyterion*, 2.95m east-west and 2.75m north-south, which was also accessed from the west aisle [3.38]. Unlike Salamis and Philon there is no apsidal recess in its east wall.

The font recess measured 2.85m north-south and 2.40m across. At its southern end was a mural apse, 1.45m deep and 1.90m across [3.39]. The font consisted of a rectangular tank, 1.65m long, 0.70m wide, with a depth of 1.12m, made cruciform by flights of stairs west and east, 0.70m wide and between 0.80 and 0.90m deep, each of three steps and preceded by a broad threshold, 0.52m deep [3.40]. A flattened torus outlined the stairs, and the floor of the font and all surfaces were tanked in hydraulic plaster (cf *Mazōtos-Petounta* [3.41]). The ends of the north and south arms of the font were dramatically convex.³⁷ The south arm [3.42], however, at 0.35m was shorter than the 0.59m. north arm where the convexity was much shallower [3.43], presumably to facilitate the hierarch's access to the *phōtizomenoi*. Trias shared with Salamis a font which, in plan, was more crucifix than cruciform.

Leaving the font, the *neophōtistoi* entered the apsidal-ended *chrismarion*. After re-robing, they would have proceeded northwards along the east aisle, turning west into a quasi-narthex, toward the basilica [3.44]. The east end of what may have been the *katechumenaion* is now blocked by an apse added after the Arab raids. Before the route was barred the *neophōtistoi* would have processed along the south corridor and probably entered the basilica through a doorway in its south aisle.

Evidence that the corridor attached to the south of the basilica served as a *katechumenaion* is provided by the remains of benches against its north and south walls extending as far as the third bay of the basilica from the east [3.45].

³⁶ Megaw (2007) 110-1

³⁷ At Alahan (Isauria) all four arms of the font are convex; Gough (1985) 129 figs 61-65

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There is no evidence for a step in the font's north arm, no evidence for subsidiary fonts, no storage recesses in the *chrismarion* and, alone of the four baptisteries, no evidence for a furnace.

3.2.4 Kourion³⁸

Kourion, probably the latest of the group, belongs to the first thirty years of the fifth century, with alterations made in the sixth and early seventh centuries.³⁹ Situated in the south of the island, it lies somewhat apart from the main group and is distinguished from them in its location to the north side of the parent basilica and by a large eastern apse which effectively creates a separate *parekklesion* parallel to the baptismal suite running the entire length of its south aisle [3.46].

Any account must be heavily indebted to Megaw's 2007 publication.⁴⁰ In explaining the baptistery's eastern apse, Megaw proposed that 'since no trace was found of any earlier floor that could be associated with the straight east wall, it is evident that the decision to introduce an apse was made in the course of the original construction.'⁴¹ This suggests that a basilical and hence longitudinal interior was intended from the outset

The overall plan was a rectangle, 16.5m by 12.17m, orientated 30° north of east and surrounded by 3m-wide corridors on three sides, and possibly to the north too, if the remains of a doorway at the north end of the narthex indicate a further corridor [3.47]. Doorways at the ends of the baptismal suite connected with the eastern and western corridors and two more doorways connected the *apodyterion* and the *chrismarion* with the south aisle of the *parekklesion*. The present mosaic pavement in the south aisle was laid around the closure screen fronting the font, suggesting that, when this pavement was laid in the seventh century, the font remained a major focus.⁴²

³⁸ Megaw (1976) 348-357 fig.D; Megaw (2007) 107-118; Pallas (1977) 282 fig 193; Papageorghiou, (1985) 310; Christou (1996) 39; Ristow (1998) no. 785-6, 273 fig. 9a

³⁹ Megaw (2007) 158

⁴⁰ Megaw (2007) 107-118

⁴¹ Megaw (2007) 113. Loverance in Morris (1990) 239 suggests 'the apse...represents an afterthought.'

⁴² Megaw (2007) 111

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A bi-axial reading remains, governed by the four columns which formed a 5m square crossing, for which, once again, a clerestory and a pyramidal roof are hypothesized. One axis is constructed between the west doorway and the east apse and the second constitutes a north-south 'nave' which has the font recess as its southern focus. The first axis has two outer aisles of 3m and the second axis has four outer aisles of 2.25m.

Two floors have been discovered under the present floor: a fourth-century pavement of rectangular slabs and, 0.12m above this, a mosaic floor of a date yet to be determined. The seventh-century mosaic floor is 0.17m higher still.

At this higher level the mosaic pavement of the south aisle was treated differently from the rest of the floor and constituted a particular emphasis on the south side of the *parekklesion* [3.48]. The western and easternmost double bays carried an imbricated motif [3.49] and between them, and immediately in front of the font, was a carpet with a trellis motif and a crow-step border [3.50]. This mosaic was carefully fitted against the fifth-century closure panels which screened the whole of the south central bay. The position of the closure screen is indicated by slots in the southern and inner faces of the southern pair of crossing columns, and by gaps in the seventh-century mosaic floor indicating the position of the posts – two between the southern pair of crossing columns and two south of the crossing columns indicating a central entrance and two lateral entrances to the enclosure. When the buttresses were added against the south wall, these side entrances became unserviceably narrow [3.51]. It is possible that at abacus level an iron bar joined the two columns on the south side of the crossing and that two more bars extended southwards joining the crossing to the south wall. Articulating the partition-wall fronting the font recess, small columns framed three marble-revetted semi-circular niches, the central one of which was only 0.40m from the north arm of the font, again facilitating the hierarch's access to the *phōtizomenoi* [3.52].

The mural east apse, 3.92m at the chord, dominated the *parekklesion* [3.53-4]. The seventh-century bema floor was paved in *opus sectile* and would have co-existed with the seventh-century mosaic floor in the central and south aisles [3.55-6].⁴³ The treatment of each of the three west-east aisles was different. The south aisle has already been referred to: the north aisle was paved with stone flags [3.57]. The seventh-

⁴³ Daszewski and Michaelides (1988) 91

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century nave mosaic was a single field, the design of which was consistent as far as the bema and consisted of an inhabited lattice framed by a cable moulding. The floor was clearly intended to be read from west to east, given the evidence of two *kantharoi* either side of a Solomon's knot inside the west doorway and two *hedera* at the crossing [3.58].⁴⁴ However, this may not have been the case with the 1.39m-square panel aligned with the western pair of crossing columns [3.59]. Framed with a *hedera rinceau*, its centre is now illegible, apart from the feet of a bird in its southeast corner [3.60]. Megaw suggests the panel was intended to be read from the east, but it is also possible that the bird formed part of a frame surrounding a now-lost motif.

One distinctive variation is the mosaic floor of the westernmost intercolumniation on the north side, which has a décor of black and white crosses enriched by purple, pink and orange tesserae [3.61].⁴⁵ The remaining intercolumniations on the north side were in-filled with a stylobate roughly laid between the existing columns.⁴⁶

Read as a cruciform building with a lantern over the crossing, four arms can be identified, two of 5m to the west and east and two of 3m to north and south [3.62]. The arms, and hence the cruciform layout of the building, may have been further emphasised by arcades, given the discovery of a number of voussoirs.⁴⁷ However, this feature may have been a late introduction, given that the buttresses against the north and south walls, presumably designed to receive the transverse arches, are not in bond and were, as is clear in the north aisle, set directly on the pavement. Megaw suggests the buttresses were 'introduced to deal with some failure in the superstructure.'⁴⁸

The crossing columns were the same height as those in the basilica and had clearly been selected for their uniformity.⁴⁹ Megaw proposed galleries above the corner compartments. Given the height of the crossing columns, he speculates that the baptistery would have looked 'disproportionately' tall in relation to its surroundings.⁵⁰

⁴⁴ Daszewski and Michaelides (1988) 129 and fig. 51

⁴⁵ Daszewski and Michaelides (1988) 129 and fig. 52

⁴⁶ Similar breaks in the westernmost intercolumniations of north aisles are to be noted at Peyia north and south and in the Acropolis basilica at Amathus.

⁴⁷ Megaw (2007) 111 points out that buttresses against the outer walls would have been necessary because of the greater span of the aisles at 3m, as against intercolumniations of 2.5m.

⁴⁸ Megaw (2007) 111 and 113

⁴⁹ Megaw (2007) 112

⁵⁰ Megaw (2007) 174

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The intention may have been to 'publicize' a building which would otherwise have been lost in what must have been a densely packed episcopal complex.

The baptismal suite may have formed the south aisle of a complete ambulatory surrounding the *parekklesion*. If so, the narthex, 16m long and 3m wide [3.63], would have constituted its west corridor corresponding to the partially excavated east corridor immediately to the east of the apse. These may have been linked by a north corridor of which only the west end has been excavated. We might speculate that all four corridors were originally stone-flagged but, with the construction of the apse, the east corridor was blocked off and the west corridor was converted into a narthex. Megaw identifies the present floor of the narthex as employing themes popular from sixth-century but probably contemporary with the final renovation.⁵¹

The *phōtizomenoi* probably renounced Satan facing the *ad limina* inscription in the narthex: 'Approach Him and be filled with light and your faces shall not be ashamed,' (Psalm 34.5) [3.64].⁵² This inscription intended to be read facing Paradise, invoking a journey towards greater illumination, reflects the over-arching symbolism of the rite.

After the Renunciation the *phōtizomenoi* proceeded southwards to enter the baptismal suite. Megaw identifies the room with benches at the west end of the suite as an *apodyterion* [3.65]. In the second chamber, closest to the font, the catechumens probably received a pre-baptismal anointing, but where the apsidal recess for the hierarch might have been there was set of stairs [3.66].

The font recess was 2.80m-deep and 1.60 across. Clamp holes indicate that it was revetted with a décor probably including little pilasters, several of which were found during the excavation.⁵³ Coloured glass and mother-of-pearl tesserae suggest that the semi-dome was decorated with mosaic, probably contemporary with the semi-dome of the basilica.⁵⁴

⁵¹ Megaw (2007) 117

⁵² Cf. Cyril of Jerusalem to the *phōtizomenoi* in the *apodyterion* at Jerusalem; 'ye were naked in the sight of all and were not ashamed.' *MCI* :2 in Cross (1986) 60

⁵³ Megaw (2007) 107-8

⁵⁴ Megaw (2007) 108

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The recess contained a rectangular tank, 1.6m long by 0.65m, and like Trias, it had a shorter north arm – 0.40m as against the 0.55m-long south arm. The font was revetted in marble and its floor sloped southwards towards a drain.⁵⁵ As at Agios Epiphanius, there was a step at the foot of the north arm, c.0.40m-high, which extended a short way into the font's western and eastern arms [3.67].

Passages only 0.70m wide, and probably vaulted, connected the font to the *apodyterion* and the *chrismarion* [3.68]. The floors of these passages were ramped steeply up from the *apodyterion*, and gently down into the *chrismarion*. There were only two steps down into the font; however, its depth was increased by stone parapets at the top of each set of stairs, 0.40 high to the west [3.69] but only 0.30m high to the east.⁵⁶

The masonry behind the font was cut through to receive a pipe leading from a furnace with a vaulted roof perforated with flues, which heated a cauldron on the platform above and from which the water was siphoned into the font. The cauldron was serviced via steps from the *apodyterion* and the *chrismarion*.

The *chrismarion* was 8.2m long and 2.8m wide [3.70]. Two semi-circular recesses in its south wall may have held the garments for the *neophōtistoi*; the sense of illumination would have been reinforced by light from windows in the same wall. A free-standing apse, probably constructed in the sixth century on the existing pavement, was attached at right-angles to the north wall and probably marked the position of the hierarch at chrismation [3.71]. Voussoirs found during the excavation indicate that the apse would have been crowned with a semi-dome [3.72].⁵⁷

The lower part of the east wall of the east corridor is fourth-century and may, Megaw proposed, have determined the orientation of the whole baptistery.⁵⁸ Benches against both walls suggest that this east aisle served for the assembly for the *neophōtistoi* prior

⁵⁵ Socrates *EH* 7.17 (2009 reprint) 283 describes how 'the water had escaped by a channel underneath, by means of which they are accustomed to empty the font. There were, however, other means of emptying fonts; 'scarcely had baptism been administered, when people would crowd around with all sorts of vessels and take away the water, some keeping it carefully in their homes whilst others watered their fields, vineyards and garden with it.'

⁵⁶ Davies (1962) 23 suggests that the purpose of steps was 'to emphasise the fact of *descent*.'

⁵⁷ Megaw (2007) 109, 173

⁵⁸ Megaw (2007) 117

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to their first communion [3.73-4]. The benches are clearly early because the floor slabs abut them.⁵⁹

The route from the baptistery to the basilica is more hypothetical at Kourion than elsewhere, given the constraints of its cliff-edge location and the number of alterations made between the beginning of the fifth century and the beginning of the seventh.

The Episcopal basilica and the *parekklesion* were both possible sites for the first communion. In the case of the Episcopal basilica, the *neophōtistoi* probably processed along the east corridor, into the north aisle or the north corridor (had there been one), round the atrium and into the basilica via the narthex, dividing either side of the *solea* [3.75-6]. Alternatively, they received a blessing at the bema of the *parekklesion* before proceeding to the Episcopal basilica. If, on the other hand, the Eucharist took place in the *parekklesion*, it is possible that, in the early phase, the *neophōtistoi* crossed the south-east compartment to receive communion at the bema, which had yet to receive its seventh-century western extension [3.77].⁶⁰ When the bema was extended to the eastern crossing columns that route proved unserviceable.⁶¹ Rather, the corridor behind the apse could have been re-instated, allowing the *neophōtistoi* access to the north aisle, from where they approached the bema via the westernmost intercolumniation, for which the seventh-century mosaic already referred to provided the threshold [3.78].

Megaw suggested that the east portico of the atrium was converted into a *katechumenaion* by in-filling its intercolumniations and building benches against the new partition [3.79].⁶² He thought that the absence of any floor beneath the east portico's marmara paving suggested that it must have been intended as a *katechumenaion* 'from the outset.'⁶³ Given that the intercolumnar infill is clearly later, it seems more likely that a *katechumenaion* was transferred to the east portico when, at some time yet to be determined, the *katechumenaia* north and south of the basilica were declared redundant [3.80].

⁵⁹ Megaw (2007) 115, 117

⁶⁰ Loverage in Morris (1990) 225-43 at 239-40 suggests that the pedestal base found in the apse of the baptistery-basilica provides evidence that 'the first Eucharist of the newly-baptised took place in the baptistery and not in the basilica proper.'

⁶¹ Megaw (2007) 116

⁶² Megaw (2007) 118, 119

⁶³ Megaw (2007) 119

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3.2.5 Kourion and Peyia

Agios Epiphanius was crucial in the development of Cypriot tri-apsidal east ends, but as presently excavated, there is no indication that its baptistery was similarly influential - rather Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon and Ayia Trias constitute a well-defined and geographically-close group. Kourion's overtly basilical plan sets it apart but shared characteristics nevertheless outweigh differences. These characteristics - cruciform fonts in cross-in-square baptisteries - have been used to draw a distinction with Peyia where a small basilica lay to the north of baptistery in the form of an open peristyle in the middle of which was a circular font, accessed by a single set of stairs [3.81]. Peyia is unique on the island, and, it is argued, represents a sixth-century re-orientation from Jerusalem towards Constantinople and the Aegean.⁶⁴ However, to an extent Peyia and Kourion were in dialogue.

The baptistery at Kourion was basilical and relatively independent of the baptismal suite immediately attached to its south. Furthermore, the basilicas at both sites had 'corridors' marked by the west ends of their bemas and the easternmost supports of their naves - namely, the eastern crossing-columns at Kourion and the T-shaped piers at the east end of the nave at Peyia [3.82]. Both 'corridors' were of similar size, 1.0m at Kourion and only a little wider at Peyia, and both were accessed across the east compartments of their south aisles [3.83-5].⁶⁵

If Peyia represents the influence of Constantinople and the Aegean, that influence was entirely localised, because, in their later refurbishments (perhaps contemporary with Peyia) the baptisteries at Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion appear to have responded to aspects of a more widely disseminated Syrian rite. In order to understand this change, the next section seeks to reconstruct a later-fourth and early-fifth-century liturgy for Cyprus.

⁶⁴ Delvoye (1966) 489f, fig. 12; Pallas (1977) 276, fig. 191; Papageorgiou (1985) 316; Michaelides (1992) 99-107 figs 56-60

⁶⁵ The 'corridor' at Kourion survived until the westward extension of the bema, probably in the seventh century. Megaw (2007) 114-15

3.3 Liturgical Evidence

During the initiation process, the individual had to follow a series of rites including...purification of the body...The most important moment of the procedure was the “voluntary death” of the initiate...followed by his “resurrection”. It was generally believed that a devotee...won a blessed life after death.⁶⁶

This description of an Isiac rite from Hellenistic/Roman Cyprus is a reminder that Egypt was a widely attested presence in the Late Antique Eastern Mediterranean.⁶⁷ Furthermore, the shape of the rite bears a striking resemblance to those liturgies which understood baptism in terms of Christ’s death and resurrection. Chapters 1 and 2 provided evidence for fourth-century contacts with Egypt; to what extent, then, did Egypt provide the setting for Cypriot baptismal practice?

3.3.1 Alexandria, Egypt and the Jordan Event

Johnson argues that Christian baptism, as death and resurrection, had its roots in the writings of Epiphanius’ *bête noire*, Origen (c.185-254).⁶⁸ However, MacDonnell points out that Origen’s frequent citation of Romans does ‘not mean that he...abandoned the previous tradition that took the baptism of Jesus as its primary paradigm.’⁶⁹ Origen identified the river Jordan with ‘descending’.⁷⁰ Indeed, in early Egyptian liturgies, the font is often referred to as the ‘Jordan.’⁷¹ Egypt, then, drew on two primary paradigms: the death and resurrection of Christ and the Jordan event.

The most vivid account of an early fourth-century Egyptian baptismal liturgy appears in the *Canons of Hippolytus*. Composed either in Alexandria or elsewhere in northern Egypt between 336-40, the *Canons* may have represented a codification of practices probably familiar to Epiphanius before he left Egypt in the 330s. Disrobing (Canon 113-5) was

⁶⁶ Anastassiades (2000) 196

⁶⁷ Roueché (2000) 580. For Tertullian and water used in the Isiac rite as ‘barren’ see Jensen (2005) 122

⁶⁸ Johnson (1999) 144

⁶⁹ MacDonnell (1996) 203

⁷⁰ Lienhard (1996) Homily 1.56: ‘We were buried with him in baptism;’ Homily 4.89, ‘Jordan’ means ‘descending.’

⁷¹ Book 2:8 of *The Canonical Responses of Timothy of Alexandria* (c.381), commands ‘...sanctify the Jordan, that is, the water of the font:’ in Day (2007) 7 and 54. See also Ratcliff (1965) 28

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followed by a double anointing (116-7), around a triple immersion (123-133) and a further anointing (134) before re-robing (135). Presbyters conducted a rite framed by an episcopal laying-on-of-hands (108 and 136).⁷² Hippolytus thus describes a powerfully symmetrical rite in which immersion is the defining event.

In seeking a model for Cyprus, we might ask two questions: firstly, if the Egyptian rite was symmetrical were the spaces in which it was performed similarly symmetrical; and secondly, what evidence is there for cruciform fonts in Egypt? Only two baptisteries - Building G at Kurūm at Tuwāl and Pelusium (al-Faramā) - have been shown by Grossmann to have had cruciform fonts, both with stairs orientated west-east.⁷³ The symmetry of the *Canons of Hippolytus* notwithstanding, there is no evidence, at either site, that the font was the focus for a symmetrical arrangement of dependent spaces and therefore it must be assumed that, in mid-fourth century Egypt, the core of the rite was assigned to a single room.⁷⁴ For a more emphatic synergy of symmetrical rite and symmetrical space it will be necessary to look elsewhere.

3.3.2 Jerusalem, Palestine and the Pauline paradigm

In the mid-330s, Epiphanius returned from Egypt to Palestine, and he may have provided a significant link between the two before Cyril assumed the bishopric of Jerusalem c.350. Chitty suggests not only that Eleutheropolis retained Egyptian links into the seventh century but also that Epiphanius was concerned to preserve Egyptian practice in his monastery at Besandūk.⁷⁵ Hence, '[a]t the beginning of the fourth century Egypt and Jerusalem were using essentially the same rite, which differed from that in use at Antioch.'⁷⁶

However, from the mid-fourth century, any debt owed by Cyril to the baptismal practices of Egypt was literally overshadowed by the topography of Golgotha as the

⁷² Whitaker (1970) 88-90

⁷³ Grossmann (2002): for Kurūm 145 n.146, fig.42 (font at south end of narthex); for Pelusium 145 n.142, fig 88; see also el-Taher and Grossmann (1997) 255-62 (n.119) 256

⁷⁴ Dependent annexes are identifiable at Hermopolis Magna (el-Ashmunein), at ʿAbū Mīnā and at the baptistery of the North Church in the same city. Müller-Wiener (1965) 133-7 figs 3-4; McKenzie (2007) 286 fig. 475; 289, fig.481, b-e; Grossmann (1983) 68-9 figs. 2-3

⁷⁵ Chitty (1966) 14, 72-3

⁷⁶ Cuming (1974)123. See Bishop (1912) 23-50 at 38 n.1 to the effect that, after the construction on Golgotha the direction of influence went into reverse and Egypt went to Jerusalem.

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‘sacred spot...of our Saviour’s passion.’ [T]his Golgotha, sacred above all such places,’ was the omphalos of Jerusalem which, for Cyril, was identified above all with the *lignum crucis*.⁷⁷

3.3.3 Cyril of Jerusalem: the *Catechetical Lectures* and the *Mystagogical Catecheses*

Cyril’s liturgy is embodied in two documents, the *Catechetical Lectures (CL)* and the later *Mystagogical Catecheses (MC)*.⁷⁸ The first lecture, the *Procatechesis*, was an introduction addressed to the full congregation. Then followed the eighteen *CL*, the last thirteen of which (6-18) constitute evidence for Jerusalemite practice at the time of Cyril’s episcopate (350-386). Doval argues that they would have been delivered in the Martyrium, probably in 351.⁷⁹ Finally, there were the four *MC* probably given at the Anastasis sometime after 382 and addressed to the *neophōtistoi* on the meaning of the initiation they had recently undergone, the first three dealing with baptism.⁸⁰

MC provides the most vivid account of the baptismal liturgy in Jerusalem at the end of the fourth century. As a key document for Cyprus, *MC* is worth quoting at some length:

2. First, you entered into the outer hall of the Baptistry, and there facing towards the West, you heard the command to stretch forth your hand...

4. ...you were commanded...to say...I RENOUNCE YOU, SATAN...Since the west is the region of sensible darkness, and he being darkness, has his dominion also in darkness, you therefore, looking with a symbolic meaning towards the West, renounce that dark and gloomy potentate.

9. When...thou renoucest Satan...there is opened to you the Paradise of God, which he planted towards the east...the place of light.

11. And these things were done in the outer chamber.⁸¹

⁷⁷ Drijvers (2004) 156; Catechesis 13.28 in Parker (1838) 157

⁷⁸ Gifford (1989) VII 62-63. For Cyril’s authorship see Yarnold (1978) 143-161. For a comparative table see Bradshaw (1996) 24. For the lectures at the Holy Sepulchre see Yarnold (1994) 68 and for the date of the lectures see Drijvers (2004) 58

⁷⁹ Doval (1997) 130. For the apparition of the Cross (*parhelion*) in the same year see Fraser (1996), 139-140, 205. Kühnel (1987) 68 construes this as a Cyrilline vision modelled on the vision of Constantine.

⁸⁰ Ferguson (2009) 473; Cross (1986) xxii

⁸¹ Cross (1986) 53-58 [modified]

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MC II describes those parts of the rite which took place in the *apodyterion* and the font.

2. As...as you entered, you put off your garment...Having stripped yourselves, you were naked; and this also imitating Christ, who hung naked on the Cross...

3. Then...you were anointed with exorcized oil, from the very hairs of your head, to your feet...

4. ...you were led to the holy pool...as Christ was carried from the Cross to the Sepulchre which is before our eyes. And each of you was asked, whether he believed in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Ghost, and you made that saving confession, and descended three times into the water, and ascended again; here also covertly pointing by a figure at the three-days burial of Christ...And at the self-same moment, you died and were born...

6 For this cause Paul...says *Know ye not that as many of us as were baptized into Jesus Christ, were baptized into His death? Therefore we are buried with Him by baptism into death...*⁸²

7...we have been planted together in the likeness of His death, we shall also in the likeness of His resurrection.⁸³

MC III deals with chrismation.

1...after you had come up from the pool of the sacred streams, [you were] given the Unction, the emblem of that wherewith Christ was anointed.

4. And you were first anointed on your forehead...Then your ears...Then your nostrils...Then your breast...For as Christ after His baptism...so likewise, having, after Holy Baptism and the Mystical Chrism, put on the whole armour of the Holy Ghost.⁸⁴

Finally, MC IV describes re-robing

But now, having put off thy old garments, and put on those that are spiritually white, thou must be continually robed in white.⁸⁵

⁸² Romans 6:3

⁸³ Cross (1986) 59-62, modified; Day (1999) 14 points out that mention of the Resurrection is absent from the baptismal liturgy because it was reserved until the Gospel of the Resurrection read by the bishop at the Anastasis.

⁸⁴ Cross (1986) 63-67. For a survey of the literature of possible locations for the baptistery see Doval (1993) 1-13

⁸⁵ Cross (1986) 70

To what extent can Cyril's rite be mapped on to what is known of the baptistery of the Holy Sepulchre?

3.3.4 The Baptistery at the Holy Sepulchre

Major parts of the fourth-century complex on Golgotha have been identified, including the Martyrium, Golgotha and the Holy Sepulchre. We know from the accounts of the Bordeaux Pilgrim, Egeria and the fifth-century *Armenian Lectionary* that there was also a baptistery, and *CL* and *MC* provide vivid accounts of its use.⁸⁶ However, for some scholars the location of the baptistery remains in doubt.

At *MC* 1.2 Cyril refers to the baptistery as 'tou baptismatos oikon' perhaps implying an autonomous structure. Vincent and Abel, Crowfoot, Khatchatrian, Coüasnon, Wharton and Doval accept that the fourth-century baptistery occupied the site of the remodelled, tripartite building of 1048.⁸⁷ Its earliest representation is probably the square structure covered by a pyramidal roof attached to the south of the Anastasis shown on the Madaba map (542-570) [3.86].⁸⁸

Day is amongst recent dissenters from a south-side location.⁸⁹ She thinks it unlikely, in less-than-fully Christian Jerusalem, that such a prominent site would have been chosen.⁹⁰ Rejecting Cyril's description in *MC* 1.2 of a distinctive structure, she prefers a more embedded location in the north-west of the complex. Her evidence rests on the account of the Bordeaux pilgrim who visited the Holy Places in 333 and whose

⁸⁶ Wilkinson (2002a) 178-9

⁸⁷ Vincent and Abel (1914) 138-141, fig. 92-3, pl. 13, 33; Crowfoot (1941) 20-1. Khatchatrian (1962) 10 fig.65 and 96-7: at 97 he argues for a quadrilobed font in a square in the central room based on Bagatti (1957) 213-227 fig. 4. See also Coüasnon (1974) 48; Wharton (1992) 313-325; Doval (1993) 1-13 and (2001) 86, n.3

⁸⁸ The first to identify the building as the baptistery was Thomsen (1929) 212-5. Donner (1992) 91 describes the building as having 'a flat red roof, two small doors and one window. It stands west of a light-brown trapezoidal space, probably the market place (*forum*) of Roman-Byzantine Jerusalem.'

⁸⁹ Day (1999) 19 and (2007) 141. Tinelli and Corbo argued for a similar location based on the discovery there of a marble basin, 1.10m long and 0.60m deep, which Wharton dates to 'the fifth and sixth centuries' (1992) 314.

⁹⁰ Cf. the baptisteries of Agios Epiphanius and Kourion as 'public' buildings. Gibson and Taylor (1994) 75 fig 45 set the baptistery further south than is usually the case in a room with an apse to the north.

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description, she claims, identified him as standing in the open court between the Sepulchre and Golgotha and looking south.

On your left is the hillock Golgotha where the Lord was crucified, and about a stone's throw from it the vault where they laid his body...By order of the Emperor Constantine there has now been built there a 'basilica'...which has beside it cisterns of remarkable beauty, and beside them a baptistery where children are baptized.⁹¹

The context for the pilgrim's description was not the western atrium but the cardo between the Sion and Neapolis gates. If he had sight of the hill he could hardly have been on it. The basilica he described on his left was the Martyrium and hence the 'bath in which the *infantes* were washed' was behind the Martyrium but visible from the cardo. As Fraser comments, '...it is a description of one passing by.'⁹² Above all, Day disregards the most appropriate place for crucifixion-based rite as the shadow of the cross itself. Hence, there is no reason to reject the widely accepted view that the fourth-century baptistery occupied the prominent site to the south of the Anastasis.

The next question concerns plan and use. Four possible layouts have achieved wide circulation: Conant (1956), Khatchatrian (1962), Coüasnon (1974) and Corbo (1981) [3.87]. I will confine my remarks to two readings. Doval maps a complex route onto Coüasnon's plan, with places of assembly in the north and south annexes and the remainder of the rite consigned to the main chamber.⁹³ In this case where was the font? Coüasnon suggested that the *phōtizomenoi* entered the font facing east.⁹⁴ If the font was in an apsidal recess, the eastern set of stairs would have been unserviceable. This is possible, given Ben-Pechat's identification of three Palestinian fonts - the north and south churches at Shivta, and El Flousiyeh - with unserviceable eastern stairs set hard against their apse walls.⁹⁵ Conant's plan and route establishes a closer correspondence with Cyprus. He posits a square court with a surrounding ambulatory, the east side of

⁹¹ Wilkinson (2002a) 31. Possibly in 333, the baptistery had yet to be built, but Avi-Yonah (1965) 54 suggests that the cisterns could be identified with the site of the baptistery because, 'The domed roof of the building favours its identification as a bath, while the red colour of its roof identifies it as a sacred building.' Gibson and Taylor (1994) 78, fig 45 identify the Pilgrim's cisterns but to the east of the site of the 'baptistery'.

⁹² Fraser (1996) 107 n.284

⁹³ Doval (2001) 87

⁹⁴ Coüasnon (1974) 49

⁹⁵ Ben Pechat (1989) 176; Rosenthal-Heginbottom (1982) 54-57 fig. 8 and plate 16 b [North Church]; 80-1, fig.11 and plates 38 a, b, and 39a [South church]; for the North Church see Ovadiah (1970) 169 pl 68 plan 167; for the South church see 171-2

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which accommodates a baptismal suite of two rooms either side of a cruciform font. His route, too, is remarkably complex and the anti-clockwise direction I have proposed for Cyprus arguably provides a more coherent reading, allowing, firstly, room for sponsors, and secondly, a progress toward the Anastasis where, according to Egeria, ‘the newly-baptized come.’⁹⁶

If the hypothetical layouts proposed for Jerusalem fall short of a comprehensive model for Cyprus, did wider Palestine provide more convincing contexts? The problem of Palestinian prototypes for Cypriot basilicas applies to baptisteries too, namely a degree of regional variation and a relative paucity of archaeological and liturgical analogues for Jerusalem. By the end of the fifth century, while there may have been more Christians than any other group, the faith had not completely penetrated Jewish Galilee or the pagan countryside.⁹⁷ And although Ovadiah tempts comparison with Kourion when he describes *phōtizomenoi* at Ascalon passing ‘via a corridor into the baptistery...which was cruciform,’ there is otherwise little evidence for fonts until the later fifth and sixth centuries⁹⁸ Similarly, there is no evidence for comparable liturgies; post-baptismal anointing barely penetrated the provinces and, as Day points out, there is insufficient evidence to substantiate the practice, even in Gaza and Caesarea.⁹⁹

3.3.5 The *christocentric* and *pneumatic*

Winkler identifies two forms of baptism in the Eastern Mediterranean at the end of the fourth century: ‘The Pauline *christocentric* death-mysticism and the Johannine *pneumatic* birth-mysticism.’¹⁰⁰ The first took as its starting point Romans 6. 3-4 and the second referred to John 3:5. The *aqua viva* rite predominated in Egypt, Syria and rural Palestine and the death-regeneration rite was overwhelmingly Jerusalemite. We should be cautious, however, in drawing too tight an affiliation between Cyprus and Jerusalem. A predominantly Pauline rite removed from Jerusalem’s topographical specificity might license the absorption of other paradigms. Furthermore, Cyril himself acknowledged the Johannine paradigm in *CL* 3.11-2 and *MC* 3.1.¹⁰¹ Origen’s identification of the Jordan

⁹⁶ Wilkinson (2002a) 163

⁹⁷ Day (1999) 8

⁹⁸ Ovadiah and de Silva (1982) 122-170, 123; Day (1999) 36

⁹⁹ Day (2007) 134 and (1999) 33

¹⁰⁰ Winkler (1985) 54

¹⁰¹ Cross (1986) 64

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with 'descending' clearly resonated with Pauline imagery of descent into the tomb and two Cypriot fonts dramatize precisely this aspect. The western entrance to the font at Agios Epiphanius was preceded by a high threshold followed by four steep steps into the font with an ascent eased by an additional fifth step [3.88]. Similarly at Kourion a steep ramp led to the top of the western stairs, followed by a high parapet on the far side of which was a steep drop before the topmost step into the font, while to the east the parapet was lower and the exit ramp almost horizontal [3.89-90].¹⁰²

3.4 Cyprus: reconstructing the early liturgy

3.4.1 *Lignum Crucis*: presence, dispersion, politics

The Cyrilline rite drew on the events for which the *lignum crucis* was the primary witness - a material presence, at once specifically located and widely dispersed.¹⁰³

In CL 4.10 Cyril describes how 'the whole world is filled with portions of the wood of the Cross.'¹⁰⁴ In Drijver's view, the distribution of relics of the Cross had a political motive as an initiative to advance the case for Jerusalem's independence from Caesarea on the basis of the Holy City's unimpeachable pedigree.¹⁰⁵ Caesarea was itself administered from Antioch whose writ also ran in Cyprus. Although Epiphanius as 'the Father of Cypriot autocephaly' was a later appellation, Cyprus would doubtless have felt a powerful bond with Jerusalem, given its own apostolicity founded on Barnabas.¹⁰⁶ A legend, possibly initiated by Cyril, implicated Cyprus more intimately with the Cross as a 'saving trophy'. Written c.1458, the *Chronicle* of the Cypriot historian, Leontios Machairas, tells how Helena, returning from the Holy Land after her discovery of the True Cross, endowed Cypriot foundations with relics of the cross of the Penitent Thief.

¹⁰² Piccirillo (1985) 345-355 identifies the high lip at Qal'at Sim'ān as indicating the point of entry into the font and the lower lip as the exit. Brenk (2007) 691-725 at 707 disagrees, hypothesising an entry from the north, exiting southwards into the adjacent basilica.

¹⁰³ Drijvers (2004) 156

¹⁰⁴ CL 4.10 also 13.4 in Parker (1838) 39, 144

¹⁰⁵ Drijvers (1992) 81-93; Cyril's *Letter to Constantius* of c.351, mentions that 'the saving wood of the Cross was found in Jerusalem...' but makes no more precise identification. See also McCauley and Stephenson (1970) II.232. The sixth-century, Cypriot *Inventio Crucis* (PG 87/3 4069) by the author of the *Laudatio Barnabae*, makes no mention of relics of the True Cross on Cyprus

¹⁰⁶ Jerusalem first broke with Caesarea and Antioch in 422 when Juvenal became bishop of Jerusalem, turning the tables on Antioch and insisting that 'according to the Apostle's order and tradition the see of Antioch should be corrected and judged' by Jerusalem. Honigman (1950) 214-5

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¹⁰⁷ Although there is no fourth-century evidence for Helena, for politically-astute Cyril, distributing relics to Cyprus made sense as a reciprocal pledge between sees seeking similar outcomes on substantially the same grounds. While Cyril makes no mention of Helena, he does date the discovery of the Cross to the reign of Constantine (324-37). Most scholars now accept that the story of Helena's discovery was of Jerusalemite origin, probably c.390, when Cyril's nephew, Gelasius of Caesarea (r.367-373, 379-395), first gave the story narrative form, probably at his uncle's urging.¹⁰⁸ Helena's 'invention' had already achieved wide currency by the 390s, when Ambrose referred to her discovery in his funeral oration for Theodosius in Milan in 395.¹⁰⁹ Given Cyril's own evidence that portions of the Cross 'almost filled the whole world,' it is conceivable that Cyprus received relics under a Cyrilline dispersion.¹¹⁰

For Cyprus and Jerusalem, the authority of Caesarea and Antioch was particularly unpalatable because their sees were occupied by Arians: Gelasius's predecessor, Acacias, in Caesarea (340-366) and a succession of Arians and semi-Arians in Antioch between 342 and 361, which remained schismatic for nearly sixty years thereafter.¹¹¹ Cyril himself was not untainted by Arianism. Jerome, writing c.380, thought the election of Cyril was part of an Arian conspiracy. Epiphanius, too, while admitting that Acacius and Cyril were at odds, nevertheless described Cyril as semi-Arian.¹¹² However equivocal a figure Cyril may have been before 381, after the Council he emerged as an avowed Nicæan, taking a leading role in promoting the Theodosian agenda, a principal purpose of which was Arianism's final suppression.

If Cyril was *persona grata* in Cyprus post-381, was *MC*, as his principal post-381 text, held in similar esteem - if, indeed, Cyril was its author? The case against Cyril and for his successor John II (386-417) has been argued on the grounds that no manuscript mentions Cyril as sole author and the oldest identifies John.¹¹³ Moreover, Jerome cites Cyril as the author of *CL* but makes no mention of *MC*. The most recent and persuasive

¹⁰⁷ Leontios Makhairas in Dawkins (1932) I. 5-9

¹⁰⁸ Drijvers (2004) 169

¹⁰⁹ S.Ambrose, *De Obitu Theodosii Oratio* 40-9. *PL* MPL016 col. 1399-1403. Staunchly Nicæan Gelasius had two periods as bishop, interrupted between 373 and 379. Heid (1989) 41 identifies the first mention of the invention as Ambrose in 395.

¹¹⁰ *CL* 10.19 in Parker (1838) 108. For doubts about the legend see Menardos (1970) 315-340. For the dispersion of relics of the Cross see Heid (1989) 49-51

¹¹¹ For Cyril as a closet Arian see Drijvers (2004) 181

¹¹² Doval (2001) 16 n.18

¹¹³ Swaan (1942) 1-43

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case for John has been made by Day, who detects Origenist traces in *MC* and argues for a date after Cyril's death in 386.¹¹⁴ This would predate by seven years the contentious encounter between Epiphanius and John over the latter's Origenist sympathies. If Epiphanius recognised John as author, *MC* might have provided an uncongenial template for Cyprus. Yet Epiphanius, ever alert to traces of the 'spiritual father of Arius,' is silent on both author and text, possibly because he found nothing Origenist in either. This is Yarnold's view, who dates *MC* to 383 or 386, describing it as totally free of the kind of 'undisciplined flights of the imagination' that Epiphanius found so repugnant in the Egyptian theologian.¹¹⁵

Unfortunately the textual evidence for Epiphanius' promotion of a Cyrilline rite in Cyprus is negligible. It is highly probable that triple immersion was the rule on the island, because Arianism asserted that immersion was once only, 'in the name of the death of Christ,' for whom there is no Resurrection because he was not consubstantial with the Father.¹¹⁶ We can also assume baptism as a once-only event because Epiphanius condemns multi-baptizers in unequivocally Pauline terms.

...it is in fact not possible to renew those who have been renewed once and fallen away. Christ cannot be born any longer to be crucified for us, nor can anyone again crucify a still uncrucified Son of God, or receive a second baptism; there is only one baptism and one renewal.¹¹⁷

Only 53 kilometres separated Cyrilline Jerusalem and Epiphaniian Besandūk.¹¹⁸ The *Vita* records three visits to Jerusalem. In Chapter 45 Epiphanius spends a 'few days' in the Holy City on the way to Egypt and at Chapter 55 he spends a further 'few days' in there before deciding to visit Hilarion in Cyprus.¹¹⁹ The first, *en route* to Egypt, was probably apocryphal but a second c.367 is quite likely and veneration of the True Cross would have been a necessary obligation. The visit mentioned in Chapter 77 is the best attested and occurred a few years after Cyril's death when, in September 393, Epiphanius arrived in Jerusalem to confront John on the subject of his perceived Origenism, an encounter

¹¹⁴ Day (2007) 139-40

¹¹⁵ Yarnold (1978)147; Drijvers (2004) 61 suggests that 'the Mystagogics are the notes of instructions Cyril gave towards the end of his episcopate and these notes were used by John for his own lecture.'

¹¹⁶ Sozomen *EH* 36 (2010 reprint) 253

¹¹⁷ Epiphanius IV 38 (51) 2,1 also 5,3 in Williams (1987) II.103, 107

¹¹⁸ For the case for and against Besandūk as the site of Epiphanius' monastery, see Rapp (1991) I.119

¹¹⁹ Rapp (1991) II. 107, 122

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which the *Vita* places at the foot of Golgotha.¹²⁰ Describing the same encounter, Jerome, too, places Epiphanius in the courtyard between the Anastasis and the Martyrium, leading a procession to the site of the crucifixion.¹²¹ Fraser goes further, suggesting that Epiphanius used the occasion of the Encaenia, the Feast of the Invention of the Cross, to preach against John.¹²² Veneration and confrontation, then, were set only a stone's throw from the baptistery at the foot of Golgotha, suggesting that Epiphanius would have encountered the architectural setting for the Cyrilline rite on at least two and possibly three occasions. But Sozomen suggests a further connection because, in addition to Easter, the Encaenia included 'initiation by baptism.'¹²³

The Johannine rite referred to a single event; the Pauline rite constructed a narrative. The first could be performed in a single space but the complexity of the second demanded a series of stations - thus Christ's stripping, crucifixion and entombment were assigned to the *apodyterion* and the font, and his Resurrection to the first communion. Nowhere were the narratological stations so encoded as they were on Cyprus. Perhaps the strongest evidence for a Cypriot preference for a Pauline rite remains its cross-in-square baptisteries, its cruciform fonts and, above all, their orientation. Arguably, Cyprus represented a corrective to Jerusalem by turning its baptisteries through ninety degrees, in conformity with the underlying symbolism of the Cyrilline rite. A west-east alignment of *apodyterion*, font and *chrismarion* permitted a more literal progress from darkness and renunciation in the west to illumination and inclusion in the east, reconstructing a stational sequence explicit in *MC* but by no means articulated in what is known of the setting to which its text presumably referred. We might conclude that *MC* implicitly recognised a mismatch between rite and setting, and, that, furthermore, it provided a template by which a fundamentally Pauline paradigm might be more fully realised in Cyprus.

¹²⁰ Rapp (1991) I.118, II.148

¹²¹ 'ante sepulchrum Domini...cum Anastasi peregreitis ad crucem...' Jerome, *Contra Johannem Hierosolymitanum* in Freemantle (1893) 3430

¹²² Fraser (1996) 177 n.558

¹²³ Sozomen *EH* 2:25 (2010 reprint) 83-4

3.5 Modifying the model

3.5.1 The material evidence

During the sixth century Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion were subject to alterations principally affecting the layout of their *chrismaria*. Despite its partly-excavated state, evidence for Proconnesian revetment at Ayios Epiphanius suggests that it too may have been the subject of a later refurbishment, perhaps when the intermediate columns in the aisles were removed.

Changes to *chrismaria* are evident at Ayios Philon probably at the same time that the baptistery received an extensive *opus sectile* décor, the floor of which substantially survives.¹²⁴ For Michaelides, the compartmentalisation characteristic of high quality *opus sectile* 'followed and echoed the architecture of the building.'¹²⁵ But Ayios Philon tells a different story.

The baptistery's west aisle was paved with hexagonal *crustae* of a pale biscuity breccia, with triangular *crustae* set against each face [3.91]. In the middle of the aisle a large star filled its entire width [3.92]. Within the star the southernmost triangle attached to the central hexagon was replaced by ogival *crustae*, suggesting a flight of rounded arrow heads directed southwards towards the *apodyterion* [3.93]. The first clue that the floor had a different agenda from the layout of the baptistery was signalled by the alignment of the star, not with the western portal to the baptistery, but slightly to its south. In the original layout, this portal was aligned with an apse in the east wall of the east aisle [3.94]. This west-east axis was entirely removed when the eastern apse was walled up. A skirting of the same biscuity breccia used in the floor suggests that walling-up the apse and reflooring the baptistery belonged to a single campaign [3.95]. A second device is figured in the floor of the east aisle, poorly preserved and confused by maladroit resetting so that only the central diamond, orientated north-south, is legible [3.96]. This was surrounded by another motif, now largely destroyed, possibly in the form of four truncated triangles, each with its base set on one side of the diamond. What begins to look like a conscious disruption of the former west-east axis is explicit in the nave. Two

¹²⁴ du Plat Taylor/Megaw (1981) 250

¹²⁵ Michaelides (1993) 72

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narrow transverse panels of *opus sectile* along its south side emphasise the baptismal suite. While the main motif in the remainder of the floor, a large circle in a square, is on axis with the font, it lies north of the axis formerly constructed by the west door and the east apse [3.97-8].

The principal effects of the new décor were, firstly, the virtual abandonment of a west-east alignment in favour of three virtually independent north-south aisles, emphasized by the slightly raised floors of the outer aisles [3.99], and, secondly, a new emphasis on the baptismal suite.

To these indications of a generally southwards pressure must be added the momentum eastwards through the three principal chambers of the baptistery, which also underwent considerable modification. The earliest layout was probably symmetrical, with one vestibule before the *apodyterion* and another after the *chrismarion*. Two later phases seem to imply a new liturgical bias towards those parts of the rite performed in the *chrismarion*. At just under 5.0m, in the second phase, the *chrismarion* was the same length as the *apodyterion* and its vestibule combined, suggesting that the *chrismarion* may indeed have been bi-cameral. If so, in the second phase, and before the insertion of the *opus sectile* floor, the two parts were combined, a recess was opened in the south wall and the east wall received the semi-circular apse and alcoves already referred to. The shelved alcoves probably held for the new garments for the *neophōtistoi* and a narrow shelf at the back of the apse was possibly for *myron*, the oil used for anointing the newly baptised [3.100].

In a third phase, probably in the later-sixth century, the new *opus sectile* floor was laid. Following the direction of the ogives filling the star motif in the west aisle, the *phōtizomenoi* progressed southwards towards the vestibule of the *apodyterion*, where the southwards-pointing ogives were repeated throughout the floor [3.101]. The centre of this first vestibule was occupied by a large diamond motif outlined in small white marble triangles, possibly with a frame of white hexagons - both cut from *spoliata* Proconnesian plaques. From the vestibule the *phōtizomenoi* turned east and entered the *apodyterion*, re-floored as a single field without a central emblem but with the same ogival *crustae* indicating the font [3.102]. Having passed through the font, the *phōtizomenoi* emerged into the quasi-vestibule of the *chrismarion* which employed the same decor as the vestibule of the *apodyterion* but with elements of the motif reversed;

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here the ogival *crustae* pointed north rather than south and the diamond motif was marked out in black rather than white triangles [3.103].

The climax of the whole scheme was the anti-clockwise circular vortex which dominated the pavement of the *chrismarion* [3.104]. It consisted of elongated hexagons, alternately breccia and Proconnesian *crustae*, which diminished in size centrifugally toward a centre. Given the rigorously symmetrical arrangement of the east wall of the *chrismarion*, it would have been possible to align the vortex with its central apse. However, its designers set their motif asymmetrically against the threshold into the east aisle. This is the concluding misalignment with a major element of the architectural setting, which began with a southwards drive in the court and continued with an eastwards drive through the baptismal suite. The vortex suggests that the final part of the rite was now performed in the context of this extraordinarily powerful transformative motif.

The south wall of the court remained a symmetrical arrangement of columns and alcoves, corresponding to the symmetry of the font which lay behind it. In the final refurbishment, what the symmetrical façade presaged the baptismal suite substantially modified. Vestibule-*apodyterion*-font-*chrismarion*-vestibule (A-B-B-A) became, in the later re-arrangement vestibule-*apodyterion*-font-vestibule-*chrismarion* (A-B-A-B) [3.105].

Despite the hazards of adducing a liturgy from its setting, the early rite clearly constructed a symmetry either side of the font, in which dis-robing and pre-baptismal anointing corresponded with re-robing and post-baptismal anointing. The change of emphasis indicated by the vortex undermined that symmetry and hence the status of the font, giving a greater eastwards-impetus towards the *chrismarion*. But was Philon a special case?

At Ayia Trias the *chrismarion* was 6.3m in length, exactly the length of its *apodyterion* and vestibule combined, suggesting that, in its initial phase, this *chrismarion* too may have been bi-cameral. Had there been a wall here, it would probably have been removed when the apse was added to the *chrismarion*'s east end [3.106]. This must have been a later addition, given the straight unbonded joints where the apse abutted

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the lateral walls. Furthermore, the apse encroached onto a corridor to the east of the baptistery, reducing it to a barely serviceable 0.55m [3.107].

There were modifications at Kourion too. A free-standing apse was built at a distance from the font, equal to the length of the westernmost annex, giving the same ABAB arrangement evident at Philon. Almost certainly a later addition, it was single-skinned and built directly on the stone flags; a straight joint abutted the north wall to which it was asymmetrically attached, leaving a metre-wide passageway to the south and a lobby to the east [3.108]. If this apse is analogous to the changes at Philon and Trias, it is distinguished from them in not being set against an east wall. Hence the lobby followed the apse rather than preceded it. Nevertheless, the late addition of honorific niches, possibly with semi-domes, at certainly three of the four processional baptisteries suggests significant change.

3.5.2 Demographic evidence

Changes to the Cypriot *chrismaria* might be explained by a decline in the number of candidates coming forward for baptism. Numbers may have been spectacularly high when, in 404, Chrysostom was confined by Empress Eudoxia while her soldiers scattered 3000 *phōtizomenoi*.¹²⁶ But by the mid-sixth century, Justinian's Novella 137 (565) complained of clerics 'ignorant of, or [who] do not perform...the ceremony of baptism.'¹²⁷ Furthermore, by the seventh century the rite of dismissing catechumens had been largely abandoned and hence *katechumenaia* allocated for mass baptism may have seemed unnecessarily spacious.¹²⁸

We can hypothesise a similar 'reduction,' given the relocation of the *katechumenaia* at Kourion from the flanking corridors of the episcopal basilica to a single *katechumenaion* in the east peristyle of the atrium.¹²⁹ Similarly Stewart's reconstruction of the sixth-century façade at Agios Epiphanius reduced the number of entrances from five to a

¹²⁶ Bury (1923) 156. The number may be exemplary based on Acts 2:41, 'They then that received his word were baptized: and there were added unto them in that day about three thousand souls.'

¹²⁷ Krueger in Kelly, Flower and Williams (2010) 62

¹²⁸ Mathews (1971) 128 writes of the capital that 'a class of catechumens, however diminished in size, seems to have survived at least until the seventh century.' Taft (1980-81) 53 n.50 confirms that by the seventh century 'The dismissals were an inoperative formality.'

¹²⁹ Megaw (2007) 119

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single central portal, suggesting a radical reduction in those excluded from the Eucharist.¹³⁰ However, given the nature of the refurbishments at Ayios Philon and Kourion, numerical decline may have been no more than the background to more significant changes to the liturgy.

3.5.3 Later liturgical Evidence

In their report of the excavations at Ayios Philon, du Plat-Taylor and Megaw suggest the following hypothesis:

The suppression of the apse in the main chamber, when the marble revetment was re-set passing across it, suggests that there would have been a change in the ritual, as seems to have been the case at Kourion also.¹³¹ Initially, the anointing with chrism may have taken place in the east aisle, before the candidates proceeded to the font, in conformity with the early practice in the Syrian church. Later, probably when the rift with the Church of Antioch deepened and the independence of the Cypriot church was confirmed...it was suggested that the practice of Jerusalem was adopted. In this, baptismal unction did not precede, but followed, the rites at the font, and took place in what became known as the *chrismarion*.¹³²

Du Plat Taylor and Megaw argue that Jerusalemite practice was adopted *after* the abandonment of the Syrian rite. However, there are good grounds for hypothesising the reverse – that a rite which drew on the narrative and topography of Jerusalem gave way, probably during the course of the sixth century, to a more eclectic paradigm.

If we choreograph Megaw's early-Syrian rite onto the baptistery at Ayios Philon we immediately encounter some awkward manoeuvrings. If the *phōtizomenoi* renounced Satan in the west, they would have crossed to the east apse for what must have been an exceptionally modest pre-baptismal anointing (given the presence of sponsors), before retracing their steps and entering the baptismal suite from the west. It seems more likely that the apse in the east aisle would have been used for a concluding greeting of the kind Doval proposed for the north annex in Jerusalem, for which the *parekklesion* at

¹³⁰ For an alternative explanation see Meyendorff (1984) 40 who suggests that 'At first [catechumens] were dismissed before the anaphora, but later they were allowed to remain as onlookers.' However, Germanus 35 in Meyendorff (1984) 85 states that 'The catechumens go out because they are not initiated into the baptism of God.'

¹³¹ Megaw (1976a) 364-367

¹³² du PlatTaylor and Megaw (1981) 236-7

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Kourion may also have served.¹³³ But how might we account for a Cypriot re-orientation away from Jerusalemite allegiance?

3.5.4 Arians and unfinished business

Principal amongst Nicaea's unfinished business was the status of the third person of the Trinity and a final suppression of Arianism. In Epiphanius' mind the two may have been linked because he accused Arius of regarding the Holy Spirit as a creature of the Son and hence a 'creature from a creature.'¹³⁴ Nevertheless, the Council of Constantinople, convened, in part, to resolve both questions, may have had more success with the former than the latter because in its so-called Dogmatic Definition, the Council of Chalcedon in 451 felt it necessary to restate the position supposedly reached in 381:

And because of those who oppose the Holy Spirit, it ratifies the teaching about the being of the Holy Spirit handed down by the 150 saintly fathers who met...in the imperial city...by clarifying their idea about the Holy Spirit by the use of scriptural testimonies against those who were trying to do away with his sovereignty.¹³⁵

What had not been affirmed at Nicaea, or Constantinople for that matter, was the Holy Spirit as consubstantial.¹³⁶ Hence the so-called Nicene-Constantinopolitan creed, and the position of the Holy Spirit, might be assigned not to 381 but to Chalcedon seventy years later. Given McDonnell's insistence that the Nicene-Constantinopolitan creed was in use as a baptismal creed well before it was a conciliar appropriation, we might ask whether the reassertion of 451 had repercussions for later-fifth and sixth-century baptismal practice.¹³⁷

3.5.5 John Chrysostom: a symmetrical liturgy

Unlike Alexandria which was collegiate, the school of Antioch was a loose association of individuals.¹³⁸ Its two leading figures were John Chrysostom (c.349-407) and Theodore of Mopsuestia (c.350-428), each of whom formulated rites in which the Holy Spirit was

¹³³ Doval (2001) 87

¹³⁴ Epiphanius VI.53 (73) 1.7 in Williams (1987) II.433-434; Dechow (1988) 286

¹³⁵ Tanner (1990) I.85

¹³⁶ Price and Gaddis (2005) 3.7

¹³⁷ McDonnell (2003) 152

¹³⁸ Maas and Kühn (2003) 7

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assigned to radically different parts of the liturgy and setting. According to Chrysostom, writing between 386 and 398, after a pre-baptismal anointing 'you go down into the sacred waters...at this moment...the Holy Spirit descends upon you.'¹³⁹ In Chrysostom, then, the font was central and the Holy Spirit was not identified with anointing with oil.

The broadly contemporary rites of Chrysostom and Cyril represent a tension between symmetry around the font and progress through it, implicit in the earliest baptismal practice - a fault-line described by Kelly as a 'considerable confusion between the theology of...chrismation and...baptism.'¹⁴⁰ For Ferguson, 'The association of the oil with the Holy Spirit...rival[ed]...the application of water for some church leaders.'¹⁴¹ In the late second or early third century, Origen identified the Holy Spirit as coming 'after the grace and renewal of baptism.'¹⁴² In the mid fourth century, Serapion's *Prayer* 16, described a post-baptismal chrismation in which the *neophōtistoi* 'become partakers of "the gift of the Holy Spirit.'¹⁴³ But perhaps the most emphatic statement of separation is a third-century Gnostic text from Syria.¹⁴⁴ The so-called *Gospel of Philip* describes "Chrism' [as] superior to baptism, for it is from the word 'Chrism' that we have been called 'Christians,' certainly not because of the word 'baptism.'¹⁴⁵

From Egypt to Syria, via Palestine, whatever the typological cast of the rite, the 'confusion' between immersion and chrismation was systemic: (1) in Cyrilline Jerusalem, 'If baptism was a death and resurrection, the gifts of the Spirit can hardly have been conferred before it;¹⁴⁶ (2) in Egypt and Syria, if the font was the Jordan, as Acts 1:5 explains, 'John truly baptized with water; but ye shall be baptized with the Holy Ghost not many days hence;¹⁴⁷ and (3) if immersion was understood as cleansing, the gift of the Holy Spirit would hardly have been appropriate before purification was complete.

¹³⁹ Harkins (1963) 52

¹⁴⁰ Kelly (1978) 435

¹⁴¹ Ferguson (2009) 855

¹⁴² Butterworth (1966) III.7 at 36

¹⁴³ Acts 2:38; Johnson (1995) 279-284; Brightman (1900) 88-113, 247-277; (1964) 43-50 suggests that Serapion's post-baptismal anointing, too, was a later addition to the Egyptian rite.

¹⁴⁴ Ehrman (2003) xi

¹⁴⁵ Robinson (1977) 144; Lee (2000) 45

¹⁴⁶ Brock (2008) 48

¹⁴⁷ Matthew 3:16; Mark 1:10. The distinction between the Jordan event and the descent of the Holy Spirit is not present in Luke and John.

3.5.6 Theodore of Mopsuestia: a procedural asymmetry

Although his *Catechetical Lectures* predated Chalcedon, the rite of Chrysostom's friend, Theodore of Mopsuestia, offers the closest match for later Cypriot baptismal practice. Theodore may have compiled his *Catechetical Lectures* in Antioch before 392 or during his episcopate in Mopsuestia, sometime before his death in 428.¹⁴⁸ He provides a link with Jerusalem, as the first Syrian to stress a Pauline typology, referring to baptism as a 'desire to participate in His death.'¹⁴⁹ Because Cyril makes no mention of re-robing until MC 4 we may assume his anointing was performed in a screened-off part of the baptistery adjacent to the font from which the candidate emerged naked.¹⁵⁰ In Chapter 27 of his fourth *Baptismal Homily*, Theodore crucially reverses the Cyrilline order:

After you have received the grace of baptism and worn a white garment that shines, the priest draws nigh unto you and signs you on your forehead and says, 'So-and-so is signed in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit.'¹⁵¹

Theodore, then, introduced a procedural asymmetry in which a mirror sequence involving disrobing and re-robing framing two anointings (ABBA) was replaced by a sequence in which divesting and re-robing were each followed by anointing (ABAB). But if Theodore offers a model for Cyprus, how are we to account for the gap between a late-fourth, early-fifth century Syrian rite and the related refurbishments undertaken at least a century later?

Meyendorff points out that Theodore had a wide readership in Chalcedonian circles.¹⁵² For Becker, 'At the same time that Theodore's works and person were condemned at the fifth ecumenical council of 553, they were emulated by writers in Latin, Greek and Syriac.' Theodore, he argues, 'was a contested figure whose influence could be felt across a wider span of the theological spectrum than many at the time would have liked to admit.'¹⁵³

¹⁴⁸ For an early date of c.383-392 see Mazza (1989) 45

¹⁴⁹ Mopsuestia in Mingana (1933) 52

¹⁵⁰ Ephraem the Syrian in Mcvey (1989) 249; also 1 John 2:20, 27; 2 Cor. 1,21

¹⁵¹ Mopseustia in Mingana (1933) 68

¹⁵² Meyendorff (1968) 57-8

¹⁵³ Becker (2006) 44

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The second possibility is that the order described in Chapter 27 of Theodore's *Baptismal Homilies* is a later interpolation. Mitchell in 1966 was the first scholar to propose this alternative; more recently, Varghese, in 1989 argued that a post-baptismal anointing associated with the Holy Spirit was such an innovation in early fifth-century Syria that it must have been an interpolation designed to conform to sixth-century practice.¹⁵⁴ If so, what might that practice have been?

3.5.7 Dionysius the Areopagite and the Barberini Euchologion

The material available for the reconstruction of the later Cypriot rite is meagre. While Syrian texts are relatively plentiful, the paucity of Constantinopolitan texts is the more disappointing given the widespread view that Constantinople was crucial to an understanding of Early Byzantine Cyprus.¹⁵⁵ While the *autocephalic* claim against Antioch was a live issue, an early Syrian rite in Cyprus seems unlikely. With the question largely resolved by the 480s, disaffection with things Syrian may have been less of an issue and given Constantinople's crucial role in confirming *autocephaly*, Cyprus may have deferred to the rite performed there. In identifying Constantinopolitan practice we are reliant on a single document, the *Barberini Euchologion* of c.790, which incorporated Constantinople's fifth-century *Ordo*.¹⁵⁶ Campbell, however, has argued that a Syrian text - the *Ecclesiastical Hierarchy* of Dionysius the Areopagite (485-518/28) - was so widely influential that it best represents sixth-century theology and practice, including a baptismal rite in which, according to Winkler, anointing and not immersion was the defining event.¹⁵⁷ Spinks brings us back to Theodore by arguing that the *Hierarchy* represents a continuation of Mopsuestian baptismal tradition.¹⁵⁸ By describing baptism as a 'Divine imitation' of 'the supremely Divine death of the Life-giving Jesus,' the Areopagite not only establishes a continuity with Pauline elements in his compatriot, he

¹⁵⁴ Varghese (1989) 98 is amongst the recent advocates of an interpolation. According to Mitchell (1966) 41 the first to suggest the possibility was Gabriel Khouri-Sarkis in 1962. See also Mopsuestia in Mingana (1933) 46 and 68-9

¹⁵⁵ E.g. Papageorghiou in Karageorghis (1986) 490-7

¹⁵⁶ Spinks (2006) 96

¹⁵⁷ Campbell (1981) 13; Winkler (1978) 36. Doubts about Dionysius as an early Christian author were expressed by Hypatius of Ephesus as early as 532, but according to Honigmann (1950) 268, 'these soon gave way to a general admiration, and both orthodox and Monophysites tried to explain them as authentic writings of the early Christian period, which were in conformity with their own doctrinal views.' Ferguson (2009) 720 identifies the writer as Greek of Syrian origin probably writing about c.500.

¹⁵⁸ Spinks (2007) 605. For the same sequence in Rome c.500 described by John the Deacon see Spinks (2006) 110

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a reaffirms those elements of the Cyrilline rite which were key to Cypriot practice.¹⁵⁹ The *Barberini* also describes 'being *planted together in the likeness of the death* (Rom.6.5.) of the Only-Begotten Son, through baptism,' raising the possibility that a largely Pauline rite predominated in the Eastern Mediterranean in the sixth- and early-seventh centuries too. But is Theodorian re-robing *before* a post-baptismal anointing also confirmed in the later rites and, if so, to what extent do their formulae accord with later changes to Cypriot baptisteries?

3:9 Apodyteria and chrismaria in the later rite

Given that the apse in the east court at Ayios Philon was walled-up and the apse in the *apodyterion* was not, we may assume that pre-baptismal anointing continued to be part of Cypriot practice into the later sixth and seventh centuries. The rites described in the *Hierarchy* and the *Barberini* would tend to support this assumption. According to the *Hierarchy*,

When the ministers have entirely unclothed him, the priests bring the holy oil of anointing. Then he [the hierarch] begins the anointing...and for the rest assigns the man to the priests for the anointing of the whole body, while he himself advances to the mother of filial adoption [the font.]¹⁶⁰

Pre-baptismal anointing in the *Barberini* is remarkably similar:

The candidate is anointed with olive oil, first by the priest on the forehead, breast and back: and then by the deacon all over the body.¹⁶¹

At the conclusion of Areopagite's rite, when the sponsor has

¹⁵⁹ Dionysius in Parker (1894) 59. The Areopagite possibly belonged to a group seeking to heal the Chalcedonian-Monophysite rift. Lacking a specifically Monophysite liturgy, we must rely on the evidence that the Monophysite Severus, Patriarch of Antioch (r.512-518) favoured a rite, part Johannine, part Pauline: see McDonnell (1991) 227. See also Ross (1957) 251 and fig.3 for a representation of Christ being baptised in the Jordan on a medallion made in Constantinople and found on Cyprus. For the Monophysite connection see Arthur (2008) 101-140

¹⁶⁰ Dionysius in Parker (1894) 56

¹⁶¹ Spinks (2006) 96

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cast the most appropriate clothing over him...they lead him again to the Hierarch, who when he has sealed the man with the most divinely operating Chrism pronounces him to be the partaker of the most divinely perfecting Eucharist.¹⁶²

According to the *Barberini* '[a]s many as are baptized in Christ have put on Christ'¹⁶³ which Spinks, drawing a comparison with the Areopagite, and on the evidence of later rites, understands as referring to re-robing.¹⁶⁴ After the post-immersion anointing the Areopagite describes how '[a]t the conclusion of all, the Hierarch invites him who has been perfected to the most Holy Eucharist.'¹⁶⁵ The *Barberini* has 'the priest approaches the entrance...with the neophytes, and the divine liturgy begins.'¹⁶⁶ Given an agreement of imagery and sequence in the Areopagite and the *Barberini*, the next step is to see how the later liturgy might be reconciled with the refurbishments on Cyprus.

All four Cypriot processional baptisteries exhibited some kind of bicameral layout before the font which was retained in the later refurbishments, the first being a lobby and the second the *apodyterion*. Megaw identifies the westernmost annex at Kourion as an *apodyterion*, because it was furnished with benches. However, it is more likely to have been a lobby.¹⁶⁷ The east corridor at Kourion, where the *neophōtistoi* assembled after chrismation, also had benches, suggesting that benches indicated waiting rooms. Furthermore, a lobby would have been essential at the west end of the baptismal suite at Kourion because the *phōtizomenoi* were naked at the pre-immersion anointing. In the rites described by Theodore, the Areopagite and the author of the *Barberini*, lobbies would have been superfluous post-immersion because the re-robing occurred immediately after the *neophōtistoi* emerged from the font.

It might be objected that re-robing could not have occurred immediately to the east of the font because, at Kourion and Trias, doorways led, respectively, into the north court or the east aisle. However, according to the Areopagite, the hierarch presided at pre- and post-baptismal anointings and at the font and would, therefore, have required means of access.¹⁶⁸ The Areopagite offers an additional explanation for the doorways –

¹⁶² Dionysius in Parker (1894) 56

¹⁶³ Whitaker (1970) 82

¹⁶⁴ Spinks (2006) 96

¹⁶⁵ Dionysius in Parker (1894) 60

¹⁶⁶ Whitaker (1970) 82

¹⁶⁷ Megaw (2007) 109

¹⁶⁸ Dionysius in Parker (1894) 56

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to admit sponsors who, post-immersion, were tasked with 'cast[ing] appropriate clothing' over the *neophotistoi*.¹⁶⁹

We do not know to what extent the more modest anointing described in the *Barberini* was witnessed, but the position of the vortex suggests that this may have been the case at Philon. Any threshold anointing must belong to Philon's final phase, because the *crustae* of its *opus sectile* floor were laid against the existing recesses in the *chrismarion's* east wall. But how are we to reconcile the symmetrical arrangement of these recesses with the asymmetry of the pavement? Most probably the bishop left his apsidal recess to anoint the *neophōtistoi*, because Theodore describes how 'the bishop comes over to you and puts a seal on your forehead.'¹⁷⁰ The Aeropagite says only that '[the bishop] makes the sign of the cross on him' with *myron*, although the *Euchologion* is more specific: the *neophōtistoi* were anointed on the eyes, nostrils, mouth and ears with the words 'the seal of the gift of the Holy Spirit.'¹⁷¹

If chrismation, rather than immersion, was now the defining event, what Kelly described as 'confusion' had become a post-Mopsuestian separation in which sealing with the gift of the Holy Spirit was the concluding and defining act. In token of its significance, the setting of the font had been in an apsidal recess crowned by a semi-dome. A similar setting for the new dispensation is attested by the addition of apses at Philon, Trias and at Kourion where there is also evidence for a semi-dome at Kourion.¹⁷² Furthermore, the length of the *chrismaria* at Trias and Kourion, with the bishop at one end, framed by a semi-dome-crowned apse, would have evoked something of the prestige of an episcopal audience hall, one in which the *charism* of the Holy Spirit and episcopal status were brought into intimate juxtaposition.¹⁷³

¹⁶⁹ Dionysius in Parker (1894) 56

¹⁷⁰ Mopsuestia in Mingana (1933) 68. It would have been more usual for a niche or apse to honour a seated hierarch: see Wharton (1987) 364

¹⁷¹ Dionysius in Parker (1894) 56

¹⁷² Megaw (2007) 201, Pl.5.4i. The *chrismarion*-apse at Philon may have been crowned by a semi-dome. Cf the mural niches at Soloi B: des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) 42-3. None of their semi-domes survive but cf. Dendera in McKenzie (2007) 283-4, figs 469-72. For a free-standing apse, throne and suppedaneum see Folio XVI, 31 of the sixth-century Vienna Genesis in Wellesz (1960) Pl.6

¹⁷³ Cf the white robes of the *candidati* of the imperial palace in Corripus *In Laudem*. III.224 in Cameron (1976) 188; Labarre (2003) 149-150

3.6 Conclusion: myron, autocephaly and episcopal authority

The Council of Ephesus (431) confirmed the right of the Church of Cyprus to ordain its own bishops, thereby granting the island the 'inalienable rites' of ecclesiastical and administrative independence from the entire pentarchy.¹⁷⁴ Writing of the Orthodox Church in the thirteenth century, Erickson noted that *autocephaly* was not only an ecclesiastical but a political issue 'which was expressed above all in the right to consecrate myron'.¹⁷⁵ Although Hill claimed that Cyprus continued to obtain *myron* from Antioch until 1860, it is arguable that, at least before the more developed form of the Pentarchy defined by the *Novella* 131, the consecration of *myron* may have been an episcopal preserve.¹⁷⁶ It might have been particularly prized by an *autocephalous* church, firstly, because, following Constantinopolitan practice, consecration involved the presence of all the island's bishops and, secondly, because the custom of incorporating *myron* from a previous preparation in the new supported Cypriot apostolicity by establishing a continuity with the oil used by the apostles in the anointing of the Christ's body. Apostolicity was similarly confirmed because conferring the *charisma* of the Holy Spirit was itself an inheritance granted to the apostles by Christ: 'Jesus is said to have baptised none but Peter; Peter to have baptised Andrew: Andrew James and John, and they the others,' and as successor to the apostles, it was, according to Cyprian, the bishop alone who was licensed to chrismate.¹⁷⁷

Brogiolo has recently argued that the rise in the power of the bishops was above all a sixth-century phenomenon.¹⁷⁸ At the beginning of this chapter I made the case for the Cyrilline rite as the exclusive and dominant baptismal liturgy in fifth century Cyprus. By the sixth century, however, Cyprus drew on a more widely dispersed rite, probably Syrian in origin, in which the defining event was relocated from the font to the *chrismarion*. At Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion the Holy Spirit was gifted beneath

¹⁷⁴ 'Resolution: that the bishops of Cyprus may themselves conduct ordinations.' Tanner (1990) I.68

¹⁷⁵ Erickson (1991) 109-10

¹⁷⁶ Hackett (1901) 31-2: 'the consecration of this holy oil is in the Orthodox Communion reserved to the Patriarchs, the Archbishops of Cyprus being of an inferior grade could not prepare it for themselves.'

¹⁷⁷ Moschos in Wortley (1992) 146; Jensen (2005) 129; Robinson (1977) 144

¹⁷⁸ Brogiolo (2011) 79-80. According to Lokin (1985) 45, in sixth-century Cyprus cases could be remitted to local bishops and dealt with in ecclesiastical courts rather than adjudicated at either Constantinople or Varna.

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honorific canopies which gave to their respective *chrismaria* something of the character of an episcopal reception room. Here *myron* constituted the transformative unguent which encoded the enhanced status of the third part of the Trinity, the rise of the bishop and *autocephaly* as an essentially episcopal privilege.

Chapter 4

4.1 Argument

Hitherto, my principal diagnostic tools have been texts, sites and plans. These permit only tentative reconstructions of buildings and the impulses of which they were the trace. Wall work holds the potential for more evocative readings but little survives on Cyprus and the survival of décor is rarer still. The principal exceptions are those apses incorporated into later structures of which the most impressive material survives from Kiti and for which, until the 1980s, evidence also remained from Lythrankomi and Livadia. There is no evidence for a Cypriot school of mosaicists, but each apse represents an aspect of the iconography of the Theotokos (Θεοτόκος), the Birth-giver of God, on Cyprus.¹ Furthermore, her appearance at Lythrankomi is amongst the earliest surviving representations in an apse mosaic.

Chapter 3 related the construction of apses in the chrismaria of Cypriot baptisteries to a sixth-century re-accentuation of episcopal power. This chapter returns to the subject of the basilica and the setting of the apse and its semi-dome, but as an honorific canopy and a site of display for the bishop and the Theotokos. The Birth-giver of God was particularly revered in Constantinople and her appearance on Cyprus has been understood as evidence of a sixth-century efflorescence from Constantinople. Van Esbroeck has argued that the import of Marian relics was a re-creation in the capital of the sacred topography of Sion, the site of her dormition, and Gethsemane, the site of her assumption.² Chapter 2 argued that, quite independently and earlier, these crucial buildings of the Theodosian renewal were cited in Cyprus. The present chapter argues two points: firstly that apse decor was integral to the symbolism of the bema and its furnishings, and secondly, that the appearance of the Theotokos on Cyprus was less of a Constantinopolitan dependence than a specifically Cypriot appropriation.

Section 1 situates the apse mosaics of Lythrankomi and Kiti as integral to a distributed and inter-referential 'exegetal scheme of church decoration...rather than [as] independent bearers of meaning.'³ The scheme extends from relative fixtures – the apse and the bema, to

¹ For objections to 'Mother of God' see Peltomaa (2001) 135

² van Esbroeck (1988)182 and (2005) 68

³ Leader-Newby (2004) 94

the mobile – ripidia (liturgical fans) and oraria (liturgical stoles). Thrones and altars have been identified by Wharton ‘a[s] those liturgical accoutrements...most intimately associated with the bishop’s authority.’⁴ Section 2 argues that these key furnishings, particularly where overshadowed by an image of the Theotokos, belong to a wider Mariological reading of the entire bema. Section 3 proposes two related sources for the orant Virgin at Livadia, the first, as a type of Gaia and woman-as-wealth-bearer, represented by the hem of her maphorion, and the second, as a type of Tyche and Victory, in which her maphorion forms ‘an impregnable wall’ sheltering the small rural community for whom she constituted the worship focus. The final section describes the ‘Constantinopolisation’ of the Theotokos and asks to what extent her place on the island might have been a reflection of her role in the capital.

4.ii. Cyprus and the Council of Ephesus

[I]t is one in its basic reality without being divided into its parts by reason of the differences between them, but rather by their relationship to the unity, it frees these parts from the difference arising from their names. It shows to each other in turn what each one is for itself.⁵

For Cyprus the most significant outcome of the Council of Ephesus in 431 was conciliar recognition of its practice, ‘according to the old prevailing custom’ and against the claim of Antioch, ‘of performing for themselves the ordination of their excellent bishops.’⁶ Cyprus, however, was something of a side issue for a Council with more pressing business. Nestorius, the Patriarch of Constantinople (r.428-431), argued that the Virgin could only be *Christotokos* and not *Theotokos*.⁷ The Council rejected Nestorianism, anathematized its author, and declared in favour of the *Theotokos* as the Mother of God.⁸

Rheginos of Salamis, Saprikios of Paphos, Zeno of Kourion, Evagrius of Soli and the Protopapas Caesarios represented Cyprus at the Council.⁹ We can imagine their collective satisfaction at the, albeit qualified, autonomy recognised by the Council, but nothing is

⁴ Wharton (1987) 373

⁵ Maximus the Confessor in Berthold (1985) 188

⁶ Campbell (2002) 18

⁷ Nestorius: ‘I do not believe in a two or three-month old God’ in Brenk (2010) 73

⁸ PG Tom LXVII. Col.119

⁹ Hackett (1901) 16-17

recorded of their reaction to the recognition accorded the Virgin. However, a Council which recognised both raises the possibility that, independently of Constantinople, the Church of Cyprus may have held the Theotokos in particular esteem.

At Lythrankomi, dated by Megaw and Hawkins to 526-30, the *Hodegetria* was set in a mandorla with archangels on either side; at Kiti, dated by Foulis to 582-602, she occupies the same space as the archangels and at Livadia, dated by Megaw and Hawkins to the early seventh century, she possibly appeared entirely alone.¹⁰ The relatively remote locations of Lythrankomi and Livadia and the non-metropolitan location of Kiti suggest that these three were survivors from a larger corpus many, if not the majority, of which were Marian [4.1].¹¹ In order to construct a Cypriot context for the Theotokos I shall first situate apse mosaics as integral to the bema, as a hierarchical and dialogic space, before examining how a Marian context would have nuanced that dynamic.

4.1 The manifold bema

A bema (*βημα*) is a raised place signifying status which, in the context of the Christian church, was usually associated with the sanctuary.¹² By the sixth-century, the sanctuary, as an enclosure at floor level (Chrysopolitissa Phase 1 and Soloi A) and the 'circumambulated presbytery' (Soloi B and Kourion) were no longer autonomous structures *in* a congregational space but were relocated eastwards to fill hitherto-empty apses at Agios Epiphanius [4.2], Kourion [4.3] and Soloi B [4.4] and a wholly new apse at Chrysopolitissa [4.5]. The bema was now indissolubly anchored to its architectural setting.

If apsidal additions to *chrismaria* represented an intrusion of the episcopal audience hall into the baptistery, then locating the bema unequivocally at the east end of the basilica, and setting the episcopal throne in the apse, represented an extension of the episcopal

¹⁰ For Lythrankomi: Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 140; Sacopoulo (1975); Papageorgiou (1966) 17-19 and (1967) 29-32; Gkioles (2002) 31-6. For Kiti: Foulis (2004) 28. For Livadia: Megaw and Hawkins (1976) 3 363-66. Also Belting-Ihm (1992) 59-60 for Lythrankomi and 61 for Kiti; Chotzakoglou in Chrysostomides and Dendrinos (2006) 101-125 for Livadia 108 fig.13 and for Lythrankomi 108-9 fig.15.

¹¹ Tesserae were found in the destruction layer of the south-west basilica at Amathus (Aupert (1996) 88) and the main apse at Katalymmata ton Plakoton amongst others.

¹² Lampe (1961) 295 identifies the bema as (1). God's Judgement Seat, (2) the pulpit, (3) the place before the Judgement Seat, (4) the place of the bishop's chair with the presbyters on either side.

presidium over the entire *aula*, giving the bishop, visually and symbolically, complete authority over the proceedings performed there.¹³ The apse honoured the hierarch and the priesthood but only rarely did it honour the altar, which generally approached the apse no further than the chord.¹⁴ The infinity curve of the apse reached its apogee in the double curve of the semi-dome which was transformed, early in the sixth century, by a new visual repertoire. Hence, the apse and its semi-dome, invariably the same width as the nave, did not end the colonnaded street of the basilica but promised a soteriological extension of it.

4.1.1 *Synthrona*

In the sixth century the single-tiered *synthronon*, with possibly an episcopal throne on axis, emerged from its occluded position behind the altar and was elevated on a series of tiered semi-circular steps, the uppermost of which constituted the clergy bench. Enthronement on this 'sacred sphenone' constituted a visually explicit promotion of episcopal authority. However, of the approximately 24 *synthrona* proposed for Cyprus [4.6], no evidence survives for an episcopal throne; hence there is nothing comparable to the thrones at Poreč c.550 [4.7] or Cyrenaica c.533-565 [4.8], despite Aupert's assertion that the Acropolis basilica at Amathus had 'a white marble *synthronon* with the episcopal throne in the centre' [4.9].¹⁵ Site evidence offers no more than the single tier of a *synthronon* with a projecting step of the kind better preserved at Peyia where the steps stop at the third of at least five tiers [4.10] or at Kalavassos-*Sirmata* where all three steps survive from the *synthronon* [4.11]¹⁶

At Lythrankomi and Kiti a correlation can be established between an actual episcopal throne at the foot of the apse and Christ 'enthroned' by the Theotokos in the semi-dome above [4.12-14]. However, only in the case of Kiti is there secure evidence for a *synthronon* [4.15]. At Lythrankomi there appear to have been opposed clergy benches and evidence from

¹³ For niches in an imperial context: Deichmann (1976) 182. The change from a multivalent space to one focused exclusively on the sanctuary was arguably as dramatic a development in the evolution of the basilica as Christian adoption of the civic basilica.

¹⁴ For a similar situation in Constantinople, Mathews (1971) 38, 109

¹⁵ Aupert (1998) 77

¹⁶ The picture is confused by an overlap between Middle Byzantine adoption of earlier *synthrona*, and the construction of new *synthronon* after Late Antique practice. Tychikos/Nemesios at Limassol, Tychikos at Palodia and the miniature *synthronon* at Agios Georgios at Kyrenia may fall into this group.

Livadia is no more than vestigial [4.16].¹⁷ Furthermore, there is no correlation between stairs and *cathedra*, there being no evidence for projecting axial stairs in any major episcopal basilica on the island.¹⁸ Nevertheless, *synthrona* were clearly signifiers of status, given the embellishments they received and, in the case of Campanopetra, of the valuables they sheltered. Paulus Silentarius describes the top tier of the *synthronon* at Hagia Sophia in Constantinople as ‘stalls of silver’ and there is evidence from Campanopetra that, while Proconnesian marble dominates, selected polychrome marbles were reserved for revetting its *synthronon*.¹⁹ These embellishments suggest that stairs and platforms were more than a means of elevation, and were integral to an overall conception of enthronement. There is evidence that the space beneath the throne too was reserved for items of special value. It was practice in the ancient Near East to retain valuable documents in a box beneath the ruler’s throne.²⁰ In the Capella di Sant’Aquilino at S.Lorenzo Maggiore in Milan, Christ is enthroned with his apostles, with the scroll-filled *capsa* at his feet [4.17].²¹ Valuables at the foot of the throne or beneath it may provide a context for what Roux terms a ‘salle du trésor’ directly beneath his proposed episcopal throne at Campanopetra [4.18]. Set into the inner wall of the *kyklion* [4.19], the half-barrel-vaulted tunnel beneath the *synthronon*’s top tier, were three recesses which Roux identified, collectively, as a *gazophylakion* and *skeuphylakion*, i.e. a treasury and a place for the vessels and vestments of the Eucharist [4.20-21].²²

4.1.2 Thrones

Whether or not there was a formal throne at Campanopetra, sitting on axis might, nevertheless, constitute enthronement. Dix characterises being seated as signifying authority, when he describes the hierarch ‘*sitting* upon the throne behind the altar which

¹⁷ Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 27. Smirnov (1887) 71 thought there had been a *synthronon*. Kiti was excavated by Dikigoropoulos in 1959 who discovered the remains of the first church. This included an early *synthronon* under two later ones. Dikigoropoulos (1961) 186. Soteriou (1935) 25 records a *synthronon* but no throne at Kiti and (at 35) no *synthronon* at Livadia. See also Foulis (2004) 14.

¹⁸ Thrones may have been portable: there may also have been broader platforms on the upper levels sufficient for a throne of the kind Roux proposes for Campanopetra.

¹⁹ Silentarius in Mango (1986) 81; Roux (1998) plan VI

²⁰ Exodus 25:16. Haran (1985) 255: ‘It seems that the practice of burying various books, documents, written oaths and covenants in a special case under the images of gods in temples was common in Egypt and in the Hittite kingdom.’

²¹ Bertelli (1988) 62-3

²² Roux (1998) 83

was his 'teacher's chair'.²³ For Mathews 'the repeated representations in Early Christian Art of Christ teaching, seated in the semi-circle of his disciples...contained for the faithful a very specific point of comparison with the view they had every Sunday of the bishop teaching, seated in the semi-circle of his clergy.'²⁴ At S.Pudenziana, around 400, Mathews hypothesises a relatively inconsequential altar dominated by a throne with clergy benches curving away either side [4.22].²⁵ In the semi-dome, the principles of this layout are repeated. A lavishly-enthroned Christ teaches the apostles who sit at his feet, receiving the teaching they will, in turn, disseminate [4.23]. For Dionysius the Areopagite the nine-stepped *synthronon* with the bishop arraigned with the nine ranks of clergy symbolized Christ amongst the angelic orders.²⁶ According to Germanus, when the bishop, *in persona Christi*, 'ascends the *synthronon* and blesses the people, this is the Son of God...bless[ing] his holy disciples'.²⁷ Hence, the bishop teaches and legislates with the authority of an unbroken lineage from Christ and the Apostles, figured only a few metres above him and at whose feet he sits.²⁸ In 381-384, Egeria described how 'The bishop's chair is placed on Golgotha behind the cross,' almost exactly the arrangement at S.Pudenziana where the enthroned Christ teaches at the foot of the cross.²⁹

At S.Pudenziana the bishop is entrusted with the church's title deed on behalf of Christ, who holds a book on which is inscribed the guarantee that 'I am the Lord, preserver of the church of Pudenziana.' Books as containers of the especially valued appear in more explicit form in the apse mosaic of the Chapel of S.Venantius in the Lateran Baptistery [4.24]. To the extreme right of the Virgin *orans*, S.Domnion and Pope Theodore hold gem-encrusted books [4.25]. Theodore, however, carries his book horizontally, which led Kendall to conclude that the Pope was not carrying a book but a reliquary.³⁰ He proposed that one gem-encrusted cover shelters the word and the other shelters a relic suggesting an equivalence of esteem and a reciprocal relationship between the value of what is carried and the status of its bearer. A similarly proportioned and gem-encrusted platform

²³ Dix (1945) 41

²⁴ Mathews (1971) 150

²⁵ Mathews (1993) 93 fig.70

²⁶ McVey (1993) 95

²⁷ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 61

²⁸ The axial throne at the foot of the apse at S.Vitale in Ravenna, if not an invention from De Ricci's late nineteenth-century restoration, may be part of the furnishings of 547.

²⁹ Egeria 25.1 in Wilkinson (2002a) 144

³⁰ Kendall (1998) 26 and n.22; Ladner (1941) pl.IXb

(*suppedaneum*) serves to identify the person and status of the Theotokos. Are we justified in seeing this platform as freighted beyond its function as simply a means of elevation?

4.1.3 Suppedanea

Thrones are bipartite - part seat, part footstool. According to Isaiah 66:1 'Heaven is my throne and the earth is my footstool.' Although apparently hierarchical, above and below, throne and footstool are in dialogue'³¹ I shall discuss the Theotokos as throne below and confine my remarks here to evidence for *suppedanea* on Cyprus.

At Lythrankomi the *suppedaneum* was edged in silver and topped in gold. Megaw and Hawkins describe what was still visible in the 1950s and 60s [4.26].

The alternating square and oval cabochon jewels have their mounts and claws drawn in gold tesserae. The square jewels are green at the center and the oval ones are of white marble which originally were doubtless pigmented with red. All the jewels are shaded with dark purple glass. Groups of four silver tesserae are set in vertical pairs to represent pearls between the jewels.³²

At Kiti the square *suppedaneum* is raised, table-like, on four legs [4.27]. Its upper surface, too, is gold and the sides are rendered in three zones, an upper and lower of alternating white (originally red?) and bronze squares, and a middle zone with rectangular emeralds on a gold ground. Even at remote Livadia, the footstool was lavishly treated with gold edged in silver [4.28]. Again the face consisted of three zones, with a similar alternation in the upper and lower bands. The middle-zone was decorated with seven red jewels (again probably white marble dipped in red pigment), alternately rectangular and diamond-shaped, probably in gold settings.³³

While the *suppedaneum* at Lythrankomi stays firmly within its mandorla, at Kiti and Livadia it breaks the integrity of the frame, projecting across the lower border of the semi-dome to engage spatially with the bema and the congregational space beyond. At one level the

³¹ C.f. Matthew 5:34-5

³² Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 57-8

³³ Megaw and Hawkins (1976) 363-366 at 364. Megaw (2007) 47 proposes a Virgin and Child for the east apse of the chapel to the north of the entrance from the forum at Kourion 'of which not a single tessera has been found.'

suppedaneum corresponds to the bema 'as a raised place signifying status' enclosed by richly decorated screens. At another the *suppedaneum* at Livadia and Kiti might be understood as an honorific canopy *au pied* which, when projected beyond the pictorial field, doubles as a fictive canopy for the bishop enthroned below.

4.1.4 Throne, footstool and altar

If 'earth is my footstool' the whole bema at S.Pudenziana, may be understood as a *suppedaneum* for both the enthroned Christ in the semi-dome and the hierarch enthroned in the apse.³⁴ But if the hierarch at the foot of the apse held the title to S.Pudenziana on behalf of Christ, he also served as a type of *capsa* beneath His throne. The altar, too, might be understood as a *capsa*, particularly when charged with a relic, or where the altar, understood as a sepulchre, contained the body of Christ as Christendom's title deed.³⁵ Particularly where the episcopal throne was raised above the level of altar, congregational sightlines could construe the altar as a footstool as, for example, in Roux's reconstruction of the apse at Campanopetra [4.29]. Moreover, the altar-as-footstool is supported by two psalmic references: 99:5 commands 'Exalt the Lord our God and bow down to his footstool' and 132:7 exhorts 'Let us go to his dwelling place; let us worship at his footstool.'

Despite Pope Felix's (r.269-274) decree 'that mass be celebrated over the memorials of martyrs,' it is sometimes asserted that Cypriot altars did not hold relics.³⁶ The very few surviving altars suggest a preference for the table-type on four to six supports.³⁷ There is evidence from the central basilica at Peyia [4.30], the Southwest basilica at Amathus [4.31-32] and two sites at Kalavastos - one at *Sirmata* [4.33-35] and another at Area V [4.36].³⁸ The

³⁴ Maximus the Confessor, 'The divine sanctuary as heaven and the beauty of the nave as earth,' in Berthold (1985) 189

³⁵ For Adomnan's use of *capsae* as reliquary see Fowler (1894) 76

³⁶ D.Nicolaou pers. comm. *Liber Pontificalis* I 158 in Davis (2010) 11. Crook (1999) 13 urges caution on this sixth-century compilation. By the fourth century the practice of charging altars with relics was widespread.

³⁷ Chalkia (1991) lists 23 Cypriot altars, the majority of which were offering tables including 6 with relief décor, 6 polylobed, 5 with frames, 4 round and 1 rectangular (from Kourion) see 136-7, 158-9, 177-8, 195-6, 216, 225 figs. 1,2,12, 65; Roux's catalogue in Argoud (1973) 133-96 at 181, 188, 192, includes 5 Sigma tables, 1 decorated with champlévé, 5 horseshoe-shaped tables; 6 polylobed fragments. The distribution of undecorated tables has yet to be established.

³⁸ No trace of an altar was discovered at Soloi: des Gagniers and Tinh (1985) 58; for Lambousa, Peyia and the Amathus see Papageorghiou (1986) figs 3,7 and 8; for Kalavastos see Rautman and McClellan (1990) 231-8

five-socket slab at Episkopi was cut down from the larger six-socket slab, which formed the base of the altar at Kourion [4.37].³⁹ Behind its centre-front post was a deep cavity c.0.22 x 0.19 at the opening, which may well have contained a relic.

The altar, rather than end-stopping a dialogic succession of throne-to-footstool, was itself understood as a throne. In his *Catechesis V*, Theodore of Mopsuestia describes the linen *katasarkion*, which covered the altar at the time of its consecration, as an image of Christ's winding sheet and the altar cloth itself, the *endyte*, as representing the glory of the Throne of God.⁴⁰ Throne and sepulchre recur in Germanus' reading of the altar as (1) 'The holy table [which] corresponds to the spot in the tomb where Christ was placed;' (2) the place of 'the mystical and unbloody sacrifice,' (3) 'the throne of God, on which, born by the Cherubim, He rested in the body,' and (4) as the table where, 'at His mystical supper, Christ sat amongst His disciples.'⁴¹ Finally he describes the hierarch standing at the altar: (5) 'God truly spoke invisibly to Moses and Moses to God; so now the priest standing between the two Cherubim.'⁴² Theodore and Germanus, then, describe a two-part altar, part table, part tomb, which Germanus also understands as a throne.⁴³ Threaded through Germanus' imagery of the tomb is the imagery of the Ark of the Covenant, particularly in his references to the Cherubim, who overshadow the Ark.⁴⁴ The Ark consisted of two parts. The upper section was the *propitiatorium* or *kapporet* which was itself, functionally bi-partite as the seat above which God spoke to Moses and, on the Day of Atonement, as Yahweh's holiest Altar of Sacrifice.⁴⁵ Beneath the *kapporet* was the 'chest of testimony,' the treasury which

³⁹ Megaw (2007) 332-3, pl.7.a; also Loverance (1990) 225-43

⁴⁰ Mopsuestia in Mingana (1933) 86; Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 83-4, 89: for problems of Germanus' authorship see 11-14. According to Hapgood (1906) 614, the double vesting of the Altar indicates its double significance: as the tomb of Christ and the throne of God. The first altar cloth represents the winding-sheet wherein the body of our Lord Jesus Christ was wrapped for burial. The second covering of the Altar, the *inditia*, of rich and brilliant material, typifies the glory of God's throne.

⁴¹ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 59

⁴² Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 91. Laderman (2007) 153 argues that the symbolic schema of the empty space between the Cherubim's wings representing the invisible presence of God in the Jewish understanding becomes the visible (incarnate) presence of the Jesus of Matthew 25: 31-34: 'When the Son of Man comes in glory and all the angels with him, he will sit on his throne.'

⁴³ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 46, 59

⁴⁴ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 59

⁴⁵ Leviticus 16:13-15; Exodus 25:21-22; Haran (1985) 255: 'If the *kapporet* with its Cherubim is God's throne, the ark itself is the footstool of the throne.'

safeguarded the Decalogue.⁴⁶ This combination of throne and vessel provided a particularly powerful template for early Christian readings of the Theotokos.

4.2. A Manifold Theotokos

4.2.1 Theotokos as throne

Oikos I (1) of the Akathistos hymn refers to the Theotokos as ‘the chair of the king.’⁴⁷ John of Damascus (c.645/6-749) describes the Theotokos in terms close to the iconography of Lythrankomi and Kiti: ‘You are the royal throne around which the angels stand.’⁴⁸ At Lythrankomi, Christ is enthroned by an already-enthroned Theotokos [4.38], while at Kiti the Theotokos no less ‘enthrones’ Christ seated on her left arm [4.39].⁴⁹

Written around the time of the Council of Ephesus, the fifth homily of Hesychius of Jerusalem describes Mary as ‘a throne not inferior to that of the cherubim,’ i.e. the *kapporet* of the Ark.⁵⁰ In the Rabbula Gospels, Folio 13v, of c.586 and therefore broadly contemporary with Kiti, a Theotokos standing beneath the canopy of the splayed wings of a cherubim may well refer to the cherubim overshadowing the *kapporet* [4.40].⁵¹ Her identification with the *kapporet*, the throne of the first person of the Trinity, belongs with her role as the throne of Christ, the second person of the Trinity. In the Rabbula gospels 13v this is evoked in the fall of the drapery between the Theotokos’ arms, reminiscent of another seat of judgment, the magistrate’s *sella curulis* [4.41] and a not dissimilar curve recurs in the leading edge of the maphorion of the Livadian Theotokos in Megaw and Hawkins’ reconstruction [4.42].⁵²

The Theotokos may also be identified as the treasury beneath the throne. At *oikos* 9 (17), the Akathistos refers to her as the ‘treasury of his providence’ and at *oikos* 12 (23), as the

⁴⁶ Exodus 39:35

⁴⁷ The translation used here is Peltomaa (2001b) 2-19 at 5. She makes no distinction between *kontakion* and *oikos* which are therefore identified in parenthesis.

⁴⁸ Cited in Brubaker and Cunningham (2011) 158. See Limberis (1994) 89 for discussion of the date of the hymn.

⁴⁹ Foulias (2004) 15 fig 7 shows a plan from the church archive that includes a throne which is absent from Soteriou (1935) 25

⁵⁰ Hesychius, Homily V ‘In honour of Mary, the Theotokos’ in Aubineau (1978) I.159

⁵¹ Hebrews 9:5

⁵² Mathews (1993) 104, fig. 76. Mathews dismisses any comparison between Christ’s throne and any imperial comparanda.

'inexhaustible Treasury of Life.'⁵³ The gem-encrusted *suppedaneum*, as a type of treasury, may also reference her as the 'unfading bud' of *oikos* 3. As a gem she is flawless: in Latin *gemma* is also an asexual bud from which a new organism grows. On clothing gems also had amuletic and apotropaic properties.⁵⁴ In the west, as *Maria Regina* [4.43-44], the Theotokos is identified by her jewelled collar; in the east, her bejewelled *suppedaneum* might also be understood as a defining and gem-protected adornment.

S.Maria Maggiore, the first Roman church dedicated to the Virgin as Theotokos, was rebuilt in 432, the year after Ephesus.⁵⁵ At the foot of the spandrels of its triumphal arch c.435, Jerusalem and Bethlehem are shown as cities protected by gem-encrusted walls and towers, for which the Akathistos provides further parallels: at *oikos* 12 (23) the Theotokos is both a tower and an 'impregnable wall of the kingdom [4.45-6].'⁵⁶ In the Adoration of the Magi on the north side of the same arch, two registers above the heavenly Jerusalem, Christ is represented enthroned above a be-jewelled *suppedaneum* which his young legs are too short to reach, leaving it in stark isolation [4.47].⁵⁷ The face side of the footstool has a proportion of 1:3.9. It may not be a coincidence that, on the south wall of the nave are three of the earliest representations of the Ark, striking in their rejection of God's instructions in Exodus 25:10 that the Ark be 2.5m cubits long and 1.5 wide and high [4.48-50].⁵⁸ The proportion of the long side in Exodus would be 1:1.6 whereas the proportions at S.Maria Maggiore are between 1:2.1 and 1:4.7. Furthermore, their shape approximates to the low, square box of Christ's *suppedaneum*, with a décor and proportion which has much in common with the fifth-century Varna reliquary which also has upper and lower bands framing a circular motif [4.51].⁵⁹ Revel-Neher suggests a parallel hypothesis – that the Ark at S.Maria Maggiore may have been based on the *sedes gestatoria*, the papal throne with attached *suppedaneum*, fitted with two gilded rings on either side through which passed two rods as bearers [4.52-3].⁶⁰

⁵³ Peltomaa (2001b) 15, 19

⁵⁴ Frankfurter (1998) 125

⁵⁵ Miles (1993)160; Rubin (2009) 95 suggests the rebuilding dates to the 420s.

⁵⁶ Peltomaa (2001b) 19

⁵⁷ Brenk (1975) 24-27 fig 48; Karpp (1966) fig.18

⁵⁸ (1) Priests and Levites carry the Ark; (2) the Ark carried across the Jordan (3) the Ark carried around Jericho. Wilpert (1917) Text III 461-3, 464-5, 465-6: Plates III 22-3.25; Karpp (1966) figs 125, 128, 138

⁵⁹ Cyprus was ruled from Varna under Justinian's reorganisation of the empire in 536. A reliquary excavated at Katalymmata ton Plakoton is of the same type as the outer reliquary from Varna. See Buschhausen (1971) 265 Pl.1, 294-5 Pl.17

⁶⁰ Revel-Neher (1995) 406; Weitzmann (1979) 631-2

These Roman arks stand in marked contrast to the only representation of the ark in an apse mosaic, at Germigny-des-Prés, c.806, which more closely follows the Biblical prescription [4.54].⁶¹ If the Arks at S.M.Maggiore make no reference to an altar, are their proportions intended to construct an equivalence between the ark on the south wall and Christ's *suppedaneum* on the triumphal arch, and hence to 1 Chronicles 28:2, 'I had in my heart to build an house of rest for the ark and for the footstool of our God?'⁶²

4.2.2 Theotokos as Ark

Apart from the two references to the Theotokos as a treasury, footstool imagery is entirely absent from the Akathistos. However, at *oikos* 12 (23), she is hailed as the 'ark gilded by the Spirit.'⁶³ This analogy runs as a *leitmotif* through early Mariology, and it is clearly a *topos* in late-fourth century Cyprus. Writing in 392 Epiphanius is emphatic that 'Mary (contained) the Word...For she herself was the holy ark.' Mary is not only a type of the Ark, the reverse is also the case: 'the ark was also made as a type of her.'⁶⁴

But the Holy Mary, the living ark, had the living Word borne within her. While she had within her another ark which was also alive, there was in the ark that had been placed in her the living Word.⁶⁵

Athanasius, in his *Homily on the Papyrus of Turin*, (373) referred to her as: 'O (Ark of the) Covenant...the Ark in which is found the golden vessel.'⁶⁶ In the following century, Proclus, patriarch of Constantinople (r.434-46) called her 'ark, because she did not carry the law, but was pregnant with the lawgiver'.⁶⁷ And Venantius Fortunatus, in the sixth century, described 'How blest that Mother in whose shrine, The Great Artificer Divine...Vouchsafed, as his ark to lie.'⁶⁸ Finally, John of Damascus (676-749) wrote that, 'the tablets written by God described

⁶¹ Freeman and Meyvaert (2001) 125, 129

⁶² Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 57-8 write of 'the square form of the footstool' at Lythrankomi; Ex.25:10-11

⁶³ Peltomaa (2001b) 19

⁶⁴ Dean (1935) 53; Luke 1:35

⁶⁵ Dean (1935) 53

⁶⁶ Lefort (1958) 5-50, 209-39

⁶⁷ Proclus, Homily V 'Encomium on Mary, the holy Virgin and Birthgiver of God' in Barkhuizen (2001)

95

⁶⁸ Miles (2001) 203

[her]; the ark of the law told [her] story.⁶⁹ The Ark of the Old Covenant, then, preceded the ‘womb of divine incarnation’ of the New Covenant.

The peak of Marian imagery of the Ark may have been co-terminus with her earliest surviving representation on Cyprus. Van Esbroeck argued that the Theotokos as the Ark ‘was introduced into the liturgy of the Dormition and became deeply rooted in the religious politics of the Byzantine Empire in the fifth and sixth centuries’.⁷⁰ He cited a new rite in both Constantinople and Jerusalem, initiated by Justinian with the intention of bringing dissenters into the Chalcedonian fold. Foulias dates Kiti to Maurice’s reign and there is evidence for that Emperor’s particular devotion to her, firstly as ‘a symbol around which to rally his dispirited realm’ and, secondly because Maurice was the first emperor for nearly two centuries to provide a *porphyrogenitus* (583-5), a son he christened ‘Theodosius’ or ‘gift of God.’⁷¹ In 591 Maurice initiated the Feast of the Dormition of the Virgin on August 15th. Like Justinian, he was active in Jerusalem and Constantinople. He built a church at Gethsemane over the Virgin’s tomb and instituted a *panegyris* at the Blachernae in 588, where the principal treasure was the Virgin’s *Maphorion*.⁷²

4.2.3 Covering and Overshadowing

If the Theotokos was understood as an Ark in the liturgies of sixth-century Constantinople and Jerusalem, she may have been similarly understood on an island that lay between them. It might be argued, for example, that the peacock’s eyes marking the wings of the Kiti archangels reference the many-eyed cherubim overshadowing the Ark [4.55]. At Lythrankomi and Kiti the manner of presenting the Theotokos as the Ark plays on the double meaning of ‘covering’ [4.56]. Firstly, the archangels’ feet rest on or near the outer edge of the base of the semi-dome and their heads converge towards its crown, hence, they ‘cover...the mercy seat.’ in the manner of the cherubim of Exodus 25:20, a sense which is most explicit at Germigny. Secondly, one of the archangels is Gabriel, the angel of the

⁶⁹ Brubaker and Cunningham (2011) 158. An inscription at the Blachernae describes the Theotokos as ‘An ark...holier than that of old, not containing the tables written by God’s hand but having received within it God himself.’ Ousterhout (1995) 101

⁷⁰ Van Esbroeck (2005) 68

⁷¹ Ekonomou (2007) 258, 263

⁷² Angelidi and Papamastorakis (2005) 209

Annunciation, by whose agency, according to *Kontakion* 3 (4), 'the Most High...overshadowed the Virgin, that she might conceive.'⁷³

4.2.4 Cherubim and Ciboria

Where the altar was set forward of the chord of the apse it was often covered by a ciborium, an independent aedicule consisting of a roof, sometimes in the form of a complete dome supported on four columns [4.57-8]. The imagery of overshadowing and covering is thematically, as it is structurally, present. Germanus referred to the altar covered by the ciborium as 'the place where [Christ] was buried...raised on a base' which '...corresponds to the Ark of the Covenant...' He goes on to draw an analogy between cherubim and ciborium: 'Next to it God commanded that two Cherubim be placed on either side - for KIB is the ark, and OURIN is the effulgence, or the light of God.'⁷⁴ This is made more explicit when, following Dionysius, he describes the priest proclaiming the *trisagion* '[w]ith the overshadowing Cherubim and Seraphim.'⁷⁵ The priest, then, is a type of the cherubim who, at Isaiah 6:3 and Revelation 4:8 sings 'Holy, holy, holy.'⁷⁶

Cherubic and seraphic overshadowings probably account for the peacocks above the ciboria on Folio 1v of the Rabbula Gospels [4.59]. It may also account for the angels with peacock-eye wings in the spandrels of the triumphal arch at Sinai (c.540), understood as a half ciborium [4.60-1], and the peacocks covering the *pigna* in the atrium of Old St Peter's understood as a full ciborium [4.62].⁷⁷ Although Megaw and Hawkins hypothesise a ciborium for Lythrankomi, no ciboria survive from Early Byzantine Cyprus.⁷⁸ However, a painted ciborium of 1500-1550 from Morphou/Güzelyurt reflects Germanus' text so closely, that one is tempted to hypothesise earlier prototypes [4.63].⁷⁹

⁷³ Peltomaa (2001b) 7

⁷⁴ Germanus in Meyendorff 5 (1984) 59

⁷⁵ Germanus in Meyendorff 41 (1984) 93

⁷⁶ Peers (2001) 47

⁷⁷ Boorsch (1982-3) 5. Peacocks now in the Braccio Nova Museum, Rome.

⁷⁸ Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 28

⁷⁹ Bolman (2010) 145

4.2.5 Cherubim in the liturgy

According to the late-fourth century *Apostolic Constitutions* ‘two deacons either side of the altar each hold a fan...of peacock feathers to ward off small flying creatures, so that they may not approach the chalice.’⁸⁰ The motion of the fans made from ‘feathers with eyes’ crossing over the altar represented the wings of the cherubim meeting across the *kapporet*. Liturgical fans (*ripidia*) were made in pairs: Ross assumed this was the case with the silver *ripidia* from Riha and Stuma, datable by control stamps to Justin II [4.64-66].⁸¹ The Riha *ripidion* makes an explicit connection between the cherubim who occupies the centre of the fan and the peacock ‘eyes’ which profile its edge.⁸² At Luke 1:35 Gabriel tells how Mary the ‘Most High will overshadow you.’ The Greek ἐπισκιάσει connotes incubation which in Luke 1:35 associates ‘the power of the highest’ hovering over the Virgin and the Child she will ‘bring to birth,’ which Gros, Best and Fuchs also identify with the Cherubim overshadowing the Ark.⁸³ *Ripidia* belong to the same topos: whether of polished silver or iridescent peacock’s feathers, they would have hovered and flashed, passing over the altar, catching the light from *polykandela* and reflecting it onto the mosaic in the semi-dome.⁸⁴ A possible correspondence between haloes and *ripidia* at Lythrankomi and Kiti is made more explicit at Germigny where *ripidia* waved over the altar would have corresponded to the halos of the ‘real’ cherubim overshadowing the ark/altar [4.67-8].⁸⁵ Further interplay between liturgical performance and apsidal imagery is suggested by the *borassus flabellifer*, (*ripidion=flabellum*) the Palmyra palms separating the angels and the mandorla at Lythrankomi, of which the broader leafed variety, according to Theophrastus, flourished on Cyprus [4.69].⁸⁶

⁸⁰ *Apostolic Constitutions* VIII.12.3 in Metzger (1987) III 179

⁸¹ See a Syriac Gospel from Deir Es-Za’Faran (c.1250) with angels under a ciborium waving *ripidia* inscribed with cherubim and a fringe of peacock’s eyes: Leroy (1964), I.374-5, II pl. 131/1; Kessler (no date) 2-4, 13; also a paten in Spier (2010) 258-259 fig.190 ascribed to Constantinople 547-550 showing angels with crossed *ripidia* of peacock feathers. For *ripidia* and S.Pudenziana see Schlatter (1992) 276-295 at 280

⁸² Mundell Mango (1986) 147-54: for Stuma (Istanbul Archaeological Museum No.3758) figs 31.4-5; for Riha (Washington, Dumbarton Oaks Collection No. 36.23) figs 32. 4-5

⁸³ Gros, Best and Fuchs (2007) 88; Exodus 24:15-16, 40:34-38; 1 Kings 8:10.

⁸⁴ Ezekiel 1.4-21 describes the Cherubim as having ‘A lustre like shining metal.’

⁸⁵ Zwirn (2008) 82-3; for *polykandela* on Cyprus, Megaw (2007) 49, 498, 531

⁸⁶ Megaw and Hawkins (1997) 97-8; Theophrastus in Hort (1916) I.141

Germanus develops an extended metaphor from the deacons waving *ripidia* above the Eucharistic vessels, who are 'in the likeness of the six-winged Seraphim and the many-eyed Cherubim,' to liturgical vestments.⁸⁷ He sees the *epitrachelia*, the presbyter's stole, as resembling 'the seraphic powers, covered, as if by wings.'⁸⁸ Deacons, too, were 'images of angelic powers [who] go around with...thin wings of linen *oraria*,' the stole, the ends of which were, at certain points in the liturgy, crossed over in imitation of wings.⁸⁹ When Justin II added the Cherubikon hymn to the Great Entrance, the faithful too were incorporated as those 'who mystically represent the Cherubim,' entering the court of the angels gathered around the throne of God,' which, at Lythrankomi and Kiti, constituted 'the holy Virgin Theotokos, His dwelling and life in the world,' accompanied by archangels.⁹⁰

4.2.6 Iconodule island?

In 577 Maurice settled a group of Syrian Monophysites on Cyprus.⁹¹ The Orthodox position was dyophysite - Christ had a human *and* a divine nature – hence the incarnate Christ could be imaged. Monophysites, on the other hand, recognised only the divine Christ, who was, therefore, beyond representation. We are well informed about the two periods of iconoclasm in 730-787 and 814-842, but we know little about the preamble to those debates and less still about debates between Orthodox and Monophysite communities on Cyprus. What evidence survives suggests that Orthodox Cypriots opposed the view that was to prevail in the capital.

Cherubim were images commissioned by God who also directed their mode of manufacture: 'And thou shalt make two cherubims of gold, of beaten work shalt thou make them.'⁹² Some indication of the part played by cherubim in the debate about images is provided by the defence offered by the Cypriot hagiographer, Leontios of Neapolis, who, in the 630s or 40s, referred specifically to cherubim 'fashioned by human hands,' arguing that, 'If you wish to

⁸⁷ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 95; mid-fifth-century Hosios David in Thessalonika conflates the cherubim of Ezekiel 1:4-28, 10:12, the seraphim of Isaiah 6:1-3 and the six-winged angels of Revelations 4:2-10

⁸⁸ Germanos in Meyendorff (1984) 67; Woodfin (2012) 7; Thornton (1996) 35-57; Psalm 102, 20-1

⁸⁹ Germanos in Meyendorff (1984) 67; Spatharakis (1976) 262; McGuckin (2004) 347; Woodfin (2012) 7

⁹⁰ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 97; Parry and Melling (1999) 117; Brightman (1896) 532; for the Cherubim as the guardian of the Throne of God see Ezekiel 1.5ff.10

⁹¹ John of Ephesus *HE* 6.15 in Payne Smith (1860) 412

⁹² Exodus 25:18; 25:20

condemn me, on account of images, then you must condemn God for ordering them to be made.⁹³ This is clearly a response to an existing debate and although details are lacking, its trajectory can be assumed, given that, as Dikigoropoulos and Mango have demonstrated, Cyprus not only escaped the depredations of the iconoclasts but regarded iconoclasm as a deviation from Orthodoxy.⁹⁴ Moreover, references to cherubim at the restoration of image veneration tend to support their role in earlier debates. At the second Council of Nicaea in 787, Tarasius the Patriarch of Constantinople (r.784-806), proclaimed 'Just as the Old Testament had the Cherubim of glory overshadowing the mercy-seat, let us likewise have images...of the Holy Mother of God...overshadowing our altars.'⁹⁵ Tarasius' remarks clearly echo those of Gregory II (r.715-731), addressed to a council convened in Rome in defence of images in 727: 'If the works of men's hands are to be rejected, then ought also the Ark of the Covenant and the cherubim to be rejected.'⁹⁶ It is possible, that, at the end of the sixth century, Cyprus was already promoting an iconodule position to which cherubim imagery was a significant presence.⁹⁷

4.2.7 Above, below, between

The uncircumscribed Word was present wholly amongst those below,
yet in no way absent from those above.
For a divine condescension occurred,
- not a descent according to place -
and a birth from the Virgin, seized by God, who hears this:
'Hail, container of the uncontainable God;⁹⁸

Peltomaa has argued that 'uncircumscribed' in line 1 of *oikos* 8 (15) of the Akathistos hymn refers to the consubstantial trinity, and 'condescension' in line 3 is a reference to 'the idea of becoming the flesh of the Logos.'⁹⁹ Lythrankomi and Kiti are usually interpreted in terms of

⁹³ Baynes (1951) 93-106 at 97:8; Leontius is probably the author of *Against the Jews* which includes perhaps the earliest defence of images in Byzantium. This survives in fragments quoted by John of Damascus in Louth (2003b) 28, 76. See also Hypatius of Ephesus in Mango (1986) 117

⁹⁴ Dikigoropoulos 273; Mango in Bryer and Herrin (1977) 4

⁹⁵ Freeman and Meyvaert (2001) 129

⁹⁶ Mendham (1850) xxiv

⁹⁷ Peers (2001) 103

⁹⁸ Peltomaa (2001b) 13

⁹⁹ Peltomaa (2001b) 13, 305

the latter.¹⁰⁰ This may be too limited an interpretation if the angels accompanying the Theotokos also reference the cherubim covering the Ark. If God 'dwellest *between* the cherubim' their wings shape the place of his habitation. Hence, Kiti, and Lythrankomi too, may reference *oikos* 8 (15), in so far as Michael and Gabriel as the 'cherubim' of the new dispensation, frame God invisible and God incarnate, as the consubstantial and 'uncircumscribed' First and Second persons of the Trinity.

Another reading of 'wholly [present] amongst those below, yet in no way absent from those above' might be dialogic. Lythrankomi and Kiti represent a Mariological counterpart to the Christological scheme at S.Pudenziana where the reconstructed setting provides a model for accessing a comparable dialogue on Cyprus – apse, décor, throne, footstool, altar and the bema itself – each references a raised place, as an index of status and a locus of the word. The *kapporet* was the place from which God spoke, which was above the footstool containing the Books of the Law. The episcopal throne which, viewed from the nave, appeared to be above the altar, was the place from which the hierarch spoke, 'ex cathedra,' below the incarnate Christ as Logos in the semi-dome. But a reigning Theotokos nuances the dialogue – she is both seat and sepulchre. As the *hodegetria* she is 'the King's throne' and evoked at the altar, she is both *kapporet* and ark.¹⁰¹ Her relationship to the episcopal throne too is distinctive: as the 'throne' in the semi-dome, she is also evoked in the throne of His representative at the foot of the apse.¹⁰² In the absence of those representatives, the episcopal throne becomes a type of *Hetoimasia*, the prepared throne of the second coming as pendant to the first coming, presented in the apses of Lythrankomi and Kiti, to which *Kontakion* 9 of the Akathistos so pertinently corresponds: 'All the ranks of the angels marvelled at the great work of your incarnation.'¹⁰³

¹⁰⁰ Ferguson (1996) 6-10

¹⁰¹ Peltomaa (2001b) 5

¹⁰² A reference explicit, for example, in the relationship between the apse décor and the cathedra at Poreč.

¹⁰³ Peltomaa (2001b) 15

4.3 The manifold *orant*?¹⁰⁴

4.3.1 Livadia's fertile crescent

The term 'Fertile Crescent' was first used by J.H. Breasted in 1916 to describe an arc from the northern littoral of the Persian Gulf, along the eastern shore of the Mediterranean to the Sinai desert [4.70].¹⁰⁵ Cyprus, on the extreme western fringe of the crescent, was not normally included, although Catling described the area around Larnaca as the 'fertile crescent' of the Cypriot Late Bronze Age.¹⁰⁶ The subject of this section, however, is not land but a visual *topos*, the curved hem of the Theotokos in the semi-dome of the apse at Livadia [4.71a-b].

In his *Historic Cyprus* (1936) Gunnis referred to 'a local superstition...that a mosaic cube carried in the pocket will cure and prevent pimples and diseases of the blood.' 'Such a superstition,' he wrote, 'is apt to militate against the survival of the mosaic.' In 1982 what little remained was destroyed when looters attempted to detach the mosaic from its semi-dome [4.72]. However, in 1971 Megaw and Hawkins had undertaken a brief survey which they published with photographs and a reconstruction, as 'A Fragmentary Mosaic of the Orant Virgin in Cyprus.'¹⁰⁷ An *orant* is a standing figure with arms raised, usually understood as an attitude of prayer.¹⁰⁸ The first part of this section proposes additional sources for her pose and the second suggests how she may have functioned in early-seventh-century Cyprus.

¹⁰⁴ See Finney (1994) 206 for the manifold *orant* i.e the deceased waiting for resurrection, a symbol of the departed in paradise, the triumphant *ekklesia*, on second- and third-century Imperial Roman coins where the image is accompanied by the legend "PIETAS", and Daniel as a *Rettungsparadigmata*.

¹⁰⁵ Breasted (1916) 131-2, 100-1

¹⁰⁶ Catling in a letter to Åström (7.2.1962) describes a "fertile crescent' from the Pouzi River to Cape Pyla,' in Åström (1965) 119 n.10

¹⁰⁷ Gunnis (1936) 328; Megaw and Hawkins (1976) 261-3 fig. 1 photos A and B; (1985) 173-198 at 195-8. See also Soteriou (1931), 484; (1935), fig. 34-35, pl.34-5; Papageorgiou (1966) 19 fig.10; Michaelides (1987b) 242 and (1992) 56-7 no.71; Papacostas (1999) II 53; Chotzakoglou (2008) 122-3. Jeffery (1918) 250 described a 'mosaic [which he dated to the 16th c.]...now in the last stage of degraded decay'.

¹⁰⁸ John Ammonius shown in the mosaic floor of St George on Mount Nebo is described in Saller and Bagatti (1949) 75 as 'in the posture of one who is praying,' Pl.29.1. At 99 they identify the *orants* with 'the souls of the deceased.' Brenk (2010) 84 was of the opinion that, '[i]n early apse mosaics Mary is never shown with a gesture of prayer,' implying that that *orant* Virgins are not at prayer.

The Livadian Theotokos stands alone in the apse. Her head and the upper part her body are draped in a *maphorion*, the leading edge of which describes a deep curve which is yet more explicit in Rabbula 13v [4.73].¹⁰⁹ ‘Explicit’ seems justified because the breasts of the Rabbula Theotokos are given such an extraordinarily physicality that they appear to fill her draped shawl in a manner more familiar from personifications of abundance.

4.3.2 Gaia and the Seasons

In the sixth century Epiphanius’ tomb was a station on the Piacenza Pilgrim’s route to the Holy Land.¹¹⁰ Had Cypriot pilgrims, following the same route to the Holy places, extended their journeys to the saint’s birthplace at Eleutheropolis they could have visited the sixth-century chapel at Khirbet el Maqerqesh, in the mosaic floor of which was a circular medallion containing the bust of a woman holding the ends of a fruit-filled, crescent-shaped sling [4.74].¹¹¹ Although she represents autumn, as part of a group of four Seasons, she is identified with the label Gaia or Earth.¹¹²

Of the Seasons, autumn was regarded as particularly fruitful. In a fourth-century mosaic floor in the Constantinian Villa in Antioch, autumn combines a fruit-filled sling with a treatment of the breasts suggesting a synergy of figure and fruitfulness [4.75]. Furthermore, the burdened sling is fullest against her womb. Understanding the sling-shaped drape in the Rabbula gospels in terms of a cornucopia may not be too far-fetched, given that the title ‘Theotokos’ emphasises the Virgin as mother rather than maid.¹¹³ *Kontakion* 3 (4) of the Akathistos extends the metaphor from ‘her fruitful womb’ to the earth (‘he made her a fertile earth’), to the Seasons (‘for all who are willing to harvest salvation.’)¹¹⁴

¹⁰⁹ Weitzmann (1977) 101 pl. 36 argues that Rabbula 13v may have been based on a mosaic given the ‘tesserae’ in its frame.

¹¹⁰ Wilkinson (2002) 129; Rapp (1991) I.38; Sozomen *EH* (2010 reprint) 316

¹¹¹ Hachlili (2009) pl.VIII 2.b

¹¹² See Gē in a 3rd or 4th century textile roundel from Egypt with personifications of the Seasons in Weitzmann (1979) 179-80

¹¹³ Cf. 4th or 5thc tapestry woven band from Egypt in Cooney (1941, reprint 1969) 69-70 fig. 217.

¹¹⁴ In *oikos* 3 (5) the Theotokos is a ‘vine-twig of unfading bud’, ‘undying fruit’, ‘the tiller’, you who cultivate’, the ‘earth that flourishes’ and ‘the meadow of delights’. Peltomaa (2001b) 7

4.3.3 Gaia, the Seasons and Tyche

The figure of Gaia is also identified by a label in the mosaic floor of the Upper Chapel of Priest John on Mount Nebo in Jordan.¹¹⁵ However, she wears a curious crown which Hachlili has described as ‘turreted...like a representation of Tyche’ – the female figure personifying the good fortune and prosperity of the city [4.76].¹¹⁶

Perhaps the most complex meeting, not of Gaia, but of the four Seasons and Tyche is the sixth-century mosaic pavement of the Hippolytus Hall at Madaba where, in the four corners of the acanthus scroll framing the pavement, the Seasons carry cornucopias and wear mural crowns [4.77-81]. These personifications might be mistaken for Tychae were it not been for a further three labelled figures outside the frame [4.82]. Rome (PVMH) wears a helmet and Gregoria (ΓΡΗΓΟΡΙΑ) and Madaba (ΜΗΔΑΒΑ) wear mural crowns. Each carries a cruciform staff in one hand and a cornucopia in the other. Rome is New Rome, i.e. Constantinople, and Gregoria has been identified by Bowersock as Antioch.¹¹⁷

Madaba appears here to be making a claim for equivalence, firstly, with the capital, despite being no more than a provincial town, and, secondly, with two patriarchates, despite being no more than a bishopric.¹¹⁸ Avner-Levy emphasises the similarity between the Tychae and the Seasons, pointing out that the attributes carried by the three Tychae are the same as those carried by the three fructive Seasons – spring, summer and autumn. The Homeric *Horae*, the forerunners of these three, provide a template for a discrete group three within a trope of four, which the three Tychae reprise.¹¹⁹ Conversely, the four Seasons put on the mural crown of metropolitan good fortune. Hence, the Hippolytus Hall underscores a crossover between Gaia and Tyche. A protective Gaia and a fructive Tyche are also witnessed in the private sphere: Maguire identifies Gaia’s force as ‘...not only generative,

¹¹⁵ For personifications of the earth see Saller and Bagatti (1949) 51, pls 9.1; 10.2. for the Church of Priest John and 69 Pls. 22.3; 23.3 for the Church of St George.

¹¹⁶ Hachlili (2009) 179n; Piccirillo (1992) 178 fig. 244, 25. See Summer in the floor of St. George on Mount Nebo for a mural Season crowned: Saller and Bagatti (1949) 72 pl.27.2

¹¹⁷ Bowersock (2006) 85

¹¹⁸ For Chalcedon in 451 when Constantine, Archbishop of Bostra signed on behalf of the ‘Bishop of Medabeni’ see Devreesse (1945) 220

¹¹⁹ Homer *Odyssey* XXIV 344; IX 135. As early as the 5thc BC *Horae* were performing the duties associated with Tyche. See Avner-Levy (1996) 364

but also medicinal,' and hence her role involved corporeal protection.¹²⁰ Conversely Avner-Levy provides evidence that Jewish brides wore a diadem called 'a city of gold', intended both as an amulet and to secure the blessings of fertility.¹²¹

Cornucopias provide a common denominator shared between Gaia, the Seasons and Tyche; Gaia's takes the form of a sling and that carried by Tyche and the Seasons takes the form of a horn of plenty. Crowns, too, are shared. Tyche effectively multiplies the single-unit crown worn by those Gaia-related personifications whose crowns usually took the form of a *kalathos* or a *modius*. The *kalathos* or corn basket, a sort of cornucopia for the head, is worn by a winged personification of spring holding up the obligatory fruit-filled sling on a semi-circular bone plaque from sixth-century Egypt and the *modius*, a measure of corn, frequently crowns Serapis as god of the grain supply [4.83].¹²²

An out-of-context Eastern Mediterranean mosaic, published by Michaelides in 2005, provides evidence of a different kind – *modius* and mural crowns both identify place: Cyprus (ΚΥΠΡΟΣ), wearing a *modius* - presumably on the basis of the island's famed fertility - alongside the only known personification of Paphos (ΠΑΦΟΣ) who wears a mural crown [4.84].¹²³

4.3.4 Gaia, Tyche and Victory

The addition of Victory to the trio of Gaia, the Seasons and Tyche, introduces a specifically Christian context.¹²⁴ Toynbee suggested that after Constantine's conversion, personifications survived where gods did not because gods provided competition. Zosimus, for example,

¹²⁰ Maguire (1990) 217

¹²¹ Avner-Levy (1996) 367

¹²² The Oxyrhynchus Papyrus 1380 identifies Isis with Abundance and Fortune, see Grenfell and Hunt (1915) pt 11 no.1380, lines 51, 88, 90, 134-5; see 190-220 at 197, 198, 211, 214, 217: line 88 identifies Isis in a Cypriot context.

¹²³ Michaelides (2005) 399-404. For an abundant Cyprus see Synesius, Letter 148 in Roques (2000) 296: 'They seek the lightest wine, the thickest honey, the thinnest oil, and the heaviest wheat. They are always singing the praises of the places where these products may be obtained, such as Cyprus...'

¹²⁴ See Weitzmann (1977) 181-2 for a 1st-2nd c. relief which originally included a winged Nike holding aloft a Zodiac in the middle of which is an *imago clipeata* of Atargatis the mistress of fertility, maternity and love. Her mural crown suggests city guardianship. She carries a wand which could be an ear of grain as a sign of fertility. Isis was worshipped as a fertility goddess in Cyprus and Egypt. A limestone head of Isis from the Temple of Aphrodite/Isis in Soloi, now in the Cyprus Museum, shows her wearing a crescent moon.

reported that, between 323 and 330, Constantine restored the temple of Rhea in Constantinople: he re-used a statue but reset its arms converting it to an *orant* as ‘Guardian and Carer of the City.’¹²⁵ Toynbee’s distinction, however, may not have been so clear-cut. In the mid-fourth century an oath sworn by a deacon referred to ‘divine and holy tyche’ and in the mid-sixth century Justinian issued a Novel proclaiming that his Tyche was a ‘living law’ granted by God.¹²⁶

If Tyche was defender of the city, Victory represented triumph over those who jeopardized its good fortune. In her alliance with Tyche, Victory introduces a new specificity – an identification with the Emperor and Constantinople as his capital. Crown-offering as Victory’s defining act and the mural crown as Tyche’s defining attribute are combined in a personification, possibly *oikoumene*, in a fourth-century sardonyx cameo of the crowning of Constantine. [4.85]¹²⁷

As the active agent in Constantinian triumph, Victory’s credentials were impeccable.¹²⁸ She may already have been an acculturated Christian when, between 420 and 424, the coinage of Theodosius II (408-450) made her faith more explicit by providing her with a tall cross, perhaps commemorating Theodosius’ renewal, in 420, of the jewelled cross on Golgotha [4.86-7].¹²⁹ This endured as an attribute until Anastasius (r.491-518) replaced the cross with a Chi-Rho [4.88].¹³⁰ Justin I (r.518-527) introduced a second Christianising motif on a solidus of 519-527 in the form of a *globus cruciger* [4.89].

4.3.5 Victories, Angels and the Theotokos

Fleet-footed, Victory eluded the temporal fixity of the Seasons and the spatial fixity of Tyche. Her flexibility was quite different from the easy exchange of attributes shared by Gaia, the Seasons and Tyche. On the coinage of Justin I Victory came to rest and turned through

¹²⁵ Zosimus II.31 in Ridley (1982) 38

¹²⁶ Kaldellis (2010) xxiii and 15 where Kaldellis doubts Procopius’ belief in a providential deity, ‘but rather in a battle between virtue and amoral chance.’ For examples Procopius *Anecdota* 10.9-10 in Dewing (1969) 123-5 and *Wars* VIII. Xii 34-35 in Dewing (1978) V 181-183

¹²⁷ Sardonyx, 4thc reworked in the 19th, 18.5 by 12.2, (Hermitage. St Petersburg).

¹²⁸ Eusebius VC 1.28 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 81: ‘...he said he saw with his own eyes, up in the sky...a cross-shaped trophy formed from light, and a text attached to it which said, ‘By this conquer’.

¹²⁹ Grierson (1982) 36

¹³⁰ Grierson (1982) 52

ninety degrees to assume a hieratic standing pose.¹³¹ Tyche too turned, particularly on coins from the Antioch mint, but it was to be her last appearance because after Justin she is altogether absent from early Byzantine coinage [4.90]. By Justin II (r.565-78), Tyche had been wholly absorbed by Constantinople who, together with Victory, had exchanged her distinguishing attributes for a *globus cruciger* as the universal signifier of the faith the pair now embodied [4.91].

An essential precondition for Victory's survival would be the ultimate test of her adaptability - namely a sex-change identifiable under Justin I.¹³² While Tyche remained resolutely female, Victory now adopted a tunic, a pallium and a girdle lowered from breast to waist, as the essential preparation for the role of an angel [4.92].¹³³ There was no one-to-one exchange, but rather a distribution of identities as the Theotokos was ascribed victories of her own.

The Theotokos as protector of Constantinople is attested by Procopius who claimed that the churches at Blachernai and Pege, approximately at the two ends of the Theodosian land walls and both dedicated to the Virgin, were 'invincible defences to the circuit wall of the city' [4.93].¹³⁴ A protecting Theotokos was not Constantinople-specific because, in the 550s, Procopius described a Justinianic church in Cadiz as 'consecrated to the Mother of God a noteworthy church thus dedicating to her the threshold of the Empire, and making this fortress impregnable for the whole race of mankind'.¹³⁵ Furthermore, Justinian's architect Victorinus invoked the Theotokos for the protection of the fortifications constructed at the Isthmus of Corinth: 'Holy Mary, Theotokos, safeguard the empire of Christ-loving Justinian'.¹³⁶

Arguably Victory was flexible enough to re-employ. Tyche, on the other hand, faced redundancy. Pentcheva confirms that Tyche was absorbed by a Theotokos increasingly

¹³¹ Grierson (1982) 35

¹³² Grierson (1982) 35

¹³³ Grierson (1982) 35, 48-9; Sears (1987) 14 suggests that from Justin I (r.518-527) Victory became an angel, apart from the reigns of Justin II (r.565-578) and Tiberius (r.574-82).

¹³⁴ Procopius *Buildings* 1.3.9 in Dewing (1954) 41; Penna (2000) 21

¹³⁵ Procopius *Buildings* 6.7.14 in Dewing (1954) 391

¹³⁶ '+ Ἁγ(ία) Μαρία Θεοτόκε, φύλαξον τήν βασιλείαν του φιλοχρίστου Ἰουστινιανου' in Bees (1941) no.2 at 5-9, fig. at 6

identified with Constantinopolis.¹³⁷ According to Limberis, sixth- and seventh-century Constantinople found in the Theotokos its Christian Tyche.¹³⁸ While she is right to construe the Theotokos as an amalgam of Tyche and Victory, the absence of Gaia from the account is a serious omission, because early in the seventh century she re-emerges as the ‘woman-as-wealth-bearer.’

4.3.6 Woman-as-wealth-bearer

Two crescent-shaped bronze stamps bearing the words KARPOI (fruits) and HYGEIA (health) and possibly used for communion bread, provide evidence that the crescent may have been understood as an autonomous image of benign providence [4.94-5].¹³⁹ The sling cornucopia certainly conforms to the trope, but as James points out, while ‘Images of Earth’ hold cornucopias, ‘images of empresses’ do not.¹⁴⁰ Nevertheless, crescent-shaped fecundity is evoked in an imperial context by the collar fringed with oversized pearl droplets worn by Empress Theodora at San Vitale in Ravenna (548) [4.96].¹⁴¹ Artefactual evidence is provided by an early seventh-century crescent-shaped necklace of gold openwork plaques mounted with three rows of stones from which hang seventeen pendant jewels on gold wires, originally embellished with more than one hundred pearls, emeralds and sapphires [4.97].¹⁴²

To suggest a resemblance between women-as-wealth-bearers, the Theotokos and the Ephesian Artemis may be stretching a point. However, this is precisely the connection made by Benko, who writes that in 431 the Ephesians ‘demonstrated in the streets shouting ‘Praised be the Theotokos’ just as their ancestors had shouted ‘Great is Artemis of the Ephesians,’ when her reputation was threatened 400 years earlier (Acts 19). ‘In the [Ephesians] minds,’ he contends, ‘there was probably little or no difference between Artemis and Mary’ [4.98].¹⁴³ The Farnese Artemis bears a striking resemblance to a 2nd century

¹³⁷ Pentcheva (2006) 14

¹³⁸ Limberis (1994) 127-130

¹³⁹ Maguire (1989) 14. Cf Weiss and Talgam (2002) 61 fig.5: in the southern margin of the Nile Festival Building at Sephoris two birds hold a garland with the inscription ‘Use in good luck.’

¹⁴⁰ James in Stafford and Herrin (2005) 297

¹⁴¹ The necklace may refer more to Theodora’s power and wealth than her fecundity. Although she had a daughter, her marriage to Justinian was childless. Diehl (1972) 69-70

¹⁴² Antikenmuseum, Berlin inv. 30219.505; Sebesta and Bonfante (2001) 89 fig 5.18

¹⁴³ Benko (1994) 256-7

Artemis from Salamis.¹⁴⁴ Both are decorated with swags variously described as eggs, breasts and the testicles of sacrificed bulls – all images of fecundity [4.99]. Furthermore, the Farnese Artemis is crowned with a particularly mural *polos*, and she wears a crescent collar from which hang remarkably pearl-like droplets. Evidence that, even at the end of the sixth century, the same figure might permit multiple interpretations comes from John of Ephesus' (c.507–c.586) *Ecclesiastical History*, in which he records that Justin 'introduced in the coinage...a female figure [almost certainly Victory], which was generally compared to Venus.'¹⁴⁵

The principal wealth carried by the Empress was a *porphyrogenitus* for the Emperor, as pendant to the incarnate Christ construed as the 'wealth' brought by the Theotokos. A wealth-bearing Theotokos might be identified with Maria Regina, who is typically shown wearing a crescent-shaped collar, and for which early evidence can be found at Santa Maria Antiqua and Santa Maria in Trastevere in Rome [4.43-4]. For an *orant* Regina, we have to turn to the Oratory of John VII (705-707) at Old St Peter's in Rome [4.100]. But Per Jonas Nordhagen describes her as more Tyche than wealth-bearer.¹⁴⁶ She is the 'new apotropaic, religio-military imagery of the Empire,' safeguarding Rome from the Langobards in 569, much as she would safeguard Constantinople in 626.¹⁴⁷

4.3.7 Theotokos as Constantinopolis/Anthousa

In the mid-fifth century Proclus associated the Theotokos with a now-familiar pair of personifications. Gaia underlies his identification of the Virgin as the earth, a fertile field spontaneously yielding grain and a meadow blossoming with flowers and fruit. Tyche underlies his repeated association of the Theotokos with 'place' as well as Season.¹⁴⁸ The two coalesce in Pentcheva's reading of *oikos* 7 (13) of the Akathistos, in which the Theotokos is a 'flower of incorruption (*anthos tes aphtharsias*). *Anthos* (flower) phonetically recalls Anthousa (*the blossoming one*), the name of the Tyche of Constantinople and counterpart of

¹⁴⁴ Güzelyurt Museum

¹⁴⁵ John of Ephesus *EH* III.14 in Payne Smith (1860) 192

¹⁴⁶ Nordhagen (1990) 58-130

¹⁴⁷ Nordhagen (2010) Unpublished conference paper

¹⁴⁸ Costas (2002)133 and (1995) 169-194 at 178-79. For general background see Leveque (1986) 242-56

the Roman Flora.¹⁴⁹ But an early-seventh century Theotokos did more than preside over the city's good fortune. She had agency in bringing it about. As an 'immovable tower' and the 'impregnable wall of the kingdom,' she instantiates the principal components of a mural crown. The Tychaean tone shifts in the following lines of the hymn in favour of the Theotokos as Victory through whom 'enemies are vanquished' and the 'trophies of victory are assured.' Hence, when Heraclius arrived in Constantinople in 610 to overthrow the tyrant Phocas (r.602-610), the sails of his fleet were emblazoned with her image and when, in 622, he left the capital to confront the Persians, an icon of the Virgin served as his 'empress general.'¹⁵⁰

4.3.8 Gaia, the Seasons and Tyche, again

No Cypriot mosaics of Gaia survive but her image may not have been unknown on the island. Maguire points out that 'In early Byzantine household textiles there is an abundance of images illustrating the fruitfulness of nature.'¹⁵¹ Personifications of fecundity almost certainly coexisted with apotropaic *orants* in the context of personal protection. For example, a gold bracelet from the Eastern Mediterranean has an *orant* Theotokos on the clasp [4.101] and a possibly Egyptian oval hematite pendant shows an *orant*, also possibly a Theotokos, invoking healing associated with an issue of blood [4.102].¹⁵²

Setting Livadia's *orant* in the same protective and domestic context would not seem out-of-place; indeed Gunnis' anecdote 'that a mosaic cube...will cure and prevent pimples and diseases of the blood' may well be a late trace of her apotropaic powers. Given the coexistence of Gaia and the *orant* Virgin in the context of textiles, we should not rule out the possibility that, for what must have been a remote rural community reliant on good harvests, the Livadian Theotokos was an interventionist icon, re-animating Gaia as the providential earth and Tyche as good fortune.¹⁵³ But can we extend Tychaean good fortune to a specific reference to place?

¹⁴⁹ Pentcheva (2001b) 14; Dagron (1974) 43-5

¹⁵⁰ Mango and Scott (1997) 427

¹⁵¹ Maguire (1990) 217

¹⁵² Kalavrezou (2003) 165 a. and b., 283-4

¹⁵³ Shilling (2011) (unpublished conference paper) sees Livadia as representing 'the rejection of natural themes and metaphors of nature in Byzantine art.'

There is some, albeit inconclusive, evidence for a Tyche on Late Antique Cyprus. Megaw suggests that a mural-crowned profile head from Salamis may have been modelled on the Antiochene Tyche [4.103].¹⁵⁴ However, the most intriguing evidence for an identification of Tyche with Cyprus comes from the Vrap treasure.

4.3.9 The Vrap cup and the metropolis of Cyprus

Personifications of cities are common; personifications of countries are rare.¹⁵⁵ However, Cyprus offers a number of exceptions. A region, Greek Lacedaemonia (ΛΑΚΕΔΑΜΟΝΙΑ), is represented in a mid-fourth century mosaic of Leda and the Swan in the House of Aion in Nea Paphos (318-324) by a female figure wearing the mural crown of a metropolis [4.104].¹⁵⁶ In the late-third or early-fourth-century mosaic of Theseus and the Minotaur in the Villa of Theseus, also in Nea Paphos, a personification of Crete (ΚΡΗΤΗ), too, wears of the crown of a city Tyche [4.105].¹⁵⁷

Now in the Metropolitan Museum in New York, the Vrap cup is decorated with repoussé busts of four mural-crowned Tychae.¹⁵⁸ Greek *tituli* round the rim identify them as Rome, Alexandria, Constantinople and Cyprus – ΠΩΛΗC ΡΩΜΗC + ΠΩΛΗC ΑΛΗC ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΗΑ + ΚΩΝCΤΑΝΤΗΝΟΠΟΛΗC + ΠΩΛΗC ΚΥΠΡΟC [4.106-109].

¹⁵⁴ Megaw (1974) 57-88 at 68 fig 8. Relief now in the Cyprus Museum. Comparison with Roux (1973) 137 raises the probability with that the Salamis Tyche is a fragment from a figured offering table. For sculptural heads women with a *corona muralis* from 5th- 4th BC Arsos, Idalion, Ayios Philon and Leucolla and coins from 4th c. BC Salamis see Beer (2002) 369-385, Koiner (2002) 1-5 and (2005) 27-33.

¹⁵⁵ Hachlili (2008)183; Weiss and Talgram in Humphrey (2002) 55-90 at 61 and 66 fig.6. Aigyptus is also a representation of Euthenia, a personification of abundance, mainly of grain.

¹⁵⁶ Michaelides (1987a) 243-4; Daszewski (1984) 304-7 fig.2

¹⁵⁷ Michaelides (1987a) 246-7; Daszewski (1970) 128-132, fig.4 pl. XXIII.1

¹⁵⁸ Found in Vrap, eastern Albania and now in the Metropolitan Museum, New York (Inv. 17.190.1710). Measurements: 15.65cm high and 12.1cm diameter. Material: three sheets of gold and some silver. Dating: Strzygowski (1917) 3-8 at 7-8 suggests manufacture in Salamis between 431-647, see also figs 2-4 pl.II; for Shelton (1979b) 27-38 at 28, 'If Cyprus is an island while the other three are cities, all four were equivalent administrative units with claims of Apostolic foundation within the early church'; Stewart (2008) 194-5 draws attention to spelling errors and suggests the so-called Period of Neutrality and the work of Arab metalsmiths. He makes a comparison with the Bamberg Tapestry attributed by Papamastorakis (2003) 375-392 at to the reign of Nicephoras Phocas, which shows two Tychai, possibly Cyprus and Crete; Minaeva (2001) 19-21 thinks a pre-sixth, seventh-century date possible.

Place of manufacture, function and date are uncertain. Shelton dated the cup to 431-647, in 2011 the Metropolitan Museum late-dated it to the 700s.¹⁵⁹ The twenty-year window between Ephesus (431) and Chalcedon (451), which raised Jerusalem to the patriarchy, might account for Jerusalem's absence, if the cup is early. If the cup is late, Jerusalem's absence could be explained by its low ranking in the Pentarchy. However, as a working hypothesis, we might assign the vessel to the late sixth or the first half of the seventh century, on two counts: firstly, the similarity of the buds on the sceptre to the treatment of the hair of a military saint depicted on a plate from the Cyprus treasure, dated to 641-51 [4.110] and, secondly, numismatic evidence that representations of Constantinopolis carrying an orb with unveiled hands are most common on the coinage of Justin II (r.565-578) [4.91-2].¹⁶⁰

Despite the unsatisfactory state of research, one thing is clear – an island is made to appear the equivalent of a city by virtue of its mural crown and its metropolitan context. It might not be in the interest of the Pentarchy to include the non-pentarchic, hence, we might assume that the cup was Cypriot, possibly designed to make a claim for pentarchic equivalence, based on an autocephalic status which provided comparable privileges while withholding a title.¹⁶¹

Sceptres and orbs were attributes of rulership. Had the cup had a liturgical use we might have expected to see the orb as a *globus cruciger* and the sceptres too as cruciform. However, a cluster of three balls are mounted on the globes and 'buds' surmount the wands, which Piguet-Panayotova has argued are 'reminiscent of the cornucopia carried by the city-goddesses in ancient representations with a sense of fertility.'¹⁶² They also recall the treatment of the flowers in the sling and around the arch of the sixth-century winged personification of Spring in the sixth-century bone plaque from Egypt referred to above [4.83]. The sceptre is particularly telling. A personification of Spring in the church of St George on Mount Nebo carries a cornucopia which is so extended as to fall between a full

¹⁵⁹ Shelton (1979b) 178; Piguet-Panoyotova (2002) 44

¹⁶⁰ Cutler (1984) 43–64 at 57. But compare a globe surmounted trefoil on a coin of Nicephorus II in Grierson (1982) 184, pl.46. no.827

¹⁶¹ See Isidore (602-636) *Etymologies* XIV.6.14, 'The island of Cyprus receives its name from the city of Cyprus which is in it,' in Barney (2006) 295

¹⁶² Piguet-Panayotova (2002) 37-74 at 45. At 46 she describes the drapes as 'two floating pieces like wings.'

cornucopia and the thyrsus, the wand carried by Dionysus 'as bringer of victory and prosperity from the east.'¹⁶³

There is no overt evidence for the Vrap Tyche as apotropaic. However, not the least remarkable characteristic of the cup's iconography are the flying drapes forming an undulating band below the inscription, described by Ostoia as wings and by Shelton as 'arching...like wings.'¹⁶⁴ A correlation need not be so fanciful, given the evidence cited earlier for liturgical vestments referencing wings and even moving in imitation of them.¹⁶⁵ Furthermore, the flying drapes of the angels on the triumphal arch at Sinai are not only strikingly similar to those on the Vrap cup, semblance is implied by wings and drapes which follow almost exactly the same profile [4.60-1].

4.3.10 An anxious dependence

Despite Justinian's re-conquest of the Empire, a sense of unease pervaded the East – plague struck between 541 and 543, which, according to Procopius, 'embraced the entire world, and blighted the lives of all men.'¹⁶⁶ The Danubian border was threatened by Slavs and there was the long and debilitating war with the Persian Empire (502-628). For Hussey, 'a marked intensification in the use of images...in the sixth and seventh centuries' is evidence of a need for additional security.¹⁶⁷ For Cameron too, 'It [was] tempting to see the shift...towards the ecclesiastical and defensive as the product of gloom and anxiety.'¹⁶⁸ Although Brown described an 'anxious dependence on an invisible Virgin,' it is arguable that anxiety and dependence generated the need for a Virgin who was altogether more visually immediate.¹⁶⁹

The three Cypriot basilicas with apse mosaics were more or less distant from the depredations of the Arab incursions which, from 649, destroyed or damaged the major basilicas of the littoral.¹⁷⁰ Kiti, closest to the coast, was a village church of modest proportions and hardly comparable with those urban basilicas which marked the littoral as

¹⁶³ Toynbee (1947) 140; Saller and Bagatti (1949) 72 Pl.27.1

¹⁶⁴ Ostoia (1969) no. 23; Shelton (1979) 28. Cf Forsyth and Weitzmann (1976) pl. CXXII B and CXXIII B.

¹⁶⁵ Woodfin (2012) 7; Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 67; Spatharakis (1976) 262

¹⁶⁶ Procopius *Wars* II xxii-xxxiii in Dewing (1914) 451

¹⁶⁷ Hussey (1990) 31

¹⁶⁸ Cameron (1979) 31

¹⁶⁹ Brown (1973) 29

¹⁷⁰ Beihammer (2000) docs 252-2, 256, 276

Christian. The island was 'a demilitarized and neutral no-man's-land' until the mid-seventh century and its towns - with the exception of early-seventh-century Salamis - remained ungarrisoned, except perhaps by a Theotokos cast as an 'unshakable tower' and an 'impregnable wall,' corresponding to the island's circuminsular cities and its more or less fixed coastline. The island-as-polis has been identified by Constantakopoulou in the Classical and Hellenistic Aegean where the inhabitants of multi-polis islands often identified with their islands more than with any individual polis.¹⁷¹ Herodotus, for example, bundled the three Rhodian *poleis* together to evoke a single metropolis.¹⁷²

4.3.11 Panagia tis Kyras

The relationship between demography and the size and number of basilicas in a settlement is notoriously slippery, but let us accept, that, with a width of less than 7m, an apse-width of 2.1m and an undetermined length, the size of Panagia tis Kyras had some bearing on the demography of this small farming community [4.111-2].¹⁷³ Evidence for an earlier basilica, probably of three aisles, is provided by a stone column on the site [4.113]. The sanctuary of this earlier building may have been remodelled in the sixth century, given the evidence of two Proconnesian chancel-screen posts serving as imposts for the vault of the north arm of this, the only cruciform church on the island [4.114-5].

Lythrankomi and Kiti offer ensembles, but what are we to make of the lone figure at Livadia? Unlike those intimations of the natural world which accompany the Theotokos at Lythrankomi or inhabit the border of the arch at Kiti, the Theotokos at Livadia is set against a decontextualised paradise from which literal evocations of the natural world are entirely absent. This can hardly be an expression of a wider aversion because the Akathistos hymn, through which she continued to be addressed and praised, constantly described the Theotokos with reference to the natural world. The Theotokos at Lythrankomi is enclosed in her mandorla, at Kiti she inhabits the same space as the angels and, if that trajectory is continued, the conclusion might be that the Theotokos at Livadia abandoned an 'elsewhere' in favour of an immediate and intercessory presence. Hence, the absence of nature has

¹⁷¹ Constantakopoulou (2005) 1

¹⁷² Constantakopoulou (2005) 7. For the flexibility of the complex poleis in Herodotus see Sherwin-White (1978) 46-47 and Herodotus I.144.3. II 178.2 in Godley (2004) 185, 493

¹⁷³ The present cruciform church is probably 12th century. Megaw (1971) 261-3

nothing to do with a preamble to the debate about images, rather the opposite. Decontextualizing is a promotion of the Theotokos as icon.

But how alone was the Livadian Theotokos? Megaw and Hawkins uncovered evidence of what may have been accompanying figures on the straight walls either side of the apse. Had the relatively compartmentalized composition at Lythrankomi and the greater spatial continuity at Kiti opened out still further here to dramatize the entire east end of the basilica, reconfiguring the apsidal arch as the 'The gateway...that faces to the east,' of Ezekiel 46:1 and the 'gate of salvation,' of *oikos* 10 (19)?¹⁷⁴ According to *oikos* 4, the Theotokos, as well as being the opener of the 'Gates of Paradise,' was also a 'defence against invisible foes.'¹⁷⁵ This would seem to accord with Megaw and Hawkins's hypothesis that the figures either side of the apse may have been similar to the Michael and Gabriel in S.Apollinare in Classe who, as early as 549, carried military standards and wore decidedly military *chlamydes* [4.116]. Alternatively the two figures may be part of a larger scheme, a Theophany perhaps, of which Megaw and Hawkins found the innermost pair. Had that been the case, Christ and the angels would have been depicted on the wall above the semi-dome, in a composition comparable to the Chapel of S.Venanzio in Rome and to the Ascension page in the Rabbula Gospels.¹⁷⁶

If the Livadian Theotokos is dated prior to the Arab invasions her role may have been confined to quite local issues, perhaps with little distinction between the domestic and the communal. If, on the other hand, Livadia is dated later than the Arab incursions, the settlement may indeed have been close to the front-line. No doubt that Mu'āwiya's goal was Constantinople, rather than the colonisation of the island. Hence, there is no reason to suppose he was interested in holding more than those coastal ports which might provide naval bases for the next stage of his advance.¹⁷⁷ Although it was relatively untouched, the hinterland, nevertheless, remained vulnerable and the inhabitants of a defenceless hamlet must have felt themselves particularly exposed. Evidence confirms that Christian practice continued after the Arab invasion, even on the coast: according to an inscription, the great

¹⁷⁴ Peltomaa (2001b) 17

¹⁷⁵ For Cherubim as the guardian of the Gates of Eden see Genesis 3.24. C.f '...when you bring us the first token of our salvation, entered the gates of this city, which, being shaped in a hollow curve...seemed to receive you in a kind of embrace.' PL.8.7.6 in MacCormick (1976) 44

¹⁷⁶ Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 38 for evidence that there was also mosaic on the wall above the apse at Lythrankomi.

¹⁷⁷ Ostrogorsky (1969) 116

basilica at Soloi was repaired in 654/5, and Archbishop Paul of Crete stopped at Cyprus on his way from Egypt to Constantinople and attended the first public reading, at Tremetousia in 655, of the new *Vita* of Spyridion. It seems probable that small-scale *de novo* building continued too.¹⁷⁸ If Livadia belonged to this later period, its Theotokos, might well be understood in terms of Constantinople in 626, and hence, as less like her contained sisters at Lythrankomi and Kiti and more icon-like, actively engaged on behalf of ‘her’ settlement.

At the beginning of this section, I identified a general acceptance of the *orant* pose as indicating prayer – for which I can find no earlier Byzantine attestation than a ninth-century poem beginning ‘I raise a mother’s hands in prayer.’¹⁷⁹ Guardianship is an attribute of the Angels of Exodus 23:20 and the plea to God to ‘Shelter us under the shelter of thy wings’ recurs *inter alia* in Ruth 2:12, Psalms 17.8, 36:7, 57:1 and Matthew 23:37. An Egyptian papyrus of 250-80, possibly the first mention of the Theotokos in a similar context, may be the origin of the Lenten *Apolytikia*: ‘We have taken refuge under the wing of thy compassion, O Theotokos.’ [4.117]¹⁸⁰ Is there a case, then, for seeing the Livadian Theotokos as precursor of the *Schutzmantelmadonna* [4.118] and the *Madonna della Misericordia* [4.119], as the most satisfying meeting of *maphorion* and *orant* as a single concept? A *kontakion* to the Holy Fathers possibly as early as 548 or as late as 626, constructs precisely this association,

It guards the precious garment of the Theotokos,
By which it is protected all the more,
Saying, ‘Lady, do always preserve me like a maidservant
under your arms...’¹⁸¹

The distinction between the public and the private spheres, which may have been more marked in the larger centres of the littoral, would have been more intimately juxtaposed in rural Livadia. Remote, but arguably more cohesive, the community of Livadia shared a common dependence on agriculture and therefore would have made quite distinctive demands on the protective attributes of their localized, even domesticated Theotokos.

¹⁷⁸ van den Ven (1953) 109-110

¹⁷⁹ Browning (1977) 296 no.5 and 307 n5.2

¹⁸⁰ Greek Papyrus 470 in Roberts (1938) 470; Johnson (2008) 247-67

¹⁸¹ Mango (2000) 23

Conclusion. A singular Virgin: 'Constantinopolitanisation' in 626

In 626 the Sassanid army, advancing from the east, stood within sight of Constantinople.¹⁸² To make matters worse, between 30,000 and 80,000 Slavs and Avars were also advancing on the city from the north-west. Three surviving first-hand accounts emphasise the Theotokos as defender of the city's walls and gates.¹⁸³ According to Theodore Synkellos, having attached icons of the *Theotokos* to the Golden Gate as phylacteries against the Avars, Patriarch Sergios addressed the enemy.¹⁸⁴

...the fighting is wholly against these pictures you foreign and devilish troops. A woman, the Mother of God, will quell all your boldness and boasting with one command...¹⁸⁵

Kaegi describes the Patriarch carrying an icon of the Virgin around the city walls.¹⁸⁶ Ekonomou suggests that the *maphorion*, too, was part of the procession.¹⁸⁷ Icon and relic, then, had agency in an early-seventh-century cult of the Theotokos which emphasised her twin roles as Victory and Tyche. This is expressed, firstly, by what Grabar has called the militarization of sacred images, beginning in the late-sixth-century when icons replaced the Constantinian *labarum* as the battle standard, and secondly, by Cameron's claim that 'at this moment [the Theotokos] fulfilled the function of a city deity.'¹⁸⁸

As thanksgiving for the deliverance of the city, on 7th August 626, the 'entire population' of Constantinople gathered for an all-night vigil at Blachernae. By adding a second Prooemium to the Akathistos, Patriarch Sergius offered 'Our Lady of Victories' exclusive patronage of 'Your city,' recasting her as Constantinopolis, in recognition of her decisive role as the city's saviour.¹⁸⁹

¹⁸² Theodore Synkellos in Kaegi (2003) 133-4; Nikephoros in Mango (1990) 125-127

¹⁸³ Weyl-Carr (2001) 64

¹⁸⁴ Whitby and Whitby (1989) 180 n.476; Ekonomou (2007) 84, 149 n.419

¹⁸⁵ Cameron (1979) 20

¹⁸⁶ Kaegi (2003) 136. There are three contemporary accounts of the siege: George of Pisidia, Theodore Synkellos and the *Chronicon Paschale*.

¹⁸⁷ Ekonomou (2007) 84; Mango in Vasilaki (2000) 22, 25 n.50 contends that the maphorion is not mentioned in contemporary accounts and that the paraded icon was an *acheiropietos* of Christ. Cameron (1979) 19 suggests that the maphorion acted as a palladium for the city.

¹⁸⁸ Grabar (1957) 31-2; Cameron (1979) 3-35 at 6, 22

¹⁸⁹ Peltomaa (2001b) 3; for Romanos the Melodist see Wellesz (1956) 146, 152 and for Sergius' part-authorship, O'Carroll (1982) 8

To you, our leader in battle and defender
O Theotokos, I, your city, delivered from sufferings,
Ascribe hymns of victory and thanksgiving.¹⁹⁰

The 114 epithets applied to the Theotokos in the Akathistos suggest a manifold and richly endowed persona. If Constantinople saw its Theotokos/Tyche in *oikos* 3 (5), Livadia may have recognised in the very same *oikos* a ‘cultivator,’ and ‘grower,’ a field of blossoming abundance and a table richly laid. Recent research, which has re-assigned the Akathistos, from Constantinople and Romanos the Melodist to c.548, to 431-451 – ie, post-Ephesus and pre-Chalcedon - speaks in favour of this wider reading.¹⁹¹ Peltomaa, identified a widespread understanding of the hymn as ‘the foundation of eastern Mariology’ and for Limberis it was ‘amongst the most widely known and popular with the laity.’¹⁹² Early dating the Akathistos allows that the earliest surviving image of the Theotokos on Cyprus represented an already widely dispersed veneration possibly originating in Egypt, but in its Late Antique manifestation, more a product of Ephesus than Constantinople.

Addressing the distribution of Proconnesian marble as an index of Constantinopolitan outreach, Mango posed the question: ‘is Proconnesos Constantinople?’¹⁹³ We might pose a similar question: ‘does ‘imperial’ imagery necessarily imply the seat of the imperial family?’ Or has the capital’s claim on the Theotokos and the success of its promotion of her cause extended as far as modern scholarship, obscuring the extent to which the Theotokos ‘regalised’ as Maria Regina was as much a papal as it was an imperial initiative.¹⁹⁴ Certainly one ‘imperial’ signifier, the two-part throne, had other claimants. Mathews argues that thrones were not imperial ‘but a consistent Roman attribute of divinity’ which Brenk extends to the *suppedaneum* as ‘not an exclusively imperial motif because it was associated in Roman art...with privileged people.’¹⁹⁵

Rather than being a Constantinopolitan initiative it seems more likely that Lythrankomi and Kiti were part of a dispersed Mediterranean tradition which flourished before the capital’s

¹⁹⁰ Peltomaa (2001b) 3

¹⁹¹ Peltomaa (2001b) 45-48

¹⁹² Peltomaa (2001b) 23; Limberis (1994) 90

¹⁹³ pers comm 26.4.12

¹⁹⁴ For the orthodox view see Osborne (2008) 102-03

¹⁹⁵ Mathews (1993) 103; Brenk (2010) 63

claim on the Virgin's exclusive patronage from 626. Although, given the depredations of the iconoclasts, it is impossible to quantify the debt owed by the Livadian Theotokos to Constantinople, it is clear that, beyond the context of prayer with which she is commonly associated, the Livadian Theotokos, too, drew on manifold antecedents for the very diversity of the benefits she bestowed.

Chapter 5.

i Argument

Had the chronology of Cypriot basilicas ended with Rautman's work at Kalavassos, seventh-century Cyprus might be characterised by small basilicas in settlements away from the immediate coast, constructed with a minimum of imported materials, the absence of which was compensated for by the versatile use of gypsum stucco. However, early-seventh-century Structure A at Katalymmata ton Plakoton represents a return to large, lavish, coastal and supra-regional buildings.

Until the discovery of Structure A the transept was entirely absent from the architecture of Late Antique Cyprus. Megaw made the case for the Baptistery Basilica at Peyia as 'a small transept basilica, a form which is otherwise unknown in Cyprus...' [5.1-2] ¹ However, this structure has no lateral extension; rather a transverse element is inserted into what remains fundamentally a basilical layout which, in common with almost all early Cypriot basilicas, confined projections to an eastern apse or apses.²

The size and assertiveness of Structure A suggests its builders intended a major statement. Because the site has yet to be fully excavated, this chapter will summarize its most plausible contexts and explore a fourth in more detail. The chapter is in four sections: (1) the material evidence, (2) cognate transepts, (3) four hypotheses and (4) conclusion.

The chapter addresses the larger question; did the layout at Katalymmata represent a turning-away from the three-aisled, tri-apsidal basilica as an affirmation of Nicene Trinitarianism? If not, how might Katalymmata represent confirmation of an Orthodoxy from which its form appears so radically to depart?

¹ Megaw (1974) 72 n.56

² Megaw (1954) 172-176 at 175; (1955) 28-34 at 33;(2007) 174 n.85. Megaw (1946) 48-56, 51-2 fig.7 made a case for a transept at Aphendrika on the basis of a step towards the east end of the south wall, a hypothesis abandoned when Papageorghiou cleared the site in the 1960s. See Papageorghiou (1964) 94-96

5.1 Structure A

5.1.1 Historical context

The seventh century opened in spectacular fashion. In 608 Heraclius (r.610-641) began a revolt against Emperor Phocas (r.601-610). The attack was probably two-pronged, Heraclius advancing via Sicily and Greece and his cousin, Niketas, advancing via Alexandria and Cyprus.³ Heraclius reached the capital on the 3rd October 610; two days later Phocas was dead and Heraclius had been crowned by his mentor, Patriarch Sergius (r.610-638).⁴

The triumph of 610 was followed by a decade of disaster. Successively, the territories surrounding Cyprus to the north, east and south succumbed to Persian advance: Cilicia and Antioch in 613, Jerusalem in 614 and Egypt in 617.⁵ In 616 the very centre of the Empire seemed about to implode as Persian troops reached Chalcedon, and looked across the Bosphorus to the city whose capture might have been their crowning achievement had not Egypt suddenly seemed the more lucrative prize.⁶

By the end of the second decade of the century, Cyprus itself looked vulnerable, if not from a Persian navy, from Persians using captured Syrian, Cilician and Egyptian ships.⁷ Although Metcalf maintains that the sea served as a disincentive, it is difficult to see why what had been the primary medium of exchange should suddenly become a bar to invasion.⁸ Furthermore, if the islanders had direct experience of its strategic position as a bridgehead to Constantinople in 610 and if, forty years later, Mu'āwiya too, saw the island as staging post for an advance on Constantinople, it seems implausible that Cyprus would have been unaware of its precarious position in the wider Persian threat to the *pax byzantina*.

³ Chrysos (1984) 53-62; Kaegi (2003) 46.n75. Mitchell (2007) 411 suggests that as part of this campaign 'the island of Cyprus was taken.'

⁴ *Chronicon Paschale* 347 in Whitby and Whitby (1989) 151-152

⁵ According to Theophanes (Mango and Scott (1997) 432 and n.1) 'In this year [AD 614/15] the Persians occupied all of Egypt and Alexandria...' but 619 is probably the correct date. See Howard-Johnston (1999) 39-40 for Heraclius' war against the Persians as a 'Christian' war through which the 'the crown of martyrdom might be won.'

⁶ Luttwak (2009) 398

⁷ Nicolle (2009) 57

⁸ Elton (2004) 1; Metcalf (2009) 379

5. Transepts: Katalymmata ton Plakoton

In the decade between 618 and 628 Heraclius took charge of the counter-attack. In 627 the Persians were defeated at Nineveh and the following year the True Cross, captured in 614, was returned in triumph to Jerusalem.⁹ Eleni Procopiou, the director of the excavation at Katalymmata, dates Structure A to the turn of the tide when the decade of disaster came to close but the decade of triumph had barely begun.

5.1.2 Katalymmata ton Plakoton: the material evidence

The excavation of Structure A was completed in 2009 [5.3]. The following season the excavation continued eastwards, exposing an east wing in the form of the nave and aisles of a conventional timber-roofed basilica, probably connected to the transept through a tribelon. Of the mosaic pavement of the nave, nine panels have been uncovered. There are no earlier floors in either part of the building, which might support the case for the east wing and transept as a single build.

Two medallions containing inscriptions, one in the nave and one in the north aisle, were intended to be read looking west [5.4].¹⁰ Nothing in the ancillary buildings – a number of rooms to the south and on the north the kind of long hall usually associated with a *katechumenion* – contradict this hypothesis. Indeed, the western portion of an atrium attached to the nave, excavated in 2011, adds to the evidence that the westwards orientation of the whole structure may have been intended from the outset [5.5-6].

5.1.3 Transept

Structure A measures 36m north-south and 14m east-west. Its walls, none surviving above a metre, are approximately 0.50m thick and constructed from rubble in poured gypsum plaster. The principal apse on the west, 5m wide at the chord, circular on the inside and five-sided on the exterior, was accompanied by two apsidioles the centres of which were 9.5m from the centre of the principal apse. The walls of the apsidioles were c.0.60m and the main apse was c.1.00m, an additional width suggesting they supported semi-domes. Furthermore, the small tesserae of gold, glass and mother-of-pearl found in the vicinity of the main apse suggest that its semi-dome carried a mosaic décor.

⁹ Nikephoros in Mango (1990) 55

¹⁰ The better preserved read 'My lord listen to my prayer' (Psalm 142)

5.1.4 Bema

The ambulatory lining the interior walls of both transept arms ended in the west against a 6.15m-square bema projecting westwards from the central apse [5.6]. Closed by this apse in the west, the bema was possibly preceded in the east by a ramp as the principal and possibly the only means of access [5.7]. The floor of the main apse retains the impression of large radially-set slabs, which would entirely accord with the floor plan of a synthronon [5.8]. Militating against this are indications of an arrangement that, by the early seventh-century, was somewhat outdated, in the form of two elongated rectangular scars in the mosaic floor, north and south of the bema, possibly indicating the position of opposed clergy benches.¹¹ Not the least striking feature of the bema was the mosaic pavement immediately in front of the apse which showed two deer flanking an acanthus from which rose a vine inhabited by birds pecking grapes [5.9-10].

The bema was surrounded by posts, constructed from rubble and poured gypsum plaster, supporting screens, one of which has been recovered. Carved from Proconnesian marble, this panel had a central pierced *stephanostaurion*, an eight-armed cross within a wreath, from which proceed two trailing ribbons, each terminating in a hederia supporting a cross. [5.11]. A short *solea* extended eastwards from the bema, with posts also constructed from poured plaster supporting closure screens set directly on the mosaic floor.

5.1.5 Apses

Unlike the central apse, for which a liturgical use seems plausible, the four subsidiary apses - two in the west wall either side of the main apse and one in the middle of each of the north and south walls – may have been martyrial sites accessed from the ambulatories [5.12]. The first supporting evidence for Structure A as martyrial was a miniature marble sarcophagus lid with *akroteria* at the corners and a funnel in the centre of its hipped roof, discovered in 2008 in the south-east corner of the south transept [5.13]. It is of a type comparable with the reliquary discovered beneath the altar at Varna containing a piece of wood hypothesised by its excavators as a piece of

¹¹ An altar, for which there is no evidence, would have been sited between the benches. See also Megaw and Hawkins (1977) 27

the True Cross [5.14].¹² The following season the remains of a Proconnesian *mensa martyris* came to light set into the south apsidiole of the west wall [5.15]. Like the *mensa* at Agios Varnavas, a funnel pierced the centre of the slab, which at Katalymmata was linked by a terracotta *cataract* presumably to a relic-deposit below [5.16].¹³ Further indication of the status of this apse is attested by evidence of gypsum screens and marble posts enclosing the *mensa*.

The most dramatic evidence for a martyrial context came from the apse in the south wall which contained a full-sized, hipped-roofed sarcophagus lid with *akroteria* and a large cross in relief in the centre, one beam of which was the full width of the lid, while the other ran along its ridge [5.17]. This cross was pierced, at its mid-point, by a funnel, similar to that in the adjacent *mensa martyris*, probably for the insertion of *brandae* given that the coffin was constructed partly in the floor without any apparent means for drawing off oil.

This lid, too, has parallels with Agios Varnavas. In 2006, excavations there exposed a Hellenistic and Roman cemetery. Among the excavated sarcophagus lids, two had transverse beams in relief similar to Katalymmata [5.18-9]. While the Katalymmata lid was a single slab, the coffin below was constructed *in situ* from separate limestone slabs. It contained one skeleton, five coins, beads, (probably from a prayer bead) and a pin [5.20]. The lid was clearly 'imported;' it was over-dimensioned for its setting because its southernmost *akroteria* were embedded in the apse wall, which must therefore have been constructed with the lid *in situ* [5.21].

The pavement panel immediately to the east of the bema, possibly ramped, may also have marked a tomb. It measured 1.35m north-south by 2.05m east-west, a length almost exactly corresponding to the width of the four minor apses [5.22]. Graves covered with mosaic panels were unknown on Cyprus until 2003 when Michaelides excavated Geroskipou-Agioi Pente.¹⁴ Unlike the *Pente* mosaics which were geometrical, Katalymmata combined the geometrical and the figural; the panel was divided into

¹² Buschhausen (1971) 263—65 figs C1. For oil see Gessel (1988) 185-188. Two holes in the sarcophagus of Mamas at Güzelyurt (Morphou) reputedly oozed healing balm. See Megaw (1958) (unpublished manuscript) 2-3, 14-15. Oil for similar purposes could be drawn off from the sarcophagus in the north apsidiole at Campanopetra. See Roux (1998) 148-9 figs 205-7

¹³ McCulloh (1976), 145-184 at 149, 155, 183-4

¹⁴ ARDA (2003) 79

eight squares arranged in pairs, with fruit at the east end, followed by two Solomon's knots, fruit and/or sandals, concluding at the west end with a cross paired with a now-destroyed motif.

Like the relic sites in the south and south-west apses, it may be assumed that the north-west and north apses also held relics, although the fall of the land here is such that little remains [5.23].¹⁵

5.1.6 Ambulatories

Further features favouring a martyrial context were the 2.5m-wide U-shaped ambulatories already referred to [5.24]. These were entered from the east but because they were 'interrupted' by the bema there was no continuous circuit. A stylobate with columns defined the interior of the ambulatory [5.25] – except along the east wall of the north wing where the columns may have been replaced by piers.

5.1.7 Décor

An indication of the quality of the décor is suggested by two Proconnesian champlévé plaques, discovered in the south-west corner of the south transept. Decorated with relief foliage and scrollwork, their recessed surfaces would have been filled with pigment, probably in a resin and lime compound [5.26].¹⁶ The plaques may have served as 'capitals' for attached pilasters supporting an arch at the west end of the south corridor.

The décor of the walls, too, must have been sumptuous; small pieces of yellow Italian marble shaped to form parts of a body almost certainly belong to an *opus sectile* figure [5.27] similar to that discovered in the Baptistery Basilica at Peyia [5.28].¹⁷

¹⁵ See introduction for Cypriot saints whose *loca sancta* were associated with ecclesiastical settings. Gunnis (1936) 453 reports that tombs of the Forty Martyrs at Timvou (Kirkklar) were in the aisles of the lower basilica, but whether they were Christian or Muslim he could not say. See also Foulias (2008), 3-24, figs 1-43; (2012) 381-389

¹⁶ Boyd in Megaw (2007) 235-320 at 236. For a comparable panel from Kourion see Pl 6.5 a.39

¹⁷ Michaelides (1987) 50, no. 60, pl XXXVID; Michaelides (1993) 69-84 and 106, fig 35; Asemakopoulou-Atzaka (1978) 106, 147 pl.53γ, δ

Plentiful marble slabs suggest that the lower walls were probably revetted, while surviving plaster fragments indicate that the upper walls were painted. However, it is overwhelmingly the quality of the floors that confirms the status of Structure A.

With the exception of a small area in the northeast corner, where only the substructure remains, the floors are remarkably well preserved. They are paved throughout with mosaic, in 20 panels decorated in a variety of geometrical configuration [5.29-30]. Charalambous, the conservator of mosaics at the site, suggests that the north and south arms of the transept have markedly different characters – on the north more glass was used and the motifs were more complex. However, the significance of the difference remains unclear.

5.1.8 Vaults, a narthex and a *metatorion*

Citing the absence of nails or any organic material indicating timber, Procopiou proposed that ‘The superstructure of the central aisles and the corridors/porticoes...were vaulted’ and that ‘[t]he central barrel vault was supported by three reinforced arches.’¹⁸ She goes on to suggest that the bema was covered by a wooden dome raised on T- and L-shaped piers. Clearly there was a timber-framed roof given the large number of tiles recovered from the site. The extent of any vaulting is likely to have been limited given a paucity of voussoirs. A 6m-wide vault covering the space enclosed by the ambulatories seems improbable: it is far more likely that vaulting was confined to the ambulatories which, at 2.5m, would correspond well with the vaulted aisles at Apendrika (2.75m) [5.31], Asomatos (c.2.45m) [5.32] and Sykha (c.2.4m) [5.33].

In January 2010, shortly after the completion of the excavation of the transverse building, Procopiou proposed that Structure A was ‘most probably a narthex.’¹⁹ If a narthex is understood as a transverse and intermediate structure between an atrium and a nave, the interpretation is problematic. Apart from a small doorway in the southern end of the west wall of Structure A [5.34], the sole means of access appears to have been not a portal, but the proposed twelve-metre-wide tribelon to the east.

¹⁸ ARDA for 2008 (2010) 59

¹⁹ www.archaeologydaily.com/news. 18.02.2010

Of the bema, Procopiou writes that it is 'clear that the raised area is not the actual *Holy Bema/Presbytery*,' and must have served as a *metatorion*, i.e. a space reserved to the bishop or the emperor.²⁰ However, so far no evidence for an axial *metatorion* in a narthex has emerged. As private apartments, imperial *metatoria* did not occupy prominent positions. The two-storey screened and curtained *metatorion* at Hagia Sophia was built into the south-east corner of Justinian's basilica.²¹ It has been suggested that a *metatorion* was intended for ecclesiastical vesting, although Mathews has questioned whether this survived as a formal event into the fifth and sixth centuries.²² Roux made the case for a *metatorion* in the apsidal south end of the narthex at Ayia Trias and a similar feature may be found in the south end of the narthex of the Central Church at Apollonia in Cyrenaica [4.8].²³ However, despite the recurrence of apsidal-ended narthexes at Agios Epiphanius, Campanopetra and Soloi [5.35], there has been no suggestion that these too accommodated *metatoria*.

By 2012 Procopiou was clear that Katalymmata was not a reverse-orientated basilica, arguing that the whole layout was that of a 'T shaped martyrion...and not the main church with the nave.' 'This' she added, 'is probably further to the east.'²⁴ Given an on-going excavation, and plans to complete work on the atrium in 2013 and any structures further east thereafter, it is essential to retain a wide interpretational remit. Certainly there is not a shred of evidence for reverse orientation in Late Antique Cyprus but neither is there evidence for a transept of any kind let alone a building on this scale. Furthermore, a western transept, western apses and a western bema (whether liturgical or not) continue to tempt more radical explanations. But how great a transgression was reverse orientation in the seventh century?

²⁰ ARDA for 2008 (2010) 59. Eusebius in Oulten *EH* VIII xxx 8-11 (1957) at II.219 n.1 for the Roman *secretarium*, a reserved space for individuals of rank, and *secretum*, the private chamber of a magistrate or judge. The seventeenth century Greek scholar and theologian Allatius (Cutler (1969) 16 wrote that 'what a mitatorium might be Xylander freely confesses in his notes on Cedrenus that he does not know.'

²¹ Mathews (1977) 133-4

²² Mathews (1977) 145

²³ Ward-Perkins, Goodchild and Reynolds (2003) 58, 65, fig 34. For apsidal ended rooms at the end of the narthex at Agios Epiphanius see Delvoye (1989) 315.. Tinh (1985) 104, n. 48 describes 'prolongations' of the narthex at Nikopolis D, Basilicas A and D at Nea Anchialos, Kraneion in Corinth and Sicyone; Couasnon (1974) 46 suggests that Eusebius's description, 'In the atrium, exedrae were placed round and about,' could be interpreted as an apsidal-ended narthex.

²⁴ Procopiou pers comm. 27/3/12. For the relationship of transepts and martyria see Lemerle (1953) 660-94 esp. 673-93

1:4 Orientation

The case *for* orientation is overwhelmingly based on the location of paradise. According to Genesis 2:8, ‘...the Lord God planted a garden eastward in Eden.’ Basil of Caesarea (330-379) wrote that ‘...all of us, during prayer look toward the sunrise, because we seek there our ancient home, Paradise, which God placed in Eden...’²⁵ For Basil’s brother, Gregory of Nyssa (c. 335-after 394), ‘If we turn toward the east it is not in order to search for God...but because the orient was our first fatherland. It was our abode when we lived in Paradise whence we were ejected.’²⁶

In the eighth century Germanus looked back over the whole early Christian period: ‘Praying toward the East is handed down to the Holy Apostles...This is because...Christ our God appeared on earth in those regions of the East where the perceptible sun rises, as the prophet says: ‘orient is his name’ (Zech 6:12)’ and ‘Bow before the Lord, all the earth, who ascended to the heaven of heavens in the East’ (Ps 67:34)...and again ‘The feet of the Lord shall stand upon the Mount of Olives in the East’ (Zech 14:4). The prophets also speak thus because of our fervent hope of receiving again the paradise in Eden, as well as the dawn of the brightness of the second coming of Christ our God, from the East.’²⁷

Chapter 12 of the third-century *Didascalia Apostolorum* provides a liturgical corollary:

For the presbyters a place in the easternmost part of the house should be assigned, and let the bishops throne be placed in their midst, and let the presbyters sit with him...For thus it should be, that in the most easterly part of the house the presbyters sit with the bishops.²⁸

Apart from apses terminating narthexes, apses on Cyprus were overwhelmingly toward the east [5.36]. The only exceptions were north-facing funerary apses, approximately 2m wide at the chord, attached to the north aisle of the fifth-century funerary basilica at Polis-Arsinoë [5.37], an apse in the same position in the extra-mural basilica at Kourion [5.38] and the late-fourth/early-fifth century tri-apsidal configuration enclosing three

²⁵ Basil of Caesarea in Pruche (1945) 192a at 236

²⁶ Gregory of Nyssa in Weiss (1926) 142-3

²⁷ Germanus in Meyendorff (1984) 63; Zech 6:12, 14:4; Ps. 67:34

²⁸ Vasey and Brock (1982) 15-16; Connolly (1929) 119-120; also Ps 67.34 LXX

tombs on the north side of Ayios Tykhonas at Amathus [5.39].²⁹ Otherwise, orientation in Cyprus was consistent if not rigorously precise.

5.2 Cognate transepts

5.2.1 Introduction 1: political geography

This survey of cognate transepts begins in the Eastern Balkans, the area to which Cyprus was assigned under Justinian's reorganisation of 536 when the island constituted the eastern extremity of a string of five provinces, *in circuitu positas insulas*, including Caria, the Cyclades, Scythia and Moesia Secunda.³⁰ It was thus removed from the governance of Antioch, a little more than 270 kms to the east, and attached to the *quaestura exercitus*, the capital of which was Odessos (Varna, Bulgaria), more than 1000 km to the west, where this survey begins.³¹

5.2.2 Introduction 2: transepts

As early as 1937, Kirsch pointed out that the transept was exceptional as the only part of the Christian basilica entirely without imperial precedent.³² Krautheimer lists four types: (a) the continuous transept as a quasi-independent unit at one end of, and at right angles to, a nave; (b) the tripartite transept in which the longitudinal body of the basilica separates two transept arms (c) the full cross transept in which the aisles are continued around all three sides of the transepts, and finally (d) the reduced cross-transept in which the aisles only continue round one or two sides.³³ Katalymmata draws on types (a) and (c).

²⁹ For Ayios Tykhonas see *ARDA* (1992) 64-5; (1994) 77-78; Aupert (2000) 90 Plan 14; *BCH* 117.2 (1993) 750-752; 119.2 (1995) 835; for Polis-Arsinoë see Najbjerg, Nicklies and Papalexandrou (2002) 139-154 at 146-50; *BCH* 114.2 (1990) 982-3; 116.2 (1992) 819

³⁰ The *Comes Orientis* had consisted of eighteen provinces. In addition to Cyprus, Justinian, removed a large part of Asia Minor and the whole of Egypt from the *Comes*. His intention may have been to wrest Cyprus from advancing Monophysitism and to invest its tax revenues in defending the vulnerable Danubian frontier. Bowersock (2000) 18-19 regards this explanation as 'undocumented and naïve.'

³¹ Initially those seeking an audience with the *quaestor* faced a 2000km round trip, before a compromise was reached, allowing audiences at Constantinople when the *quaestor* was in residence. For Justinian's letter to Bonus see Pohlsander (1999) 53-4

³² Kirsch (1937) 223

³³ Krautheimer (1971) 59-60

5.2.3 The Balkans

In 1977 Megaw suggested that the westwards orientation of Cypriot church-builders could be directly related to Justinian's reorganisation of 536.³⁴ If so, the west and east Balkans tell quite different stories.

The transept at Katalymmata is divisible into three equal squares, each of approximately twelve metres, the divisions marked by the columns at the ends of the ambulatories closest to the bema, the western pair of which were discovered *in situ*. The greatest concentration of such tripartite transepts is in the western Balkans, hence, beyond the borders of the *quaestura*.³⁵ Furthermore, they belong to Krautheimer's definition (c) in which cruciformity consists of an extended nave with attached wings.³⁶

Closer parallels are found in the eastern Balkans where aisled transepts can be identified in both cruciform and T-shaped basilicas. In cruciform basilicas, like St Demetrios in Thessalonika (629-634) the aisles ended in the east arm either side of the presbytery [5.40].³⁷ In T-shaped Basilica A at Philippi (c.500) the nave aisles continued into the transept, ending against the east wall but without being returned along it [5.41].³⁸

5.2.4 Asia Minor

Both basilicas at Perge had reduced-cross transepts. Fifth or sixth-century Perge A was T-shaped. The aisles of its transepts were a continuation of those of the nave but they lined only two of the three sides of each transept arm [5.42]. Dated by Rott to the fourth century, Perge B is close to 'transeptual' Peyia: in both a non-projecting transept is defined by T-shaped piers at the ends of the nave [5.43].³⁹

³⁴ Megaw (1997) 350

³⁵ From Crete in the south, to Achaea, Epirus Vetus and Nova, and Dalmatia in the north. For Crete see Almyrida Apokoronas and Ayia Sophia at Panormos; for Achaea see Corinth-Lechaion, (450-70 and 518-27); for Epirus Nova see Arapaj near Dyrrachion, Byllis, and Dodona. For Epirus Vetus see Bowden (2003) 105-151; for Butrint see Molla (2012 forthcoming).

³⁶ Krautheimer (1941) 353-429

³⁷ Hoddinott (1963) 181-3 figs 89 and 92

³⁸ Krautheimer and Ćurčić (1986) 119

³⁹ Rott (1908) 50 figs 19, 20

5.2.5 Comes Orientis

In Syria and Jordan transeptual buildings are rare, with the exception of the equal-armed layouts at Antioch-Kaoussié (387) [5.44] and Qal'at Sim'ān (c.470) [5.45]. More often, as in Asia Minor, the preference was for box plans with transverse elements formed from lateral extensions often in the form of pastophoria; for example St Sergius (c.520) and Basilica B at Rusafa (490-520) [5.46]. The basilica at Serdjilla, possibly 372, but remodelled in the fifth or sixth century, had a T-shaped plan the bar of which, in addition to the north arm of the transept, enclosed the apse and the pastophoria [5.47].⁴⁰

The transepts of fourth-century Mambre in Palestine and Phase II at Baalbek were similarly inclusive of a number subdivided spaces for which transverse roofs provided a degree of coherence.⁴¹ Generally late-fourth and early-fifth century Palestinian transepts remained undeveloped. The memorial basilica of et-Tabgha (c.500) had a transept in which the aisles of the nave were turned along one side of the transept arms only [5.48].⁴² The plan of early fifth century Aristobulias, in the vicinity of Eleutheropolis, was close to Perge B in its combination of a transept 'thickened' to the east by an apse accompanied by pastophoria from which lateral projections were entirely absent [5.49].⁴³

5.2.6 Egypt

Alexandria retained links with Cyprus at least until the Persian invasion c.618 which brought the *annona* to an end. I shall return to the great pilgrimage church at Ābū Mīnā in more detail below. The large transept basilica at Marea lies barely 20 kms north of that great pilgrimage church [5.50]. Although the ends of its transepts are semi-circular rather than rectangular, Marea shares with Ābū Mīnā, Phase II a circuit around the transept arms continuous with the aisles of the nave. Although its protruding apse, rare in Egypt, suggests connections with the wider Mediterranean, semi-circular transepts

⁴⁰ For Syria and Lebanon see Donceel-Voûte (1988), 273 figs, 249-250 (St Sergius); 280 fig. 259 (Basilica B); 298 fig. 280 (Serdjilla); 334, fig. 318 (Baalbek)

⁴¹ Ovadiah (1970) 190 writes that basilicas of cruciform plan do not exist in Palestine although there is literary evidence for Gaza and a church at Schechem; for Mambre see 131-3, fig.135 pl.55.

⁴² Schneider (1934) 33-39 Plan I

⁴³ Ovadiah (1970) Aristobulias, No.99 pl.45

5. Transepts: Katalymmata ton Plakoton

are uniquely Egyptian.⁴⁴ Nearly 400km further south Hermopolis Magna (c.430-40) has a similar plan with the principal exception that its apse is mural [5.51]. Hermopolis, a church of comparable size to Ābū Mīnā also had transepts with semi-circular terminations and an ambulatory continuous with the aisles but 'interrupted' by the westwards projection of the bema.

If the Balkans, Asia Minor and *Comes Orientis* offer less than complete models for Katalymmata, there are four examples where the case is clearer, the last two of which raise issues which Katalymmata, too, may be addressing.⁴⁵

5.3 Four hypotheses

It should be said at the outset that the purpose of this section is to situate seventh-century Katalymmata in the context of the wider Eastern Mediterranean. Since each hypothesis contributes to the total picture it is not my intention to argue for the case for any one - which would, in any case, be foolhardy given the present state of research. Rather than evidence for a particular bias, the space given to each hypothesis, therefore, is related the part each plays in the construction of that wider context.

5.3.1 Hypothesis 1: Constantinople

5.3.1.i The Blachernai

The identification of reliquary sites in a transeptual setting suggests that Katalymmata owed little to the capital, where the cult of relics was less well-developed and where there was, according to Hill '...no transept in any of the known fifth-century basilicas of Constantinople.'⁴⁶ Recent scholarship, however, has questioned this assumption in respect of the Blachernai, the 96m by 36m, three-aisled basilica, ascribed to Pulcheria c.450-453 and described by Procopius almost exactly a century later.⁴⁷ According to Theophanes, Justin II (r.565-578) 'added (*apsides*), the northern one and the southern

⁴⁴ McKenzie (2007) 286-7

⁴⁵ Grossmann (2008) 97-136. For Marea see Grossmann (2002) 397 fig.9

⁴⁶ Hill (1996) 39

⁴⁷ For sources, see Janin (1953) 175; (1969) 161-171 and Procopius *Buildings* I.iii in Dewing (1954) 39-41.

one, i.e., in the big church, which he made cruciform' [5.52].⁴⁸ However, this is likely to refer to the hemicycles of the interior, rather than the T-shaped basilica to which Allatius was probably referring in his seventeenth-century descriptions of churches in the form of a cross, where he says 'in this way Cedrenus describes the church of the Blachernae.'⁴⁹

5.3.1.ii SS Peter and Paul, and SS Sergius and Bacchus

In autumn 2011 Katalymmata's excavators hypothesised a second basilica attached to the east side of the atrium. Constantinople provides a possible exemplar for a similar sharing, in Procopius' description of Justinian's basilica of Peter and Paul.⁵⁰ The self-conscious *romanitas* of this combined dedication is supported by Justinian's request, in 519, for Petrine and Pauline relics for his new foundation, which, in line with its well-attested policy, Rome refused.⁵¹ Peter and Paul shared an atrium (or corridor) with another combined dedication - SS Sergius and Bacchus (527-536),

being at the same time joined to each other and rivalling each other: and they share the same entrances and are like each other in all respects...In just one respect, however, do they differ. For the long axis of one of them is built straight, while in the other the columns stand for the most part in a semi-circle.⁵²

The 'semi-circle' must refer to centrally-planned Sergius and Bacchus, which bears the inscription: 'the God-crowned Theodora...whose constant toil lies in unsparing efforts to nourish the destitute' [5.53].⁵³ Mango proposed that 'the destitute' were some 500 Monophysites sheltered by Theodora in the Hormisdas Palace and that Sergius and Bacchus was built for them.⁵⁴ John of Ephesus recognises that Syrians were amongst 'the destitute' and, furthermore, he asserts, in Syria, Sergius was held in high esteem.⁵⁵ It

⁴⁸ Mango (1998) 61-76, 64, fig. 1; Theophanes in Mango and Scott (1997) 361

⁴⁹ Allatius in Cutler (1969) 26

⁵⁰ Procopius *Buildings* I iv in Dewing (1954) 43-45

⁵¹ Procopius *Buildings* I iv in Dewing (1954) 43-4; Justinian's church is dated by Mango (1975) 385-393 at 385 to 518-27

⁵² Procopius *Buildings* I iv in Dewing (1954) 43-45; Mango (1975) 387 suggests that the two may have been joined by a 'private corridor', although in (1972) 190 he had opted for 'a common atrium.'

⁵³ Fowden (1999) 132-133 for Sergius, Syria's patron saint, honoured by Justinian with a 'splendid abode.' For dating: Bardill (2000)10

⁵⁴ Mango (1972) 189-93

⁵⁵ Brooks (1924) 677

might be argued that in the juxtaposition of the two churches, Peter and Paul signify a Justinianic affiliation with martyrial Rome, and that Sergius and Bacchus, signify the Empress's affiliation with Monophysite Syria, where Sergius and Bacchus were martyred. A demonstration that theological difference might achieve a degree of concord entirely fits with Justinian's policy, at least towards those Monophysites closer to home.⁵⁶ While there is no evidence that Katalymmata was involved in a similar accommodation, judgement should be reserved for two reasons: firstly, there was a significant sixth- and early-seventh-century Monophysite community on the island and, secondly, there may have been an association of western orientation with Monophysitism.

In 1929 Butler, describing mid-seventh-century Ba'albek, wrote that before the Arab raids 'the church was remodelled in the orthodox fashion.'⁵⁷ In 1974, Widrig proposed that in predominantly Monophysite Cyrenaica, the large number of the sixth-century churches with western apses identified them as Monophysite, a position he later modified.⁵⁸

5.3.2 Hypothesis 2: The Holy Sepulchre Complex

In his description of S.Paolo fuori le Mura, Brandenburg hypothesises Theodosius' basilica as a reference to the Holy Sepulchre complex - the nave serving as the Martyrium, and the transept, functioning as the west court and Anastasis together, reserved for the *memoria* and pilgrims.⁵⁹

A reference to Jerusalem pilgrimage might be still more relevant for the transept at Katalymmata, given that it had an, albeit truncated, system of circulation. Had Katalymmata received relics from Jerusalem, which it displayed at the west end in a reverse-orientated focus that too might serve to reinforce a Jerusalemite reference.

⁵⁶ For Theodora's aversion to Rome see Browning (1971) 158

⁵⁷ Butler (1929) 72-4

⁵⁸ Widrig (1975) 143-4, 184-5, 188; at 184-5 suggested where pairs of churches occupied a single site their capacity would have exceeded the size of their congregations. One could, he argued, have been Orthodox and the other Monophysite. However, in (1978) 124 n.67 he changed his mind preferring, 'That the opposed apses of the two churches [at Latrun] perhaps unite them liturgically...Basilica B is clearly a burial church while Basilica A is conspicuously not.' But for Monophysitism and western orientation see Goodchild (1967) 114-124: at 120 he suggests that of the paired churches at Lamluda, Mgarnes, Qasr el-Lebia and Qasr Silou the fortified church was orthodox. See also Abusbee (1985) 202

⁵⁹ Brandenburg (2005) 126

Furthermore, were Katalymmata to belong to a decade later than Procopiou proposes, its ground plan might be understood in terms of the return of the True Cross to the Holy Sepulchre in 629.

5.3.3 Hypothesis 3 Abū Mīnā and John the Almsgiver⁶⁰

5.3.3.i Abū Mīnā

The great pilgrimage basilica of Abū Mīnā, 60km to the west of Alexandria, was completed c.490, in two phases.⁶¹ The transept of late-fourth-century Phase I was continuous, with a proportion of c.1:4 [5.54]. It was distinguished from the main body of the basilica by the addition of a column 'blocking' the east ends of the aisles. A single apse, slightly smaller than the width of the nave, was directly attached to the east of the transept. Phase II incorporated the nave and aisles of Phase I but enlarged the overall transept by wrapping an ambulatory around it, changing its overall proportion to 1:2.25 [5.55]. Phase II retained the Phase I foundations as a stylobate for the white marble colonnades of Phase II, an evolution to which, it could be argued, Katalymmata makes reference.⁶² A new main apse was built east of the first; otherwise the only apsidal features were the mural niches which provided a focus in the north and south walls [5.56-7]. These were sumptuously embellished with white marble columns framing the niche, from which a curb projected marking the position of a post-and-panel-screen, comparable, perhaps, with setting for the southwest apse at Katalymmata.⁶³

Both Abū Mīnā and Katalymmata had U-shaped corridors lining the walls of each transept arm [5.58]. Furthermore, in both transepts the status of the north and south apses were probably enhanced by arches at each end of that part of the ambulatory adjacent to them, for which the evidence of attached pilasters survives at both sites. Two small doorways at the outer ends of the east wall at Abū Mīnā occupy approximately the same position as the one doorway in the west wall at Katalymmata.

⁶⁰ For transept basilicas in Egypt, Grossmann (2002) 35-36; Kaufmann (1910) figs. 22-3 Pl. 30. See also Hermopolis Magna in Grossmann (2002) 441-443 fig. 59 where the transepts ended in full-width apses with a columnar ambulatory which ended against the bema in a similar manner to Katalymmata.

⁶¹ Grossmann (1981) 129-133

⁶² McKenzie (2007) 291

⁶³ Grossmann in Atiya I. (1991) 24-29 and Bagnall (2007) 118

The principal differences between the two are Abū Mīnā's eastern orientation, and the joining of its U-shaped ambulatories by a corridor passing between its circumambulatory bema and the new apse wall, utilizing what, at Agios Epiphanius, Soloi and Kourion, would have been 'empty apses' [5.59]. Taken together, the aisles of the nave and transept constructed a continuous corridor lining the walls of the entire building, servicing pilgrims worshipping at the shrine of St Menas in the Martyr Church abutting the basilica to the west.

Despite these differences, there is good evidence for Cypriot links with Abū Mīnā. Administratively, Egypt and Cyprus were both attached to the periphery of the *Praefectura praetorio Orientis* until the re-organisation of 536. The principal trade link was the mobile archipelago of the ships of the *annona* – until c.618 when the Persians captured Alexandria. The extent of the rupture is unclear because Cypriot red slip is recorded at Abū Mīnā from the fourth century to c.700 and in sufficient quantity for Hayes to suggest that a substantial part of Cypriot production (LRA 1) must have been exported to Alexandria and the Fayum.⁶⁴

Pilgrim traffic, too, must have been considerable: witness, for example, an ampulla from Abū Mīnā discovered at Peyia.⁶⁵ Abū Mīnā may have been part of a two-centre pilgrimage coupled with the healing shrine of Cyrus and John at Menouthis, 19kms to the east of Alexandria, which, like the shrine of Abū Mīnā, was built under Patriarch Theophilus (386-412).⁶⁶ It is known that Cypriot pilgrims favoured Menouthis: Leontios, in his *Vita* of the Cypriot, John the Almsgiver, implies a degree of equality between the two, describing how he worshipped both at Menouthis and at the shrine of Abū Mīnā.⁶⁷

5.3.3.ii John the Almsgiver

John the Almsgiver, who was born in Amathus c.552, was raised to the patriarchy of Alexandria in 610. When he arrived in the Egyptian capital, the Monophysites held the Nile valley and all but seven churches in the capital were in their hands. By the time the

⁶⁴ Hayes (1972) 371-86, 419-20; Hayes (1980) 528-9 lxix; (1980) 377

⁶⁵ Papacostas (2001) 118

⁶⁶ Montserrat (1998) 271 and 274; Grossmann (2002) 217-221; Chadwick (1974) 53 for Sophronios panegyric on Menouthis as a healing shrine; 53 n.1 for oil from the lamps at the shrine applied to the limbs to effect a cure; 54 for Sophronios' ophthalmia cured at the shrine.

⁶⁷ Festugière (1974) 345, 362, 375-76, 408-9; Dawes and Baynes (1996) 208; Papacostas (2001) 113

5. Transepts: Katalymmata ton Plakoton

Persians overran Alexandria, occasioning John's departure for Amathus, seventy of the city's churches were Orthodox.⁶⁸ Although John did not reach Cyprus until 619, he could have initiated a building programme there, given that it is unlikely that he died before 620 'at the earliest.'⁶⁹ Moreover, John's last years in Cyprus coincide with Procopiou's dating for Katalymmata almost exactly.

Of the two accounts of John's life, the *Laudatio* by Sophronios, (634-638) after the notes by John Moschos (c.550-619), only survives in the form published by Delehaye in 1927.⁷⁰ It is probably reliable, given that John and Sophronios were both in Alexandria during John's patriarchate.⁷¹ The second account, a Supplement to the *Laudatio* (c.641-2), was written by Leontios, bishop of Neapolis, at the invitation of Bishop Arkadios of Salamis.⁷² According to Chapter 14 of the *Laudatio*,

John once received relics from Jerusalem of Stephen, the first martyr, and of James the brother of our Lord; so he built a chapel in the name of this first great martyr and having made a list of all his belongings he generously dedicated them to this chapel.⁷³

'Chapel' is a narrow interpretation for the more flexible *oikos* of the original. Mango assumed that John's *oikos* was 'a church in honour of St.Stephen' and that John 'bequeathed all his possessions to it,' including, presumably, the relics in his care.⁷⁴ To 'Amathus' as the assumed location for this building, Mango adds a question mark. If Katalymmata, rather than Amathus, was commissioned by John, was Katalymmata, less than 25kms from Amathus, also the site of John's interment? The *Laudatio* and the *Vita* clearly identify Amathus where 'he departed to be with his beloved Lord' and 'the church of St.Tychon ...where the revered body of the blessed Patriarch John was laid to

⁶⁸ Dawes and Baynes (1996) 201

⁶⁹ Mango (1984) 39

⁷⁰ Chadwick (1974) 49-55. See 51 for Sophronios as the *Laudatio*'s sole author. See also Delehaye (1927) 19-25

⁷¹ Mango (1984) 34, 40

⁷² Mango (1984) 29, 33, 39-40

⁷³ Dawes and Baynes (1996) 208. The *Vita* makes no mention of the relics but does mention a building programme including hostels, asylums and monasteries; see Dawes and Baynes (1996) 253. The dispersion of Stephen's relics probably began in the 430s with the oratory and later the martyrion built on the Mount of Olives by Melania the Younger to house his relics. Clark (1984) 177 for the oratory and 174 for the martyrion.

⁷⁴ Mango (1984) 38

rest.⁷⁵ Furthermore, the *Vita* refers to the three tombs, perhaps those on the north side of Ayios Tykhonas, which were occupied by two holy bishops who 'took the Saint between them.'⁷⁶ Amathus would certainly be appropriate for John's interment, as the city of his birth. Conversely, if John commissioned Katalymmata, it would have been an appropriate resting place for the patriarch who protected the relics of Stephen and James during his life-time, and might be expected to be protected by them after his death – indeed, is the *stephanostaurion* of the closure screen a reference to Stephen (Στέφανος) as the crown or wreath of victory over death [5.11]? There is also the possibility, given the brief window between John's arrival on the island and his death, that Katalymmata was the work of his followers and that they referenced Ābū Mīnā, in part, because the two saints shared November 11th as their feast day.

5.3.4 Hypothesis 4: Rome and the Lateran Council of 649

In a late-sixth, early-seventh-century context, Katalymmata must have looked obstinately old-fashioned. Distinguishing between a congregational nave and a martyrial transept, for example, was predominantly a fourth-century preference. Furthermore, the tribelon proposed by Procopiou as the opening between the nave and the transept may have been an archaizing reference to the *fastigium* and the Lateran (324) [5.61].⁷⁷ Finally, Old St Peter's (c.319-22), Constantine's *memoria* over the tomb of St. Paul in the Via Ostiense (324) and the basilica he built on the Lateran (also 324) were all reverse-orientated, and so too were the Holy Sepulchre (326), Antioch (327) and Tyre (315) - hence western orientation, too, might be understood as referencing fourth-century practice.

But why might a basilica nearly 2000km away, 300 years old and in the Latin west be referenced in the early-seventh century in the Orthodox east? Disaffection might cement alliances of the apparently distant; hence, one hypothesis might be that Katalymmata's builders sought to use a structural affinity in order to claim a theological one.

⁷⁵ Dawes and Baynes (1996) 206, 261

⁷⁶ Dawes and Baynes (1996) 257; Mango (1984) 37

⁷⁷ For Old St Peter's see *CBCR* V fig 202: de Blaauw (1994) I.117-27, II figs 1-3

5.3.4.i Numismatic justification

Procopiou's dating fits so well with what we know of John the Almsgiver that one might question the point of looking further. But how secure is dating based on the evidence of stray finds? Metcalf is cautious: 'It is well known among local collectors that the copper coins of Heraclius and of Constans II are by far the most abundant Byzantine stray finds on Cyprus.'⁷⁸ 'At least we should recognise that two or three coins, however well-stratified, are unlikely to be a large enough sample...'⁷⁹ Furthermore, 'coins remained in circulation for varying lengths of time, e.g. some of the coins of Heraclius may well have been lost during the reign of Constans,' that is as late as the end of the 670s.⁸⁰ Metcalf's reservations permit a wider window for Katalymmata, one for which Michaelides' insistence that '...as yet, there is not a single mosaic floor that can be securely dated to after the mid-7th century', provides an approximate *terminus ante quem*.⁸¹

5.4.3.ii Material Evidence

The closest parallels for Katalymmata are the continuous transepts of Old St Peter's and S.Paolo fuori le mura, in so far as all three shared a proportion of 1:3. Of the three further continuous transepts in Rome, possibly 'copies' of their Petrine and Pauline predecessors, only S.Stefano degli Abissini (847-855) had the same proportions, S.Anastasia (499?), and S.Prassede (817-824) having proportions of 1:25 and 1:5 respectively.'⁸²

5.4.3.iii Old St Peter's⁸³

The transept at Old St Peter's was 66.43m x 17.87m.⁸⁴ Two *tribela* at its north and south ends marked the limits of its 1:3 proportion and four more separated the transept from

⁷⁸ Metcalf (2009) 36

⁷⁹ Metcalf (2009) 189

⁸⁰ Metcalf (2009) 150

⁸¹ Michaelides (1993) 77

⁸² Barrows (1927) esp. 405,412, 141, who argues for a Constantinian date.

⁸³ *CBCR* V 165-279

⁸⁴ *CBCR* V 243

the end of the aisles.⁸⁵ On the basis of a drawing in the National Museum of Stockholm (c.1530), Krautheimer suggested that

The function of these columns which shut off the aisles from the transept and thus isolated the latter, stressed not only the separate and segregated position of the transept which houses the saint's tomb but they also emphasise its character as a memorial site, in contrast to the nave which is but a congregational hall⁸⁶

5.3.4.iv S.Paolo fuori le mura⁸⁷

Two basilicas are to be distinguished here: Constantine's small *cella memoriae* and, sixty years later, Theodosius's basilica of 384 on the same site.⁸⁸ Theodosius's promotion of Paul may have been a specific response to Constantine's identification with Peter: S.Paolo bore the inscription, 'Theodosius commenced the hall, which is hallowed by the body of Paul, the teacher of the world.' At S.Paolo too, the transept, (71.1m x 24.2m), was an autonomous element. Here wide-barred T-shaped piers at the ends of the aisles served to separate the two elements rather than the *tribela* of Old St.Peter's.⁸⁹

5.3.4.v Constantinian asymmetry and its Theodosian 'correction'

If Katalymmata 'copied' Old St Peter's was the reference to a particular building or to a wider *romanitas*? Did Peter and Paul, for example, constitute a single *concordia fratrum* inextricably associated with Rome?

Thacker claims that the *Depositio martyrum* (354), that part of the *Liber Pontificalis* devoted to the martyrs, implies a joint commemoration to Peter and Paul on the Via Appia from 258. In the fifth and sixth centuries, the apostles' *passio* was celebrated on the 29th June at Old St.Peter's and S.Paolo, as well as at the shrine on the Appian Way.⁹⁰ By the time Katalymmata was under construction, celebrations had extended to two days: 29 June for Peter and the 30 June for Paul. Krautheimer too concluded that there

⁸⁵ CBCR V 261 fig.229

⁸⁶ Krautheimer (1949) 212 and fig 1 remarks that the continuous transept was seldom imitated in the city and was rarer still outside it.

⁸⁷ CBCR V 93-164

⁸⁸ CBCR V117 fig.99

⁸⁹ CBCR V Pl.3

⁹⁰ Thacker (2007) 21

was 'a constant synonymy of the names of Saint Peter and Paul...throughout the early Christian period.'⁹¹

However, there was a major break in this 'constant synonymy.' With his lavish endowment at Old St.Peter's (c.320-333), Constantine could be seen as casting himself as the Peter of Matthew 16:18, an association endorsed by the comparative modesty of his investment on the Via Ostiense. This imbalance in the *concordia* lasted until 386, when Theodosius commissioned its 'corrective' - the sumptuous basilica that replaced the Via Ostiense *memoria*, while matching, even surpassing, Constantine's *memoria* on the Vatican Hill.⁹² It is possible that both sets of relics remained on the Via Appia as late as 384, before being remitted to their respective basilicas. But even if St.Peter's had been understood as covering the actual tomb of Peter, the new S.Paolo might still represent imperial sponsorship of a reunion of equals.⁹³

The construction of S.Paolo also proclaimed that, once more, Christian Rome and Christendom itself were under the co-patronage of Christ's leading apostles who, because they constituted the legitimizing authority for both pope and emperor, were reclaimed as its co-founders and co-rulers.⁹⁴ Quasi-regal binaries were a Roman *topos*: according to Thacker, the apostles replaced Romulus and Remus as the city's new Christian founders.⁹⁵ Pope Damasus (r.366-384) identified the pair with the city when he wrote, 'Rome deserves more than any other to defend these as her own citizens.'⁹⁶ In the fourth century, then, Peter, Paul and Rome constituted a triad, with the city cast as *ad limina apostolorum*. But what evidence is there, that citing one part of the triad constituted a reference to *tutta Roma* as late as the sixth and early seventh century?

Krautheimer has pointed out that the reference to Old St.Peter's in the *Life of Pope Sylvester* (r.314-335) in the *Liber Pontificalis* 1:176-8 was 'intended to make San Paolo appear as important as St.Peter's.'⁹⁷ The *Liber* was written at the beginning of the sixth century, long after the events it described, and must have been intended as a re-

⁹¹ Krautheimer (1941) 399

⁹² Hall (1992) 161; Williams and Friell (1995) 57

⁹³ Lançon (2001) 31 argues that 'The new structure exalted the apostle of the gentiles to the point of placing him on an equal footing with Peter.'

⁹⁴ Krautheimer (1941) 353-429. fig. 382

⁹⁵ Thacker (2007) 43

⁹⁶ Thacker (2007) 32 n.100

⁹⁷ *CBCR* V 97

affirmation of Petrine-Pauline equality, given its insistence that St.Peter's and S.Paolo were both built by Constantine at Sylvester's urging and similarly embellished - even though the archaeology suggests otherwise.⁹⁸ Further evidence for apostolic symmetry at the end of the sixth century is provided by Gregory the Great's (r.590-604) renovations at both sites. Sometime after his accession he remodelled the *memoria* at St.Peter's and by 594 he had probably begun work at S.Paolo.⁹⁹ One conclusion might be that Petrine/Pauline parity in sixth-century Rome represented the continuation of an essentially Theodosian *concordia*.

If seventh-century Katalymmata referenced Early Christian Rome, what might the motivation have been? For that it will be necessary to refer once more to Chalcedon in 451.

5.3.4.vi Chalcedon: Rome, Constantinople and the Monophysites

At Chalcedon two apparently distinct issues were discussed, which would fracture the Empire internally, leaving it vulnerable externally. The first, the conflict between Rome and Constantinople, coalesced around Canon 28:

One Hundred and Fifty Bishops...(who assembled in...Constantinople, which is new Rome...)...do enact and decree the *same* things concerning the privileges of *the most Holy church* of Constantinople, which is New Rome...And...*equal privileges to the most holy throne* of New Rome, justly judging that the city which...enjoys *equal privileges* with the old imperial Rome, *should in ecclesiastical matters also be magnified as she...*¹⁰⁰

The addition of 'and rank next after her' is a weak coda barely concealing the Canon's underlying intent, which was immediately apparent to Pope Leo I (440-461), who upheld Rome's apostolic primacy: '...the most holy Pope of Old Rome, and then the Patriarch of Constantinople, and then those of Alexandria, and Antioch, and Jerusalem.'¹⁰¹

The second issue was the Monophysite heresy, which had its origins in early-fifth-century debates, which denied that Christ and mankind shared a common nature. The doctrine was condemned at Chalcedon which proclaimed the Orthodox position of 'the

⁹⁸ Davis (2000) 19-20

⁹⁹ Thacker (2007) 49; Davis (1989) 60; Birch (1998) 36

¹⁰⁰ www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf214 30.1.10.[my italics]

¹⁰¹ Schaff and Wallace (2007) 288

two indivisible and unconfused natures in Jesus Christ our God,' one divine and one human.¹⁰² Despite Chalcedon, the Monophysite heresy proved resilient enough to render the Empire vulnerable on its eastern flank, where Monophysite sympathies were particularly strong. Far from being smothered under Persian occupation, Monophysite communities arguably flourished. The Persians may even have seemed less loathsome than their Chalcedonian opponents - a disposition exploited by Khosrau II (r.590-628) who sponsored a Monophysite synod at Ctesiphon in 614.¹⁰³

Finding an accommodation between Chalcedonians and Monophysites obsessed emperors from the end of the fifth century to the beginning of the seventh. The earliest attempt, the *Henotikon* (482), was issued by Emperor Zeno (r.474-475; 476-491) and was primarily addressed to Alexandria, Egypt and Cyrenaica, as a bridgehead to a wider conciliation with Palestine and Syria.¹⁰⁴ The *Henotikon* reaffirmed the human and divine nature of Christ, but forbade talk of his single or dual natures.¹⁰⁵ It did little to narrow the gap between Chalcedonians and Monophysites, but it increased the theological distance between Rome and Constantinople, which, for as long as the *Henotikon* was in force, i.e. to 519, were out of communion. Rome saw the *Henotikon*, firstly, as a challenge to its apostolic primacy and, secondly, as excessively compliant with Alexandria.¹⁰⁶ The *Henotikon* was finally jettisoned under Justin I (450-527), probably at the urging of his nephew Justinian (r.527-565).

5.3.4.vii Cyprus in the Monophysite Mediterranean

In 542, Justinian's Empress, Theodora (c.500-548), appointed Jacob Baradaeus (c.490-578) as bishop to the Monophysites in the eastern Mediterranean. Although his see included Cyprus, there is no evidence that Baradaeus actually visited the island.¹⁰⁷ His 'shadow' church was rural, peripatetic, and underground. Baradaeus means 'man in rags' and John of Ephesus describes him in terms evoking the *paysan* Christ: he 'would

¹⁰² Duffy and Parker (1979) 81

¹⁰³ Evans (1996) 186; Haldon (1990) 287; Metcalf (2009) 304

¹⁰⁴ Olster (1985) 94 for John the Almsgiver as pro-Heraclian but shocked at Heraclian novelties; 96 and 106 n.19 for Maurice's persecution of the Monophysites; 95 for opposition to an Orthodox-Monophysite accommodation as largely provincial; 96-7 for Khosrau's Monophysite council of c.612-614.

¹⁰⁵ Frend (1972) 177

¹⁰⁶ Pelikan (1971) I.274-5; Davis (2000) 43-4; Evans (2000) 105

¹⁰⁷ Binns (2002) 147; Garland (1999) esp. 11-39; Allen (2002) 95-6; Kyrris in Wezler, Albrecht and Hammes Schmidt (1992) 280-288 at 282-3

complete all the work of his ministry in one night and perhaps one day, and would pass the next night 30 or 40 miles or more further on.’

Baradaeus’ Cypriot ministry implies a pre- mid-sixth century Monophysite community on the island.¹⁰⁸ The first firm evidence for Monophysites is provided by John of Ephesus, who records that, in 577-8, during the Persian wars, Maurice (539-602) then still a general, transferred a group of Monophysite Syrians to Cyprus, where ‘they had lands allotted them among all the villages throughout Cyprus and dwelt there.’¹⁰⁹

Thus land that was previously untilled was everywhere returned to cultivation. Numerous armies were also raised from among them...At the same time every household was furnished with servants on account of the easy rate at which slaves were procured.

One reading might be that the Cypriot Monophysites were a suppressed minority, farming barren and marginal land, serving as conscripts and enslaved domestics. If it is not a case of double accounting, the following year Maurice transferred a group of Armenian refugees from Arzanene to the island, some of whom were Akephaloi - Monophysites of a particularly extreme persuasion.¹¹⁰ In 609 the position of the Cypriot Akephaloi was strengthened when Persian forces, under Khosrau, captured Edessa, forcing its Monophysite bishop and leader of the Akephaloi, Paul the One-Eyed, to flee to Cyprus.¹¹¹ The island’s Monophysite community would have been augmented by Syrian refugees who, according to Paul the Deacon and John Moschos, arrived in Cyprus in 610, presumably fleeing the same event.¹¹² Cyprus, indeed, must have been the first port of call for large numbers of those fleeing as the Empire’s eastern flank crumbled.¹¹³

¹⁰⁸ Atiya (1968) 182; Vööbos (1973) 17-26 at 24

¹⁰⁹ John of Ephesus in Payne Smith (1860) 412; *Evagrius Scholasticus* in Whitby and Whitby (2000) 282; Krueger (1996) 11; Metcalf (2009) 374-5

¹¹⁰ Kyrris (1985) 172; Morrison and Sodini (2002) 192; Theophylact Simocatta in Whitby and Whitby (1986) 97. For ‘the already composite population of the island’ see Hill (1940-52) I, 281.

¹¹¹ Segal (1970) 98; Verghese (1968) 196-211 esp.197

¹¹² Metcalf (2009) 375

¹¹³ Englezakis (1995) 47; Metcalf (2009) 305. Kyrris (1970) 176 suggests that Mardaites, ethnically mixed groups of guerrillas, associated with the Mamas cult, may have arrived on the island but not before 578

5.3.4.viii Cyprus and Monoenergism

Monoenergism taught Christ's two natures and 'one theandric activity.'¹¹⁴ It was formulated by Sergius, Patriarch of Constantinople, who, c.619, wrote to Paul the One-Eyed with an outline of this new strategy of accommodation; however, there is no evidence that Paul was persuaded. In 623 Heraclius met Paul at Erzerum in Armenia, but Paul proved no more malleable than before. The following year Paul was exiled to Cyprus. However, it is unclear how, or if, the two events were related. Suffice it to say that, about 625-6, Heraclius turned Paul's *île prison* into an *île laboratoire*, demanding that Arkadios, bishop of Salamis (r.630-643) teach the 'one hegumenic energy.'¹¹⁵ If the 'theological experiment' could work on Cyprus, so it was argued, it might be applied as 'balm to the wounds of the entire Empire.'¹¹⁶

In 631 Heraclius appointed Cyrus of Phasis to the see of Alexandria (r.630-43), where he had considerable success winning dissenters to the Monoenergist cause. In 630 Armenia acceded, then Antioch in 631 and Alexandria in 633 - and in the same year, albeit rather briefly, Pope Honorius too was persuaded. For a moment it must have looked to Heraclius as though he might achieve the consensus his predecessors found so elusive. But as success seemed close, opposition stirred.

Having returned to Palestine for his enthronement as patriarch of Jerusalem in 634, Sophronios continued to brood on Constantinople's derogation of Chalcedon. But the figure around whom opposition to Monoenergism and its successors coalesced was Sophronios' pupil, Maximus the Confessor (580-662), whose early career epitomized the strains in the Empire. He had been *prōtosēkrētis* of the Imperial Chancellery in Constantinople, but sometime after 610 left his post to become a monk, eventually making his way to Carthage, travelling either *via* Crete or Cyprus, arriving there c.628-630.¹¹⁷ In Carthage he entered a monastery, the *hegumen* of which was probably

¹¹⁴ Allen and Neil (2002) 10; Meyendorff (1989) 336-7

¹¹⁵ Winkelmann (1987) 515-559 no.14 at 519; Kyrris (1992) 280-288 at 283 suggests Arkadios reigned from 625/6 to the end of 641

¹¹⁶ Hill (1940) I. 283. Stewart (2010) 163 suggests that 'Because of its independent and powerfully hierarchical system, heresies such as Arianism and Monophysitism did not affect Cyprus as they did other Byzantine provinces.'

¹¹⁷ Sherwood (1952) 3

5. Transepts: Katalymmata ton Plakoton

Sophronios, who alerted his new pupil to the threat of Monoenergism.¹¹⁸ The two began a *logomachia* against the innovations of Heraclius, Maximus arguing for Petrine Orthodoxy and ‘the voices of the fathers’ as expressed in the proceedings of the Ecumenical Councils.¹¹⁹

Having failed to persuade his fellow bishops that they too were in error, Sophronios returned to Cyprus, which he had visited previously sometime between 614 and 619.¹²⁰ He appealed to Arkadios to convene a synod to confront the Monoenergist issue. Although Arkadios believed that Sophronios and his companions ‘resisted the truth,’ he nevertheless, acceded to the demand.¹²¹

5.3.4.ix Cypriot synod 1

In 634, 46 delegates assembled at Agios Epiphanius.¹²² The odds moved against Sophronios and Maximus when Arkadios invited Cyrus to act as synodal moderator. The conciliatory Honorius was represented by Gaios and the Constantinopolitan patriarch, Sergius, was represented by Petros. But the principal protagonists declined to attend; instead Anastasios represented Maximus and Sophronios sent eight bishops under his jurisdiction.¹²³

The Syriac ‘Life,’ of Maximus which had its own Monophysite agenda, evokes a rather rancorous assembly failing to agree a communiqué.¹²⁴ Rather, Arkadios sent a copy of Maximus’ and Sophronios’ views to Heraclius, even though the Cypriot bishop believed that ‘Everyone who accepts this doctrine and believes it in his heart will be anathema.’¹²⁵ And so it was. Heraclius dismissed the letter and issued an Edict insisting that ‘everyone who confessed [this doctrine] should be ejected from his position.’¹²⁶ If Sophronios thought that he could use Cyprus to bring the Monoenergist debate to boiling point, his project clearly failed, but equally, Arkadios’ success was no more than

¹¹⁸ Ekonomou (2007) 88; Sherwood (1952) 6

¹¹⁹ Ekonomou (2007) 94; Pelikan in Heinzer and Schönborn (1982) 387-9; Allen and Neil (2002) 3

¹²⁰ Moschus in Wortley (1992) 21; Chadwick (1974) 58

¹²¹ Brock (1973) 317

¹²² Stewart (2008) 178; Winkelmann (1987) 515-559 no.33 at 523; Cameron (1992) 27-49. Schick (1995) 61 dates the Cypriot synod to between 634-338

¹²³ Brock (1973) 316; Louth (1996) 6

¹²⁴ Brock (1973) 299-346; Allen and Neil (2002) 13

¹²⁵ Brock (1973) 316

¹²⁶ Kaegi (2003) 271

provisional, as he saw Honorius recant, the Syrians become increasingly uneasy and events in Egypt, once a text-book case of conciliation, take a turn for the worse, until, in 634/5 Heraclius abandoned his Monoenergist venture altogether – but not the attempt to achieve accommodation with the Monophysites.¹²⁷

5.3.4.x The Ekthesis

Over six days in 636 a Byzantine army was defeated by the forces of Islam at Yarmuk in a battle that was to prove the turning of the tide against the Empire. When Heraclius returned to the capital, Sergius handed him the text of a new theology-of-conciliation, based not on Christ's single operation, but on his single will.¹²⁸ Heraclius took no action until 638 when he fixed the *Ekthesis* to the doors Hagia Sophia, as Monotheletism's founding charter.¹²⁹ But in order to insulate invention from the test-bed of debate, the imperium again demanded silence, this time on the subject of Christ's divine energies.

5.3.4.xi Cypriot synod 2

The ideas which coalesced in the *Ekthesis* dated back to the 620s, indeed, at times, debates around the 'one theandric energy' and the 'one will' were barely distinguishable. Sophronios, indeed, saw no need to make a distinction - one compromise with Chalcedon being as reprehensible as another. Adjudication having gone against him in Cyprus in 633/4, his next option was to appeal directly to Rome, as 'the only port of salvation.'¹³⁰

Arkadios died early in 643, and with unseemly haste, on the 26th May, in the same year, a second Cypriot synod assembled under his successor, Sergius of Salamis (c.643-55) which rejected Monotheletism as emphatically as Arkadios had accepted its predecessor. A letter from Sergius to Pope Theodore I (r.642-649) was unequivocally pro-Roman, affirming Cypriot Orthodoxy and repudiating 'innovation.'¹³¹ At the first Cypriot synod all the patriarchates with the exception of Antioch were represented, but despite its location and the role of Arkadios, it cannot be used as evidence for the theological

¹²⁷ Frend (1972) 351

¹²⁸ Ekonomou (2007) 85-6; Theophanes in Mango and Scott (1997) 460-461; Haldon (1990) 48 suggests that after 631 Cyrus of Alexandria also had a hand in shaping the Monothelite formula.

¹²⁹ Winkelmann (1987) no.50 at 526-7; Kyrris (1985) 169-70; Chrysos (1978) 73

¹³⁰ According to Herrin (1987) 250 Africa too turned to Rome.

¹³¹ Haldon (1990) 306; Winkelmann (1987) no.83 at 533

colour of Cyprus in the 630s. For the 640s, on the other hand, the second synod - presumably an assembly of entirely Cypriot clerics - is probably more reliable. Indeed, the second synod was so rapidly convened and so emphatic a *volte face*, as to raise doubts about the extent to which, even in the 630s, Arkadios' views corresponded with those of his Church.

By the time of the second Cypriot synod, Rome's anti-monothelite credentials were firmly established. But despite anti-*Ekthesis* synods convened by Pope Severinus (r. May-August 640) in 640 and John IV (r. 640-642) the following year, the *Ekthesis* remained securely attached to the doors of Hagia Sophia.¹³² In 641 there were three Emperors: Heraclius died, to be succeeded by Heraklonas (r. February-September 641) and finally by Heraclius's grandson Constans II (r.641-668).

5.3.4.xii The *Typos*

Constans set aside the *Ekthesis*, issuing a new edict, the *Typos* (647/8), which simply replaced one posting at Hagia Sophia with another, and one prohibition with one more comprehensive than its predecessor, forbidding any discussion of the 'one will and one energy, or two energies and two wills' on pain of defrocking, excommunication, expropriation or banishment.¹³³ Constans, then, continued the policy of his grandfather in still more draconian fashion. If he exacerbated Cypriot and Roman estrangement from the capital, he also energised his opponents finally to be rid its theologies-of-conciliation.

5.3.4.xiii The Sixth Ecumenical Council of 649

In six years the Pentarchy was savaged: the Arabs took Antioch in 636, Jerusalem in 637 and Alexandria in 642, leaving the two remaining patriarchates polarised between Heraclian innovation in Constantinople and conciliar orthodoxy upheld by Rome. For Constantinople, military success depended on achieving theological compromise, but Rome felt justified by countering that compromise was exactly the problem: according to Pope Severinus 'the safety of your state is contingent on right belief, and only if you rightly believe in Him will the Lord grant success to your arms.'¹³⁴ For Rome,

¹³² Hussey (1986) 18

¹³³ Ekonomou (2007) 100

¹³⁴ Cited in Metcalf (2009) 301

Constantinople's 'compromise' was distasteful because it was theologically wrongheaded, but also because it represented an attempt by the imperium to coerce the church into submission.

On both counts, the Council convened by Pope Martin (r.649-653) at the Lateran in 649 constituted an emphatic riposte.¹³⁵ It not only epitomized the rupture in the *symphonia* of church and state, it was anti-imperial in its very constitution and outcomes.¹³⁶ Martin was the only pope during the Byzantine Papacy (537-752) consecrated without imperial approval and the Council was the first convened under the rubric 'ecumenical', which was a clerical and not an imperial initiative. Justifying it as the 'Sixth Council', Maximus wrote to the Cypriot monk, Marinus, that it was convened through 'the divine inspiration of God.'¹³⁷ The final response to the capital was the total rejection of its 'innovations:' Monotheletism was anathematized, the *Ekthesis* and the *Typos* were rejected and in its 10th and 11th Canons the Council reasserted the human and divine wills of Christ.¹³⁸ From an assembly of entirely Western bishops - with one exception - such an outcome might come as no surprise.¹³⁹ But the exception seems to have been Leontios of Neapolis, suggesting that as the lone representative from the east, Cyprus had a particular investment in the Council's outcomes¹⁴⁰

4. Conclusion: an insular invention?

Just as there was debate over the wording used to express orthodox belief, it seems that there was a similar debate about what architectural form best expressed and symbolised that belief.¹⁴¹

This chapter has been a speculative exploration of Cyprus in the early-seventh-century, prompted firstly by the incompleteness of the excavation at Katalymmata and secondly by the wide time-frame identified by Metcalf for Heraclian stray finds. Of the four proposed sources for Katalymmata – the Holy Sepulchre, the Hormisdas churches, Ābū Mīnā and Rome - the last two are supported by more ample corroborative evidence.

¹³⁵ Winkelmann (1987) no.110 at 538

¹³⁶ Cameron (1996) VII 39; Haldon (1990) 57

¹³⁷ Ekonomou (2007) 117; Winkelmann (1987) no.93 at 534

¹³⁸ Ekonomou (2007) 113, 116; Allen and Neil (2002) 20, 70-1, 180 n.52

¹³⁹ Ekonomou (2007) 113

¹⁴⁰ Ekonomou (2007) 132. At 56 Ekonomou refers to a 'glowing biography' of John the Almsgiver by 'Leontios, bishop of Naples.'

¹⁴¹ Balderstone (2007) 1

However, it has not been my intention to exclude other hypotheses, to assume that my own are discrete, or to reject binary models.

While I have reservations about the formal typology Balderstone seeks to establish, there may indeed be a correspondence between architectural form and theological position, but it remains wholly contingent, often as a response to doctrinal crises and local conditions. For example, in Chapter 2 I argued that churches associated with Arianism would not have provided congenial models for Orthodox builders, and that, conversely, a Nicene response might well involve plans with recurring triads. Megaw's evidence for a predominance of three-aisled triapsidal basilicas on Cyprus suggests that a 'Nicene response' might, nevertheless, be quite local.¹⁴² Furthermore, Butler's and Widrig's association of reverse orientation with Monophysitism might apply in Syria and Cyrenaica, but might not apply in Cyprus, if Katalymmata is taken to instantiate a reference to Roman orthodoxy.

If solving the Katalymmata puzzle is a quest too far, what can be demonstrated is that, in its layout, the building leapfrogs more immediate connections of geography, trade, jurisdiction and administration, and quite self-consciously eschews the island's three-aisled, tri-apsidal and orientated vernacular. Present evidence suggests that, in the seventh century, none of the *ex novo* basilicas built on the island were large-scale, with the exception of the Acropolis Basilica at Amathus. The three basilicas at Kalavassos-*Kopetra* (late 6th-mid 7thc.) and the basilica at Souni (7thc.) represented a deeper penetration of the hinterland, and Alassa (early 7thc), 12km inland and altogether invisible from the sea, represents a penetration deeper still.¹⁴³ Katalymmata, on the other hand, appears to have been Mediterranean in its immediate setting and its outlook, but that conclusion might be mediated by the question posed at the end of Chapter 1: 'was Akrotiri an island?' It was functionally insular, because it was better serviced by sea than by land. It might also be argued that, in the sixth- and early-seventh

¹⁴² Megaw (1997) 348

¹⁴³ For the Acropolis Basilica at Amathus see Aupert (1998) 72-82; *ARDA* (1986), 51-3; (1988), 45-6, (1990), 48-49; *BCH* 109.2 (1984) 979-81 figs 21-28; 110.2 (1986) 884-899 figs 3-37; 111.2 (1987) 741-54 figs 18-36; 113.2 (1989) 860-71 figs 9-27, 875-878 figs 32-36; 114.2 (1990) 994 figs 9-10; 115.2 (1991) 751-66 figs 1-22; 119.2 (1995) 705-709 figs 4-9, 833. For Alassa: Flourentzos (1996); *BCH* 109.2 (1985) 935 fig. 94; 110.2 (1986) 876-7; 111.2 (1987) 682; for Souni see *BCH* 121 (1997), 929-30 fig.62; *ARDA*, (1996), 48-49. For Kalavassos see *ARDA* (1989) 50-1; (1990) 55-6; (1991) 54, 60-61; (1992) 60-1; *BCH* 115 (1991) 10-12, 814; 116 (1992) 812-13; Papageorghiou, (1986), 492-93; Rautman (2000) 317-331, (2001) 307-318, (2004) 189-217, (2006) 453-463; Rautman and McClellan (1989) 157-166; (1989-90) 14-29; (1990) 231-238; (1991) 225-236; (1994) 289-93.

centuries Cyprus had isolation thrust upon it, set adrift, as it was, at the eastern extremity of the *quaestura exercitus*, which, as the Empire's eastern flank began to disintegrate, also became the eastern extremity of the Empire itself. How might the Akrotiri Peninsula be understood in this apparent relegation? There is, for example, an identification of minorities with peninsulas. Perhaps the Monophysites, rather than remaining dispersed, consolidated their congregation on Akrotiri, as the Maronites, who first arrived on the island in 686, were later to do on the Kormakiti and, as, much later, the Orthodox Greek enclaves were to do on the Karpas. If so, are we justified in seeing Akrotiri as 'fuori le mura,' understood as outside the 'wall' of the circuminsular cities? *Ābū Mīnā* may provide a parallel: Grossmann has suggested the North Church, outside the walls of *Ābū Mīnā*, was probably Monophysite, representing a stark contrast with the strongly Chalcedonian city.¹⁴⁴

We might, on the other hand, see Akrotiri, not as a remote promontory, but as a gateway. Cypriot saints could be particularly punctual in their post-mortem interventions; the crucial role played by Barnabas in the island's claim against Antioch four centuries after his death is surely witness to their long-term efficacy. If Katalymmata is dated to the decade of disaster or to between 630 and 650 another intervention by the especial dead would have been no more than timely. To be effective against invasion, this community of saints, perhaps those assembled by John the Almsgiver, would have been of most value where the island was most vulnerable, at a point all-but surrounded by what, by the mid-seventh century, might have been understood as a marine no-mans-land.¹⁴⁵ Furthermore, as relics and images became increasingly charged with the same potential, the relics at Katalymmata and the image of the Theotokos at Livadia, - one serving the whole island, the other a remote settlement - might increasingly be understood as similarly operating *Rettungsparadigmata*.¹⁴⁶

Finally we come to the question: Constantinople or Rome? Disaffection with the capital, which had been festering prior to the Council of 381, coalesced around the Council of

¹⁴⁴ Grossmann (1998) 295

¹⁴⁵ Stephen's hand was one of the relics deposited in the Chapel of St Stephen in the Daphne, the private living quarters of the imperial family in the Palace. See Kalavrezou (1997) 53-79. Coincidentally, the Gospel of Matthew, found with the relics of Barnabas, was deposited in the same chapel: see Ebersolt (1951) 18

¹⁴⁶ Finney (1994) 206

Chalcedon which, while confirming Constantinople as Christendom's second city, made a barely veiled claim for primacy.¹⁴⁷ This seismic shift in the relative equilibrium of the Pentarchy left Rome threatened and produced howls of protest from Egypt, Syria and Palestine. Disaffection was compounded by Constantinople's maladroit attempts at presenting an ultimately political ambition as theologically driven. Demanding silence was not only the crudest way of safeguarding dubious doctrine from the rigours of debate, it was an assertion of the capital's right to arbitrate.

A century-and-a-half after Chalcedon, Rome and Alexandria continued to harbour grievances for their *de facto* demotion.¹⁴⁸ Cyprus, already seen by Constantinople as 'other', may have sympathised, having been coerced into 'insularity' at the tail end of the *quaestura*, a grievance compounded by high taxes imposed in the sixth century and alien theologies in the seventh.¹⁴⁹

The extension of Constantinopolitan dominance to matters of faith must have weighed heavily amongst Orthodox Cypriots threatened with participating in Heraclius' Monoenergist experiment. In his letter of the early 640s to the Cypriot monk, Marinus, Maximus includes an anti-Monothelite treatise suggesting not only that he sympathised with the pressures brought to bear on the island's orthodox community, but that he might be their voice on a wider Mediterranean stage.¹⁵⁰ Maximus, too, rejected the capital's innovations, accommodations, and its demands for silence when those accommodations failed – as they inevitably did. If novelty was the antithesis of Orthodoxy, it followed that innovation was an index of heresy and hence, Heraclian Monoenergism and Monothelism were, *de facto*, heretical. The appeal to Rome was perfectly straightforward: 'the see of St Peter [was] the sole Christian centre with the historical weight and authority to pronounce on theological divisions of dubious authority.'¹⁵¹

¹⁴⁷ Sozomen *EH* (2010 reprint) 288

¹⁴⁸ Ostrogorsky (1969) 120

¹⁴⁹ Mango (1976) 1-13

According to John Lydos 'He [Justinian] instituted...a prefect as overseer...having set aside for him three provinces, which were almost the most prosperous of all [including] Cerastis (it is now called Cyprus...)...' in Bandy (1983) II:29 at 127

¹⁵⁰ Sherwood (1952) 5-6, 32; Louth (1996) 56, for Opusculum 7 see 180-191: at 5 Louth suggests that Maximus visited Cyprus.

¹⁵¹ Herrin (1987) 250

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The appeal of Constantinople is harder to sustain. The appearance of large quantities of ready-worked marble, much of it from the island of Proconnesos, close to Constantinople, cannot, in itself, be taken as evidence that ‘this general period [wa]s characterised by a strong orientation of the art and architecture of the island toward the metropolis.’¹⁵² While the ambo at Peyia may have been the very latest the capital had to offer, its setting was entirely traditional – a three aisled, triapsidal, timber-roofed basilica, very much the kind of church described by Maximus.¹⁵³ Although he would have been familiar with St Polyeuktos (524-527), Hagia Sophia (532-537) and the Holy Apostles (consecrated 550), Maximus omits all references to domes, vaulting and centralised structures.¹⁵⁴ He stresses, instead, the horizontal and the successional relationship of the nave and sanctuary.¹⁵⁵

If Katalymmata looked to Old St Peter’s, it may have been less a reference to a specific building than to a diachronic *tutta Roma*, part the Rome of the Apostle’s martyrdom in 67, part the history of the first Christians, part Constantinian and Theodosian Rome, but, in the years immediately before the Arab invasion, it was above all, about the debates leading to the Lateran Council of 649.¹⁵⁶ If the island no longer occupied a nodal position at the crossroads of Eastern Christendom, its faith position was no less central than three hundred years before, only now Rome rather than Constantinople stood as orthodoxy’s guarantor. Hence, Cyprus did not so much emerge from its insularity, as Megaw alleged in 1974, but changed its address. There is, perhaps, no more eloquent testimony to its claim for doctrinal centrality than the letter Sergius of Salamis addressed to Pope Theodore six years earlier, which can have lost none of its force or relevance when it was given a public reading before the 105 bishops assembled at the Lateran in October 649,

Christ our God, has instituted your Apostolic chair, O holy head, as a God-fixed and immovable foundation. For thou, as truly spake the Divine Word, art Peter, and upon thy foundation the pillars of the church are fixed, and to thee He committed the keys of Heaven...Thou art the destroyer of profane heresies...Destroy the blasphemies and insolence of the new heretics with their novel expressions. For nothing is wanting in your orthodox and pious definition and

¹⁵² Michaelides (2001b) 53

¹⁵³ Ward-Perkins (2000) 73, 75

¹⁵⁴ Bardill (2011) 93-100, argues for a timber roof rather than a dome at Polyeuktos

¹⁵⁵ Harrison (1986) 407-410

¹⁵⁶ Riedinger (1974) 60-65

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tradition for the augmentation of the Faith amongst us. For we - inspired one, you who hold converse with the holy Apostles and sit with them – believe and confess from of old...that 'each nature works with the communion of the other what is proper to it.'¹⁵⁷

Sergius' letter is probably the most powerful affirmation of Nicene orthodoxy by a bishop of Cyprus since Epiphanius. If Katalymmata's architects intended a comparably powerful statement, the context of the Lateran Council could explain its apparently historicising, pro-Romanness as a compelling response to Constantinople's derogation of doctrinal Orthodoxy.¹⁵⁸ If so, Structure A at Katalymmata ton Plakoton might, indeed, represent an affirmation of the very tradition its architecture appears to reject.

¹⁵⁷ <http://mb-soft.com/believe/txc/monothel.htm>. 22. 1. 10

¹⁵⁸ Metcalf (2009) 19

Chapter 6

6.i Argument and resumé

If, as Megaw, Papageorghiou, Bakirtzis, Michaelides and Metcalf have proposed, Cyprus 'emerged' from its 'insular traditions,' to greater engagement with Constantinople, what were the fourth-century origins of those traditions, when did 'emergence' take place and what into? Or is there an alternative reading: no emergence, but rather a shifting engagement with the patriarchal centres of the Eastern Mediterranean - a challenge, therefore, to accounts in which the dominance of Constantinople is central. If the Mediterranean was more diverse in the sixth century than at any time since the second we might also question the diversity of Cyprus itself, which by the end of the sixth century, was probably more mixed than Orthodox histories have allowed.¹

The conclusion is in three sections, each advancing the case for an inversion of the 'emergence' paradigm. The first argues that, with the appointment of Epiphanius as bishop of Salamis in 367, Cyprus occupied a central position in fourth-century faith-forging. Moreover, in the construction of Orthodoxy a sense of the 'new' prevailed in which Epiphanius was a prime mover.² The second section revisits two issues: Constantinople's appropriation of Jerusalem in a bid for ecclesiastical pre-eminence and the corresponding attempt by its patriarchs to requisition titular pre-eminence. The third discusses how, despite this estrangement, twentieth century scholarship, beguiled by the 'Constantinople mystique', has continued to champion dependence on a charismatic capital.

6.1 Epiphanius: the shock of the new.³

Christianity produced a new style of life, created new loyalties, gave people new ambitions and new satisfactions.⁴

¹ Angold (2001) 38

² Metcalf (2009) 301 n.1 describes Epiphanius 'as puritanical by bent.'

³ Hughes (1991)

⁴ Momigliano (1963) 6

6. Conclusion

6.1.1 A case for the prosecution?

Epiphanius, the principal heresiologist of the new age, has not always received a sympathetic hearing from modern scholars. Some see heresiology as ‘an embarrassment to modern scholars...’⁵ Others find Epiphanius an uncongenial cleric. For Young he is neither ‘an original thinker [n]or an attractive personality.’⁶ Sprengler in his foreword to Epiphanius’ *Treatise on Weights and Measures*, attacks its author as an ‘addleheaded old pedant’ with ‘a crabbed old single-track mind’ and a preference for a ‘side-track,’ usually ending in ‘a rather unsavoury mess.’⁷ The *Panarion* he describes ‘as the best for want of a better.’⁸ For Hill, Epiphanius combines ‘the most extensive erudition with real mediocrity...and...most obstinate bias.’⁹ His most recent translator, Williams, writes that ‘Of all the church fathers, Epiphanius is generally the most disliked.’¹⁰ Williams complains of the *Panarion*’s ‘long stretches of dull prose, recurring theological formulas...repetitious sentences...and...passages that are nothing but a tangle.’¹¹ Among recent scholars, Flower is more generous, recognising Epiphanius’ debt to Galen and emphasising those aspects of the *Panarion* which bear on the author’s concern with his reputation as a scholarly, meticulous and tenacious researcher, diagnosing error and offering the cure of Orthodoxy to those who succumb.¹²

6.1.2 The *Panarion*: method, intent, extent.

Epiphanius examined each heresy with the rigour of a natural scientist, establishing its background, its beliefs, its manipulation and distortion of Biblical authority and the tainted practices that were the result. Arguably heretics were more dangerous than pagans – deviators being more pernicious than outright opponents. According to Young ‘Epiphanius hunted out error, believing that κακοπιστία (bad belief) was worse than άπιστία (lack of belief).’¹³ By concluding with the principal locations of heretical practice,

⁵ Cameron (2003) 472-3

⁶ Young (1983) 133

⁷ Sprengler (1935) viii-ix

⁸ Sprengler (1935) viii

⁹ Hill I (1940) 249

¹⁰ Williams (2009) I.xxxi

¹¹ Williams (2009) I.xxx

¹² Flower (2011) 70-87

¹³ Young (1983) 133

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Epiphanius compiled a cartography of heresy which, for Kim, constructed a ‘heresy-belt’ beyond which lay ‘the wilderness of heresy’ itself.¹⁴ Unlike the enemies of the empire who, though they threatened its borders, mostly lived beyond them, heretics were the empire’s co-habitees.¹⁵ Hence, Epiphanius was at his most forensic investigating his own backyard, where the faith was at its most vibrant, discussed, and contested.

If Cyprus was a backwater before Epiphanius’ arrival, it subsequently constituted a conceptual *panoptikon* from which error might be identified. To the south lay Egypt with six heresies in sixteen locations. Asia Minor, to the north, was noted for the variety and proliferation of its deviations. Schismatic Antioch’s hegemony over Cyprus generated a particularly ferocious examination.¹⁶ Conforming to the rubric, the-closer-to-home-the-fiercer-the-interrogation, Palestine is credited with five heresies in twenty-three locations, although only one heresy is identified on Cyprus itself, perhaps to advance the island’s thoroughgoing Orthodoxy. However, the *Vita* increases this number to six, probably to introduce the episode of Theodosius’ support for Epiphanius against the heretics, an intimacy reinforced in 381 when Emperor and Bishop met as ‘equals’ in Constantinople, and the following year, when Epiphanius ministered to the Emperors children in Rome¹⁷

6.1.3 Opening the defence

Epiphanius became the most celebrated in Egypt and Palestine by his attainments in monastic philosophy, and was chosen by the inhabitants of Cyprus to act as the bishop of the metropolis of their island. Hence he is, I think, the most revered man under the whole heaven...and when he threw himself into civic affairs, he conducted them with so much virtue that he became known in a little while to all citizens and every variety of foreigner...¹⁸

¹⁴ Kim (2006) 243-6

¹⁵ Lyman (2000) 156

¹⁶ Kim (2006) 244-5

¹⁷ Kim (2006) Table 20.2. For Valentinians, the one Cypriot heresy listed in the *Panarion* see Epiphanius II.31 in Williams (1997) I.152-161; for the Apollinarians see Epiphanius VII 57 (77) 2:2-3 in Williams (1994) II.568-569. See Lyman (1997) 446 for Epiphanius’ confrontation with Apollinarians on Cyprus in 370. Hackett (1901) 12, on the basis of the *Vita*, increases Cypriot heresies to six; ‘Orphites, Sabellians, Nicolaitans, followers of Simon Magos, Basilidians and Carpocratians.’ See also Rapp (1991), I 176, 180, 185; II 157-165, 176

¹⁸ Sozomen *EH* 6.32 (2010 reprint) 266

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When Epiphanius arrived in Jerusalem in 393 to accuse John of Jerusalem of promoting Origenism, Jerome described how Epiphanius' enemies cast him as a 'silly old man.' However, in the next sentence Jerome described how 'a crowd of all ages...was flowing to meet [Epiphanius], presenting to him their little ones, kissing his feet, plucking the fringes of his garment' and how 'he...could hardly stand against the waves of the surging crowd' and how 'the people who had been called together were kept waiting until the seventh hour by the mere hope of hearing Epiphanius.'¹⁹ Jerome compared John with Epiphanius to John's detriment – 'you are not his superior in respect of years, of learning, of his exemplary life, or of the judgement of the whole world.'²⁰ Jerome revered Epiphanius as 'holy', 'learned', 'highly venerated' 'great' and 'the father of almost all the bishops...'²¹ He praised Epiphanius' elegance of style, nicknaming him *Pentaglossis* (five-tongued) from his (probably partial) command of Hebrew, Syriac, Egyptian, Greek and Latin.²² He also spoke of 'the brothers...whom love of the holy man had brought there from all parts of the world.'²³

Post-mortem, Epiphanius was one of the first bishops considered holy and amongst the earliest to be celebrated by a *Vita*, (c.439-478).²⁴ His fame as a healer began during his lifetime and miracles occurred at the time of his death and continued thereafter. Sozomen, describes how 'demons were expelled and diseases healed at his tomb.'²⁵ Indeed the tomb became so celebrated that Anastasius the Sinaïte (d.post-700) advised that pilgrims first seek conventional remedies to relieve the pressure at the shrine.²⁶ In the sixth century Epiphanius was celebrated by an inscription in the Hagiasma of Nicodemus at Salamis-Constantia in which he is presented as the equal of the island's patron saint; 'Barnabas the apostle is our foundation. Epiphanius our great governor.'²⁷

In the letter at the beginning of the *Panarion* its commissioning clerics address its author, 'For we are not alone, but all who hear of you, confess that the Saviour has

¹⁹ Fremantle (1893) 430

²⁰ Fremantle (1893) 427

²¹ Dechow (1988) 28

²² Fremantle (1892) 514. For a more negative view see Farrar (1895) 378: 'all his life long [he] entertained that rooted belief in his own theological infallibility...he had now sunk into senile vanity.'

²³ Jerome 'To Eustochium' *Letter* CVIII in Fremantle (1893)198

²⁴ Rapp (2005) 18

²⁵ Sozomen *HE* VII 27 (2010 reprint) 316

²⁶ Flusin (1991) 381-409 at 400-1

²⁷ du Plat Taylor (1933) 97-108; (1939) 443-445; Sacopoulo (1962) 62-87

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raised you as a new herald, a new John.’²⁸ However unlikely an association of Epiphanius-and-the-new may seem, the juxtaposition bears examination. A sense of the new characterised the years following the Edict of 313. Eusebius describes how ‘when the advent of our Saviour, Jesus Christ, recently shone forth on all men, it was confessedly a new race.’²⁹ He speaks of a ‘fresh new Jerusalem’ in contrast to the old Jerusalem on the Temple Mount. Furthermore, he urges his readers’ indulgence for his *Ecclesiastical History*, ‘since we are the first to enter on the undertaking, as travellers on some desolate and untrodden way.’³⁰

6.1.4 Three Christian capitals

And they shall say, this land that was desolate is become like the garden of Eden.³¹

Investment in the already-established might be understood as *renovatio*. Investment in the ‘desolate and untrodden’ might be construed as an altogether more decisive statement about the new. Cartographically Constantinople, Cyprus and Jerusalem were aligned. Each foundation myth imagined an-all-but-clean-slate. Furthermore, all three were the subject of Imperial investment. Constantinople and Jerusalem were insignificant before Constantine, and Salamis was the second city after Paphos until Constantius II.³² The site Constantine chose as his new capital in 324 was a relative backwater, barely a twentieth of the size of Old Rome and with a population proportionately smaller still.³³ Hadrian’s *Colonia Aelia Capitolina*, would become Jerusalem only two years after the foundation of Constantinople. Josephus (37-100) had described the aftermath of the destruction of the city by the Romans in the year 70 in terms of an apocalyptic vision in which the city was ‘so completely levelled to the ground as to leave visitors to the spot no ground for believing that it had ever been inhabited.’³⁴

²⁸ Epiphanius’ *Ancoratus* was written for the Pamphylians in 374, the *Panarion* for Syrian Monks, Paul and Acacius in 376 and *On Weights and Measures* for a Persian priest in 392. Kyrris (1987) 99

²⁹ Eusebius I.4.2 in Lake (1959) I.39

³⁰ VC3:33:2 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 135; Eusebius I.1.3 in Lake (1959) I.9

³¹ Ezekiel 36:35

³² In the fourth- or early-fifth century *Peutingier Table* Jerusalem is represented as a double house. Rome, Constantinople and Antioch, on the other hand, are represented by Tychae. Ammianus Marcellinus in Rolfe XIV.8.11 (1982) 71 lists Palestine’s five ‘splendid cities, none of which yields to any of the others’ but Jerusalem is not included amongst them.

³³ Dagron (1974) 524-25; Durliat (1990) 269, 250-57. On population see Jones (1964) 698.

³⁴ Josephus *The Jewish War* 7.1.1 in Thackeray (1928) III.505

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Sites not already desolate could be constructively laid waste, hence the erasure to the subsoil, preceding the construction of the Holy Sepulchre complex. According to a now-lost account by Gelasius of Ceasarea (r.367-373), Constantine's mother Helena was in the Holy Land between 326-8 inaugurating the new age with 'public works,' which embellished 'the Holy City with splendid new buildings.'³⁵ On her return journey, according to Machairas 'embroidered' 15th century account, she landed in Cyprus where her patronage was preceded by the desolation of a thirty-six year drought.

with the result that the island was depopulated, and [the drought was said] not to have come to an end until Helena...had founded churches on Stavrovouni and at Tokhni.'³⁶

A similar pattern of desolation-preceding-renewal occurs only a few years later when Salamis suffered the cumulative effects of two natural disasters - the earthquake of 331-2 and the earthquake and tidal wave of 342. Theophanes' *Chronographia*, describes both in much the same terms; 'a very severe earthquake in Cyprus [in which] the city of Salamis collapsed'.³⁷ Malalas, describing the aftermath of both, writes that 'what did not disappear under a tidal wave was levelled to the foundations.'³⁸

The conversion of sites, from the insignificant or desolate into self-consciously 'new' centres, would have generated an inescapable sense of renewal throughout the Eastern Empire, providing the context for the relocation of the Cypriot capital from 'old' imperial Paphos to new Christian Salamis-Constantia in 346.³⁹ Hence, a city with a new name and status, situated between the New Rome, consecrated in 330 and the New Jerusalem consecrated in 336, would surely have conceived its identity in terms of this specifically Christian axis-of-the-new.⁴⁰ Around 570 the Piacenza pilgrim linked Constantinople with Epiphanius' shrine at Salamis, *en route* to Jerusalem. His account testifies to a continuity of regard for Epiphanius at the end of the sixth century, and to his shrine as a *locum*

³⁵ Amidon (1997) 10.7 at 16-17; see also Eusebius *Demonstratio Evangelica* 8:3 in Ferrar (1920) 2.141: 'and Jerusalem shall be a quarry.'

³⁶ Makhairas in Dawkins (1932) 2, 8. Hill (1940) I.246 describes 'a terrible drought and famine, at some time in the first half of the fourth century' which Hackett (1901) 8 dates to 324.

³⁷ Theophanes in Mango and Scott. (1997) 48 and 61 respectively.

³⁸ Malalas XII in Hill (1940) I.245. Jerome in his *Vita* of Hilarion (390), precedes his description of Hilarion's arrival on Cyprus (ch.42) with a description of an earthquake (ch.40) during which 'ships were dumped on steep mountain sides and hung there' White (1998) 111-2

³⁹ Hill I (1940) 251 suggests that Paphos may have been deemed unsuitable for the new religion given its pagan past.

⁴⁰ Kyrris (1985) 163

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sanctum between the *loca sancta* of Constantinople and Jerusalem. For Elsner, when the Bordeaux Pilgrim arrived in the Holy City in 333, he was not simply visiting sites associated with the historic Jesus - he had travelled via the new Constantinople to see the New Jerusalem.

The text sees as the two principal centres of the East not the old established cities like Antioch...but the new city of Constantinople...and the non-city of Jerusalem, which until Constantine's succession was nothing but a provincial backwater.⁴¹

Casting 'old' as pejorative lay at the centre of a new affinity between the new cities of Salamis-Constantia and Jerusalem. Cyprus was ruled directly from Antioch and Jerusalem was 'a rather insignificant province administered from Caesarea,' on behalf of Antioch.⁴²

6.1.5 Agios Epiphanius and the Theodosian renewal

As we saw in Chapter 2, Theodosius' basilica on Sion, probably the model for Agios Epiphanius, also rose from an erased site.⁴³ Writing between 314 and 318, Eusebius described Sion as 'a Roman farm...I have seen the bulls ploughing there, and the sacred site sown with seed.'⁴⁴ If Epiphanius' description was first-hand, it too could date from his return from Egypt to Palestine c.333 and his appointment to Cyprus in 367 - there being no record of Epiphanius in Jerusalem between 367-393. If he travelled to Jerusalem from his monastery at Besandūk, he would have entered the city through the Sion Gate to face Mount Sion. However, his clearly retrospective description in Chapter 14 of *On Weights and Measures* dates from 392, the year before Epiphanius' confrontation with John.

⁴¹ Elsner (2000) 189

⁴² Day (1999) 2. Lokin (1985) 40 writes that, by the sixth century it was customary to appeal directly to Constantinople rather than to the Count of the East.

⁴³ Papageorghiou (1993) 31 describes 'new' Salamis as 'beyond the limits of the Roman city...to the south and south-east. Sion too lay to the south beyond the limits of Roman Aelia Capitolina as it existed between 135-326

⁴⁴ Eusebius *Demonstratio Evangelica* 8:3 in Ferrar (1920) 2.141. Following the burning of the Marneion on the site on which the Eudoxiana was to be built 'the ashes were carried away and all the abominations were destroyed,' Mark the Deacon, ch.76, in Hill (1913) 87

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And he found the temple of God trodden down and the whole city devastated save for a few houses and the church of God, which was small...⁴⁵

The renaming of Aelia Capitolina as Jerusalem belongs to the milieu of Nicaea in 325, confirmed by the consecration of the *New Jerusalem* itself - the Holy Sepulchre complex, in 335.⁴⁶ It is generally assumed that the renaming of Constantinople had to wait until the Council of 381, the third Canon of which gave the city 'the prerogative of honour after the Bishop of Rome because Constantinople is the New Rome.' However, Sozomen permits an earlier date for this identification,

Constantinople was not only already favoured with this appellation, it was also in the enjoyment of many privileges, - such as a senate of its own, and the division of the city into ranks and orders; it was also governed by its own magistrates, and possessed contracts, laws, and immunities in equal degree with those of Rome in Italy.⁴⁷

Although Sozomen is not specific, Socrates suggests that 'New Rome' was a Constantinian appellation. Hence, we may be justified in seeing the 'newness' of Jerusalem and Constantinople as part of a single contemporaneous concept. Sozomen describes how,

Constantine 'having rendered it equal to imperial Rome, he named it Constantinople, establishing by law that it should be designated New Rome. This law was engraven on a pillar erected in public view in the Strategium.'⁴⁸

The imperium also invested in an entirely new assembly, the Ecumenical Council. The first Council in 325, generated a building campaign of which Constantine's Holy Sepulchre was the foremost monument. The second Council in 381 generated a similar campaign of which the Theodosian basilica on Sion may have been the signature building.⁴⁹ It is possible that Epiphanius attended the consecration of both. He was in

⁴⁵ Dean (1935) 3.30. Isaiah, 1:8 and CL16.18 in Parker (1838) 212

⁴⁶ Eusebius VC III:33 in Cameron and Hall (1999) 135, 284 for the Holy Sepulchre complex as the New Jerusalem. There is evidence that 'the New Jerusalem' was a common epithet for new church building, e.g. Eusebius HE X.iv.2-6 in Lake (1980) II.399 for Tyre as the New Jerusalem.

⁴⁷ Sozomen HE 7.9 (2010 reprint) 288; Dagron (1974) 45. Arguably 381 achieved for Constantinople what Constantine failed to achieve or had not wished to, namely the Christianisation, even Christening, of the city.

⁴⁸ Socrates HE 1.16 (2009 reprint) 46

⁴⁹ Alchermes (1994) 167-178, 168

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Palestine at the dedication of the New Jerusalem in 335 and was in Jerusalem itself when Sion was dedicated c.394.⁵⁰

6.1.6 The New Jerusalem

Telfer described Jerusalem's 'aggressive newness.'⁵¹ Certainly a constant supply of discoveries was necessary to re-inforce the reputation of Jerusalem's unique historicity, including Solomon's ring, a phial of oil of anointment of the Old Testament kings, the lance which pierced Christ's side and the Stone of Unction.⁵² It might be thought that, by raising Jerusalem to the patriarchate in 451, the Council of Chalcedon brought the 'New Jerusalem' project to fruition. But because Jerusalem was last in the pentarchic order - recognition fell somewhat short of triumph; indeed as we shall see, from the fifth century its reputation was prey to appropriation by Constantinople.

6.1.7 Sion and Salamis

In compiling the *Panarion*, Epiphanius used the *Book of Jubilees* which constructs an association of Sion with the new,

...from the day of the [new] creation when the heavens and the earth shall be renewed and all their creation according to the powers of the heaven, and according to all the creation of the earth, until the sanctuary of the Lord shall be made in Jerusalem on Mount Zion....⁵³

It was an intention of Constantine's New Jerusalem to extinguish the old Jewish omphalos on the Temple Mount by replacing it with a new Christian omphalos on Golgotha.⁵⁴ By the 350s, Cyril of Jerusalem, the author of a 'new and wholeheartedly positive approach to Jerusalem and its theological significance,' clearly understood the site of the crucifixion as an omphalos.⁵⁵

⁵⁰ For the possibility that Epiphanius had already left to take part in the Synod of Rome held in 382 see Hackett (1901) 12

⁵¹ Telfer (1955) 54

⁵² Wharton (1995) 92-3

⁵³ *The Book of Jubilees* I: 27-8 in Charles (1917) 40; See also Alexander (1997) 147-158 and for the political implications of Sion as the omphalos see Askowith (1947) 225

⁵⁴ Kühnel (1987) 88; Rubin (1999) 20-21

⁵⁵ Walker (1992) 85

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In 393 Epiphanius was almost certainly one of the fifty bishops in Jerusalem for the celebration of the *Encaenia* – the Feast of the Veneration of the Cross - and given his mission against John, he had more need than most to be there.⁵⁶ Following Fraser's reconstruction of the Feast, Epiphanius could have joined the stationary liturgy in the Anastasis on September 13th 393, he would have been in the Martyrium on September 14th and on the following day he would have processed the 200 paces from the Constantinian Golgotha to the Theodosian basilica on Sion.⁵⁷

Epiphanius, then, would have known the foremost structure of the Theodosian renewal, and given his own commitment to the deliberations of the Council of 381 and his attachment to Jerusalem, the appearance of a comparable structure on Cyprus, begun only a few years later, could be understood as continuing a tradition of post-Theodosian tri-apsidal buildings which, while it had its origins in Jerusalem, came to characterise the Late Roman basilicas of Cyprus as nowhere else in the Eastern Mediterranean.

6.1.8 The Cyrilline baptismal paradigm

Chapter 3 described how in the 350s, Jerusalem provided the context for an entirely new baptismal paradigm based on the symbolism of the Cross, a rite which differed from the older Egyptian and Syrian liturgies which took their paradigm from Christ's baptism in the Jordan. The pretext for Cyril's 'innovation' was Helena's 'invention' of the Cross, a discovery which collapsed the temporal distance between a historic Jesus and a fourth-century present. According to Cyril, 'Others merely hear. We see and touch.'⁵⁸ This liturgy was not only site-specific, it was an innovation by Cyril in the 350s, drawing its Biblical justification from Romans 6: 3-4 - a liturgy of 'renunciation and profession,' hence, essentially a drama of old and new. Furthermore, Epiphanius' description of baptism as regeneration is strikingly similar to the 'newness of life' of Romans 6:4. Less than a decade before Epiphanius' return to Jerusalem in the early 390s, Cyril produced a more codified version of his rite, describing a tripartite narrative which, however configured, never achieved an entirely satisfactory fit with the accepted layout of the baptistery in Jerusalem for which the rite was presumably designed. Cruciform fonts were widespread but cruciform fonts in bi-axial baptisteries were a Cypriot innovation

⁵⁶ Epiphanius 'Letter to John of Jerusalem', Letter LI in Fremantle (1893) 83-89

⁵⁷ Fraser (1996) 240

⁵⁸ Cited in Doval (2001) 182

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onto which Cyril's revision of 383-386 could be more completely inscribed. Arguably Epiphanius was the means of transmission for this new rite, which he may have known both at its inception in the 350s when he was abbot at Besandūk, at its revision in the 380s, and at its practice in the 90s.

6.1.9 Epiphanius rehabilitated?

It is not difficult, studying the *Panarion* in isolation, to conjure an image of a cleric lambasting those who strayed beyond his own Orthodox world-view. But add the wider evidence and a different picture emerges – of a theologian/diplomat, active in the major centres of eastern Christendom as well as 'Arabia, Asia Minor (Pamphylia, Pisidia), Syria, Phoenicia, Egypt, Palestine, Mesopotamia, Persia etc.',⁵⁹ engaging with its most recent theological, liturgical, conciliar and architectural developments.⁶⁰ Hackett is quite clear, 'Hardly a religious event of any importance occurred during the period of his long life, in which he did not play a conspicuous part.'⁶¹

Epiphanian orientation towards Jerusalem is attested in references at Salamis to the Sion of the 390s and to Cyril's baptismal rite of the mid-380s. Indeed, the imperceptible interval between appearance in Jerusalem and practice on Cyprus suggests that, at the end of the fourth century and the opening of the fifth, far from being insular, Cyprus was Jerusalemite in both its affiliation and outlook.

However paradoxical it may seem, fourth-century Orthodoxy cannot be equated with conservatism. Rather, Orthodoxy was a swiftly changing concept as councils and synods addressed the unfinished business of previous assemblies and responded to theological non-compliance. One only has to compare Nicaea's preoccupation with the nature of Christ in 325 with Constantinople's preoccupations with the Holy Spirit around 381, to understand why Orthodoxy was a work-in-progress. That being the case, it may be worth re-appraising one commonly held assumption and one commonly used strategy. The first is the assumption that Epiphanius' encounter with John of Jerusalem was exclusively an attack on his perceived Origenism. The second is the use Epiphanius' texts

⁵⁹ Kyrris (1985) 166

⁶⁰ Kim (2006) 248, describes how, through the *Panarion* 'Epiphanius elevated his own importance by means of the creation of a new Roman Empire and a new ideology of separation.'

⁶¹ Hackett (1901) 12. Englezakis (1995) 30-1, also establishes Epiphanius as a major figure in the affairs of the Eastern Mediterranean.

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as the primary determinants of his place in the later-fourth-century Eastern Mediterranean.

In the 390s the Origenist crisis, which had been brewing since the 330s, finally turned the deserts of late fourth-century Egypt into a disputatious cauldron, the repercussions of which spread to monastic Palestine. Epiphanius' mission of 393-4 sought not only to staunch the spread of heresy to Besandūk but to rebut John's perceived Origenism.⁶² While not disputing this as a major cause for the confrontation, it is worth considering a second. The Jerusalem project - begun by Constantine, pursued by Cyril, promoted by Theodosius, and disseminated by Epiphanius - was put in jeopardy by John precisely when, after the achievements c.381, Jerusalem might have been expected to consolidate its position against Caesarea. Epiphanius would have been alarmed that the case for Cypriot independence was undermined, given that, under John's stewardship, the case for Jerusalem's own independence was more or less abrogated, allowing Antioch via Caesarea to re-establish its authority. Two examples may suffice: at the Council of Constantinople in 394, Gelasius of Caesarea represented the whole of Palestine and John did not attend and in September 400 Theophilus of Alexandria wrote to a synod convened in Jerusalem, the city over which John ostensibly had jurisdiction, but the reply relegated John to second place after Eulogius of Caesarea.⁶³

A pre-occupation with the *Panarion* as archaeology-of-heresy and its author as an entrenched conservative, has constructed an aura of retrospection around the work. But a more prospective reading is also permissible. Taft wrote of Germanus that he 'was what every theologian must be: a man of tradition and a man of his times'⁶⁴ But traditions are made, not inherited, and Epiphanius' business was safeguarding what had already been achieved, as the foundation for achievements to come. The *Panarion*, arguably, responds to a particular period of anxiety. Not only was the majority of the population pagan throughout the fourth century; Julian the Apostate's reign (355-363) predated the composition of the *Panarion* by hardly more than a decade and

⁶² According to Young (1983) 141, Egyptian monasteries were already split between pro- and anti-Origenist factions at the time of Epiphanius' stay in Egypt in the early 330s. In the later fourth century the conflict reached a new pitch with a resurgent Origenism espoused by the monks of Nitria opposed by the monks of Sceta. Jerome (c.340/2-420) and Theophilus of Alexandria (r. 385-412), were both originally of an Origenist persuasion but changed sides, joining cause with Epiphanius in 394 and 400 respectively.

⁶³ Honigsmann (1950) 209-279, 212-6; Drijvers (2004) 178-9

⁶⁴ Taft (1980-81) 45-75, 72

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Theodosius' Edict of Thessalonika (380) establishing the sole legitimacy of Christianity, lay two years in the future.⁶⁵ Indeed, the whole project of shaping Orthodoxy was hardly half-a-century old when Epiphanius began a crucial text for a regenerate heresiology and the role of the heresiologist.⁶⁶ Although Orthodoxy may appear antipathetic to the new, it was necessarily pioneering in the manner of its formation. In this context, the *Panarion* should be understood as an authoritative survey, charting the route by which the 'true road' of Orthodoxy might reach fulfilment.⁶⁷

6.2. Internal frictions, vociferous margins

6.2.1 Generative centres: recipient satellites

The dangers of constructing large conclusions from incomplete evidence, notwithstanding, this section turns to two issues which give grounds for questioning the extent of any later Cypriot re-orientation towards Constantinople. By the late-sixth and early-seventh centuries the appellation 'orthodox' had a number of claimants - Monophysites, Monoenergists and Monothelites, as well as those Orthodox communities opposed to all three - a widespread factionalism which challenged the concept of the empire as part generative centre, part recipient satellites. Cameron, for example, has suggested that, in the seventh century, the relationship between Constantinople and Cyprus was far from stable,

Cyprus was left exposed and could expect only limited help from the capital...when monothelism was officially espoused...⁶⁸

Wharton suggests the opposite: not help sought, but rather islands highly selective in what they took from the capital.⁶⁹ The disjuncture that both accounts expose belongs to a mood of anxiety with origins in the mid-sixth century. The plague that struck in 541/2, and recurred in 558 and 573/4, arrived by the same seaways which brought wealth in the fifth and early sixth-centuries. It reduced the Empire's population by as much as 30%, debilitating the survivors and contributing to the 'ruralisation' of cities and a

⁶⁵ Theodosian Code Bk XVI.1.2 in Pharr (2001) 440

⁶⁶ Cameron (2003) 471 writes that '...heresiology did not begin...with...the *Panarion*...but from that moment it never looked back.'

⁶⁷ Epiphanius IV. 59.12.2-5 in Williams (1994) II.112

⁶⁸ Cameron (1996) VI.28

⁶⁹ Wharton (1988) 162

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greater penetration of the countryside. The situation was compounded by the so-called 'dust veil' which, from about 530, was responsible for cold, arid winters, drought and the coolest summers for a millennium-and-a-half.⁷⁰ The empire was further ravaged by the Persian wars in 540-5, 572-91 and 605-28 and by Arab invasions from 634/5. The fragility of the Empire was such that two emperors considered abandoning their capital altogether: Heraclius for Carthage and Constans II for Syracuse.⁷¹ Moreover, refugees arriving on Cyprus constituted tangible proof of the collapse of Byzantine control of the territories surrounding the island to the north, south and east.

Nevertheless, the capital sought to restore its dominance through a number of maladroit initiatives, principal amongst which were its theological innovations, Monoenergism and Monothelitism. Two sixth-century appropriations, conceived with the intention of refiguring Christendom after the centralised administration of the state, have received rather less attention. The first was New Rome's attempt to requisition the reputation of New Jerusalem and the second was the arrogation by the Constantinopolitan patriarch of the title 'ecumenical,' perceived as a threat to the distributed authority of the Pentarchy.

6.2.2 Becoming Jerusalem

The *Vita* of Daniel the Stylite, written between 492 and 496, describes 'a venerable man' advising the stylite to 'go to Byzantium and you will see a second Jerusalem, namely Constantinople.'⁷² Fourth-century Jerusalem had been Constantinople's Christian capital - a provincial city becoming a metropolis under the aegis of a capital, which for much of the same century was itself no more than moderately-sized and provincial. Jerusalem, however, was more a memorial than a metropolis. It was embellished and endowed as befitted the ambitions that Constantinople had for it but it remained essentially a client city whose political ambitions barely exceeded demands for independence from Caesarea. It was clearly no match for the other Pentarchic cities behind which it trailed in order of precedence. By the later-fifth century, Constantinople, while still endowing

⁷⁰ Laiou and Morrison (2007) 38; Stathakopoulos (2004) 39-40, 265-268

⁷¹ Ostrogorsky (1969) 92-3, 122; Haldon (1997) 59

⁷² Dawes and Baynes (1996) 12-13. Ousterhout (2006) 105 for Nicholas Mesarites reprimanding his brother John for travelling to the Holy Land when so much of the Holy Land was in Constantinople. Generally, however, Ousterhout is critical of the idea that Constantinople appropriated Jerusalem.

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Jerusalem, nevertheless recalled some of its investment as part of a strategy of self-promotion as *the* pre-eminent Christian city. A principal strategy in its campaign was the identification of the Emperor with David and the city he founded and with Solomon as its principal architect, both understood as precursors of Christ.⁷³ This Jerusalemite Constantinople was, according to Corippus (c.500-568), specifically imperial. He describes the throne room in the palace as 'another heaven.'⁷⁴ Even Anicia Juliana's (462-527/28) S.Polyeuktos (524-527) and Justinian's Hagia Sophia (532-537) which emulated and arguably 'surpassed' Solomon's Temple, could be understood as falling within the domain of a palace.⁷⁵

No emperor was as closely identified with Solomon's predecessor David as Heraclius. In a sermon of 627, Synkellos refers to the Emperor as like '...David in his piety toward the divine...[M]ay the Lord crown him with victories, just as with David.'⁷⁶ In 629 Heraclius recovered the True Cross, the Holy Lance and the Sponge from the Persians. Very shortly thereafter Heraclius/David is celebrated in a group of plates, control-stamped to 629-630, discovered at Karavas, in northern Cyprus in 1902. The collection consists of one large plate showing David defeating Goliath, together with four medium and four small plates. David identified in Luke 2:23-38 and Matthew 1:1-17 as a forerunner of Christ, was almost certainly conceived here as an image of a Christological Heraclius defeating the Persians. Although the True Cross is not represented *in* the plates, it may have been represented *by* them, because they were probably designed to be displayed to form what Wander identified as a 'Chrismon, the monogram of Christ' [6.1].⁷⁷

The reconfiguration of Constantinople as Jerusalem was ultimately vested in the Emperor's curatorial role as patron of the True Cross. When Helena removed most of the Cross from Jerusalem in 327, she also brought the nails which had attached Christ to the Cross and which, according to Theodoret, she incorporated into her son's helmet, retaining some for a bridle for his horse.⁷⁸ Justin II assembled further relics of the Cross,

⁷³ For David, I Chronicles 17: 12-3; for Solomon, Matthew 12:42

⁷⁴ Corippus *In Laudem*. III 240 in Cameron (1976) 68, 107. For Constantinopolitans as Israelites see Angold (2001) 2. On the palace relics - the trumpets from the fall of Jericho and Moses rod see Dagron (1984) 248 n.162, 301. On Biblical relics in court ceremonial see Dagron (2003) 101

⁷⁵ Anicia Juliana '...has...surpassed the...renowned Solomon, raising a temple to receive God', in Paton (1916) I: 10 at 9-11; Cameron (1976) IV 280 at 81, 115, 204-05

⁷⁶ Leader (2000) 413 argues that 'the David narrative does not always have to have an imperial meaning.'

⁷⁷ Wander (1973) 95

⁷⁸ Theodoret *EH* xxvii in Walford (1843) 63

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depositing them in the palace chapels confirming the palace's status, more than any church, as the principal *locus sanctus* of the city.⁷⁹ If those parts of the Cross recovered under Heraclius were returned triumphantly to Jerusalem on 21st March 630, as sources allege, they were soon remitted to Constantinople, given that in 634/5, Sophronios surrendered the keys of Jerusalem to Caliph Umar.⁸⁰ For Klein, 'It was the alleged return of the True Cross from Jerusalem that effectively transformed Constantinople into a 'New Jerusalem''.⁸¹

While sustaining the empire involved investment in its furthest reaches, remaking the New and Heavenly Jerusalem in Constantinople challenged the identity of Jerusalem, further isolated largely Monophysite Alexandria and wholly Monophysite Antioch, and had repercussions for Cyprus too.

6.2.3 The Ecumenical Patriarch and the ecclesiology of communion

A claim for the supremacy for Constantinople's patriarch was an almost inevitable outcome of the promotion of the capital as the New Jerusalem. In his sixth novel, Justinian claimed that the Patriarch and the Emperor together constituted a 'God-established' diarchy which permitted his patriarch to lay claim to the title of 'ecumenical,' (*οικουμενικός*) and hence pre-eminence.⁸² To both Orthodox and Monophysite detractors this unilateral declaration was a title conferred without entitlement and a blatant attempt to destabilize the Pentarchy as an ecclesiology of communion.⁸³ Both Monophysites and Orthodox drew on Ecumenical Councils to argue what was fundamentally the same case against an 'ecumenical' patriarch. Monophysites accepted the Councils of 325 and 381 but rejected Chalcedon's definition of Christ's two natures. It is sometimes forgotten that Rome and Alexandria, too, had grave reservations about Chalcedon as instituting a *de facto* relegation of their respective sees.

⁷⁹ Klein (2004) 39. For Barnabas' Gospel of St. Matthew housed in the church St Stephen built in 428 by Pulcheria in the Daphne in the Great Palace, see Eberholt (1951) 18 and Maraval (1985) 96

⁸⁰ Mango and Scott (1997) 471-72. The case for re-siting Jerusalem in Constantinople was the likelihood that the Holy City would succumb to invasion, a threat particularly acute in the 630s.

⁸¹ Klein (2006) 89

⁸² Meyendorff (1974) 83-4

⁸³ Demacopoulos (2009) 619-21

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The Monophysite John of Ephesus' account of the confrontation between John Scholasticus, Patriarch of Constantinople (r.565-577) and Stephan, a bishop of Cyprus who, although a Monophysite, 'continued in union with Chalcedon'.⁸⁴ John of Ephesus, who enjoyed the protection of Theodora and had been commissioned by Justinian to convert the pagans and heretics in Asia Minor, not only adopted a conciliatory tone when referring to the Emperor, he constructed his case against Scholasticus in language to which an Orthodox cleric, too, might assent. If, as seems probable, it was John's intention to make his case acceptable to a wide constituency we might assume that his case was Orthodox - at least in tone.

6.2.4 Stephan of Cyprus and Gregory the Great

In 568 Stephan is recorded as living in Constantinople, and it not clear how much, if any, time he spent in Cyprus. However, John of Ephesus' description of the Constantinopolitan patriarch compelling bishops to submit to reconsecration 'and return to their diocese as suffragans' suggests not only that Stephan may have been active in the life of his flock, but that Scholasticus' campaign was not exclusively against Monophysite bishops,⁸⁵

...the bishops of Constantinople were making that attempt...of raising themselves to the headship of the Christian Church. Constantinople was not merely then 'a second Rome,'...it was raised in importance far above its western rival, and the residence of the emperor there, gave to its patriarch the opportunity of gaining...the support of the secular power. Already we find them assuming the title of Ecumenical bishop...and probably John's purpose was to extend the authority of his see, by compelling bishops beyond its limits, such as Paul of Antioch and Stephan of Cyprus, &c., to submit to reconsecration at his hands and return to their dioceses as his suffragans.⁸⁶

Having been banished and beaten by Scholasticus' agents, Stephan was brought before Justin II (r.565-578),

Stephan...entered the king's presence...exclaiming, 'Woe! Woe! Christianity is ruined: the regulations of the Christian church are overthrown: all the constitutions and canons of the church

⁸⁴ John of Ephesus *EH* II.3 in Payne Smith (1860) 22

⁸⁵ John of Ephesus *EH* I.11 in Payne-Smith (1860) 10. For 'so-called caesaropapism which reduced the bishops to the status of magistrates,' see Monks (1953) 349

⁸⁶ John of Ephesus *EH* I.11 in Payne-Smith (1860) 10

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of God are confounded and trampled underfoot and are undone! What means this wickedness, that contrary to the law the priesthood of the orthodox Christians is annulled by those who are now in power, and another new one substituted in its place? For lo! These twenty years have I...been a bishop canonically consecrated by the orthodox...and now that I have yielded myself, and submitted to you, this man...wishes to depose me also from the priesthood of the orthodox, and to ordain me afresh in his own. Let him show the canons where he learnt this; or say whether it is from ignorance and not understanding the canons of the church, that he thus acts...⁸⁷

Having invoked conciliar authority, Stephan sought to drive a wedge between Emperor and Patriarch,

If too this commandment proceeds from you, and thus acts with your privity, let everyone know it: but be well assured that his purpose is, that after your reign is over, the blame and fault of breaking the canons shall rest upon you, and he intends that you should be included with him in the violation of the laws of the church...⁸⁸

When the king heard these things, and perceived that Stephan had good reason for finding fault, and was supported by the canons in his arguments, he...blamed and reprobated the proceeding..., And then he commanded that such a thing should never again be done in the church of God: and published immediately a royal edict forbidding everyone from ever again venturing to annul the priesthood...When however the edict was drawn up, and John knew that a decisive order was about to be published, he and his partisans contrived by bribery to put the obnoxious decree out of the way; and it was never seen again!

And there was great enmity between John and Stephan on this account all their days.⁸⁹

John died in 577 but the date of Stephan's death is unknown. When the 'ecumenical' crisis re-emerged it was no longer an ecclesiastical but rather an imperial initiative. In 587 Maurice awarded the title to Scholasticus' successor-but-one, John IV (582-595). When John used it in the synodal report to Pope Pelagius II (579-590), the Pope protested. His successor, Pope Gregory (r.599-604) went further, accusing John of seizing a new title: 'you despise your brethren, and seek to be called the one and only

⁸⁷ John of Ephesus *EH* I.16 in Payne Smith (1860) 19-20

⁸⁸ John of Ephesus *EH* I.16 in Payne Smith (1860) 20

⁸⁹ John of Ephesus *EH* I.16 in Payne Smith (1860) 21-2

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bishop.⁹⁰ Rome had a special case to plead: having refused to accept the 3rd Canon of 381 and the 28th Canon of 451, it was outraged that Constantinople, whose claim to patriarchal status it considered without foundation, should, nevertheless, claim titular primacy. Gregory wrote to John IV,

...you desire to raise yourself above them [the bishops] with your proud title and to trample on their names in comparison with your own...⁹¹

Gregorian Rome, a centre arguably 'more equal than others,' nevertheless held the collegiality of the Pentarchy in trust. In a letter to Eulogius, the Chalcedonian Patriarch of Alexandria (r.580-608), Gregory wrote,

...my honour is the Universal Church. My honour is the solid strength of my brethren. Then I have been truly honoured, when the honour owed to each individual is not denied.⁹²

Furthermore, he claims biblical authority for his ecclesiology of communion,

What are Paul, Andrew and John but the heads of particular communities? And yet all were members under one head [Christ]...all of these made up the body of the Lord, and were constituted as members of his Church, and no one ever wanted to be called universal.⁹³

John IV's death did little to diffuse the issue. His successor Cyriacus (r.596-606) adopted the title and Maurice rebuked Pope Gregory for his continued opposition.⁹⁴ Although the shape of the debate in late-sixth-century Cyprus has gone unrecorded, Englezakis' remark that 'Cyprus was to remain aligned with Rome in the struggles against Monothoetism and iconoclasm,' implies an existing allegiance to which the issue of the ecumenical patriarch may have been crucial.⁹⁵ If so, the dissension, so well documented

⁹⁰ To John, Bishop of Constantinople 5.44 in Martyn (2004) 1.365-6. Meyendorff (1989) at 305 suggests that Gregory misunderstood the 'ecumenical' issue.

⁹¹ Gregory 5.18 in Martyn (2004) 2.367

⁹² Gregory 8.29 in Martyn (2004) 2.525

⁹³ Gregory in Martyn (2004) 2.367. Dvornik (1966) 79-81 suggests that Gregory was overreacting and that John had no such universalist intentions. Markus (1981) 30-1 argues that Gregory's protest of 595 had already been voiced by his predecessors which Ullmann (1962) 37 and 37 n. 3 dates to Pelagius II when the patriarch claimed 'universal jurisdictional power, the same claim...enshrined in the *principatus* of the Roman church.'

⁹⁴ Meyendorff (1989) 306

⁹⁵ Englezakis (1995) 38

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for the 630s and 40s may have had its origins in the late 560s or early 570s as part of a wider attempt by Constantinople to promote its dominance.

If these examples do, indeed, construct a trajectory of estrangement, arguably it reached its apogee in the island's adherence to imagery, in opposition to iconoclasm as the defining theological issue for the capital between 730-787 and 814-842.⁹⁶ Evidence for the Cypriot position comes from the 'Life of Stephen the Younger', (c713-764), in which Stephen advises iconodule monks to seek refuge in Cyprus, and from 771, when banishment to the island was a 'punishment' for monks of similar persuasion.⁹⁷ Despite this evidence, the idea of Constantinople as the charismatic presence toward which its satellites were inevitably drawn retains a powerful hold on the scholarly imagination.

6.3. Coda: the 'Constantinople Mystique'

Sometimes one almost has the impression that everything we possess is but a reflection of lost originals of superb quality. That cannot of course be true: the mosaics now existing in Hagia Sophia, for example, must have been amongst the best of which the Empire's capital was capable. And yet these also, for all their excellence, give the impression that there must have existed yet others of unimaginable grandeur.⁹⁸

Although he is not specifically identified, Demus' sense of loss fits the exilic, empire-deprived art historians described by Mathews as exponents of the 'Emperor Mystique'.⁹⁹ Mathews claims that, 'on the eve of the Second World War,' middle-European scholars were preoccupied 'with the pomp and circumstance of the Roman Empire.'¹⁰⁰ He identifies a '...common thread uniting the work of these...scholars' as 'nostalgia for lost empire.'¹⁰¹ However, a preoccupation with Empire might be sustained as much by continuity as loss.

Cyprus had been absorbed into the British Empire in 1878; it became a Crown Colony in 1924 and gained its independence 1960. Varnava, writing of British Rule in Cyprus, asserts that 'Imperialism is a frame of mind...that dominates the politics, society, culture

⁹⁶ Dikigoropoulos (1958) 109-10 n.100

⁹⁷ Gill (1940) 114-39; Talbot (1998) xi

⁹⁸ Demus (1964) 109

⁹⁹ Mathews (1993) 16 cites Kantorowicz, Alföldi and Grabar. I am grateful to John Mitchell, pers comm., for pointing out that the Demus he knew was 'not at all a lost empires man...who hankered after a lost golden age.'

¹⁰⁰ Mathews (1993) 16

¹⁰¹ Mathews (1993) 19

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of foreign entities...formally and informally.¹⁰² This culturally dominant ‘frame of mind,’ may have been present among the English scholars who led Cypriot archaeology for the first three-quarters of the twentieth century, establishing the groundwork for subsequent scholarship.¹⁰³ Their research was integral to their status as colonial administrators. Jeffery was curator of Ancient Monuments (1903-1935), Gunnis was Inspector of Antiquities for the Cyprus museum (1932-1936), having served as Private Secretary to the Island’s governor (1926-1932) and Megaw was director of the Department of Antiquities from 1936 until the end of colonial rule in 1960 and continued to add to the corpus of Cyprus studies from his new base at the British School at Athens until his death in 2006.¹⁰⁴

Culturally dominant models not only survived colonial rule, they found their most explicit statement as late as Megaw’s 1974 article, ‘Byzantine Architecture and Decoration in Cyprus: Metropolitan or Provincial?’ His thesis that the whole ‘language of church decoration in Cyprus was a Constantinopolitan *koine*...’ assumed the authenticity of metropolitan Constantinople as the control against which a ‘synthetic’ Cyprus might be interrogated.¹⁰⁵ He identifies a ‘dependence’ in the ‘apostle borders’ at Lythrankomi which ‘confirm[s] the attachment of the mosaic to metropolitan art.’¹⁰⁶ At Kiti too, he finds ‘eloquent witness to the close ties that linked Cyprus with the capital in the decades before the first Arab raids.’¹⁰⁷ However, iconoclasm and the city’s periodically disturbed later history robbed the capital of anything that might serve for comparison. Furthermore, surviving evidence for early Byzantium ‘is found in non-Constantinopolitan contexts.’¹⁰⁸ For Megaw, these contexts were not a patina of examples, but implied ‘dissemination from the centre, Constantinople itself.’¹⁰⁹ A ‘centre’ lacking examples and a rich ‘periphery’ tempted reconstructions of a Constantinople ‘imaginaire’ from evidence garnered from satellites able to provide no more than ‘a reflection of lost

¹⁰² Varnava (2008) 14

¹⁰³ This account, however, gives insufficient weight to the Swedes, Americans, Poles, French *et al* who have contributed so much to Cypriot archaeology.

¹⁰⁴ Pilides (2009); Symons (1987) 3-10; Catling (2007) 1-10. See also Given (2005) 210-211 and Secretis (2005) 214-18

¹⁰⁵ Megaw (1974) 57-88, 72

¹⁰⁶ Megaw (1974) 68, 74

¹⁰⁷ Megaw (1974) 57-88, 76

¹⁰⁸ Eastmond (2008) 770

¹⁰⁹ Megaw (1974) 74. C.f. Demus (1964) 90, ‘Byzantine art was in fact the art of one city...Constantinople alone’.

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originals of superb quality.’¹¹⁰ To some extent the ‘Constantinople mystique’ was sustained by the very strategy that might have been used to interrogate it - a dichotomy of centre and periphery which allocated quality to a centre whose ‘mystique’ was conserved by its separation from compliant satellites where quality was less assured. This remarkably enduring model can be found metonymically in sixth-century Cyprus in the supposed allocation of a barren periphery to the Arzanene and Syrian minorities by a conceptual and probably Orthodox Cypriot centre. It recurs in post-colonial Cyprus in the tendency of the former colony to reconfigure parts of its population (Turks, Maronites, Armenians) and its geography (Kormakiti, Akrotiri, Akamas) as marginal, in confirmation of its own newly-acquired centrality. In this milieu, the binary model has continued to nourish scholars who, more than thirty years after Megaw, restated the case for Constantinopolitan dominance.¹¹¹

Wharton, seeking to recover the ‘periphery’ by removing its pejorative accretions, nevertheless accepted that ‘Constantinople was unquestionably the dominant...centre.’¹¹² Furthermore, her attempt to distinguish a reactive periphery from a *region* ‘where no metropolitan influence is discernible’ is problematic, given that ‘region’ evokes a quasi-national identity.¹¹³ Recent scholarship, finding the concept of a monocentric state less straightforward, is more inclined to see elite production, so long the assumed signature of the centre, as more polycentric and homogeneously dispersed. Angold proposes a ‘Mediterranean more diverse in the sixth century than it had in the days of the Antonines...’¹¹⁴ Polycentricity certainly fits a Cyprus of decentred and circuminsular cities which lacked a central capital until the 10th century.¹¹⁵ Furthermore, in the fourth century ‘Roman’ Paphos coexisted with ‘Egyptian’ Salamis and in the sixth the governor may have resided in Amathus and the bishop in Salamis, a qualified equality shared with a more-or-less polycentric Pentarchy.¹¹⁶

Often understood in terms fragments detached from a more enduring mass, islands are vulnerable to ‘peripherization’ of a particularly circumscribed kind. The opening chapter

¹¹⁰ C.f Piccirillo (1997) ix

¹¹¹ Castelnuovo (1986) 43-8

¹¹² Wharton (1986) 75; (1988) 162

¹¹³ Wharton (1988) 11-12; Jones (1959) 295; Geary (2003)

¹¹⁴ Angold (2001) 38

¹¹⁵ Although Trifillios was bishop of Ledra (Lefkosia) as early as 348, his see was minor.

¹¹⁶ The sole reference to a governor in Amathus comes from *The Life of John the Almsgiver*: see Dawes and Baynes (1996) 199, 256

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of this thesis offered an alternative - islands as fluid, responsive, agile and nodal. The island's earliest basilicas vied with the largest and most lavish in Christendom and the setting for its baptismal liturgy was more Jerusalemite than Jerusalem. Indeed, Dagron's proposition that Jerusalem was Constantine's Christian capital allows the possibility that, in the fourth and fifth centuries, Constantinople and Cyprus, shared a common focus and hence were more closely allied than at any time before the Arab invasions. On the other hand, despite Justinian's *de facto* relegation of the island to the tail end of the *quaestura exercitus*, there is little evidence of a drift into insularity and conservatism, sometimes construed as the conjoined twins of Orthodoxy. The earliest apse mosaics of the Theotokos survive from Cyprus and the development of the *topos* was rich in innovation: the Theotokos enclosed in a mandorla at Lythrankomi 'escaped' to extend her dominion across the entire east wall of the basilica at Livadia barely a century later.

On the other hand architectural innovation is more a characteristic of the early period than the later. The triapsidal east end, which, in the late-fourth and early-fifth century, had been closely associated with the formation of Nicene-Constantinopolitan Orthodoxy, had, by the sixth century, become a more or less standard type. Lateral walls may have acquired north and south corridors but they were never challenged by anything as radical as a transept which, of course, makes the layout, scale and treatment at Katalymmata as remarkable as it is challenging to explain.

The lack of transepts in Constantinople and the absence of domed churches in Cyprus - at least before the Middle Byzantine period - suggest different preferences on the island and in the capital. Furthermore, as I argued in the final chapter, by 643 Cypriot Orthodoxy was more central, and metropolitan, (i.e. Roman), than metropolitan Constantinople's accommodation with 'provincial' Monophysitism. Indeed, engagement with, and disengagement from, the regions and major metropoleis of the eastern Mediterranean evokes an island remarkably flexible in its affiliations: adhesion to monastic Egypt and Cyrilline Jerusalem in the fourth century, antipathy towards hegemonic Antioch in the fourth and fifth, gift exchange with Zenonian Constantinople in the fifth century, an altogether more conflicted relationship with Constantinople in the sixth, to outright opposition in the seventh. This is unpromising material from which to forge a narrative of island remoteness progressively exposed to greater 'imperial outreach'. Rather the island's integration into complex and changing networks of

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exchange, in so far as they generated sophisticated syntheses of architecture, liturgy and imagery, characterised Late Antique Cyprus as a 'fluid zone of transition.'

Abbreviations

<i>AA</i>	Archäologischer Anzeiger
<i>AAA</i>	Acta ad archaeologiam et artium historiam pertinentia
<i>AAAd</i>	Antichità Altoadriatiche
<i>ΆΒαρ</i>	Ἄποστολος Βαρνάβας
<i>AB</i>	Analecta Bollandiana
<i>ABSA</i>	Annual of the British School at Athens
<i>ABull</i>	Art Bulletin
<i>ActaArch</i>	Acta Archaeologica
<i>ACLS</i>	American Council of Learned Societies
<i>AF</i>	Art Front
<i>AH</i>	Art History
<i>AHyp</i>	Acta Hyperborea
<i>AHR</i>	American Historical Review
<i>AJA</i>	American Journal of Archaeology
<i>ALW</i>	Archiv für Liturgiewissenschaft
<i>AntJ</i>	Antiquaries Journal
<i>ANRW</i>	Aufstieg und Neidergang der Römischen Welt
<i>APSP</i>	Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society
<i>ASOR</i>	American Schools of Oriental Research
<i>ARDA</i>	Annual Report of the Department of Antiquities
<i>AR</i>	Archaeological Reports in <i>JHS</i>
<i>AT</i>	Antiquité Tardive
<i>BA</i>	Biblical Archaeologist
<i>BASOR</i>	Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research
<i>BCH</i>	Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique
<i>ΒΔ</i>	ΒΥΖΑΝΤΙΝΟΣ ΔΟΜΟΣ
<i>BHG</i>	Bibliotheca hagiographica 3 vols
<i>BSAC</i>	Bulletin de la Societé d'archéologie copte
<i>BSSA</i>	Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America
<i>BullAAAS</i>	Bulletin of the American Academy of Arts and Sciences
<i>BZ</i>	Byzantinische Zeitschrift
<i>CA</i>	Cahiers Archéologiques
<i>CBQ</i>	Catholic Biblical Quarterly
<i>CHR</i>	Cyprus Historical Review
<i>CH</i>	Church History
<i>CIEB</i>	Congrès international d'études Byzantines
<i>CL</i>	Cyril of Jerusalem. Catechetical Lectures
<i>Corsi</i>	Corsi di cultura sull'arte ravennate e bizantina
<i>DOP</i>	Dumbarton Oaks Papers
<i>EHR</i>	English Historical Review
<i>FA</i>	Fasti Archeologici
<i>GOTR</i>	Greek Orthodox Theological Review
<i>HL</i>	Das Heilige Land
<i>HTR</i>	Harvard Theological Review
<i>H&T</i>	History and Theory
<i>IJNA</i>	International Journal of Nautical Archaeology
<i>ISJ</i>	Island Studies Journal
<i>JAR</i>	Journal of Anthropological Research
<i>JbAC</i>	Jahrbuch für Antike und Christentum
<i>JBR</i>	Journal of Bible and Religion
<i>JECS</i>	Journal of Early Christian Studies
<i>JED</i>	Journal of Economic Development
<i>JFA</i>	Journal of Field Archaeology

<i>JHI</i>	Journal of the History of Ideas
<i>JHS</i>	Journal of Hellenic Studies
<i>JJS</i>	Journal of Jewish Studies
<i>JLA</i>	Journal of Late Antiquity
<i>JLH</i>	Jahrbuch für Liturgik und Hymnologie
<i>JLR</i>	Journal of Law and Religion
<i>JMEMS</i>	Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies
<i>JOAC</i>	Journal of Agrarian Change
<i>JÖB</i>	Jahrbuch der Österreichischen Byzantinistik
<i>JPS</i>	Journal of the Polynesian Society
<i>JQR</i>	Jewish Quarterly Review
<i>JRA</i>	Journal of Roman Archaeology
<i>JRS</i>	Journal of Roman Studies
<i>JSAH</i>	Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians
<i>JTS</i>	Journal of Theological Studies
<i>JWP</i>	Journal of World Prehistory
<i>ΚΣ</i>	ΚΥΠΡΙΑΚΑΙ ΣΠΟΥΔΑΙ
<i>LA</i>	Liber Annuus
<i>MC</i>	Cyril of Jerusalem. Mystagogical Catecheses
<i>MDAIK</i>	Mitteilungen des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts Abteilungen Kairo
<i>MHR</i>	Mediterranean Historical Review
<i>MMAB</i>	The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin
<i>MMJ</i>	Metropolitan Museum Journal
<i>MSpätAByz</i>	Mitteilungen zur Spätantiken Archäologie und Byzantinischen Kunstgeschichte
<i>Mus</i>	Le Muséon, Revue d'Etudes Orientales
<i>NEA</i>	Near Eastern Archaeology
<i>NH</i>	Pliny <i>Natural History</i>
<i>NPNF</i>	Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers
<i>OCP</i>	Orientalia Christiana Periodica
<i>OpAth</i>	Opuscula Atheniensi
<i>OrChr</i>	Oriens Christianus
<i>PAM</i>	Polish Archaeology in the Mediterranean
<i>PastPre</i>	Past and Present
<i>PBSR</i>	Papers of the British School at Rome
<i>PG</i>	Patrologia Graeca
<i>PL</i>	Patrologia Latina
<i>PO</i>	Patrologia Orientalis
<i>Problsk</i>	Problemi na izkustvoto
<i>PROC AAAS</i>	Proceedings of the American Academy of Arts and Sciences
<i>PSA</i>	Proceedings of the Society of Antiquaries
<i>RAC</i>	Rivista di archeologia Cristiana
<i>RDAC</i>	Report of the Department of Antiquities Cyprus
<i>REB</i>	Revue des études byzantines
<i>RESEE</i>	Revue des études sud-est européennes
<i>SCH</i>	Studies in Church History
<i>StPatr</i>	Studia Patristica
<i>SubGr</i>	Subseciva Groningana
<i>TESG</i>	Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie
<i>TIBG</i>	Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers
<i>TRHS</i>	Transactions of Royal Historical Society
<i>TM</i>	Travaux et Mémoires
<i>TS</i>	Theological Studies
<i>VC</i>	Vigilae Christianae
<i>VO</i>	Vicino Oriente
<i>WA</i>	World Archaeology
<i>ZDPV</i>	Zeitschrift des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins

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